

Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 3 to 31

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*This paper shows how to create magic squares with a **perfect square number** for the total sum entries. This has been done in five ways. Initially, the two ways are using entries as **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** for odd order magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for even order magic squares. This process satisfy an interesting property known by **uniformity property**. The second way is also give two kind of magic squares with entries sum as **perfect square**. It is based on magic squares generated by **Pythagorean triples**. This procedure give many magic squares based on interval and order of magic squares. In this work, only the first value considered giving least possible **perfect square sum** of entries. In this way also there are two possibilities, one using entries as **consecutive odd numbers** and second using entries as **consecutive natural numbers** for odd order magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for even order magic squares. In all the four possibilities given above not even a single one give us **minimum perfect square** sum of entries. By using the entries as nonnegative numbers, a fifth procedure is considered to get **minimum perfect square** sum of entries. These entries are either consecutive natural numbers for odd order magic squares and consecutive fraction numbers for even order magic squares. For each order, the work is divided in three parts resulting in five magic squares with **perfect square sum** of entries. Recently, author [21] applied this idea of **perfect square sum** of entries to write area representations magic squares. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 31. Further orders from 32 to 47 are given in Taneja [22].*

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA;

Instagram: @crazynumbers.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Series and Magic Square Sums	7
2.1	Number Series Sums	7
2.2	Perfect Square Sums of Entries	8
2.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries Satisfying Pythagorean Triples	11
2.3.1	Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares	12
2.4	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	15
3	Magic Squares of Order 3	18
3.1	Uniformity Property	19
3.2	Pythagorean Triple	19
3.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	20
4	Magic Squares of Order 4	21
4.1	Uniformity Property	21
4.2	Pythagorean Triple	22
4.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	23
5	Magic Squares of Order 5	24
5.1	Uniformity Property	24
5.2	Pythagorean Triple	25
5.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	26
6	Magic Squares of Order 6	27
6.1	Uniformity Property	27
6.2	Pythagorean Triple	28
6.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	29
7	Magic Squares of Order 7	30
7.1	Uniformity Property	30
7.2	Pythagorean Triple	31
7.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	32

8 Magic Squares of Order 8	33
8.1 Uniformity Property	33
8.2 Pythagorean Triple	34
8.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	35
9 Magic Squares of Order 9	36
9.1 Uniformity Property	36
9.2 Pythagorean Triple	37
9.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	38
10 Magic Squares of Order 10	39
10.1 Uniformity Property	39
10.2 Pythagorean Triple	40
10.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	41
11 Magic Squares of Order 11	42
11.1 Uniformity Property	42
11.2 Pythagorean Triple	43
11.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	44
12 Magic Squares of Order 12	45
12.1 Uniformity Property	45
12.2 Pythagorean Triple	47
12.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	49
13 Magic Squares of Order 13	50
13.1 Uniformity Property	50
13.2 Pythagorean Triple	51
13.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	53
14 Magic Squares of Order 14	55
14.1 Uniformity Property	55
14.2 Pythagorean Triple	56
14.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	58
15 Magic Squares of Order 15	60

15.1 Uniformity Property	60
15.2 Pythagorean Triple	61
15.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	63
16 Magic Squares of Order 16	65
16.1 Uniformity Property	65
16.2 Pythagorean Triple	67
16.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	70
17 Magic Squares of Order 17	71
17.1 Uniformity Property	72
17.2 Pythagorean Triple	74
17.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	76
18 Magic Squares of Order 18	78
18.1 Uniformity Property	78
18.2 Pythagorean Triple	79
18.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	81
19 Magic Squares of Order 19	83
19.1 Uniformity Property	83
19.2 Pythagorean Triple	86
19.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	89
20 Magic Squares of Order 20	91
20.1 Uniformity Property	91
20.2 Pythagorean Triple	94
20.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	96
21 Magic Squares of Order 21	97
21.1 Uniformity Property	98
21.2 Pythagorean Triple	100
21.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	102
22 Magic Squares of Order 22	104
22.1 Uniformity Property	104

22.2 Pythagorean Triple	107
22.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	110
23 Magic Squares of Order 23	112
23.1 Uniformity Property	112
23.2 Pythagorean Triple	115
23.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	118
24 Magic Squares of Order 24	120
24.1 Uniformity Property	120
24.2 Pythagorean Triple	123
24.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	125
25 Magic Squares of Order 25	127
25.1 Uniformity Property	127
25.2 Pythagorean Triple	130
25.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	133
26 Magic Squares of Order 26	135
26.1 Uniformity Property	135
26.2 Pythagorean Triple	138
26.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	141
27 Magic Squares of Order 27	143
27.1 Uniformity Property	143
27.2 Pythagorean Triple	146
27.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	149
28 Magic Squares of Order 28	151
28.1 Uniformity Property	151
28.2 Pythagorean Triple	154
28.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	156
29 Magic Squares of Order 29	158
29.1 Uniformity Property	158
29.2 Pythagorean Triple	161

29.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	164
30 Magic Squares of Order 30	166
30.1 Uniformity Property	166
30.2 Pythagorean Triple	168
30.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	170
31 Magic Squares of Order 31	172
31.1 Uniformity Property	173
31.2 Pythagorean Triple	175
31.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	178

1 Introduction

Recently, the author [3, 4, 5] worked on magic squares connected with Pythagorean triples. In these, works the sum of all entries of a magic square are always a perfect square. The work in Pythagorean triples and patterns are done by author in [6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. On the other side the author worked extensively on magic squares in different situations, such as, **block-wise** [11, 12, 16, 17], **block-bordered** [13, 14, 16], **block-wise-bordered** [17, 18, 19], etc. In this we shall try to extend and revise previous works.

This paper shows how to create magic squares with a **perfect square number** for the total sum entries. This has been done in five ways. Initially, the two ways are using entries as **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** for odd order magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for even order magic squares. This process satisfy an interesting property known by **uniformity property**. The second way is also give two kind of magic squares with entries sum as **perfect square**. It is based on magic squares generated by **Pythagorean triples**. This procedure give many magic squares based on interval and order of magic squares. In this work, only the first value considered giving least possible **perfect square sum** of entries. In this way also there are two possibilities, one using entries as **consecutive odd numbers** and second using entries as **consecutive natural numbers** for odd order magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for even order magic squares. In all the four possibilities given above not even a single one give us **minimum perfect square** sum of entries. By using the entries as nonnegative numbers, a fifth procedure is considered to get **minimum perfect square** sum of entries. These entries are either consecutive natural numbers for odd order magic squares and consecutive fraction numbers for even order magic squares. For each order, the work is divided in three parts resulting in five magic squares with **perfect square sum** of entries. Recently, author [21] applied this idea of **perfect square sum** of entries to write area representations magic squares. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 31. Further

orders from 32 to 47 are given in Taneja [22].

Summarizing, there are main three points studied in this work. These three point lead us to five magic squares of for each order. See below the details:

1. Write magic squares with entries as **consecutive odd numbers** satisfying **uniformity property**;
2. Write magic squares with entries as **consecutive natural numbers** for **odd order** magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for **even order** magic squares satisfying **uniformity property**;
3. Write magic squares arising due to **Pythagorean triples** having **perfect square sum** of entries as **consecutive odd numbers**;
4. Write magic squares arising due to **Pythagorean triples** having **perfect square sum** of entries as **consecutive natural numbers** for **odd order** magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for **even order** magic squares.
5. Write magic squares with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries with **consecutive natural numbers** for **odd order** magic squares and **consecutive fraction numbers** for **even order** magic squares.

In order to write above magic squares there are some basic ideas given in the following Section 2.

2 Series and Magic Square Sums

This section presents some basic ideas of series and magic square sums.

2.1 Number Series Sums

(i) It is well-known that the **positive natural number** series sum is given by

$$T_n := 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

The sequence T_n is also famous for showing **Pascal's triangle values**.

(ii) It is well-known that sum of **odd number** series is given by

$$T_n := 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + (2n - 1) = n^2, \quad n \geq 1. \quad (2)$$

In case of magic squares, let's write $n = k^2$, then we have

$$T_{k^2} := 1 + 3 + 5 + \dots + (2k^2 - 1) = k^4, \quad k \geq 1. \quad (3)$$

2.2 Perfect Square Sums of Entries

Below is a general formula for writing **perfect square sum** of entries of a magic squares.

Let us consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(n, k) &= T(n) - T(n - k) \\
 &= (n - k + 1) + (n - k + 3) + \cdots + n \\
 &= k \left(n - \frac{k - 1}{2} \right), \quad n \geq k, \\
 &= \frac{k}{2} (2n - k + 1), \quad n \geq k
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

a) For **even order** magic squares $k = 2p$:

$$G := k \left(n - \frac{2p - 1}{2} \right). \tag{5}$$

In this case, the expression $n - \frac{2p - 1}{2}$ is never a natural number. Thus, there is no magic square of **consecutive even numbers** having perfect square sum of entries.

b) For **odd order** magic squares, $k = 2p + 1$

$$G := T(n) - T(n - k) = k \left(n - \frac{2p + 1 - 1}{2} \right) = k(n - p), \tag{6}$$

In this case, we can always find a natural number, such that $k(n - p)$ is a perfect square with $n - p \geq k$. In particular, for $n - p = k$, we have $G := k^2$, and the sum of all the entries is given as $T_{k^2} := k^4$.

From equations (3) and (6), we conclude that there are at least two ways of writing magic squares with all entries summing to a **perfect square**:

(i) *Magic squares with **consecutive odd numbers** starting from 1;*

(ii) *Magic squares with **consecutive natural numbers**.*

For the first case (i), the result is always possible in view of (3), i.e., we can always construct magic squares of any order with **odd numbers** entries starting from 1 resulting in **perfect square sum** of entries.

For the second case (ii). We can always write natural numbers from **consecutive odd numbers**. Let's suppose, we have $M := \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n - 3, 2n - 1\}$ be a set of n odd numbers. In this case a mid-point is $\frac{(1+2n-1)}{2} = n$. Total we have n elements. Then the first and last elements for the natural numbers are given by $n - \frac{n-1}{2} = \frac{n+1}{2}$ and $n + \frac{n-1}{2} = \frac{3n-1}{2}$. Obviously, in case of magic squares, $n = k^2$. The the set of natural numbers giving the same sum is $K := \left\{ \frac{k^2+1}{2}, \frac{k^2+3}{2}, \dots, \frac{3(k^2-1)}{2} - 1, \frac{3k^2-1}{2} \right\}$. This set has natural values only when k is odd number.

Summarizing, we have following result.

Result 1. For the **odd number** entries starting from 1, there is a magic square with perfect square sum of entries given by

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \textbf{Magic Square Order:} & k; \\
 \textbf{Odd numbers entries:} & M := \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2k^2 - 3, 2k^2 - 1\}; \\
 \textbf{Natural numbers entries:} & K := \left\{ \frac{k^2 + 1}{2}, \frac{k^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, \frac{3(k^2 - 1)}{2} - 1, \frac{3k^2 - 1}{2} \right\}; \\
 \textbf{Magic Square Sum:} & \mathbf{S}_{k \times k} := k^3; \\
 \textbf{Total Entries Sum:} & \mathbf{T}_{k^2} := k^4.
 \end{array}$$

For simplicity, let's represent the **uniformity** as,

$$\langle k, k^2, k^3, k^4 \rangle \tag{7}$$

where

- $k \rightarrow$ order of a magic square;
- $k^2 \rightarrow$ total number of entries;
- $k^3 \rightarrow$ magic square sum;
- $k^4 \rightarrow$ sum of all the entries of a magic square.

It happens with all the magic squares with **consecutive odd numbers** entries starting from 1. Also the same happens with **consecutive natural numbers** obtained based on odd order entries having the same magic sum. See the list below:

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. Order 3 , $\mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 27$, $\mathbf{T}_9 := 81 = 9^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 15, 17\}$ or $E := \{5, 6, \dots, 11, 13\}$ |
| 2. Order 4 , $\mathbf{S}_{4 \times 4} := 64$, $\mathbf{T}_{16} := 256 = 16^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31\}$ or $E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 43/2, 47/2\}$ |
| 3. Order 5 , $\mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 125$, $\mathbf{T}_{25} := 625 = 25^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 47, 49\}$ or $E := \{13, 14, \dots, 35, 37\}$ |
| 4. Order 6 , $\mathbf{S}_{6 \times 6} := 216$, $\mathbf{T}_{36} := 1296 = 36^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71\}$ or $E := \{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 103/2, 107/2\}$ |
| 5. Order 7 , $\mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 343$, $\mathbf{T}_{49} := 2401 = 49^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 95, 97\}$ or $E := \{25, 26, \dots, 71, 73\}$ |
| 6. Order 8 , $\mathbf{S}_{8 \times 8} := 512$, $\mathbf{T}_{64} := 4096 = 64^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$ or $E := \{65/2, 67/2, \dots, 187/2, 191/2\}$ |
| 7. Order 9 , $\mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 729$, $\mathbf{T}_{81} := 6561 = 81^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$ or $E := \{41, 42, \dots, 119, 121\}$ |
| 8. Order 10 , $\mathbf{S}_{10 \times 10} := 1000$, $\mathbf{T}_{100} := 10000 = 100^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 197, 199\}$ or $E := \{101/2, 103/2, \dots, 295/2, 299/2\}$ |
| 9. Order 11 , $\mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 1331$, $\mathbf{T}_{121} := 14641 = 121^2$, | $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 239, 241\}$ or $E := \{61, 62, \dots, 179, 181\}$ |

10. **Order 12**, $S_{12 \times 12} := 1728$, $T_{144} := 20736 = 144^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 285, 287\}$ or $E := \{145/2, 147/2, \dots, 427/2, 431/2\}$
11. **Order 13**, $S_{13 \times 13} := 2197$, $T_{169} := 28561 = 169^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 335, 337\}$ or $E := \{85, 86, \dots, 251, 253\}$
12. **Order 14**, $S_{14 \times 14} := 2744$, $T_{196} := 38416 = 196^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 389, 391\}$ or $E := \{197/2, 199/2, \dots, 583/2, 587/2\}$
13. **Order 15**, $S_{15 \times 15} := 3375$, $T_{225} := 50625 = 225^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 447, 449\}$ or $E := \{113, 114, \dots, 335, 337\}$
14. **Order 16**, $S_{16 \times 16} := 4096$, $T_{256} := 65536 = 256^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 509, 511\}$ or $E := \{257/2, 259/2, \dots, 763/2, 767/2\}$
15. **Order 17**, $S_{17 \times 17} := 4913$, $T_{289} := 83521 = 289^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 575, 577\}$ or $E := \{145, 146, \dots, 431, 433\}$
16. **Order 18**, $S_{18 \times 18} := 5832$, $T_{324} := 104976 = 324^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 645, 647\}$ or $E := \{325/2, 327/2, \dots, 967/2, 971/2\}$
17. **Order 19**, $S_{19 \times 19} := 6859$, $T_{361} := 130321 = 361^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 719, 721\}$ or $E := \{181, 182, \dots, 539, 541\}$
18. **Order 20**, $S_{20 \times 20} := 8000$, $T_{400} := 160000 = 400^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 797, 799\}$ or $E := \{401/2, 403/2, \dots, 1195/2, 1199/2\}$
19. **Order 21**, $S_{21 \times 21} := 9261$, $T_{441} := 194481 = 441^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 879, 881\}$ or $E := \{221, 222, \dots, 659, 661\}$
20. **Order 22**, $S_{22 \times 22} := 10648$, $T_{484} := 234256 = 484^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 965, 967\}$ or $E := \{485/2, 487/2, \dots, 1447/2, 1451/2\}$
21. **Order 23**, $S_{23 \times 23} := 12167$, $T_{529} := 279841 = 529^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1055, 1057\}$ or $E := \{265, 266, \dots, 791, 793\}$
22. **Order 24**, $S_{24 \times 24} := 13824$, $T_{576} := 331776 = 576^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1149, 1151\}$ or $E := \{577/2, 579/2, \dots, 1723/2, 1727/2\}$
23. **Order 25**, $S_{25 \times 25} := 15625$, $T_{625} := 390625 = 625^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1247, 1249\}$ or $E := \{313, 314, \dots, 935, 937\}$
24. **Order 26**, $S_{26 \times 26} := 17576$, $T_{676} := 456976 = 676^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1349, 1351\}$ or $E := \{677/2, 679/2, \dots, 2023/2, 2027/2\}$
25. **Order 27**, $S_{27 \times 27} := 19683$, $T_{729} := 531441 = 729^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1455, 1457\}$ or $E := \{365, 366, \dots, 1091, 1093\}$
26. **Order 28**, $S_{28 \times 28} := 21952$, $T_{784} := 614656 = 784^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1565, 1567\}$ or $E := \{785/2, 787/2, \dots, 2347/2, 2351/2\}$
27. **Order 29**, $S_{29 \times 29} := 24389$, $T_{841} := 707281 = 841^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1679, 1681\}$ or $E := \{421, 422, \dots, 1259, 1261\}$
28. **Order 30**, $S_{30 \times 30} := 27000$, $T_{900} := 810000 = 900^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1797, 1799\}$ or $E := \{901/2, 903/2, \dots, 2695/2, 2699/2\}$
29. **Order 31**, $S_{31 \times 31} := 29791$, $T_{961} := 923521 = 961^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1919, 1921\}$ or $E := \{481, 482, \dots, 1439, 1441\}$
30. **Order 32**, $S_{32 \times 32} := 32768$, $T_{1024} := 1048576 = 1024^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2045, 2047\}$ or $E := \{1025/2, 1027/2, \dots, 3067/2, 3071/2\}$
31. **Order 33**, $S_{33 \times 33} := 35937$, $T_{1089} := 1185921 = 1089^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2175, 2177\}$ or $E := \{545, 546, \dots, 1631, 1633\}$
32. **Order 34**, $S_{34 \times 34} := 39304$, $T_{1156} := 1336336 = 1156^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2309, 2311\}$ or $E := \{1157/2, 1159/2, \dots, 3463/2, 3467/2\}$
33. **Order 35**, $S_{35 \times 35} := 42875$, $T_{1225} := 1500625 = 1225^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2447, 2449\}$ or $E := \{613, 614, \dots, 1835, 1837\}$
34. **Order 36**, $S_{36 \times 36} := 46656$, $T_{1296} := 1679616 = 1296^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2589, 2591\}$ or $E := \{1297/2, 1299/2, \dots, 3883/2, 3887/2\}$
35. **Order 37**, $S_{37 \times 37} := 50653$, $T_{1369} := 1874161 = 1369^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2735, 2737\}$ or $E := \{685, 686, \dots, 2051, 2053\}$
36. **Order 38**, $S_{38 \times 38} := 54872$, $T_{1444} := 2085136 = 1444^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 2885, 2887\}$ or $E := \{1445/2, 1447/2, \dots, 4327/2, 4331/2\}$
37. **Order 39**, $S_{39 \times 39} := 59319$, $T_{1521} := 2313441 = 1521^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3039, 3041\}$ or $E := \{761, 762, \dots, 2279, 2281\}$
38. **Order 40**, $S_{40 \times 40} := 64000$, $T_{1600} := 2560000 = 1600^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3197, 3199\}$ or $E := \{1601/2, 1603/2, \dots, 4795/2, 4799/2\}$
39. **Order 41**, $S_{41 \times 41} := 68921$, $T_{1681} := 2825761 = 1681^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3359, 3361\}$ or $E := \{841, 842, \dots, 2519, 2521\}$
40. **Order 42**, $S_{42 \times 42} := 74088$, $T_{1764} := 3111696 = 1764^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3525, 3527\}$ or $E := \{1765/2, 1767/2, \dots, 5287/2, 5291/2\}$

41. **Order 43**, $S_{43 \times 43} := 79507$, $T_{1849} := 3418801 = 1849^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3695, 3697\}$ or $E := \{925, 926, \dots, 2771, 2773\}$
 42. **Order 44**, $S_{44 \times 44} := 85184$, $T_{1936} := 3748096 = 1936^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 3869, 3871\}$ or $E := \{1937/2, 1939/2, \dots, 5803/2, 5807/2\}$
 43. **Order 45**, $S_{45 \times 45} := 91125$, $T_{2025} := 4100625 = 2025^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 4047, 4049\}$ or $E := \{1013, 1014, \dots, 3035, 3037\}$
 44. **Order 46**, $S_{46 \times 46} := 97336$, $T_{2116} := 4477456 = 2116^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 4229, 4231\}$ or or $E := \{2117/2, 2119/2, \dots, 6343/2, 6347/2\}$
 45. **Order 47**, $S_{47 \times 47} := 103823$, $T_{2209} := 4879681 = 2209^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 4415, 4417\}$ or $E := \{1105, 1106, \dots, 3311, 3313\}$
- (8)

2.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries Satisfying Pythagorean Triples

In one of previous work [20], the author obtained the following result connecting magic squares and Pythagorean triples:

Result 2. *A general formula relating Pythagorean triples and magic squares given by*

$$F(n, k) := (n(2k + n), 2k(k + n), 2k(k + n) + n^2), k \in \mathbf{N}_+, \quad (9)$$

where n is the order of a magic square and k is the gap between two consecutive term of two consecutive Pythagorean triples representing same order magic squares. The right side of the function $F(n, k)$ is written in terms of a Pythagorean triples, i.e., (a, b, c) .

The entries of magic squares are given by

$$E_1(n, k) := \{4k(k + n) + 1, 4k(k + n) + 3, \dots, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 3, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 1\};$$

$$E_2(n, k) := \left\{4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 1}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3(n^2 - 1)}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3n^2 - 1}{2}\right\}.$$

The entries $E_1(n, k)$ are for all order magic squares resulting in **consecutive odd numbers**. The entries $E_2(n, k)$ are only for **odd order magic squares** resulting in **consecutive natural numbers**. In this case, the sum of entries is the same in both the situations. In view of this, there is a **uniformity property** given in (??), i.e., $\langle n, n^2, n^3, n^4 \rangle$. The **Pythagorean triples** given in (??) generates magic squares with entries given in $E_1(n, k)$ and $E_1(n, k)$ with sum of entries as **perfect squares**. The sum of these entries is **minimum** when $k = 1$.

2.3.1 Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares

For $k = 1$ in (13), there is minimum value resulting in a **perfect square sum** of entries magic square satisfying the **Pythagorean triples**. See below the list for the magic squares from orders 3 to 47:

1. **(8,15,17)** $\Rightarrow 17^2 - 8^2 = 15^2, 17 - 8 = 3^2$, **Order 3**, $S_{3 \times 3} := 75$, $T_9 := 15^2$,
 $E = \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}$ or $E = \{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$
2. **(10,24,26)** $\Rightarrow 26^2 - 10^2 = 24^2, 26 - 10 = 4^2$, **Order 4**, $S_{4 \times 4} := 144$, $T_{16} := 24^2$,
 $E = \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$ or $E = \{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 85/2, 87/2\}$
3. **(12,35,37)** $\Rightarrow 37^2 - 12^2 = 35^2, 37 - 12 = 5^2$, **Order 5**, $S_{5 \times 5} := 245$, $T_{25} := 35^2$,
 $E = \{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\}$ or $E = \{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$
4. **(14,48,50)** $\Rightarrow 50^2 - 14^2 = 48^2, 50 - 14 = 6^2$, **Order 6**, $S_{6 \times 6} := 384$, $T_{36} := 48^2$,
 $E = \{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\}$ or $E = \{93/2, 95/2, \dots, 161/2, 163/2\}$
5. **(16,63,65)** $\Rightarrow 65^2 - 16^2 = 63^2, 65 - 16 = 7^2$, **Order 7**, $S_{7 \times 7} := 567$, $T_{49} := 63^2$,
 $E = \{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\}$ or $E = \{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$
6. **(18,80,82)** $\Rightarrow 82^2 - 18^2 = 80^2, 82 - 18 = 8^2$, **Order 8**, $S_{8 \times 8} := 800$, $T_{64} := 80^2$,
 $E = \{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$ or $E = \{137/2, 139/2, \dots, 261/2, 263/2\}$
7. **(20,99,101)** $\Rightarrow 101^2 - 20^2 = 99^2, 101 - 20 = 9^2$, **Order 9**, $S_{9 \times 9} := 1089$, $T_{81} := 99^2$,
 $E = \{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$ or $E = \{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$
8. **(22,120,122)** $\Rightarrow 122^2 - 22^2 = 120^2, 122 - 22 = 10^2$, **Order 10**, $S_{10 \times 10} := 1440$, $T_{100} := 120^2$,
 $E = \{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\}$ or $E = \{189/2, 191/2, \dots, 385/2, 387/2\}$
9. **(24,143,145)** $\Rightarrow 145^2 - 24^2 = 143^2, 145 - 24 = 11^2$, **Order 11**, $S_{11 \times 11} := 1859$, $T_{121} := 143^2$,
 $E = \{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\}$ or $E = \{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$
10. **(26,168,170)** $\Rightarrow 170^2 - 26^2 = 168^2, 170 - 26 = 12^2$, **Order 12**, $S_{12 \times 12} := 2352$, $T_{144} := 168^2$,
 $E = \{53, 55, \dots, 337, 339\}$ or $E = \{249/2, 251/2, \dots, 533/2, 535/2\}$
11. **(28,195,197)** $\Rightarrow 197^2 - 28^2 = 195^2, 197 - 28 = 13^2$, **Order 13**, $S_{13 \times 13} := 2925$, $T_{169} := 195^2$,
 $E = \{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\}$ or $E = \{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$
12. **(30,224,226)** $\Rightarrow 226^2 - 30^2 = 224^2, 226 - 30 = 14^2$, **Order 14**, $S_{14 \times 14} := 3584$, $T_{196} := 224^2$,
 $E = \{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$ or $E = \{317/2, 319/2, \dots, 705/2, 707/2\}$
13. **(32,255,257)** $\Rightarrow 257^2 - 32^2 = 255^2, 257 - 32 = 15^2$, **Order 15**, $S_{15 \times 15} := 4335$, $T_{225} := 255^2$,
 $E = \{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$ or $E = \{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$
14. **(34,288,290)** $\Rightarrow 290^2 - 34^2 = 288^2, 290 - 34 = 16^2$, **Order 16**, $S_{16 \times 16} := 5184$, $T_{256} := 288^2$,
 $E = \{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$ or $E = \{393/2, 395/2, \dots, 901/2, 903/2\}$

15. **(36,323,325)** $\Rightarrow 325^2 - 36^2 = 323^2$, $325 - 36 = 17^2$, **Order 17**, $S_{17 \times 17} := 6137$, $T_{289} := 323^2$,
 $E = \{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\}$ or $E = \{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$
16. **(38,360,362)** $\Rightarrow 362^2 - 38^2 = 360^2$, $362 - 38 = 18^2$, **Order 18**, $S_{18 \times 18} := 7200$, $T_{324} := 360^2$,
 $E = \{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$ or $E = \{477/2, 479/2, \dots, 1121/2, 1123/2\}$
17. **(40,399,401)** $\Rightarrow 401^2 - 40^2 = 399^2$, $401 - 40 = 19^2$, **Order 19**, $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$, $T_{361} := 399^2$,
 $E = \{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\}$ or $E = \{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\}$
18. **(42,440,442)** $\Rightarrow 442^2 - 42^2 = 440^2$, $442 - 42 = 20^2$, **Order 20**, $S_{20 \times 20} := 9680$, $T_{400} := 440^2$,
 $E = \{85, 87, \dots, 881, 883\}$ or $E = \{569/2, 571/2, \dots, 1365/2, 1367/2\}$
19. **(44,483,485)** $\Rightarrow 485^2 - 44^2 = 483^2$, $485 - 44 = 21^2$, **Order 21**, $S_{21 \times 21} := 11109$, $T_{441} := 483^2$,
 $E = \{89, 91, \dots, 967, 969\}$ or $E = \{309, 310, \dots, 748, 749\}$
20. **(46,528,530)** $\Rightarrow 530^2 - 46^2 = 528^2$, $530 - 46 = 22^2$, **Order 22**, $S_{22 \times 22} := 12672$, $T_{484} := 528^2$,
 $E = \{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$ or $E = \{669/2, 671/2, \dots, 1633/2, 1635/2\}$
21. **(48,575,577)** $\Rightarrow 577^2 - 48^2 = 575^2$, $577 - 48 = 23^2$, **Order 23**, $S_{23 \times 23} := 14375$, $T_{529} := 575^2$,
 $E = \{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\}$ or $E = \{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\}$
22. **(50,624,626)** $\Rightarrow 626^2 - 50^2 = 624^2$, $626 - 50 = 24^2$, **Order 24**, $S_{24 \times 24} := 16224$, $T_{576} := 624^2$,
 $E = \{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\}$ or $E = \{777/2, 779/2, \dots, 1925/2, 1927/2\}$
23. **(52,675,677)** $\Rightarrow 677^2 - 52^2 = 675^2$, $677 - 52 = 25^2$, **Order 25**, $S_{25 \times 25} := 18225$, $T_{625} := 675^2$,
 $E = \{105, 107, \dots, 1351, 1353\}$ or $E = \{417, 418, \dots, 1040, 1041\}$
24. **(54,728,730)** $\Rightarrow 730^2 - 54^2 = 728^2$, $730 - 54 = 26^2$, **Order 26**, $S_{26 \times 26} := 20384$, $T_{676} := 728^2$,
 $E = \{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$ or $E = \{893/2, 895/2, \dots, 2241/2, 2243/2\}$
25. **(56,783,785)** $\Rightarrow 785^2 - 56^2 = 783^2$, $785 - 56 = 27^2$, **Order 27**, $S_{27 \times 27} := 22707$, $T_{729} := 783^2$,
 $E = \{113, 115, \dots, 1567, 1569\}$ or $E = \{477, 478, \dots, 1204, 1205\}$
26. **(58,840,842)** $\Rightarrow 842^2 - 58^2 = 840^2$, $842 - 58 = 28^2$, **Order 28**, $S_{28 \times 28} := 25200$, $T_{784} := 840^2$,
 $E = \{117, 119, \dots, 1681, 1683\}$ or $E = \{1017/2, 1019/2, \dots, 2581/2, 2583/2\}$
27. **(60,899,901)** $\Rightarrow 901^2 - 60^2 = 899^2$, $901 - 60 = 29^2$, **Order 29**, $S_{29 \times 29} := 27869$, $T_{841} := 899^2$,
 $E = \{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$ or $E = \{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$
28. **(62,960,962)** $\Rightarrow 962^2 - 62^2 = 960^2$, $962 - 62 = 30^2$, **Order 30**, $S_{30 \times 30} := 30720$, $T_{900} := 960^2$,
 $E = \{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$ or $E = \{1149/2, 1151/2, \dots, 2945/2, 2947/2\}$
29. **(64,1023,1025)** $\Rightarrow 1025^2 - 64^2 = 1023^2$, $1025 - 64 = 31^2$, **Order 31**, $S_{31 \times 31} := 33759$, $T_{961} := 1023^2$,
 $E = \{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ or $E = \{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\}$
30. **(66,1088,1090)** $\Rightarrow 1090^2 - 66^2 = 1088^2$, $1090 - 66 = 32^2$, **Order 32**, $S_{32 \times 32} := 36992$, $T_{1024} := 1088^2$,

- $E = \{133, 135, \dots, 2177, 2179\}$ or $E = \{1289/2, 1291/2, \dots, 3333/2, 3335/2\}$
31. **(68,1155,1157)** $\Rightarrow 1157^2 - 68^2 = 1155^2$, $1157 - 68 = 33^2$, **Order 33**, $S_{33 \times 33} := 40425$, $T_{1089} := 1155^2$,
 $E = \{137, 139, \dots, 2311, 2313\}$ or $E = \{681, 682, \dots, 1768, 1769\}$
32. **(70,1224,1226)** $\Rightarrow 1226^2 - 70^2 = 1224^2$, $1226 - 70 = 34^2$, **Order 34**, $S_{34 \times 34} := 44064$, $T_{1156} := 1224^2$,
 $E = \{141, 143, \dots, 2449, 2451\}$ or $E = \{1437/2, 1439/2, \dots, 3745/2, 3747/2\}$
33. **(72,1295,1297)** $\Rightarrow 1297^2 - 72^2 = 1295^2$, $1297 - 72 = 35^2$, **Order 35**, $S_{35 \times 35} := 47915$, $T_{1225} := 1295^2$,
 $E = \{145, 147, \dots, 2591, 2593\}$ or $E = \{757, 758, \dots, 1980, 1981\}$
34. **(74,1368,1370)** $\Rightarrow 1370^2 - 74^2 = 1368^2$, $1370 - 74 = 36^2$, **Order 36**, $S_{36 \times 36} := 51984$, $T_{1296} := 1368^2$,
 $E = \{149, 151, \dots, 2737, 2739\}$ or $E = \{1593/2, 1595/2, \dots, 4181/2, 4183/2\}$
35. **(76,1443,1445)** $\Rightarrow 1445^2 - 76^2 = 1443^2$, $1445 - 76 = 37^2$, **Order 37**, $S_{37 \times 37} := 56277$, $T_{1369} := 1443^2$,
 $E = \{153, 155, \dots, 2887, 2889\}$ or $E = \{837, 838, \dots, 2204, 2205\}$
36. **(78,1520,1522)** $\Rightarrow 1522^2 - 78^2 = 1520^2$, $1522 - 78 = 38^2$, **Order 38**, $S_{38 \times 38} := 60800$, $T_{1444} := 1520^2$,
 $E = \{157, 159, \dots, 3041, 3043\}$ or $E = \{1757/2, 1759/2, \dots, 4641/2, 4643/2\}$
37. **(80,1599,1601)** $\Rightarrow 1601^2 - 80^2 = 1599^2$, $1601 - 80 = 39^2$, **Order 39**, $S_{39 \times 39} := 65559$, $T_{1521} := 1599^2$,
 $E = \{161, 163, \dots, 3199, 3201\}$ or $E = \{921, 922, \dots, 2440, 2441\}$
38. **(82,1680,1682)** $\Rightarrow 1682^2 - 82^2 = 1680^2$, $1682 - 82 = 40^2$, **Order 40**, $S_{40 \times 40} := 70560$, $T_{1600} := 1680^2$,
 $E = \{165, 167, \dots, 3361, 3363\}$ or $E = \{1929/2, 1931/2, \dots, 5125/2, 5127/2\}$
39. **(84,1763,1765)** $\Rightarrow 1765^2 - 84^2 = 1763^2$, $1765 - 84 = 41^2$, **Order 41**, $S_{41 \times 41} := 75809$, $T_{1681} := 1763^2$,
 $E = \{169, 171, \dots, 3527, 3529\}$ or $E = \{1009, 1010, \dots, 2688, 2689\}$
40. **(86,1848,1850)** $\Rightarrow 1850^2 - 86^2 = 1848^2$, $1850 - 86 = 42^2$, **Order 42**, $S_{42 \times 42} := 81312$, $T_{1764} := 1848^2$,
 $E = \{173, 175, \dots, 3697, 3699\}$ or $E = \{2109/2, 2111/2, \dots, 5633/2, 5635/2\}$
41. **(88,1935,1937)** $\Rightarrow 1937^2 - 88^2 = 1935^2$, $1937 - 88 = 43^2$, **Order 43**, $S_{43 \times 43} := 87075$, $T_{1849} := 1935^2$,
 $E = \{177, 179, \dots, 3871, 3873\}$ or $E = \{1101, 1102, \dots, 2948, 2949\}$
42. **(90,2024,2026)** $\Rightarrow 2026^2 - 90^2 = 2024^2$, $2026 - 90 = 44^2$, **Order 44**, $S_{44 \times 44} := 93104$, $T_{1936} := 2024^2$,
 $E = \{181, 183, \dots, 4049, 4051\}$ or $E = \{2297/2, 2299/2, \dots, 6165/2, 6167/2\}$
43. **(92,2115,2117)** $\Rightarrow 2117^2 - 92^2 = 2115^2$, $2117 - 92 = 45^2$, **Order 45**, $S_{45 \times 45} := 99405$, $T_{2025} := 2115^2$,
 $E = \{185, 187, \dots, 4231, 4233\}$ or $E = \{1197, 1198, \dots, 3220, 3221\}$
44. **(94,2208,2210)** $\Rightarrow 2210^2 - 94^2 = 2208^2$, $2210 - 94 = 46^2$, **Order 46**, $S_{46 \times 46} := 105984$, $T_{2116} := 2208^2$,
 $E = \{189, 191, \dots, 4417, 4419\}$ or $E = \{2493/2, 2495/2, \dots, 6721/2, 6723/2\}$
45. **(96,2303,2305)** $\Rightarrow 2305^2 - 96^2 = 2303^2$, $2305 - 96 = 47^2$, **Order 47**, $S_{47 \times 47} := 112847$, $T_{2209} := 2303^2$,
 $E = \{193, 195, \dots, 4607, 4609\}$ or $E = \{1297, 1298, \dots, 3504, 3505\}$

$$\dots \dots \dots \quad (10)$$

2.4 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let p be an order of a magic square, i.e., $k = p^2$. Then from equations (4) or (5), we have

$$p\sqrt{\frac{2n - p^2 + 1}{2}} = p\sqrt{n - \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}} = t, \quad t \in \mathbf{N}_+, \quad n \geq p^2,$$

The sum of all entries of a magic square is given by

$$\mathbf{T}_1 + \mathbf{T}_1 + \dots + \mathbf{T}_{p^2}$$

where $\mathbf{T}_1 = n - p^2 + 1$ and $\mathbf{T}_{p^2} := n$.

Again, let's consider, $n = m^2 + \frac{p^2-1}{2}$, and then we have

$$G(m, p) := p\sqrt{\left(m^2 + \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{p^2 - 1}{2}\right)} = t, \quad t \in \mathbf{N}_+, \quad n \geq p^2. \quad (11)$$

In this case, how do we find the minimum value of m ? For simplicity, let's write,

$$L(n, k) := \left(\sqrt{k}, n - k + 1, n, \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}}, G(n, k)^2, \sqrt{G(n, k)}\right), \quad (12)$$

where $n = m^2 + \frac{p^2-1}{2}$, $k = p^2$ and p is the order of a magic square.

From above we observe that, if $\sqrt{G(n, k)}$ equals the order of a magic square then, we have a **uniformity case**. This only happens when $m = p$. And, first positive entry obtained from m give us a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Let's summarize above details in the following result.

Result 3. *Let's consider,*

$$L(n, k) := \left(\sqrt{k}, n - k + 1, n, \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}}, G(n, k)^2, \sqrt{G(n, k)}\right), \quad (13)$$

where $n = m^2 + \frac{p^2-1}{2}$, $k = p^2$ and p is the order of a magic square. The first positive values obtained by considering m , $m \in \mathbf{N}_+$ in expression (5) lead us to a magic square with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

For simplicity, let's write $L(a, b, c, d, e, f)$, for the representations given in expression (13), where

- $a \rightarrow$ Order of magic square;
- $b \rightarrow$ First member of a sequence;
- $c \rightarrow$ Last member of a sequence;
- $d \rightarrow$ Sum of magic square;
- $e \rightarrow$ Sum of all entries of a magic square;
- $f \rightarrow$ Uniformity, if $a = f$.

... (14)

According to formula given in equation (11), below is a list of odd order magic square with entries, magic sum and total sum resulting in magic squares with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries:

- | | | |
|--|-------------------------------|--|
| 1. Order 3 , $S_{3 \times 3} := 12$, | $T_9 := 36 = 6^2$, | $E := \{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$ |
| 2. Order 4 , $S_{4 \times 4} := 36$, | $T_{16} := 144 = 12^2$, | $E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$ |
| 3. Order 5 , $S_{5 \times 5} := 80$, | $T_{25} := 400 = 20^2$, | $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 27, 28\}$ |
| 4. Order 6 , $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$, | $T_{36} := 900 = 30^2$, | $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$ |
| 5. Order 7 , $S_{7 \times 7} := 175$, | $T_{49} := 1225 = 35^2$, | $E := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$ |
| 6. Order 8 , $S_{8 \times 8} := 288$, | $T_{64} := 2304 = 48^2$, | $E := \{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$ |
| 7. Order 9 , $S_{9 \times 9} := 441$, | $T_{81} := 3969 = 63^2$, | $E := \{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$ |
| 8. Order 10 , $S_{10 \times 10} := 640$, | $T_{100} := 6400 = 80^2$, | $E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$ |
| 9. Order 11 , $S_{11 \times 11} := 704$, | $T_{121} := 7744 = 88^2$, | $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 123, 124\}$ |
| 10. Order 12 , $S_{12 \times 12} := 972$, | $T_{144} := 11664 = 108^2$, | $E := \{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$ |
| 11. Order 13 , $S_{13 \times 13} := 1300$, | $T_{169} := 16900 = 130^2$, | $E := \{16, 17, \dots, 183, 184\}$ |
| 12. Order 14 , $S_{14 \times 14} := 1400$, | $T_{196} := 19600 = 140^2$, | $E := \{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$ |
| 13. Order 15 , $S_{15 \times 15} := 1815$, | $T_{225} := 27225 = 165^2$, | $E := \{9, 10, \dots, 232, 233\}$ |
| 14. Order 16 , $S_{16 \times 16} := 2304$, | $T_{256} := 36864 = 192^2$, | $E := \{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$ |
| 15. Order 17 , $S_{17 \times 17} := 2448$, | $T_{289} := 41616 = 204^2$, | $E := \{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$ |
| 16. Order 18 , $S_{18 \times 18} := 3042$, | $T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2$, | $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$ |
| 17. Order 19 , $S_{19 \times 19} := 3724$, | $T_{361} := 70756 = 266^2$, | $E := \{16, 17, \dots, 375, 376\}$ |
| 18. Order 20 , $S_{20 \times 20} := 4500$, | $T_{400} := 90000 = 300^2$, | $E := \{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$ |
| 19. Order 21 , $S_{21 \times 21} := 4725$, | $T_{441} := 99225 = 315^2$, | $E := \{5, 6, \dots, 444, 445\}$ |
| 20. Order 22 , $S_{22 \times 22} := 5632$, | $T_{484} := 123904 = 352^2$, | $E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$ |

21. **Order 23**, $S_{23 \times 23} := 6647$, $T_{529} := 152881 = 391^2$, $E := \{25, 26, \dots, 552, 553\}$
 22. **Order 24**, $S_{24 \times 24} := 6936$, $T_{576} := 166464 = 408^2$, $E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$
 23. **Order 25**, $S_{25 \times 25} := 8100$, $T_{625} := 202500 = 450^2$, $E := \{12, 13, \dots, 635, 636\}$
 24. **Order 26**, $S_{26 \times 26} := 9386$, $T_{676} := 244036 = 494^2$, $E := \{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$
 25. **Order 27**, $S_{27 \times 27} := 10800$, $T_{729} := 291600 = 540^2$, $E := \{36, 37, \dots, 763, 764\}$
 26. **Order 28**, $S_{28 \times 28} := 11200$, $T_{784} := 313600 = 560^2$, $E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$
 27. **Order 29**, $S_{29 \times 29} := 12789$, $T_{841} := 370881 = 609^2$, $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 860, 861\}$
 28. **Order 30**, $S_{30 \times 30} := 14520$, $T_{900} := 435600 = 660^2$, $E := \{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$
 29. **Order 31**, $S_{31 \times 31} := 15004$, $T_{961} := 465124 = 682^2$, $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 963, 964\}$
 30. **Order 32**, $S_{32 \times 32} := 16928$, $T_{1024} := 541696 = 736^2$, $E := \{35/2, 37/2, \dots, 2079/2, 2081/2\}$
 31. **Order 33**, $S_{33 \times 33} := 19008$, $T_{1089} := 627264 = 792^2$, $E := \{32, 33, \dots, 1119, 1120\}$
 32. **Order 34**, $S_{34 \times 34} := 21250$, $T_{1156} := 722500 = 850^2$, $E := \{95/2, 97/2, \dots, 2403/2, 2405/2\}$
 33. **Order 35**, $S_{35 \times 35} := 21875$, $T_{1225} := 765625 = 875^2$, $E := \{13, 14, \dots, 1236, 1237\}$
 34. **Order 36**, $S_{36 \times 36} := 24336$, $T_{1296} := 876096 = 936^2$, $E := \{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 2645/2, 2647/2\}$
 35. **Order 37**, $S_{37 \times 37} := 26973$, $T_{1369} := 998001 = 999^2$, $E := \{45, 46, \dots, 1412, 1413\}$
 36. **Order 38**, $S_{38 \times 38} := 27702$, $T_{1444} := 1052676 = 1026^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 2899/2, 2901/2\}$
 37. **Order 39**, $S_{39 \times 39} := 30576$, $T_{1521} := 1192464 = 1092^2$, $E := \{24, 25, \dots, 1543, 1544\}$
 38. **Order 40**, $S_{40 \times 40} := 33640$, $T_{1600} := 1345600 = 1160^2$, $E := \{83/2, 85/2, \dots, 3279/2, 3281/2\}$
 39. **Order 41**, $S_{41 \times 41} := 34481$, $T_{1681} := 1413721 = 1189^2$, $E := \{1, 2, \dots, 1680, 1681\}$
 40. **Order 42**, $S_{42 \times 42} := 37800$, $T_{1764} := 1587600 = 1260^2$, $E := \{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 3561/2, 3563/2\}$
 41. **Order 43**, $S_{43 \times 43} := 41323$, $T_{1849} := 1776889 = 1333^2$, $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 1884, 1885\}$
 42. **Order 44**, $S_{44 \times 44} := 45056$, $T_{1936} := 1982464 = 1408^2$, $E := \{113/2, 115/2, \dots, 3981/2, 3983/2\}$
 43. **Order 45**, $S_{45 \times 45} := 46080$, $T_{2025} := 2073600 = 1440^2$, $E := \{12, 13, \dots, 2035, 2036\}$
 44. **Order 46**, $S_{46 \times 46} := 50094$, $T_{2116} := 2304324 = 1518^2$, $E := \{63/2, 65/2, \dots, 4291/2, 4293/2\}$
 45. **Order 47**, $S_{47 \times 47} := 54332$, $T_{2209} := 2553604 = 1598^2$, $E := \{52, 53, \dots, 2259, 2260\}$
- (15)

The letter **E** represents **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries; **S** represents magic square sum and **T** represents sum of entries as **perfect square sum**. In this case the sum of entries of magic squares are **minimum perfect square sum**

Remark 2.1. *In all cases, we use **consecutive natural numbers** starting from 1. Amongst the magic squares*

studied here the magic square of order 7 is the only ones starting with the number 1 that yield a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. According to Sloane [2], the next magic square with **consecutive natural numbers** entries starting with the number 1 that yields a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries are of orders, 7, 41, 239, etc. It should be noted that we are working with natural numbers entries for the magic squares. The magic square of order 3 is the only magic squares, where the **minimum perfect square sum** of entries is same in both the cases, such as **uniformity property** and **Pythagorean triples**. There are only two magic squares where the **minimum perfect square sum** of entries starts from 0. These magic squares are of orders 3 and 17.

Remark 2.2. Above there are three types of Lists of magic squares given in (8), (12) and (4). In each case we always have magic squares with **perfect square sum** of entries. All the three Lists (8), (12) and (14) covers all order magic squares. The difference is that the list (8) satisfy **uniformity property** given in (6). The List (12) brings magic squares with **minimum perfect sum** of entries. The list (14) is related with **Pythagorean triples**. It brings magics squares with **least** values of entries with **perfect square sum** satisfying the **Pythagorean theorem**. These are obtained by taking $k = 1$ in (13). $k = 2$ in (13), the magic square generated are with higher values of entries.

Below are magic squares of orders 3 to 31 with **consecutive odd numbers** entries starting from 1. In all these case, we get a magic sum as a **third power** of order of a magic square, i.e., if the magic square is of order k , then the magic sum is k^3 . In case of odd order magic squares, there are two more possibilities are written. One with **consecutive natural number entries** and another with **minimum perfect square magic sum**. In each case, the **Pythagorean triples** are given. Then these **Pythagorean triples** are analysed to check further existence of different magic squares.

Write magic squares with **perfect square sum** of entries in the following cases:

- (i) **consecutive odd numbers** entries with **uniformity property**;
- (ii) **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries with **uniformity property**;
- (iii) **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries with **minimum perfect square sum**;
- (iv) **consecutive odd numbers** entries with least value of entries satisfy **Pythagoras theorem**;
- (v) **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries with least value of satisfying **Pythagoras theorem**.

The item (v) is not done here. It is left for the readers. It can be done on the similar lines of items (ii) or (iii). In case of item (i) the odd numbers starts from 1, while in case of item (iv), they are not necessarily start from 1.

Remark 2.3.

3 Magic Squares of Order 3

This section brings magic squares of order 3 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (8), (10) and (15).

3.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 1 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 3, \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 27, \quad T_9 := 81 = 9^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 15, 17\} \text{ or } E := \{5, 6, \dots, 11, 13\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 3 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 3.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 15, 17\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{5, 6, \dots, 11, 13\}$, the magic squares of order 3 are given by

			27
3	13	11	27
17	9	1	27
7	5	15	27
27	27	27	27

			27
6	11	10	27
13	9	5	27
8	7	12	27
27	27	27	27

The magic squares of order 3 given in Examples 3.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 27 = 3^3; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 27 = 81 = 9^2 = 3^4;$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 3.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 3, 3^2, 3^3, 3^4 \rangle$.

3.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 1 given in List (10):

$$(8, 15, 17) \Rightarrow 17^2 - 8^2 = 15^2, \quad 17 - 8 = 3^2, \quad \text{Order } 3, \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 75, \quad T_9 := 15^2, \\ E = \{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\} \text{ or } E = \{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 3 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 3.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{17, 19, \dots, 31, 33\}$, and **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{21, 22, \dots, 28, 29\}$, the magic squares of order 3 are given by

			75
23	33	19	75
21	25	29	75
31	17	27	75
75	75	75	75

			75
24	29	22	75
23	25	27	75
28	21	26	75
75	75	75	75

The magic squares of order 3 given in Examples 3.2 are with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 27 = 3^3; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 27 = 81 = 9^2 = 3^4;$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 3.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (8,15,17)**, i.e., $8^2 + 15^2 = 17^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

Remark 3.1. We observe that in both the cases, i.e., **uniformity** and **Pythagorean triples**, the sums are same. But is it not true in general. This shall be seen in further order magic squares given in subsequent sections.

3.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 1 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 3, } S_{3 \times 3} := 12, \quad T_9 := 36 = 6^2, \quad E := \{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 3 given below.

Example 3.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$, the magic square of order 3 is given by

			12
1	6	5	12
8	4	0	12
3	2	7	12
12	12	12	12

The magic square of order 3 given in Example 3.3 is with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. See below the details:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 12; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 12 = 36 = 6^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

Remark 3.2. It is the first example with entries starts from 0. The same will happen again with the magic square of order 17.

4 Magic Squares of Order 4

This section brings magic squares of order 4 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

4.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 2 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 4, \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 64, \quad T_{16} := 256 = 16^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 29, 31\} \text{ or } E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 43/2, 47/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 4 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 4.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 29, 31\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 43/2, 47/2\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 are given by

		64	64	64	64
	13	23	1	27	64
64	3	25	15	21	64
64	31	5	19	9	64
64	17	11	29	7	64
	64	64	64	64	64

		64	64	64	64
	14.5	19.5	8.5	21.5	64
64	9.5	20.5	15.5	18.5	64
64	23.5	10.5	17.5	12.5	64
64	16.5	13.5	22.5	11.5	64
	64	64	64	64	64

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 given in Example 4.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 64 = 4^3; \quad T_{16} := 256 = 16^2 = 4^4.$$

Also the magic squares given in Example 4.1 satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 4, 4^2, 4^3, 4^4 \rangle$.

4.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 2 given in List (10):

$$(10, 24, 26) \Rightarrow 26^2 - 10^2 = 24^2, \quad 26 - 10 = 4^2, \quad \text{Order 4, } S_{4 \times 4} := 144, \quad T_{16} := 24^2,$$

$$E = \{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\} \text{ or } E = \{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 85/2, 87/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 4 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 4.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{21, 23, \dots, 49, 51\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 85/2, 87/2\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 are given by

		144	144	144	144
	33	43	21	47	144
144	23	45	35	41	144
144	51	25	39	29	144
144	37	31	49	27	144
	144	144	144	144	144

		144	144	144	144
	34.5	39.5	28.5	41.5	144
144	29.5	40.5	35.5	38.5	144
144	43.5	30.5	37.5	32.5	144
144	36.5	33.5	42.5	31.5	144
	144	144	144	144	144

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 given in Example 4.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 144 = 12^2; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 144 = 576 = 24^2$$

The magic squares given in Example 4.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (10,24,26)**, i.e., $10^2 + 24^2 = 26^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

4.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 2 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 4, } S_{4 \times 4} := 36, \quad T_{16} := 144 = 12^2, \quad E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 4 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 4.3. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 is given by

		36	36	36	36
	7.5	12.5	1.5	14.5	36
36	2.5	13.5	8.5	11.5	36
36	16.5	3.5	10.5	5.5	36
36	9.5	6.5	15.5	4.5	36
	36	36	36	36	36

The magic square of order 4 given in Example 4.3 is **pandiagonal** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. See below the details:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 36 = 6^2; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 36 = 144 = 12^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

5 Magic Squares of Order 5

This section brings magic squares of order 5 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

5.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 3 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 5, \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 125, \quad T_{25} := 625 = 25^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 47, 49\} \text{ or } E := \{13, 14, \dots, 35, 37\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 5 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 5.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 15, 17\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{13, 14, \dots, 35, 37\}$, the magic squares of order 5 are given by

		125	125	125	125	125
	1	17	23	39	45	125
125	33	49	5	11	27	125
125	15	21	37	43	9	125
125	47	3	19	25	31	125
125	29	35	41	7	13	125
	125	125	125	125	125	125

		125	125	125	125	125
	13	21	24	32	35	125
125	29	37	15	18	26	125
125	20	23	31	34	17	125
125	36	14	22	25	18	125
125	27	30	33	16	19	125
	125	125	125	125	125	125

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 given in Example 5.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are of equal sum. See the details below:

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 125 = 5^3; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 125 = 625 = 25^2 = 5^4.$$

The magic squares given in Example 5.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 5, 5^2, 5^3, 5^4 \rangle$.

5.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 3 given in List (10):

$$(12, 35, 37) \Rightarrow 37^2 - 12^2 = 35^2, \quad 37 - 12 = 5^2, \quad \text{Order 5}, \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 245, \quad T_{25} := 35^2,$$

$$E = \{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\} \text{ or } E = \{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 5 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 5.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{25, 27, \dots, 71, 73\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{37, 38, \dots, 60, 61\}$, the magic squares of order 5 are given by

		245	245	245	245	245
	25	37	49	61	73	245
245	59	71	33	35	47	245
245	43	45	57	69	31	245
245	67	29	41	53	55	245
245	51	63	65	27	39	245
	245	245	245	245	245	245

		245	245	245	245	245
	37	43	49	55	61	245
245	54	60	41	42	48	245
245	46	47	53	59	40	245
245	58	39	45	51	52	245
245	50	56	57	38	44	245
	245	245	245	245	245	245

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 given in Example 5.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 245; \quad T_{25} = 5 \times 245 = 1225 = 35^2.$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 5.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (12,35,37)**, i.e., $12^2 + 35^2 = 37^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

5.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 3 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 5, } S_{5 \times 5} := 80, \quad T_{25} := 400 = 20^2, \quad E := \{4, 5, \dots, 27, 28\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 5 with **natural numbers entries**.

Example 5.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{4, 5, 6, \dots, 27, 28\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 is given by

		80	80	80	80	80
	4	10	16	22	28	80
80	21	27	8	9	15	80
80	13	14	20	26	7	80
80	25	6	12	18	19	80
80	17	23	24	5	11	80
	80	80	80	80	80	80

The **panidagoal** magic square of order 5 given in Example 5.3 is **pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. See the details below

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 80; \quad T_{25} = 5 \times 80 = 400 = 20^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

6 Magic Squares of Order 6

This section brings magic squares of order 6 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

6.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 4 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 6, \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 216, \quad T_{36} := 1296 = 36^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71\} \text{ or } E := \{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 103/2, 107/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 6 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 6.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 69, 71\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 103/2, 107/2\}$, the magic squares of order 6 are given by

						216
1	45	55	67	33	15	216
57	13	69	27	41	9	216
23	11	25	53	61	43	216
63	31	7	47	19	49	216
37	65	21	5	59	29	216
35	51	39	17	3	71	216
216	216	216	216	216	216	216

						216
18.5	52.5	51.5	50.5	19.5	23.5	216
47.5	25.5	45.5	26.5	28.5	42.5	216
41.5	40.5	32.5	33.5	37.5	30.5	216
35.5	31.5	38.5	39.5	34.5	36.5	216
24.5	43.5	27.5	44.5	46.5	29.5	216
48.5	22.5	20.5	21.5	49.5	53.5	216
216	216	216	216	216	216	216

The magic squares of order 6 given in Example 6.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 216 = 6^3; \quad T_{625} := 6 \times 216 = 31441 = 1296 = 36^2 = 6^4.$$

The magic squares given in Example 6.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 6, 6^2, 6^3, 6^4 \rangle$.

6.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 4 given in List (10):

$$(14, 48, 50) \Rightarrow 50^2 - 14^2 = 48^2, \quad 50 - 14 = 6^2, \quad \text{Order } 6, \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 384, \quad T_{36} := 48^2,$$

$$E = \{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\} \text{ or } E = \{93/2, 95/2, \dots, 161/2, 163/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 6 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 6.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{29, 31, \dots, 97, 99\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{93/2, 95/2, \dots, 161/2, 163/2\}$, the magic squares of order 6 are given by

						384
29	97	95	93	31	39	384
87	43	83	45	49	77	384
75	73	57	59	67	53	384
63	55	69	71	61	65	384
41	79	47	81	85	51	384
89	37	33	35	91	99	384
384	384	384	384	384	384	384

						384
46.5	80.5	79.5	78.5	47.5	51.5	384
75.5	53.5	73.5	54.5	56.5	70.5	384
69.5	68.5	60.5	61.5	65.5	58.5	384
63.5	59.5	66.5	67.5	62.5	64.5	384
52.5	71.5	55.5	72.5	74.5	57.5	384
76.5	50.5	48.5	49.5	77.5	81.5	384
384	384	384	384	384	384	384

The magic squares of order 6 given in Example 6.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. Both the examples, are with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 384; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 384 = 2304 = 48^2$$

The magic squares given in Example 6.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (14,48,50)**, i.e., $14^2 + 48^2 = 50^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

6.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 4 given in List (15):

4.

$$\text{Order 6, } S_{6 \times 6} := 150, \quad T_{36} := 900 = 30^2, \quad E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 6 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 6.3. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$, a magic square of order 6 is given by

						150
7.5	41.5	40.5	39.5	8.5	12.5	150
36.5	14.5	34.5	15.5	17.5	31.5	150
30.5	29.5	21.5	22.5	26.5	19.5	150
24.5	20.5	27.5	28.5	23.5	25.5	150
13.5	32.5	16.5	33.5	35.5	18.5	150
37.5	11.5	9.5	10.5	38.5	42.5	150
150	150	150	150	150	150	150

The magic square of order 6 given in Example 6.3 is with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries.

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 150; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 150 = 600 = 30^2$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

7 Magic Squares of Order 7

This section brings magic squares of order 7 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

7.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 5 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 7, \quad S_{7 \times 7} := 343, \quad T_{49} := 2401 = 49^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 95, 97\} \text{ or } E := \{25, 26, \dots, 71, 73\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 7 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 7.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 95, 97\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{25, 26, \dots, 71, 73\}$, the magic squares of order 7 are given by

		343	343	343	343	343	343	343
	1	17	33	49	65	81	97	343
343	79	95	13	15	31	47	63	343
343	45	61	77	93	11	27	29	343
343	25	41	43	59	75	91	9	343
343	89	7	23	39	55	57	73	343
343	69	71	87	5	21	37	53	343
343	35	51	67	83	85	3	19	343
	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343

		343	343	343	343	343	343	343
	25	33	41	49	57	65	73	343
343	64	72	31	32	40	48	56	343
343	47	55	63	71	30	38	39	343
343	37	45	46	54	62	70	29	343
343	69	28	36	44	52	53	61	343
343	59	60	68	27	35	43	51	343
343	42	50	58	66	67	26	34	343
	343	343	343	343	343	343	343	343

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7 given in Example 7.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the examples are with equal magic sums. See the details below:

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 343 = 7^3; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 343 = 2401 = 49^2 = 7^4.$$

The magic squares given in Example 7.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 7, 7^2, 7^3, 7^4 \rangle$.

7.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 5 given in List (10):

$$(16, 63, 65) \Rightarrow 65^2 - 16^2 = 63^2, \quad 65 - 16 = 7^2, \quad \text{Order 7, } S_{7 \times 7} := 567, \quad T_{49} := 63^2,$$

$$E = \{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\} \text{ or } E = \{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 7 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 7.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{33, 35, \dots, 127, 129\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{57, 58, \dots, 104, 105\}$, the magic squares of order 7 are given by

		567	567	567	567	567	567	567
	33	49	65	81	97	113	129	567
567	111	127	45	47	63	79	95	567
567	77	93	109	125	43	59	61	567
567	57	73	75	91	107	123	41	567
567	121	39	55	71	87	89	105	567
567	101	103	119	37	53	69	85	567
567	67	83	99	115	117	35	51	567
	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567

		567	567	567	567	567	567	567
	57	65	73	81	89	97	105	567
567	96	104	63	64	72	80	88	567
567	79	87	95	103	62	70	71	567
567	69	77	78	86	94	102	61	567
567	101	60	68	76	84	85	93	567
567	91	92	100	59	67	75	83	567
567	74	82	90	98	99	58	66	567
	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567

The **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7 given in Example 7.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 567 \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 567 = 2304 = 48^2.$$

The magic squares given in Example 7.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (14,48,50)**, i.e., $56^2 + 783^2 = 785^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

7.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 5 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 7, } S_{7 \times 7} := 175, T_{49} := 1225 = 35^2, E := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 7 with **natural numbers entries**.

Example 7.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, 48, 49\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 is given by

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

The magic square of order 7 given in Example 7.3 is **pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. This is one of the example with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries starting from the number 1.

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 175; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 175 = 2401 = 1225 = 35^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

8 Magic Squares of Order 8

This section brings magic squares of order 8 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

8.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 6 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 8, \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 512, \quad T_{64} := 4096 = 64^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\} \text{ or } E := \{65/2, 67/2, \dots, 187/2, 191/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 8 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 8.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{65/2, 67/2, \dots, 187/2, 191/2\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 are given by

		512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512
	57	79	1	119	41	95	17	103	512
512	7	113	63	73	23	97	47	89	512
512	127	9	71	49	111	25	87	33	512
512	65	55	121	15	81	39	105	31	512
512	59	77	3	117	43	93	19	101	512
512	5	115	61	75	21	99	45	91	512
512	125	11	69	51	109	27	85	35	512
512	67	53	123	13	83	37	107	29	512
	512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512

		512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512
	60.5	71.5	32.5	91.5	52.5	79.5	40.5	83.5	512
512	35.5	88.5	63.5	68.5	43.5	80.5	55.5	76.5	512
512	95.5	36.5	67.5	56.5	87.5	44.5	75.5	48.5	512
512	64.5	59.5	92.5	39.5	72.5	51.5	84.5	47.5	512
512	61.5	70.5	33.5	90.5	53.5	78.5	41.5	82.5	512
512	34.5	89.5	62.5	69.5	42.5	81.5	54.5	77.5	512
512	94.5	37.5	66.5	57.5	86.5	45.5	74.5	49.5	512
512	65.5	58.5	93.5	38.5	73.5	50.5	85.5	46.5	512
	512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512	512

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 given in Example 8.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 4 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{8 \times 8} = 512 = 8^3; \quad T_{64} = 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2 = 8^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 256; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2.$$

The magic squares given in Example 8.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 8, 8^2, 8^3, 8^4 \rangle$.

8.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 6 given in List (10):

$$(18, 80, 82) \Rightarrow 82^2 - 18^2 = 80^2, \quad 82 - 18 = 8^2, \quad \text{Order } 8, \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 800, \quad T_{64} := 80^2,$$

$$E = \{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\} \text{ or } E = \{137/2, 139/2, \dots, 261/2, 263/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 8 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 8.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{137/2, 139/2, \dots, 261/2, 263/2\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 are given by

		800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800
	67	117	107	45	89	159	145	71	800
800	87	161	143	73	61	123	101	51	800
800	37	115	125	59	79	137	151	97	800
800	81	135	153	95	43	109	131	53	800
800	111	41	55	129	133	83	93	155	800
800	139	77	99	149	113	39	57	127	800
800	121	63	49	103	163	85	75	141	800
800	157	91	69	147	119	65	47	105	800
	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800

		800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800
	83.5	108.5	103.5	72.5	94.5	129.5	122.5	85.5	800
800	93.5	130.5	121.5	86.5	80.5	111.5	100.5	75.5	800
800	68.5	107.5	112.5	79.5	89.5	118.5	125.5	98.5	800
800	90.5	117.5	126.5	97.5	71.5	104.5	115.5	76.5	800
800	105.5	70.5	77.5	114.5	116.5	91.5	96.5	127.5	800
800	119.5	88.5	99.5	124.5	106.5	69.5	78.5	113.5	800
800	110.5	81.5	74.5	101.5	131.5	92.5	87.5	120.5	800
800	128.5	95.5	84.5	123.5	109.5	82.5	73.5	102.5	800
	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 given in Example 8.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are not magic square, but sum of their entries are same. Moreover, the the blocks of order 2×4 are of equal sums as of magic square of order 8. See below the details

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 800; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$T_{16} := 1600 = 40^2.$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 8.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (56,783,785)**, i.e., $56^2 + 783^2 = 785^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Moreover, both the magic squares are **bimagic** with their respective **bimagic sums**, $Sb_{8 \times 8} = 90920$ and $Sb_{8 \times 8} = 82730$. Even though the magic sums are same but the **bimagic** sums are different.

8.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 6 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 8, } S_{8 \times 8} := 288, \quad T_{64} := 2304 = 48^2, \quad E := \{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 8 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 8.3. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$, a **pandiagonal magic square of order 8** is given by

		288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288
	32.5	43.5	4.5	63.5	24.5	51.5	12.5	55.5	288
288	7.5	60.5	35.5	40.5	15.5	52.5	27.5	48.5	288
288	67.5	8.5	39.5	28.5	59.5	16.5	47.5	20.5	288
288	36.5	31.5	64.5	11.5	44.5	23.5	56.5	19.5	288
288	33.5	42.5	5.5	62.5	25.5	50.5	13.5	54.5	288
288	6.5	61.5	34.5	41.5	14.5	53.5	26.5	49.5	288
288	66.5	9.5	38.5	29.5	58.5	17.5	46.5	21.5	288
288	37.5	30.5	65.5	10.5	45.5	22.5	57.5	18.5	288
	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288	288

The magic square of order 8 given in Example 8.3 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 288; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 144; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 144 = 576 = 24^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

9 Magic Squares of Order 9

This section brings magic squares of order 9 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

9.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 7 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 9, \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 729, \quad T_{81} := 6561 = 81^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\} \text{ or } E := \{41, 42, \dots, 119, 121\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 9 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 9.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{41, 42, \dots, 119, 121\}$, the **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9 are given by

		729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729
	15	97	131	121	47	75	71	153	19	729
729	73	125	45	23	69	151	129	13	101	729
729	155	21	67	99	127	17	43	77	123	729
729	27	55	161	133	5	105	83	111	49	729
729	103	137	3	53	81	109	159	25	59	729
729	113	51	79	57	157	29	1	107	135	729
729	39	85	119	145	35	63	95	141	7	729
729	61	149	33	11	93	139	117	37	89	729
729	143	9	91	87	115	41	31	65	147	729
	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729

		729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729
	48	89	106	101	64	78	76	117	50	729
729	77	103	63	52	75	116	105	47	91	729
729	118	51	74	90	104	49	62	79	102	729
729	54	68	121	107	43	93	82	96	65	729
729	92	109	42	67	81	95	120	53	70	729
729	97	66	80	69	119	55	41	94	108	729
729	60	83	100	113	58	72	88	111	44	729
729	71	115	57	46	87	110	99	59	85	729
729	112	45	86	84	98	61	56	73	114	729
	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729	729

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9 given in Example 9.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums, and the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 729 = 9^3; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 729 = 6561 = 81^2 = 9^4;$$

$$S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := 243; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 243 = 729 = 27^2.$$

The magic squares given in Example 9.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 9, 9^2, 9^3, 9^4 \rangle$.

9.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 7 given in List (10):

$$(20, 99, 101) \Rightarrow 101^2 - 20^2 = 99^2, \quad 101 - 20 = 9^2, \quad \text{Order } 9, \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 1089, \quad T_{81} := 99^2,$$

$$E = \{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\} \text{ or } E = \{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 9 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 9.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$, the magic squares of order 9 are given by

									1089
57	181	143	189	97	59	123	85	155	1089
195	103	65	129	91	161	45	169	131	1089
117	79	149	51	175	137	201	109	71	1089
145	53	183	61	185	99	157	119	87	1089
67	191	105	163	125	93	133	41	171	1089
151	113	81	139	47	177	73	197	111	1089
179	147	55	95	63	187	83	159	121	1089
101	69	193	89	165	127	167	135	43	1089
77	153	115	173	141	49	107	75	199	1089
1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089

									1089
89	151	132	155	109	90	122	103	138	1089
158	112	93	125	106	141	83	145	126	1089
119	100	135	86	148	129	161	115	96	1089
133	87	152	91	153	110	139	120	104	1089
94	156	113	142	123	107	127	81	146	1089
136	117	101	130	84	149	97	159	116	1089
150	134	88	108	92	154	102	140	121	1089
111	95	157	105	143	124	144	128	82	1089
99	137	118	147	131	85	114	98	160	1089
1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 9 given in Example 9.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 3 aren't magic squares, but sum of 9 members in each case are the same as of magic square. See below the details:

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1089; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2;$$

$$T_9 := 1089 = 33^2.$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 9.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (20,99,101)**, i.e., $20^2 + 99^2 = 101^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Moreover, the magic squares given in Example 9.2 are **bimagic** with their respective **bimagic sums**, $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 151449$ and $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 136689$. Even though the magic sums are same but the **bimagic** sums are different.

9.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 7 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 9, } S_{9 \times 9} := 441, \quad T_{81} := 3969 = 63^2, \quad E := \{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 9.

Example 9.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{9, 10, 11, \dots, 88, 89\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

		441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
	10	26	30	41	45	61	69	76	83	441
441	42	49	56	64	80	84	14	18	34	441
441	68	72	88	15	22	29	37	53	57	441
441	28	17	21	59	36	52	87	67	74	441
441	60	40	47	82	71	75	32	9	25	441
441	86	63	79	33	13	20	55	44	48	441
441	19	35	12	50	54	43	78	85	65	441
441	51	58	38	73	89	66	23	27	16	441
441	77	81	70	24	31	11	46	62	39	441
	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441

The magic square of order 9 given in Example 9.3 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 441; \quad T_{729} := 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 147; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 147 = 441 = 21^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

10 Magic Squares of Order 10

This section brings magic squares of order 10 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

10.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 8 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 10, \quad S_{10 \times 10} := 1000, \quad T_{100} := 10000 = 100^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 197, 199\} \text{ or } E := \{101/2, 103/2, \dots, 295/2, 299/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 10 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 10.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 197, 199\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{101/2, 103/2, \dots, 295/2, 299/2\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 10 are given by

181	171	31	167	35	27	7	195	3	183
25	93	115	37	155	77	131	53	139	175
177	43	149	99	109	59	133	83	125	23
21	163	45	107	85	147	61	123	69	179
191	101	91	157	51	117	75	141	67	9
1	95	113	39	153	79	129	55	137	199
185	41	151	97	111	57	135	81	127	15
13	161	47	105	87	145	63	121	71	187
189	103	89	159	49	119	73	143	65	11
17	29	169	33	165	173	193	5	197	19

140.5	135.5	65.5	133.5	67.5	63.5	53.5	147.5	51.5	141.5
62.5	96.5	107.5	68.5	127.5	88.5	115.5	76.5	119.5	137.5
138.5	71.5	124.5	99.5	104.5	79.5	116.5	91.5	112.5	61.5
60.5	131.5	72.5	103.5	92.5	123.5	80.5	111.5	84.5	139.5
145.5	100.5	95.5	128.5	75.5	108.5	87.5	120.5	83.5	54.5
50.5	97.5	106.5	69.5	126.5	89.5	114.5	77.5	118.5	149.5
142.5	70.5	125.5	98.5	105.5	78.5	117.5	90.5	113.5	57.5
56.5	130.5	73.5	102.5	93.5	122.5	81.5	110.5	85.5	143.5
144.5	101.5	94.5	129.5	74.5	109.5	86.5	121.5	82.5	55.5
58.5	64.5	134.5	66.5	132.5	136.5	146.5	52.5	148.5	59.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 10.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. The inner block of order 8 is formed by 4 equal sums of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The inner blocks of order 8 are also a **pandiagonal** magic squares. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= 1000 = 10^3; & T_{100} &:= 10 \times 1000 = 10000 = 100^2 = 10^4; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 400; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The magic squares given in Example 10.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4 \rangle$.

10.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 8 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned}
 (22, 120, 122) &\Rightarrow 122^2 - 22^2 = 120^2, \quad 122 - 22 = 10^2, \quad \text{Order 10, } S_{10 \times 10} := 1440, \quad T_{100} := 120^2, \\
 E &= \{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\} \text{ or } E = \{189/2, 191/2, \dots, 385/2, 387/2\}
 \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 10 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 10.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{45, 47, \dots, 241, 243\}$, and the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{189/2, 191/2, \dots, 385/2, 387/2\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 10 are given by

225	215	75	211	79	71	51	239	47	227
69	111	161	151	89	133	203	189	115	219
221	131	205	187	117	105	167	145	95	67
65	81	159	169	103	123	181	195	141	223
235	125	179	197	139	87	153	175	97	53
45	155	85	99	173	177	127	137	199	243
229	183	121	143	193	157	83	101	171	59
57	165	107	93	147	207	129	119	185	231
233	201	135	113	191	163	109	91	149	55
61	73	213	77	209	217	237	49	241	63

184.5	179.5	109.5	177.5	111.5	107.5	97.5	191.5	95.5	185.5
106.5	127.5	152.5	147.5	116.5	138.5	173.5	166.5	129.5	181.5
182.5	137.5	174.5	165.5	130.5	124.5	155.5	144.5	119.5	105.5
104.5	112.5	151.5	156.5	123.5	133.5	162.5	169.5	142.5	183.5
189.5	134.5	161.5	170.5	141.5	115.5	148.5	159.5	120.5	98.5
94.5	149.5	114.5	121.5	158.5	160.5	135.5	140.5	171.5	193.5
186.5	163.5	132.5	143.5	168.5	150.5	113.5	122.5	157.5	101.5
100.5	154.5	125.5	118.5	145.5	175.5	136.5	131.5	164.5	187.5
188.5	172.5	139.5	128.5	167.5	153.5	126.5	117.5	146.5	99.5
102.5	108.5	178.5	110.5	176.5	180.5	190.5	96.5	192.5	103.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 10 given in Example 10.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner blocks of order 8 are **bimagic** squares with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 4 aren't magic squares but the total entries sum is same. See below the details:

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 1440; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 1440 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1152; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1152 = 9216 = 96^2;$$

$$T_{16} := 2304 = 48^2.$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 10.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (22,120,122)**, i.e., $22^2 + 120^2 = 122^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Moreover, the magic squares given in Example 10.2 are **bimagic** squares with **bimagic** sums $Sb_{8 \times 8} = 176808$ and $Sb_{8 \times 8} = 168618$ respectively. Even though the magic sums are same but the **bimagic** sums are different.

10.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 8 given in List (15):

8.

$$\text{Order 10, } S_{10 \times 10} := 640, \quad T_{100} := 6400 = 80^2, \quad E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 10 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 10.3. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 is given by

104.5	99.5	29.5	97.5	31.5	27.5	17.5	111.5	15.5	105.5
26.5	60.5	71.5	32.5	91.5	52.5	79.5	40.5	83.5	101.5
102.5	35.5	88.5	63.5	68.5	43.5	80.5	55.5	76.5	25.5
24.5	95.5	36.5	67.5	56.5	87.5	44.5	75.5	48.5	103.5
109.5	64.5	59.5	92.5	39.5	72.5	51.5	84.5	47.5	18.5
14.5	61.5	70.5	33.5	90.5	53.5	78.5	41.5	82.5	113.5
106.5	34.5	89.5	62.5	69.5	42.5	81.5	54.5	77.5	21.5
20.5	94.5	37.5	66.5	57.5	86.5	45.5	74.5	49.5	107.5
108.5	65.5	58.5	93.5	38.5	73.5	50.5	85.5	46.5	19.5
22.5	28.5	98.5	30.5	96.5	100.5	110.5	16.5	112.5	23.5

The magic square of order 10 given in Example 10.3 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The inner block of order 8 is formed by 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The inner block of order 8 is also a **pandiagonal** magic square. See below the details:

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 640; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 640 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 512; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 256; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

11 Magic Squares of Order 11

This section brings magic squares of order 11 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

11.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 9 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 11, \quad S_{11 \times 11} := 1331, \quad T_{121} := 14641 = 121^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 239, 241\} \text{ or } E := \{61, 62, \dots, 179, 181\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 11 with different entries. Below are these magic

squares.

Example 11.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 239, 241\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{61, 62, \dots, 179, 181\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11 are given by

23	39	35	31	27	225	227	231	235	239	19
241	83	181	99	93	167	103	79	177	107	1
237	109	81	173	95	85	183	105	89	169	5
233	171	101	91	175	111	77	179	97	87	9
229	119	55	189	129	41	193	115	51	197	13
21	199	117	47	185	121	57	195	125	43	221
25	45	191	127	49	201	113	53	187	123	217
29	155	145	63	165	131	67	151	141	71	213
33	73	153	137	59	157	147	69	161	133	209
37	135	65	163	139	75	149	143	61	159	205
223	203	207	211	215	17	15	11	7	3	219

23	39	35	31	27	225	227	231	235	239	19
241	83	181	99	93	167	103	79	177	107	1
237	109	81	173	95	85	183	105	89	169	5
233	171	101	91	175	111	77	179	97	87	9
229	119	55	189	129	41	193	115	51	197	13
21	199	117	47	185	121	57	195	125	43	221
25	45	191	127	49	201	113	53	187	123	217
29	155	145	63	165	131	67	151	141	71	213
33	73	153	137	59	157	147	69	161	133	209
37	135	65	163	139	75	149	143	61	159	205
223	203	207	211	215	17	15	11	7	3	219

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11 given in Example 11.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are with equal magic sums. The inner block of order 9 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{11 \times 11} &:= 1331 = 11^3; & T_{121} &:= 11 \times 1331 = 14641 = 121^2 = 11^4; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2; \\
 Sm_{3 \times 3} &:= 363; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 363 = 1089 = 33^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The magic squares given in Example 11.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 11, 11^2, 11^3, 11^4 \rangle$.

11.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 9 given in List (10):

$$(24, 143, 145) \Rightarrow 145^2 - 24^2 = 143^2, \quad 145 - 24 = 11^2, \quad \text{Order 11}, \quad S_{11 \times 11} := 1859, \quad T_{121} := 143^2,$$

$$E = \{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\} \text{ or } E = \{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 11 with different entries. Below are these magic

squares.

Example 11.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{49, 51, \dots, 287, 289\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{109, 110, \dots, 228, 229\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11 are given by

71	87	83	79	75	273	275	279	283	287	67
289	105	229	191	237	145	107	171	133	203	49
285	243	151	113	177	139	209	93	217	179	53
281	165	127	197	99	223	185	249	157	119	57
277	193	101	231	109	233	147	205	167	135	61
69	115	239	153	211	173	141	181	89	219	269
73	199	161	129	187	95	225	121	245	159	265
77	227	195	103	143	111	235	131	207	169	261
81	149	117	241	137	213	175	215	183	91	257
85	125	201	163	221	189	97	155	123	247	253
271	251	255	259	263	65	63	59	55	51	267

120	128	126	124	122	221	222	224	226	228	118
229	137	199	180	203	157	138	170	151	186	109
227	206	160	141	173	154	189	131	193	174	111
225	167	148	183	134	196	177	209	163	144	113
223	181	135	200	139	201	158	187	168	152	115
119	142	204	161	190	171	155	175	129	194	219
121	184	165	149	178	132	197	145	207	164	217
123	198	182	136	156	140	202	150	188	169	215
125	159	143	205	153	191	172	192	176	130	213
127	147	185	166	195	179	133	162	146	208	211
220	210	212	214	216	117	116	114	112	110	218

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11 given in Example 11.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner blocks of order 9 are **bimagic** squares. The blocks of order 3 aren't magic squares, but sum of 9 members in each case are the same as of magic square. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11 \times 11} &:= 1959; & T_{121} &:= 11 \times 1859 = 20449 = 143^2; \\ S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1521; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1521 = 13689 = 117^2; \\ & & T_9 &:= 1521 = 39^2. \end{aligned}$$

Both the magic squares given in Example 11.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (24,143,145)**, i.e., $24^2 + 143^2 = 145^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in a **perfect square**. The magic squares given in Examples 11.2 are also **bimagic** squares with **bimagic** sums $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 276729$ and $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 261969$ respectively. Even though the magic sums are same but the **bimagic** sums are different.

11.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 9 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 11, } S_{11 \times 11} := 704, T_{121} := 7744 = 88^2, E := \{4, 5, \dots, 123, 124\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 11.

Example 11.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{4, 5, 6, \dots, 123, 124\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 is given by

15	23	21	19	17	116	117	119	121	123	13
124	45	94	53	50	87	55	43	92	57	4
122	58	44	90	51	46	95	56	48	88	6
120	89	54	49	91	59	42	93	52	47	8
118	63	31	98	68	24	100	61	29	102	10
14	103	62	27	96	64	32	101	66	25	114
16	26	99	67	28	104	60	30	97	65	112
18	81	76	35	86	69	37	79	74	39	110
20	40	80	72	33	82	77	38	84	70	108
22	71	36	85	73	41	78	75	34	83	106
115	105	107	109	111	12	11	9	7	5	113

The magic square of order 11 given in Example 11.3 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 9 is **pandiagonal** with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 704; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 704 = 7744 = 88^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 576; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 576 = 5184 = 72^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 192; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 192 = 576 = 24^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

12 Magic Squares of Order 12

This section brings magic squares of order 12 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

12.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 10 given in List (8):

Order 12, $S_{12 \times 12} := 1728$, $T_{144} := 20736 = 144^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 285, 287\}$ or $E := \{145/2, 147/2, \dots, 427/2, 431/2\}$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 12 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 12.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 285, 287\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 is given by

		1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728
	109	215	1	251	111	213	3	249	113	211	5	247	1728
1728	35	217	143	181	33	219	141	183	31	221	139	185	1728
1728	287	37	179	73	285	39	177	75	283	41	175	77	1728
1728	145	107	253	71	147	105	255	69	149	103	257	67	1728
1728	115	209	7	245	117	207	9	243	119	205	11	241	1728
1728	29	223	137	187	27	225	135	189	25	227	133	191	1728
1728	281	43	173	79	279	45	171	81	277	47	169	83	1728
1728	151	101	259	65	153	99	261	63	155	97	263	61	1728
1728	121	203	13	239	123	201	15	237	125	199	17	235	1728
1728	23	229	131	193	21	231	129	195	19	233	127	197	1728
1728	275	49	167	85	273	51	165	87	271	53	163	89	1728
1728	157	95	265	59	159	93	267	57	161	91	269	55	1728
	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728

Example 12.2. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{145/2, 147/2, \dots, 427/2, 431/2\}$, a **pandiagonal magic square of order 12** is given by

		1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728
	126.5	179.5	72.5	197.5	127.5	178.5	73.5	196.5	128.5	177.5	74.5	195.5	1728
1728	89.5	180.5	143.5	162.5	88.5	181.5	142.5	163.5	87.5	182.5	141.5	164.5	1728
1728	215.5	90.5	161.5	108.5	214.5	91.5	160.5	109.5	213.5	92.5	159.5	110.5	1728
1728	144.5	125.5	198.5	107.5	145.5	124.5	199.5	106.5	146.5	123.5	200.5	105.5	1728
1728	129.5	176.5	75.5	194.5	130.5	175.5	76.5	193.5	131.5	174.5	77.5	192.5	1728
1728	86.5	183.5	140.5	165.5	85.5	184.5	139.5	166.5	84.5	185.5	138.5	167.5	1728
1728	212.5	93.5	158.5	111.5	211.5	94.5	157.5	112.5	210.5	95.5	156.5	113.5	1728
1728	147.5	122.5	201.5	104.5	148.5	121.5	202.5	103.5	149.5	120.5	203.5	102.5	1728
1728	132.5	173.5	78.5	191.5	133.5	172.5	79.5	190.5	134.5	171.5	80.5	189.5	1728
1728	83.5	186.5	137.5	168.5	82.5	187.5	136.5	169.5	81.5	188.5	135.5	170.5	1728
1728	209.5	96.5	155.5	114.5	208.5	97.5	154.5	115.5	207.5	98.5	153.5	116.5	1728
1728	150.5	119.5	204.5	101.5	151.5	118.5	205.5	100.5	152.5	117.5	206.5	99.5	1728
	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728	1728

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12 given in Examples 12.1 and 12.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 1728 = 12^3; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 1728 = 20736 = 144^2 = 12^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 576; \quad T_{12} := 4 \times 576 = 2304 = 48^2.$$

The Examples 12.1 and 12.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 12, 12^2, 12^3, 12^4 \rangle$.

12.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 10 given in List (10):

10.

$$(26, 168, 170) \Rightarrow 170^2 - 26^2 = 168^2, \quad 170 - 26 = 12^2, \quad \text{Order 12, } S_{12 \times 12} := 2352, \quad T_{144} := 168^2,$$

$$E = \{53, 55, \dots, 337, 339\} \text{ or } E = \{249/2, 251/2, \dots, 533/2, 535/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 12 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 12.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{53, 55, \dots, 337, 339\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 is given by

		2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352
	247	53	153	195	95	289	207	107	301	331	137	237	2352
2352	57	151	245	287	193	99	299	205	111	141	235	329	2352
2352	149	249	55	97	291	191	109	303	203	233	333	139	2352
2352	313	119	219	225	125	319	165	65	259	277	83	183	2352
2352	123	217	311	317	223	129	257	163	69	87	181	275	2352
2352	215	315	121	127	321	221	67	261	161	179	279	85	2352
2352	185	285	91	61	255	155	145	339	239	197	297	103	2352
2352	93	187	281	251	157	63	335	241	147	105	199	293	2352
2352	283	89	189	159	59	253	243	143	337	295	101	201	2352
2352	227	327	133	115	309	209	79	273	173	167	267	73	2352
2352	135	229	323	305	211	117	269	175	81	75	169	263	2352
2352	325	131	231	213	113	307	177	77	271	265	71	171	2352
	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352

Example 12.4. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{249/2, 251/2, \dots, 533/2, 535/2\}$, a **pandiagonal magic square of order 12** is given by

		2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352
	221.5	124.5	174.5	195.5	145.5	242.5	201.5	151.5	248.5	263.5	166.5	216.5	2352
2352	126.5	173.5	220.5	241.5	194.5	147.5	247.5	200.5	153.5	168.5	215.5	262.5	2352
2352	172.5	222.5	125.5	146.5	243.5	193.5	152.5	249.5	199.5	214.5	264.5	167.5	2352
2352	254.5	157.5	207.5	210.5	160.5	257.5	180.5	130.5	227.5	236.5	139.5	189.5	2352
2352	159.5	206.5	253.5	256.5	209.5	162.5	226.5	179.5	132.5	141.5	188.5	235.5	2352
2352	205.5	255.5	158.5	161.5	258.5	208.5	131.5	228.5	178.5	187.5	237.5	140.5	2352
2352	190.5	240.5	143.5	128.5	225.5	175.5	170.5	267.5	217.5	196.5	246.5	149.5	2352
2352	144.5	191.5	238.5	223.5	176.5	129.5	265.5	218.5	171.5	150.5	197.5	244.5	2352
2352	239.5	142.5	192.5	177.5	127.5	224.5	219.5	169.5	266.5	245.5	148.5	198.5	2352
2352	211.5	261.5	164.5	155.5	252.5	202.5	137.5	234.5	184.5	181.5	231.5	134.5	2352
2352	165.5	212.5	259.5	250.5	203.5	156.5	232.5	185.5	138.5	135.5	182.5	229.5	2352
2352	260.5	163.5	213.5	204.5	154.5	251.5	186.5	136.5	233.5	230.5	133.5	183.5	2352
	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352	2352

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12 given in Examples 12.3 and 12.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 2352; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 2352 = 28224 = 168^2.$$

Both the Examples 12.3 and 12.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (26, 168, 170)**, i.e., $26^2 + 168^2 = 170^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

12.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 10 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 12, } S_{12 \times 12} := 972, \quad T_{144} := 11664 = 108^2, \quad E := \{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 12 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 12.5. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 is given by

		972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972
	63.5	116.5	9.5	134.5	64.5	115.5	10.5	133.5	65.5	114.5	11.5	132.5	972
972	26.5	117.5	80.5	99.5	25.5	118.5	79.5	100.5	24.5	119.5	78.5	101.5	972
972	152.5	27.5	98.5	45.5	151.5	28.5	97.5	46.5	150.5	29.5	96.5	47.5	972
972	81.5	62.5	135.5	44.5	82.5	61.5	136.5	43.5	83.5	60.5	137.5	42.5	972
972	66.5	113.5	12.5	131.5	67.5	112.5	13.5	130.5	68.5	111.5	14.5	129.5	972
972	23.5	120.5	77.5	102.5	22.5	121.5	76.5	103.5	21.5	122.5	75.5	104.5	972
972	149.5	30.5	95.5	48.5	148.5	31.5	94.5	49.5	147.5	32.5	93.5	50.5	972
972	84.5	59.5	138.5	41.5	85.5	58.5	139.5	40.5	86.5	57.5	140.5	39.5	972
972	69.5	110.5	15.5	128.5	70.5	109.5	16.5	127.5	71.5	108.5	17.5	126.5	972
972	20.5	123.5	74.5	105.5	19.5	124.5	73.5	106.5	18.5	125.5	72.5	107.5	972
972	146.5	33.5	92.5	51.5	145.5	34.5	91.5	52.5	144.5	35.5	90.5	53.5	972
972	87.5	56.5	141.5	38.5	88.5	55.5	142.5	37.5	89.5	54.5	143.5	36.5	972
	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972	972

The magic square of order 12 given in Example 12.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 972; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 972 = 11664 = 108^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 324; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 324 = 1296 = 36^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

13 Magic Squares of Order 13

This section brings magic squares of order 13 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

13.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 11 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 13, \quad S_{13 \times 13} := 2197, \quad T_{169} := 28561 = 169^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 335, 337\} \text{ or } E := \{85, 86, \dots, 251, 253\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 13 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 13.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 335, 337\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{85, 86, \dots, 251, 253\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13 are given by

311	293	297	301	305	309	313	17	13	9	5	1	23
3	71	87	83	79	75	273	275	279	283	287	67	335
7	289	131	229	147	141	215	151	127	225	155	49	331
11	285	157	129	221	143	133	231	153	137	217	53	327
15	281	219	149	139	223	159	125	227	145	135	57	323
19	277	167	103	237	177	89	241	163	99	245	61	319
21	69	247	165	95	233	169	105	243	173	91	269	317
307	73	93	239	175	97	249	161	101	235	171	265	31
303	77	203	193	111	213	179	115	199	189	119	261	35
299	81	121	201	185	107	205	195	117	209	181	257	39
295	85	183	113	211	187	123	197	191	109	207	253	43
291	271	251	255	259	263	65	63	59	55	51	267	47
315	45	41	37	33	29	25	321	325	329	333	337	27

240	231	233	235	237	239	241	93	91	89	87	85	96
86	120	128	126	124	122	221	222	224	226	228	118	252
88	229	150	199	158	155	192	160	148	197	162	109	250
90	227	163	149	195	156	151	200	161	153	193	111	248
92	225	194	159	154	196	164	147	198	157	152	113	246
94	223	168	136	203	173	129	205	166	134	207	115	244
95	119	208	167	132	201	169	137	206	171	130	219	243
238	121	131	204	172	133	209	165	135	202	170	217	100
236	123	186	181	140	191	174	142	184	179	144	215	102
234	125	145	185	177	138	187	182	143	189	175	213	104
232	127	176	141	190	178	146	183	180	139	188	211	106
230	220	210	212	214	216	117	116	114	112	110	218	108
242	107	105	103	101	99	97	245	247	249	251	253	98

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13 given in Example 13.1 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner block of order 9 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 2197 = 13^3; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 2197 = 28561 = 169^2 = 13^4;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 1859; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 1859 = 20449 = 143^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1521; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 1521 = 13689 = 117^2;$$

$$S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := 507; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 507 = 1521 = 39^2.$$

The magic squares given in Example 13.1 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 13, 13^2, 13^3, 13^4 \rangle$.

13.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 11 given in List (10):

$$(28, 195, 197) \Rightarrow 197^2 - 28^2 = 195^2, 197 - 28 = 13^2, \text{ Order } 13, S_{13 \times 13} := 2925, T_{169} := 195^2,$$

$$E = \{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\} \text{ or } E = \{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 13 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 13.2. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{57, 59, \dots, 391, 393\}$, and the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{141, 142, \dots, 308, 309\}$, the **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13 are given by

367	349	353	357	361	365	369	73	69	65	61	57	79
59	127	143	139	135	131	329	331	335	339	343	123	391
63	345	161	285	247	293	201	163	227	189	259	105	387
67	341	299	207	169	233	195	265	149	273	235	109	383
71	337	221	183	253	155	279	241	305	213	175	113	379
75	333	249	157	287	165	289	203	261	223	191	117	375
77	125	171	295	209	267	229	197	237	145	275	325	373
363	129	255	217	185	243	151	281	177	301	215	321	87
359	133	283	251	159	199	167	291	187	263	225	317	91
355	137	205	173	297	193	269	231	271	239	147	313	95
351	141	181	257	219	277	245	153	211	179	303	309	99
347	327	307	311	315	319	121	119	115	111	107	323	103
371	101	97	93	89	85	81	377	381	385	389	393	83

296	287	289	291	293	295	297	149	147	145	143	141	152
142	176	184	182	180	178	277	278	280	282	284	174	308
144	285	193	255	236	259	213	194	226	207	242	165	306
146	283	262	216	197	229	210	245	187	249	230	167	304
148	281	223	204	239	190	252	233	265	219	200	169	302
150	279	237	191	256	195	257	214	243	224	208	171	300
151	175	198	260	217	246	227	211	231	185	250	275	299
294	177	240	221	205	234	188	253	201	263	220	273	156
292	179	254	238	192	212	196	258	206	244	225	271	158
290	181	215	199	261	209	247	228	248	232	186	269	160
288	183	203	241	222	251	235	189	218	202	264	267	162
286	276	266	268	270	272	173	172	170	168	166	274	164
298	163	161	159	157	155	153	301	303	305	307	309	154

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13 given in Example 13.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. Both the magic squares are of equal magic sums. The inner blocks of order 9 are magic square. The blocks of order 3 aren't magic squares but the sum of 9 members in each case are same. See below the details:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 2925; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 2925 = 38025 = 195^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 2475; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 2475 = 27225 = 165^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 2025; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 2025 = 18225 = 135^2;$$

$$T_9 := 2025 = 45^2.$$

Both magic squares given in Example 13.2 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (28,195,197)**, i.e., $28^2 + 195^2 = 197^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Also the inner blocks of order 9 are **bimagic** squares with respective **bimagic** sums $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 460545$ and $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 475305$. Even though the magic sums are same but the **bimagic** sums are different.

13.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 11 given in List (15):

Order 13, $S_{13 \times 13} := 1300$, $T_{169} := 16900 = 130^2$, $E := \{16, 17, \dots, 183, 184\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 13 with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

Example 13.3. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{16, 17, 18, \dots, 183, 184\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 is given by

171	162	164	166	168	170	172	24	22	20	18	16	27
17	51	59	57	55	53	152	153	155	157	159	49	183
19	160	81	130	89	86	123	91	79	128	93	40	181
21	158	94	80	126	87	82	131	92	84	124	42	179
23	156	125	90	85	127	95	78	129	88	83	44	177
25	154	99	67	134	104	60	136	97	65	138	46	175
26	50	139	98	63	132	100	68	137	102	61	150	174
169	52	62	135	103	64	140	96	66	133	101	148	31
167	54	117	112	71	122	105	73	115	110	75	146	33
165	56	76	116	108	69	118	113	74	120	106	144	35
163	58	107	72	121	109	77	114	111	70	119	142	37
161	151	141	143	145	147	48	47	45	43	41	149	39
173	38	36	34	32	30	28	176	178	180	182	184	29

The magic square of order 13 given in Example 13.3 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** magic squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1300; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 1300 = 130^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 1100; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 1100 = 12100 = 110^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 900; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 900 = 8100 = 90^2;$$

$$S_{m_{3 \times 3}} := 300; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 300 = 900 = 30^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

14 Magic Squares of Order 14

This section brings magic squares of order 14 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

14.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 12 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order 14, } S_{14 \times 14} := 2744, \quad T_{196} := 38416 = 196^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 389, 391\} \text{ or } E := \{197/2, 199/2, \dots, 583/2, 587/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 14 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 14.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 389, 391\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is given by

27	15	375	19	371	23	391	13	363	31	359	35	355	367
389	161	267	53	303	163	265	55	301	165	263	57	299	3
5	87	269	195	233	85	271	193	235	83	273	191	237	387
385	339	89	231	125	337	91	229	127	335	93	227	129	7
9	197	159	305	123	199	157	307	121	201	155	309	119	383
381	167	261	59	297	169	259	61	295	171	257	63	293	11
353	81	275	189	239	79	277	187	241	77	279	185	243	39
341	333	95	225	131	331	97	223	133	329	99	221	135	51
49	203	153	311	117	205	151	313	115	207	149	315	113	343
345	173	255	65	291	175	253	67	289	177	251	69	287	47
45	75	281	183	245	73	283	181	247	71	285	179	249	347
349	327	101	219	137	325	103	217	139	323	105	215	141	43
41	209	147	317	111	211	145	319	109	213	143	321	107	351
25	377	17	373	21	369	1	379	29	361	33	357	37	365

Example 14.2. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{197/2, 199/2, \dots, 583/2, 587/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is given by

111.5	105.5	285.5	107.5	283.5	109.5	293.5	104.5	279.5	113.5	277.5	115.5	275.5	281.5
292.5	178.5	231.5	124.5	249.5	179.5	230.5	125.5	248.5	180.5	229.5	126.5	247.5	99.5
100.5	141.5	232.5	195.5	214.5	140.5	233.5	194.5	215.5	139.5	234.5	193.5	216.5	291.5
290.5	267.5	142.5	213.5	160.5	266.5	143.5	212.5	161.5	265.5	144.5	211.5	162.5	101.5
102.5	196.5	177.5	250.5	159.5	197.5	176.5	251.5	158.5	198.5	175.5	252.5	157.5	289.5
288.5	181.5	228.5	127.5	246.5	182.5	227.5	128.5	245.5	183.5	226.5	129.5	244.5	103.5
274.5	138.5	235.5	192.5	217.5	137.5	236.5	191.5	218.5	136.5	237.5	190.5	219.5	117.5
268.5	264.5	145.5	210.5	163.5	263.5	146.5	209.5	164.5	262.5	147.5	208.5	165.5	123.5
122.5	199.5	174.5	253.5	156.5	200.5	173.5	254.5	155.5	201.5	172.5	255.5	154.5	269.5
270.5	184.5	225.5	130.5	243.5	185.5	224.5	131.5	242.5	186.5	223.5	132.5	241.5	121.5
120.5	135.5	238.5	189.5	220.5	134.5	239.5	188.5	221.5	133.5	240.5	187.5	222.5	271.5
272.5	261.5	148.5	207.5	166.5	260.5	149.5	206.5	167.5	259.5	150.5	205.5	168.5	119.5
118.5	202.5	171.5	256.5	153.5	203.5	170.5	257.5	152.5	204.5	169.5	258.5	151.5	273.5
110.5	286.5	106.5	284.5	108.5	282.5	98.5	287.5	112.5	278.5	114.5	276.5	116.5	280.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 14 given in Examples 14.1 and 14.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner block of order 12 is **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{14 \times 14} = 2744 = 14^3; \quad T_{196} := 12 \times 2744 = 38416 = 196^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 2352; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 2352 = 28224 = 168^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 784; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 784 = 3136 = 56^2.$$

The Examples 14.1 and 14.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 14, 14^2, 14^3, 14^4 \rangle$.

14.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 12 given in List (10):

$$(30,224,226) \Rightarrow 226^2 - 30^2 = 224^2, 226 - 30 = 14^2, \text{ Order } 14, S_{14 \times 14} := 3584, T_{196} := 224^2,$$

$$E = \{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\} \text{ or } E = \{317/2, 319/2, \dots, 705/2, 707/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 14 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 14.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is given by

87	75	435	79	431	83	451	73	423	91	419	95	415	427
449	307	113	213	255	155	349	267	167	361	391	197	297	63
65	117	211	305	347	253	159	359	265	171	201	295	389	447
445	209	309	115	157	351	251	169	363	263	293	393	199	67
69	373	179	279	285	185	379	225	125	319	337	143	243	443
441	183	277	371	377	283	189	317	223	129	147	241	335	71
413	275	375	181	187	381	281	127	321	221	239	339	145	99
401	245	345	151	121	315	215	205	399	299	257	357	163	111
109	153	247	341	311	217	123	395	301	207	165	259	353	403
405	343	149	249	219	119	313	303	203	397	355	161	261	107
105	287	387	193	175	369	269	139	333	233	227	327	133	407
409	195	289	383	365	271	177	329	235	141	135	229	323	103
101	385	191	291	273	173	367	237	137	331	325	131	231	411
85	437	77	433	81	429	61	439	89	421	93	417	97	425

Example 14.4. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{317/2, 319/2, \dots, 705/2, 707/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is given by

171.5	165.5	345.5	167.5	343.5	169.5	353.5	164.5	339.5	173.5	337.5	175.5	335.5	341.5
352.5	281.5	184.5	234.5	255.5	205.5	302.5	261.5	211.5	308.5	323.5	226.5	276.5	159.5
160.5	186.5	233.5	280.5	301.5	254.5	207.5	307.5	260.5	213.5	228.5	275.5	322.5	351.5
350.5	232.5	282.5	185.5	206.5	303.5	253.5	212.5	309.5	259.5	274.5	324.5	227.5	161.5
162.5	314.5	217.5	267.5	270.5	220.5	317.5	240.5	190.5	287.5	296.5	199.5	249.5	349.5
348.5	219.5	266.5	313.5	316.5	269.5	222.5	286.5	239.5	192.5	201.5	248.5	295.5	163.5
334.5	265.5	315.5	218.5	221.5	318.5	268.5	191.5	288.5	238.5	247.5	297.5	200.5	177.5
328.5	250.5	300.5	203.5	188.5	285.5	235.5	230.5	327.5	277.5	256.5	306.5	209.5	183.5
182.5	204.5	251.5	298.5	283.5	236.5	189.5	325.5	278.5	231.5	210.5	257.5	304.5	329.5
330.5	299.5	202.5	252.5	237.5	187.5	284.5	279.5	229.5	326.5	305.5	208.5	258.5	181.5
180.5	271.5	321.5	224.5	215.5	312.5	262.5	197.5	294.5	244.5	241.5	291.5	194.5	331.5
332.5	225.5	272.5	319.5	310.5	263.5	216.5	292.5	245.5	198.5	195.5	242.5	289.5	179.5
178.5	320.5	223.5	273.5	264.5	214.5	311.5	246.5	196.5	293.5	290.5	193.5	243.5	333.5
170.5	346.5	166.5	344.5	168.5	342.5	158.5	347.5	172.5	338.5	174.5	336.5	176.5	340.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 14 given in Examples 14.3 and 14.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner block of order 12 is **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{14 \times 14} = 3584; \quad T_{196} := 12 \times 3584 = 50176 = 224^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 3072; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 3072 = 36864 = 192^2;$$

Both the Examples 14.3 and 14.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (30,224,226)**, i.e., $30^2 + 224^2 = 226^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

14.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 12 given in List (15):

12.

Order 14, $S_{14 \times 14} := 1400$, $T_{196} := 19600 = 140^2$, $E := \{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 14 **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 14.5. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is given by

15.5	9.5	189.5	11.5	187.5	13.5	197.5	8.5	183.5	17.5	181.5	19.5	179.5	185.5
196.5	82.5	135.5	28.5	153.5	83.5	134.5	29.5	152.5	84.5	133.5	30.5	151.5	3.5
4.5	45.5	136.5	99.5	118.5	44.5	137.5	98.5	119.5	43.5	138.5	97.5	120.5	195.5
194.5	171.5	46.5	117.5	64.5	170.5	47.5	116.5	65.5	169.5	48.5	115.5	66.5	5.5
6.5	100.5	81.5	154.5	63.5	101.5	80.5	155.5	62.5	102.5	79.5	156.5	61.5	193.5
192.5	85.5	132.5	31.5	150.5	86.5	131.5	32.5	149.5	87.5	130.5	33.5	148.5	7.5
178.5	42.5	139.5	96.5	121.5	41.5	140.5	95.5	122.5	40.5	141.5	94.5	123.5	21.5
172.5	168.5	49.5	114.5	67.5	167.5	50.5	113.5	68.5	166.5	51.5	112.5	69.5	27.5
26.5	103.5	78.5	157.5	60.5	104.5	77.5	158.5	59.5	105.5	76.5	159.5	58.5	173.5
174.5	88.5	129.5	34.5	147.5	89.5	128.5	35.5	146.5	90.5	127.5	36.5	145.5	25.5
24.5	39.5	142.5	93.5	124.5	38.5	143.5	92.5	125.5	37.5	144.5	91.5	126.5	175.5
176.5	165.5	52.5	111.5	70.5	164.5	53.5	110.5	71.5	163.5	54.5	109.5	72.5	23.5
22.5	106.5	75.5	160.5	57.5	107.5	74.5	161.5	56.5	108.5	73.5	162.5	55.5	177.5
14.5	190.5	10.5	188.5	12.5	186.5	2.5	191.5	16.5	182.5	18.5	180.5	20.5	184.5

The magic square of order 14 given in Example 14.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The inner block of order 12 is **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1400; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 1400 = 19600 = 140^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 1200; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 1200 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 400; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

15 Magic Squares of Order 15

This section brings magic squares of order 15 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

15.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 13 given in List (8):

Order 15, $S_{15 \times 15} := 3375,$ $T_{225} := 50625 = 225^2,$ $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 447, 449\}$ or $E := \{113, 114, \dots, 335, 337\}$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 15 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 15.1. For the *consecutive odd numbers* entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 447, 449\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 is given by

		3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375
	1	173	221	355	375	5	171	219	357	373	3	169	217	359	377	3375
3375	341	385	15	151	233	339	387	13	155	231	337	389	17	153	229	3375
3375	165	211	353	371	25	163	215	351	369	27	167	213	349	367	29	3375
3375	383	11	175	225	331	381	9	177	223	335	379	7	179	227	333	3375
3375	235	345	361	23	161	237	343	365	21	159	239	347	363	19	157	3375
3375	61	143	191	325	405	65	141	189	327	403	63	139	187	329	407	3375
3375	311	415	75	121	203	309	417	73	125	201	307	419	77	123	199	3375
3375	135	181	323	401	85	133	185	321	399	87	137	183	319	397	89	3375
3375	413	71	145	195	301	411	69	147	193	305	409	67	149	197	303	3375
3375	205	315	391	83	131	207	313	395	81	129	209	317	393	79	127	3375
3375	31	113	251	295	435	35	111	249	297	433	33	109	247	299	437	3375
3375	281	445	45	91	263	279	447	43	95	261	277	449	47	93	259	3375
3375	105	241	293	431	55	103	245	291	429	57	107	243	289	427	59	3375
3375	443	41	115	255	271	441	39	117	253	275	439	37	119	257	273	3375
3375	265	285	421	53	101	267	283	425	51	99	269	287	423	49	97	3375
	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375

Example 15.2. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{113, 114, 115, \dots, 336, 337\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 is given by

		3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375
	113	199	223	290	300	115	198	222	291	299	114	197	221	292	301	3375
3375	283	305	120	188	229	282	306	119	190	228	281	307	121	189	227	3375
3375	195	218	289	298	125	194	220	288	297	126	196	219	287	296	127	3375
3375	304	118	200	225	278	303	117	201	224	280	302	116	202	226	279	3375
3375	230	285	293	124	193	231	284	295	123	192	232	286	294	122	191	3375
3375	143	184	208	275	315	145	183	207	276	314	144	182	206	277	316	3375
3375	268	320	150	173	214	267	321	149	175	213	266	322	151	174	212	3375
3375	180	203	274	313	155	179	205	273	312	156	181	204	272	311	157	3375
3375	319	148	185	210	263	318	147	186	209	265	317	146	187	211	264	3375
3375	215	270	308	154	178	216	269	310	153	177	217	271	309	152	176	3375
3375	128	169	238	260	330	130	168	237	261	329	129	167	236	262	331	3375
3375	253	335	135	158	244	252	336	134	160	243	251	337	136	159	242	3375
3375	165	233	259	328	140	164	235	258	327	141	166	234	257	326	142	3375
3375	334	133	170	240	248	333	132	171	239	250	332	131	172	241	249	3375
3375	245	255	323	139	163	246	254	325	138	162	247	256	324	137	161	3375
	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 15 given in Examples 15.1 and 15.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 3375; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 3375 = 50625 = 225^2 = 15^4;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 1125; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1125 = 5625 = 75^2.$$

The Examples 15.1 and 15.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 15, 15^2, 15^3, 15^4 \rangle$.

15.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 13 given in List (10):

(32,255,257) $\Rightarrow 257^2 - 32^2 = 255^2$, $257 - 32 = 15^2$, **Order 15**, $S_{15 \times 15} := 4335$, $T_{225} := 255^2$,
 $E = \{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$ or $E = \{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 15 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 15.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 is given by

		4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335
	435	193	239	437	211	219	439	213	215	441	191	235	443	187	237	4335
4335	223	449	195	241	429	197	243	425	199	221	445	201	217	447	203	4335
4335	209	225	433	189	227	451	185	229	453	205	231	431	207	233	427	4335
4335	135	463	269	137	481	249	139	483	245	141	461	265	143	457	267	4335
4335	253	149	465	271	129	467	273	125	469	251	145	471	247	147	473	4335
4335	479	255	133	459	257	151	455	259	153	475	261	131	477	263	127	4335
4335	75	493	299	77	511	279	79	513	275	81	491	295	83	487	297	4335
4335	283	89	495	301	69	497	303	65	499	281	85	501	277	87	503	4335
4335	509	285	73	489	287	91	485	289	93	505	291	71	507	293	67	4335
4335	375	163	329	377	181	309	379	183	305	381	161	325	383	157	327	4335
4335	313	389	165	331	369	167	333	365	169	311	385	171	307	387	173	4335
4335	179	315	373	159	317	391	155	319	393	175	321	371	177	323	367	4335
4335	405	103	359	407	121	339	409	123	335	411	101	355	413	97	357	4335
4335	343	419	105	361	399	107	363	395	109	341	415	111	337	417	113	4335
4335	119	345	403	99	347	421	95	349	423	115	351	401	117	353	397	4335
	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335

Example 15.4. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$, a **pandiagonal magic square of order 15** is given by

		4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335
	362	241	264	363	250	254	364	251	252	365	240	262	366	238	263	4335
4335	256	369	242	265	359	243	266	357	244	255	367	245	253	368	246	4335
4335	249	257	361	239	258	370	237	259	371	247	260	360	248	261	358	4335
4335	212	376	279	213	385	269	214	386	267	215	375	277	216	373	278	4335
4335	271	219	377	280	209	378	281	207	379	270	217	380	268	218	381	4335
4335	384	272	211	374	273	220	372	274	221	382	275	210	383	276	208	4335
4335	182	391	294	183	400	284	184	401	282	185	390	292	186	388	293	4335
4335	286	189	392	295	179	393	296	177	394	285	187	395	283	188	396	4335
4335	399	287	181	389	288	190	387	289	191	397	290	180	398	291	178	4335
4335	332	226	309	333	235	299	334	236	297	335	225	307	336	223	308	4335
4335	301	339	227	310	329	228	311	327	229	300	337	230	298	338	231	4335
4335	234	302	331	224	303	340	222	304	341	232	305	330	233	306	328	4335
4335	347	196	324	348	205	314	349	206	312	350	195	322	351	193	323	4335
4335	316	354	197	325	344	198	326	342	199	315	352	200	313	353	201	4335
4335	204	317	346	194	318	355	192	319	356	202	320	345	203	321	343	4335
	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 15 given in Examples 15.3 and 15.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 4335; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 4335 = 65025 = 255^2. \quad Sm_{3 \times 3} := 867; \quad T_{225} := 3 \times 867 = 2601 = 51^2.$$

Both the Examples 15.3 and 15.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (32, 255, 257)**, i.e., $32^2 + 255^2 = 257^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

15.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 13 given in List (15):

13.

Order 15, $S_{15 \times 15} := 1815$, $T_{225} := 27225 = 165^2$, $E := \{9, 10, \dots, 232, 233\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 15.

Example 15.5. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{9, 10, 11, \dots, 232, 233\}$, a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 is given by

		1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815
	9	95	119	186	196	11	94	118	187	195	10	93	117	188	197	1815
1815	179	201	16	84	125	178	202	15	86	124	177	203	17	85	123	1815
1815	91	114	185	194	21	90	116	184	193	22	92	115	183	192	23	1815
1815	200	14	96	121	174	199	13	97	120	176	198	12	98	122	175	1815
1815	126	181	189	20	89	127	180	191	19	88	128	182	190	18	87	1815
1815	39	80	104	171	211	41	79	103	172	210	40	78	102	173	212	1815
1815	164	216	46	69	110	163	217	45	71	109	162	218	47	70	108	1815
1815	76	99	170	209	51	75	101	169	208	52	77	100	168	207	53	1815
1815	215	44	81	106	159	214	43	82	105	161	213	42	83	107	160	1815
1815	111	166	204	50	74	112	165	206	49	73	113	167	205	48	72	1815
1815	24	65	134	156	226	26	64	133	157	225	25	63	132	158	227	1815
1815	149	231	31	54	140	148	232	30	56	139	147	233	32	55	138	1815
1815	61	129	155	224	36	60	131	154	223	37	62	130	153	222	38	1815
1815	230	29	66	136	144	229	28	67	135	146	228	27	68	137	145	1815
1815	141	151	219	35	59	142	150	221	34	58	143	152	220	33	57	1815
	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 15.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 1815; \quad T_{729} := T_{225} := 15 \times 1815 = 27225 = 165^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 605; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 605 = 3025 = 55^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

16 Magic Squares of Order 16

This section brings magic squares of order 16 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

16.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 14 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 16, \quad S_{16 \times 16} := 4096, \quad T_{256} := 65536 = 256^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 509, 511\} \text{ or } E := \{257/2, 259/2, \dots, 763/2, 767/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 16 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 16.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 509, 511\}$ is given by

		4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096
	213	315	37	459	183	345	71	425	241	287	1	495	147	381	99	397	4096
4096	43	453	219	309	73	423	185	343	15	481	255	273	109	387	157	371	4096
4096	475	53	299	197	441	87	329	167	511	17	271	225	413	115	365	131	4096
4096	293	203	469	59	327	169	439	89	257	239	497	31	355	141	403	125	4096
4096	243	285	3	493	145	383	97	399	215	313	39	457	181	347	69	427	4096
4096	13	483	253	275	111	385	159	369	41	455	217	311	75	421	187	341	4096
4096	509	19	269	227	415	113	367	129	473	55	297	199	443	85	331	165	4096
4096	259	237	499	29	353	143	401	127	295	201	471	57	325	171	437	91	4096
4096	151	377	103	393	245	283	5	491	179	349	67	429	209	319	33	463	4096
4096	105	391	153	375	11	485	251	277	77	419	189	339	47	449	223	305	4096
4096	409	119	361	135	507	21	267	229	445	83	333	163	479	49	303	193	4096
4096	359	137	407	121	261	235	501	27	323	173	435	93	289	207	465	63	4096
4096	177	351	65	431	211	317	35	461	149	379	101	395	247	281	7	489	4096
4096	79	417	191	337	45	451	221	307	107	389	155	373	9	487	249	279	4096
4096	447	81	335	161	477	51	301	195	411	117	363	133	505	23	265	231	4096
4096	321	175	433	95	291	205	467	61	357	139	405	123	263	233	503	25	4096
	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

Example 16.2. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 16 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{257/2, 259/2, \dots, 763/2, 767/2\}$ is given by

		4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096
	234.5	285.5	146.5	357.5	219.5	300.5	163.5	340.5	248.5	271.5	128.5	375.5	201.5	318.5	177.5	326.5	4096
4096	149.5	354.5	237.5	282.5	164.5	339.5	220.5	299.5	135.5	368.5	255.5	264.5	182.5	321.5	206.5	313.5	4096
4096	365.5	154.5	277.5	226.5	348.5	171.5	292.5	211.5	383.5	136.5	263.5	240.5	334.5	185.5	310.5	193.5	4096
4096	274.5	229.5	362.5	157.5	291.5	212.5	347.5	172.5	256.5	247.5	376.5	143.5	305.5	198.5	329.5	190.5	4096
4096	249.5	270.5	129.5	374.5	200.5	319.5	176.5	327.5	235.5	284.5	147.5	356.5	218.5	301.5	162.5	341.5	4096
4096	134.5	369.5	254.5	265.5	183.5	320.5	207.5	312.5	148.5	355.5	236.5	283.5	165.5	338.5	221.5	298.5	4096
4096	382.5	137.5	262.5	241.5	335.5	184.5	311.5	192.5	364.5	155.5	276.5	227.5	349.5	170.5	293.5	210.5	4096
4096	257.5	246.5	377.5	142.5	304.5	199.5	328.5	191.5	275.5	228.5	363.5	156.5	290.5	213.5	346.5	173.5	4096
4096	203.5	316.5	179.5	324.5	250.5	269.5	130.5	373.5	217.5	302.5	161.5	342.5	232.5	287.5	144.5	359.5	4096
4096	180.5	323.5	204.5	315.5	133.5	370.5	253.5	266.5	166.5	337.5	222.5	297.5	151.5	352.5	239.5	280.5	4096
4096	332.5	187.5	308.5	195.5	381.5	138.5	261.5	242.5	350.5	169.5	294.5	209.5	367.5	152.5	279.5	224.5	4096
4096	307.5	196.5	331.5	188.5	258.5	245.5	378.5	141.5	289.5	214.5	345.5	174.5	272.5	231.5	360.5	159.5	4096
4096	216.5	303.5	160.5	343.5	233.5	286.5	145.5	358.5	202.5	317.5	178.5	325.5	251.5	268.5	131.5	372.5	4096
4096	167.5	336.5	223.5	296.5	150.5	353.5	238.5	281.5	181.5	322.5	205.5	314.5	132.5	371.5	252.5	267.5	4096
4096	351.5	168.5	295.5	208.5	366.5	153.5	278.5	225.5	333.5	186.5	309.5	194.5	380.5	139.5	260.5	243.5	4096
4096	288.5	215.5	344.5	175.5	273.5	230.5	361.5	158.5	306.5	197.5	330.5	189.5	259.5	244.5	379.5	140.5	4096
	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096	4096

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 16 given in Examples 16.1 and 16.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 4096 = 16^3; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 4096 = 65536 = 256^2 = 16^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1024; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1024 = 4096 = 64^2.$$

The Examples 16.1 and 16.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 16, 16^2, 16^3, 16^4 \rangle$.

16.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 14 given in List (10):

$$(34, 288, 290) \Rightarrow 290^2 - 34^2 = 288^2, 290 - 34 = 16^2, \text{ Order } 16, S_{16 \times 16} := 5184, T_{256} := 288^2,$$

$$E = \{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\} \text{ or } E = \{393/2, 395/2, \dots, 901/2, 903/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 16 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 16.3. A **block-wise bimagic** square of order 16 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{69, 71, \dots, 577, 579\}$ is given by

																5184
69	375	545	307	113	355	565	263	155	425	463	253	191	397	491	217	5184
531	321	87	357	551	277	131	337	477	239	137	443	505	203	173	415	5184
311	517	371	97	291	561	327	117	233	475	445	143	205	511	409	171	5184
385	83	293	535	341	103	273	579	431	157	251	457	395	185	223	493	5184
159	429	459	249	187	393	495	221	81	387	533	295	101	343	577	275	5184
473	235	141	447	509	207	169	411	519	309	99	369	563	289	119	325	5184
237	479	441	139	201	507	413	175	323	529	359	85	279	549	339	129	5184
427	153	255	461	399	189	219	489	373	71	305	547	353	115	261	567	5184
177	419	501	199	133	439	481	243	127	333	555	281	91	361	527	317	5184
487	213	195	401	467	257	151	421	569	267	109	351	541	303	73	379	5184
227	497	391	181	247	453	435	161	269	575	345	107	297	539	381	79	5184
405	167	209	515	449	147	229	471	331	121	287	557	367	93	315	521	5184
123	329	559	285	95	365	523	313	165	407	513	211	145	451	469	231	5184
573	271	105	347	537	299	77	383	499	225	183	389	455	245	163	433	5184
265	571	349	111	301	543	377	75	215	485	403	193	259	465	423	149	5184
335	125	283	553	363	89	319	525	417	179	197	503	437	135	241	483	5184
5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184

Example 16.4. A **block-wise bimagic** square of order 16 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{393/2, 395/2, \dots, 901/2, 903/2\}$ is given by

																5184
196.5	349.5	434.5	315.5	218.5	339.5	444.5	293.5	239.5	374.5	393.5	288.5	257.5	360.5	407.5	270.5	5184
427.5	322.5	205.5	340.5	437.5	300.5	227.5	330.5	400.5	281.5	230.5	383.5	414.5	263.5	248.5	369.5	5184
317.5	420.5	347.5	210.5	307.5	442.5	325.5	220.5	278.5	399.5	384.5	233.5	264.5	417.5	366.5	247.5	5184
354.5	203.5	308.5	429.5	332.5	213.5	298.5	451.5	377.5	240.5	287.5	390.5	359.5	254.5	273.5	408.5	5184
241.5	376.5	391.5	286.5	255.5	358.5	409.5	272.5	202.5	355.5	428.5	309.5	212.5	333.5	450.5	299.5	5184
398.5	279.5	232.5	385.5	416.5	265.5	246.5	367.5	421.5	316.5	211.5	346.5	443.5	306.5	221.5	324.5	5184
280.5	401.5	382.5	231.5	262.5	415.5	368.5	249.5	323.5	426.5	341.5	204.5	301.5	436.5	331.5	226.5	5184
375.5	238.5	289.5	392.5	361.5	256.5	271.5	406.5	348.5	197.5	314.5	435.5	338.5	219.5	292.5	445.5	5184
250.5	371.5	412.5	261.5	228.5	381.5	402.5	283.5	225.5	328.5	439.5	302.5	207.5	342.5	425.5	320.5	5184
405.5	268.5	259.5	362.5	395.5	290.5	237.5	372.5	446.5	295.5	216.5	337.5	432.5	313.5	198.5	351.5	5184
275.5	410.5	357.5	252.5	285.5	388.5	379.5	242.5	296.5	449.5	334.5	215.5	310.5	431.5	352.5	201.5	5184
364.5	245.5	266.5	419.5	386.5	235.5	276.5	397.5	327.5	222.5	305.5	440.5	345.5	208.5	319.5	422.5	5184
223.5	326.5	441.5	304.5	209.5	344.5	423.5	318.5	244.5	365.5	418.5	267.5	234.5	387.5	396.5	277.5	5184
448.5	297.5	214.5	335.5	430.5	311.5	200.5	353.5	411.5	274.5	253.5	356.5	389.5	284.5	243.5	378.5	5184
294.5	447.5	336.5	217.5	312.5	433.5	350.5	199.5	269.5	404.5	363.5	258.5	291.5	394.5	373.5	236.5	5184
329.5	224.5	303.5	438.5	343.5	206.5	321.5	424.5	370.5	251.5	260.5	413.5	380.5	229.5	282.5	403.5	5184
5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184	5184

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 16 given in Examples 16.3 and 16.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 4 are magic squares with equal magic and entries sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 5184; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 5184 = 82944 = 288^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 1296; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1296 = 5184 = 72^2.$$

Both the Examples 16.3 and 16.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (34,288,290)**, i.e., $6^2 + 288^2 = 290^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Moreover, the magic squares given in Examples 16.3 and 16.4 are **bimagic** with different **bimagic** sums given respectively as $Sb_{16 \times 16} = 2029136$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16} = 2029136$.

16.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 14 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 16, } \mathbf{S}_{16 \times 16} := 2304, \mathbf{T}_{256} := 36864 = 192^2, \mathbf{E} := \{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 16 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 16.5. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 16 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$ is given by

		2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304
	122.5	173.5	34.5	245.5	107.5	188.5	51.5	228.5	136.5	159.5	16.5	263.5	89.5	206.5	65.5	214.5	2304
2304	37.5	242.5	125.5	170.5	52.5	227.5	108.5	187.5	23.5	256.5	143.5	152.5	70.5	209.5	94.5	201.5	2304
2304	253.5	42.5	165.5	114.5	236.5	59.5	180.5	99.5	271.5	24.5	151.5	128.5	222.5	73.5	198.5	81.5	2304
2304	162.5	117.5	250.5	45.5	179.5	100.5	235.5	60.5	144.5	135.5	264.5	31.5	193.5	86.5	217.5	78.5	2304
2304	137.5	158.5	17.5	262.5	88.5	207.5	64.5	215.5	123.5	172.5	35.5	244.5	106.5	189.5	50.5	229.5	2304
2304	22.5	257.5	142.5	153.5	71.5	208.5	95.5	200.5	36.5	243.5	124.5	171.5	53.5	226.5	109.5	186.5	2304
2304	270.5	25.5	150.5	129.5	223.5	72.5	199.5	80.5	252.5	43.5	164.5	115.5	237.5	58.5	181.5	98.5	2304
2304	145.5	134.5	265.5	30.5	192.5	87.5	216.5	79.5	163.5	116.5	251.5	44.5	178.5	101.5	234.5	61.5	2304
2304	91.5	204.5	67.5	212.5	138.5	157.5	18.5	261.5	105.5	190.5	49.5	230.5	120.5	175.5	32.5	247.5	2304
2304	68.5	211.5	92.5	203.5	21.5	258.5	141.5	154.5	54.5	225.5	110.5	185.5	39.5	240.5	127.5	168.5	2304
2304	220.5	75.5	196.5	83.5	269.5	26.5	149.5	130.5	238.5	57.5	182.5	97.5	255.5	40.5	167.5	112.5	2304
2304	195.5	84.5	219.5	76.5	146.5	133.5	266.5	29.5	177.5	102.5	233.5	62.5	160.5	119.5	248.5	47.5	2304
2304	104.5	191.5	48.5	231.5	121.5	174.5	33.5	246.5	90.5	205.5	66.5	213.5	139.5	156.5	19.5	260.5	2304
2304	55.5	224.5	111.5	184.5	38.5	241.5	126.5	169.5	69.5	210.5	93.5	202.5	20.5	259.5	140.5	155.5	2304
2304	239.5	56.5	183.5	96.5	254.5	41.5	166.5	113.5	221.5	74.5	197.5	82.5	268.5	27.5	148.5	131.5	2304
2304	176.5	103.5	232.5	63.5	161.5	118.5	249.5	46.5	194.5	85.5	218.5	77.5	147.5	132.5	267.5	28.5	2304
	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304	2304

The magic square of order 16 given in Example 16.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{16 \times 16} = 2304; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 2304 = 36864 = 192^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 576; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 576 = 2304 = 48^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

17 Magic Squares of Order 17

This section brings magic squares of order 17 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

17.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 15 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 17, \quad S_{17 \times 17} := 4913, \quad T_{289} := 83521 = 289^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 575, 577\} \text{ or } E := \{145, 146, \dots, 431, 433\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 17 with different entries. Below are these magic squares. See below these two magic squares.

Example 17.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 575, 577\}$ is given by

31	575	571	567	563	559	555	551	549	39	43	47	51	55	59	63	35
1	435	193	239	437	211	219	439	213	215	441	191	235	443	187	237	577
5	223	449	195	241	429	197	243	425	199	221	445	201	217	447	203	573
9	209	225	433	189	227	451	185	229	453	205	231	431	207	233	427	569
13	135	463	269	137	481	249	139	483	245	141	461	265	143	457	267	565
17	253	149	465	271	129	467	273	125	469	251	145	471	247	147	473	561
21	479	255	133	459	257	151	455	259	153	475	261	131	477	263	127	557
25	75	493	299	77	511	279	79	513	275	81	491	295	83	487	297	553
545	283	89	495	301	69	497	303	65	499	281	85	501	277	87	503	33
541	509	285	73	489	287	91	485	289	93	505	291	71	507	293	67	37
537	375	163	329	377	181	309	379	183	305	381	161	325	383	157	327	41
533	313	389	165	331	369	167	333	365	169	311	385	171	307	387	173	45
529	179	315	373	159	317	391	155	319	393	175	321	371	177	323	367	49
525	405	103	359	407	121	339	409	123	335	411	101	355	413	97	357	53
521	343	419	105	361	399	107	363	395	109	341	415	111	337	417	113	57
517	119	345	403	99	347	421	95	349	423	115	351	401	117	353	397	61
543	3	7	11	15	19	23	27	29	539	535	531	527	523	519	515	547

Example 17.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive natural number** entries $\{145, 146, 147, \dots, 432, 433\}$ is given by

160	432	430	428	426	424	422	420	419	164	166	168	170	172	174	176	162
145	362	241	264	363	250	254	364	251	252	365	240	262	366	238	263	433
147	256	369	242	265	359	243	266	357	244	255	367	245	253	368	246	431
149	249	257	361	239	258	370	237	259	371	247	260	360	248	261	358	429
151	212	376	279	213	385	269	214	386	267	215	375	277	216	373	278	427
153	271	219	377	280	209	378	281	207	379	270	217	380	268	218	381	425
155	384	272	211	374	273	220	372	274	221	382	275	210	383	276	208	423
157	182	391	294	183	400	284	184	401	282	185	390	292	186	388	293	421
417	286	189	392	295	179	393	296	177	394	285	187	395	283	188	396	161
415	399	287	181	389	288	190	387	289	191	397	290	180	398	291	178	163
413	332	226	309	333	235	299	334	236	297	335	225	307	336	223	308	165
411	301	339	227	310	329	228	311	327	229	300	337	230	298	338	231	167
409	234	302	331	224	303	340	222	304	341	232	305	330	233	306	328	169
407	347	196	324	348	205	314	349	206	312	350	195	322	351	193	323	171
405	316	354	197	325	344	198	326	342	199	315	352	200	313	353	201	173
403	204	317	346	194	318	355	192	319	356	202	320	345	203	321	343	175
416	146	148	150	152	154	156	158	159	414	412	410	408	406	404	402	418

Both the Examples 17.1 and 17.2 are **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with equal magic sums. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** and with equal sum blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3. See below the details:

$$S_{17 \times 17} = 4913 = 17^3; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 4913 = 83521 = 289^2 = 17^4;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 4335; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 4335 = 65025 = 255^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 867; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 867 = 2601 = 51^2.$$

Both the Examples 17.1 and 17.2 satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 17, 17^2, 17^3, 17^4 \rangle$.

17.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 15 given in List (10):

$$(36, 323, 325) \Rightarrow 325^2 - 36^2 = 323^2, \quad 325 - 36 = 17^2, \quad \text{Order } 17, \quad S_{17 \times 17} := 6137, \quad T_{289} := 323^2,$$

$$E = \{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\} \text{ or } E = \{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 17 with different entries. Below are these magic squares. See below these two magic squares.

Example 17.3. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{73, 75, \dots, 647, 649\}$ is given by

103	647	643	639	635	631	627	623	621	111	115	119	123	127	131	135	107
73	137	571	195	373	529	197	511	285	343	469	227	451	315	403	409	649
77	375	553	139	557	181	345	493	199	497	271	405	433	229	437	301	645
81	559	167	361	555	163	499	257	331	495	223	439	287	391	435	253	641
85	541	165	583	169	347	481	225	523	259	317	421	255	463	289	377	637
89	193	349	527	151	585	283	319	467	211	525	313	379	407	241	465	633
93	141	569	191	369	535	201	509	281	339	475	231	449	311	399	415	629
97	371	549	145	561	179	341	489	205	501	269	401	429	235	441	299	625
617	565	171	359	551	159	505	261	329	491	219	445	291	389	431	249	105
613	539	161	579	175	351	479	221	519	265	321	419	251	459	295	381	109
609	189	355	531	149	581	279	325	471	209	521	309	385	411	239	461	113
605	143	573	187	365	537	203	513	277	335	477	233	453	307	395	417	117
601	367	545	147	563	183	337	485	207	503	273	397	425	237	443	303	121
597	567	173	363	547	155	507	263	333	487	215	447	293	393	427	245	125
593	543	157	575	177	353	483	217	515	267	323	423	247	455	297	383	129
589	185	357	533	153	577	275	327	473	213	517	305	387	413	243	457	133
615	75	79	83	87	91	95	99	101	611	607	603	599	595	591	587	619

Example 17.4. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{217, 218, \dots, 504, 505\}$ is given by

232	504	502	500	498	496	494	492	491	236	238	240	242	244	246	248	234
217	249	466	278	367	445	279	436	323	352	415	294	406	338	382	385	505
219	368	457	250	459	271	353	427	280	429	316	383	397	295	399	331	503
221	460	264	361	458	262	430	309	346	428	292	400	324	376	398	307	501
223	451	263	472	265	354	421	293	442	310	339	391	308	412	325	369	499
225	277	355	444	256	473	322	340	414	286	443	337	370	384	301	413	497
227	251	465	276	365	448	281	435	321	350	418	296	405	336	380	388	495
229	366	455	253	461	270	351	425	283	431	315	381	395	298	401	330	493
489	463	266	360	456	260	433	311	345	426	290	403	326	375	396	305	233
487	450	261	470	268	356	420	291	440	313	341	390	306	410	328	371	235
485	275	358	446	255	471	320	343	416	285	441	335	373	386	300	411	237
483	252	467	274	363	449	282	437	319	348	419	297	407	334	378	389	239
481	364	453	254	462	272	349	423	284	432	317	379	393	299	402	332	241
479	464	267	362	454	258	434	312	347	424	288	404	327	377	394	303	243
477	452	259	468	269	357	422	289	438	314	342	392	304	408	329	372	245
475	273	359	447	257	469	318	344	417	287	439	333	374	387	302	409	247
488	218	220	222	224	226	228	230	231	486	484	482	480	478	476	474	490

Both the Examples 17.3 and 17.4 are **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with equal magic sums. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with equal sum blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. See below the details:

$$S_{17 \times 17} = 6137; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 6137 = 104329 = 323^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 5415; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 5415 = 81225 = 285^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 1805; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1805 = 9025 = 95^2.$$

Both the Examples 17.3 and 17.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (36, 323, 325)**, i.e., $36^2 + 323^2 = 325^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

17.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 15 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 17, } S_{17 \times 17} := 2448, T_{289} := 41616 = 204^2, E := \{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 17 as given below:

Example 17.5. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive natural number** entries $\{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$ is given by

15	287	285	283	281	279	277	275	274	19	21	23	25	27	29	31	17
0	217	96	119	218	105	109	219	106	107	220	95	117	221	93	118	288
2	111	224	97	120	214	98	121	212	99	110	222	100	108	223	101	286
4	104	112	216	94	113	225	92	114	226	102	115	215	103	116	213	284
6	67	231	134	68	240	124	69	241	122	70	230	132	71	228	133	282
8	126	74	232	135	64	233	136	62	234	125	72	235	123	73	236	280
10	239	127	66	229	128	75	227	129	76	237	130	65	238	131	63	278
12	37	246	149	38	255	139	39	256	137	40	245	147	41	243	148	276
272	141	44	247	150	34	248	151	32	249	140	42	250	138	43	251	16
270	254	142	36	244	143	45	242	144	46	252	145	35	253	146	33	18
268	187	81	164	188	90	154	189	91	152	190	80	162	191	78	163	20
266	156	194	82	165	184	83	166	182	84	155	192	85	153	193	86	22
264	89	157	186	79	158	195	77	159	196	87	160	185	88	161	183	24
262	202	51	179	203	60	169	204	61	167	205	50	177	206	48	178	26
260	171	209	52	180	199	53	181	197	54	170	207	55	168	208	56	28
258	59	172	201	49	173	210	47	174	211	57	175	200	58	176	198	30
271	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	14	269	267	265	263	261	259	257	273

It is **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** and with equal sum blocks of **semi-magic** square of order 3. See below the details:

The magic square of order 17 given in Example 17.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{17 \times 17} = 2448; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 2448 = 41616 = 204^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 2160; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 2160 = 32400 = 180^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 432; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 432 = 1296 = 36^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

18 Magic Squares of Order 18

This section brings magic squares of order 18. in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

18.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 16 given in List (8):

Order 18, $S_{18 \times 18} := 5832$, $T_{324} := 104976 = 324^2$, $E := \{1, 3, \dots, 645, 647\}$ or $E := \{325/2, 327/2, \dots, 967/2, 971/2\}$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 18 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares. Below are both the examples.

Example 18.1. A *block-wise* magic square of order 18 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 645, 647\}$ is given by

																		5832
1	613	611	577	35	107	3	615	609	579	33	105	5	617	607	581	31	103	5832
539	143	503	145	181	433	537	141	501	147	183	435	535	139	499	149	185	437	5832
431	397	253	287	359	217	429	399	255	285	357	219	427	401	257	283	355	221	5832
323	251	361	395	289	325	321	249	363	393	291	327	319	247	365	391	293	329	5832
109	467	179	469	505	215	111	465	177	471	507	213	113	463	175	473	509	211	5832
541	73	37	71	575	647	543	75	39	69	573	645	545	77	41	67	571	643	5832
7	619	605	583	29	101	9	621	603	585	27	99	11	623	601	587	25	97	5832
533	137	497	151	187	439	531	135	495	153	189	441	529	133	493	155	191	443	5832
425	403	259	281	353	223	423	405	261	279	351	225	421	407	263	277	349	227	5832
317	245	367	389	295	331	315	243	369	387	297	333	313	241	371	385	299	335	5832
115	461	173	475	511	209	117	459	171	477	513	207	119	457	169	479	515	205	5832
547	79	43	65	569	641	549	81	45	63	567	639	551	83	47	61	565	637	5832
13	625	599	589	23	95	15	627	597	591	21	93	17	629	595	593	19	91	5832
527	131	491	157	193	445	525	129	489	159	195	447	523	127	487	161	197	449	5832
419	409	265	275	347	229	417	411	267	273	345	231	415	413	269	271	343	233	5832
311	239	373	383	301	337	309	237	375	381	303	339	307	235	377	379	305	341	5832
121	455	167	481	517	203	123	453	165	483	519	201	125	451	163	485	521	199	5832
553	85	49	59	563	635	555	87	51	57	561	633	557	89	53	55	559	631	5832
5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832

Example 18.2. A **block-wise** magic square of order 18 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{325/2, 327/2, \dots, 967/2, 971/2\}$ is given by

																		5832
162.5	468.5	467.5	450.5	179.5	215.5	163.5	469.5	466.5	451.5	178.5	214.5	164.5	470.5	465.5	452.5	177.5	213.5	5832
431.5	233.5	413.5	234.5	252.5	378.5	430.5	232.5	412.5	235.5	253.5	379.5	429.5	231.5	411.5	236.5	254.5	380.5	5832
377.5	360.5	288.5	305.5	341.5	270.5	376.5	361.5	289.5	304.5	340.5	271.5	375.5	362.5	290.5	303.5	339.5	272.5	5832
323.5	287.5	342.5	359.5	306.5	324.5	322.5	286.5	343.5	358.5	307.5	325.5	321.5	285.5	344.5	357.5	308.5	326.5	5832
216.5	395.5	251.5	396.5	414.5	269.5	217.5	394.5	250.5	397.5	415.5	268.5	218.5	393.5	249.5	398.5	416.5	267.5	5832
432.5	198.5	180.5	197.5	449.5	485.5	433.5	199.5	181.5	196.5	448.5	484.5	434.5	200.5	182.5	195.5	447.5	483.5	5832
165.5	471.5	464.5	453.5	176.5	212.5	166.5	472.5	463.5	454.5	175.5	211.5	167.5	473.5	462.5	455.5	174.5	210.5	5832
428.5	230.5	410.5	237.5	255.5	381.5	427.5	229.5	409.5	238.5	256.5	382.5	426.5	228.5	408.5	239.5	257.5	383.5	5832
374.5	363.5	291.5	302.5	338.5	273.5	373.5	364.5	292.5	301.5	337.5	274.5	372.5	365.5	293.5	300.5	336.5	275.5	5832
320.5	284.5	345.5	356.5	309.5	327.5	319.5	283.5	346.5	355.5	310.5	328.5	318.5	282.5	347.5	354.5	311.5	329.5	5832
219.5	392.5	248.5	399.5	417.5	266.5	220.5	391.5	247.5	400.5	418.5	265.5	221.5	390.5	246.5	401.5	419.5	264.5	5832
435.5	201.5	183.5	194.5	446.5	482.5	436.5	202.5	184.5	193.5	445.5	481.5	437.5	203.5	185.5	192.5	444.5	480.5	5832
168.5	474.5	461.5	456.5	173.5	209.5	169.5	475.5	460.5	457.5	172.5	208.5	170.5	476.5	459.5	458.5	171.5	207.5	5832
425.5	227.5	407.5	240.5	258.5	384.5	424.5	226.5	406.5	241.5	259.5	385.5	423.5	225.5	405.5	242.5	260.5	386.5	5832
371.5	366.5	294.5	299.5	335.5	276.5	370.5	367.5	295.5	298.5	334.5	277.5	369.5	368.5	296.5	297.5	333.5	278.5	5832
317.5	281.5	348.5	353.5	312.5	330.5	316.5	280.5	349.5	352.5	313.5	331.5	315.5	279.5	350.5	351.5	314.5	332.5	5832
222.5	389.5	245.5	402.5	420.5	263.5	223.5	388.5	244.5	403.5	421.5	262.5	224.5	387.5	243.5	404.5	422.5	261.5	5832
438.5	204.5	186.5	191.5	443.5	479.5	439.5	205.5	187.5	190.5	442.5	478.5	440.5	206.5	188.5	189.5	441.5	477.5	5832
5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 18 given in Examples 18.1 and 18.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 5832 = 18^3; \quad T_{324} := 104976 = 324^2 = 18^4;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 1944; \quad T_{36} := 11664 = 108^2.$$

The Examples 18.1 and 18.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 18, 18^2, 18^3, 18^4 \rangle$.

18.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 16 given in List (10):

$$(38,360,362) \Rightarrow 362^2 - 38^2 = 360^2, 362 - 38 = 18^2, \text{ Order } 18, S_{18 \times 18} := 7200, T_{324} := 360^2,$$

$$E = \{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\} \text{ or } E = \{477/2, 479/2, \dots, 1121/2, 1123/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 16 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares. Below are both the examples.

Example 18.3. A *block-wise* magic square of order 18 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries $\{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$ is given by

																		7200
77	689	687	653	111	183	79	691	685	655	109	181	81	693	683	657	107	179	7200
615	219	579	221	257	509	613	217	577	223	259	511	611	215	575	225	261	513	7200
507	473	329	363	435	293	505	475	331	361	433	295	503	477	333	359	431	297	7200
399	327	437	471	365	401	397	325	439	469	367	403	395	323	441	467	369	405	7200
185	543	255	545	581	291	187	541	253	547	583	289	189	539	251	549	585	287	7200
617	149	113	147	651	723	619	151	115	145	649	721	621	153	117	143	647	719	7200
83	695	681	659	105	177	85	697	679	661	103	175	87	699	677	663	101	173	7200
609	213	573	227	263	515	607	211	571	229	265	517	605	209	569	231	267	519	7200
501	479	335	357	429	299	499	481	337	355	427	301	497	483	339	353	425	303	7200
393	321	443	465	371	407	391	319	445	463	373	409	389	317	447	461	375	411	7200
191	537	249	551	587	285	193	535	247	553	589	283	195	533	245	555	591	281	7200
623	155	119	141	645	717	625	157	121	139	643	715	627	159	123	137	641	713	7200
89	701	675	665	99	171	91	703	673	667	97	169	93	705	671	669	95	167	7200
603	207	567	233	269	521	601	205	565	235	271	523	599	203	563	237	273	525	7200
495	485	341	351	423	305	493	487	343	349	421	307	491	489	345	347	419	309	7200
387	315	449	459	377	413	385	313	451	457	379	415	383	311	453	455	381	417	7200
197	531	243	557	593	279	199	529	241	559	595	277	201	527	239	561	597	275	7200
629	161	125	135	639	711	631	163	127	133	637	709	633	165	129	131	635	707	7200
7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200

Example 18.4. A **block-wise** magic square of order 18 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{477/2, 479/2, \dots, 1121/2, 1123/2\}$ is given by

																		7200
238.5	544.5	543.5	526.5	255.5	291.5	239.5	545.5	542.5	527.5	254.5	290.5	240.5	546.5	541.5	528.5	253.5	289.5	7200
507.5	309.5	489.5	310.5	328.5	454.5	506.5	308.5	488.5	311.5	329.5	455.5	505.5	307.5	487.5	312.5	330.5	456.5	7200
453.5	436.5	364.5	381.5	417.5	346.5	452.5	437.5	365.5	380.5	416.5	347.5	451.5	438.5	366.5	379.5	415.5	348.5	7200
399.5	363.5	418.5	435.5	382.5	400.5	398.5	362.5	419.5	434.5	383.5	401.5	397.5	361.5	420.5	433.5	384.5	402.5	7200
292.5	471.5	327.5	472.5	490.5	345.5	293.5	470.5	326.5	473.5	491.5	344.5	294.5	469.5	325.5	474.5	492.5	343.5	7200
508.5	274.5	256.5	273.5	525.5	561.5	509.5	275.5	257.5	272.5	524.5	560.5	510.5	276.5	258.5	271.5	523.5	559.5	7200
241.5	547.5	540.5	529.5	252.5	288.5	242.5	548.5	539.5	530.5	251.5	287.5	243.5	549.5	538.5	531.5	250.5	286.5	7200
504.5	306.5	486.5	313.5	331.5	457.5	503.5	305.5	485.5	314.5	332.5	458.5	502.5	304.5	484.5	315.5	333.5	459.5	7200
450.5	439.5	367.5	378.5	414.5	349.5	449.5	440.5	368.5	377.5	413.5	350.5	448.5	441.5	369.5	376.5	412.5	351.5	7200
396.5	360.5	421.5	432.5	385.5	403.5	395.5	359.5	422.5	431.5	386.5	404.5	394.5	358.5	423.5	430.5	387.5	405.5	7200
295.5	468.5	324.5	475.5	493.5	342.5	296.5	467.5	323.5	476.5	494.5	341.5	297.5	466.5	322.5	477.5	495.5	340.5	7200
511.5	277.5	259.5	270.5	522.5	558.5	512.5	278.5	260.5	269.5	521.5	557.5	513.5	279.5	261.5	268.5	520.5	556.5	7200
244.5	550.5	537.5	532.5	249.5	285.5	245.5	551.5	536.5	533.5	248.5	284.5	246.5	552.5	535.5	534.5	247.5	283.5	7200
501.5	303.5	483.5	316.5	334.5	460.5	500.5	302.5	482.5	317.5	335.5	461.5	499.5	301.5	481.5	318.5	336.5	462.5	7200
447.5	442.5	370.5	375.5	411.5	352.5	446.5	443.5	371.5	374.5	410.5	353.5	445.5	444.5	372.5	373.5	409.5	354.5	7200
393.5	357.5	424.5	429.5	388.5	406.5	392.5	356.5	425.5	428.5	389.5	407.5	391.5	355.5	426.5	427.5	390.5	408.5	7200
298.5	465.5	321.5	478.5	496.5	339.5	299.5	464.5	320.5	479.5	497.5	338.5	300.5	463.5	319.5	480.5	498.5	337.5	7200
514.5	280.5	262.5	267.5	519.5	555.5	515.5	281.5	263.5	266.5	518.5	554.5	516.5	282.5	264.5	265.5	517.5	553.5	7200
7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 18 given in Examples 18.3 and 18.4 are respectively with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 7200; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 7200 = 129600 = 360^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 2400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2400 = 14400 = 120^2.$$

Both the Examples 18.3 and 18.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (38,360,362)**, i.e., $38^2 + 360^2 = 362^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

18.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 16 given in List (15):

Order 18, $S_{18 \times 18} := 3042$, $T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 18 **fraction numbers** entries. See below the example.

Example 18.5. A **block-wise** magic square of order 18 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$ is given by

																		3042
7.5	313.5	312.5	295.5	24.5	60.5	8.5	314.5	311.5	296.5	23.5	59.5	9.5	315.5	310.5	297.5	22.5	58.5	3042
276.5	78.5	258.5	79.5	97.5	223.5	275.5	77.5	257.5	80.5	98.5	224.5	274.5	76.5	256.5	81.5	99.5	225.5	3042
222.5	205.5	133.5	150.5	186.5	115.5	221.5	206.5	134.5	149.5	185.5	116.5	220.5	207.5	135.5	148.5	184.5	117.5	3042
168.5	132.5	187.5	204.5	151.5	169.5	167.5	131.5	188.5	203.5	152.5	170.5	166.5	130.5	189.5	202.5	153.5	171.5	3042
61.5	240.5	96.5	241.5	259.5	114.5	62.5	239.5	95.5	242.5	260.5	113.5	63.5	238.5	94.5	243.5	261.5	112.5	3042
277.5	43.5	25.5	42.5	294.5	330.5	278.5	44.5	26.5	41.5	293.5	329.5	279.5	45.5	27.5	40.5	292.5	328.5	3042
10.5	316.5	309.5	298.5	21.5	57.5	11.5	317.5	308.5	299.5	20.5	56.5	12.5	318.5	307.5	300.5	19.5	55.5	3042
273.5	75.5	255.5	82.5	100.5	226.5	272.5	74.5	254.5	83.5	101.5	227.5	271.5	73.5	253.5	84.5	102.5	228.5	3042
219.5	208.5	136.5	147.5	183.5	118.5	218.5	209.5	137.5	146.5	182.5	119.5	217.5	210.5	138.5	145.5	181.5	120.5	3042
165.5	129.5	190.5	201.5	154.5	172.5	164.5	128.5	191.5	200.5	155.5	173.5	163.5	127.5	192.5	199.5	156.5	174.5	3042
64.5	237.5	93.5	244.5	262.5	111.5	65.5	236.5	92.5	245.5	263.5	110.5	66.5	235.5	91.5	246.5	264.5	109.5	3042
280.5	46.5	28.5	39.5	291.5	327.5	281.5	47.5	29.5	38.5	290.5	326.5	282.5	48.5	30.5	37.5	289.5	325.5	3042
13.5	319.5	306.5	301.5	18.5	54.5	14.5	320.5	305.5	302.5	17.5	53.5	15.5	321.5	304.5	303.5	16.5	52.5	3042
270.5	72.5	252.5	85.5	103.5	229.5	269.5	71.5	251.5	86.5	104.5	230.5	268.5	70.5	250.5	87.5	105.5	231.5	3042
216.5	211.5	139.5	144.5	180.5	121.5	215.5	212.5	140.5	143.5	179.5	122.5	214.5	213.5	141.5	142.5	178.5	123.5	3042
162.5	126.5	193.5	198.5	157.5	175.5	161.5	125.5	194.5	197.5	158.5	176.5	160.5	124.5	195.5	196.5	159.5	177.5	3042
67.5	234.5	90.5	247.5	265.5	108.5	68.5	233.5	89.5	248.5	266.5	107.5	69.5	232.5	88.5	249.5	267.5	106.5	3042
283.5	49.5	31.5	36.5	288.5	324.5	284.5	50.5	32.5	35.5	287.5	323.5	285.5	51.5	33.5	34.5	286.5	322.5	3042
3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042

The **block-wise** magic square of order 18 given in Example 18.5 is with **minimum perfect square** sum of entries.

The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 3042; \quad T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 1014; \quad T_{36} := 6084 = 78^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

19 Magic Squares of Order 19

This section brings magic squares of order 19 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

19.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 17 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 19, \quad \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 6859, \quad \mathbf{T}_{361} := 130321 = 361^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 719, 721\} \text{ or } E := \{181, 182, \dots, 539, 541\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 19 with different entries. Below are these magic squares. See below these magic squares.

Example 19.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 719, 731\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

39	71	67	63	59	55	51	47	43	689	691	695	699	703	707	711	715	719	35
721	103	647	643	639	635	631	627	623	621	111	115	119	123	127	131	135	107	1
717	73	137	571	195	373	529	197	511	285	343	469	227	451	315	403	409	649	5
713	77	375	553	139	557	181	345	493	199	497	271	405	433	229	437	301	645	9
709	81	559	167	361	555	163	499	257	331	495	223	439	287	391	435	253	641	13
705	85	541	165	583	169	347	481	225	523	259	317	421	255	463	289	377	637	17
701	89	193	349	527	151	585	283	319	467	211	525	313	379	407	241	465	633	21
697	93	141	569	191	369	535	201	509	281	339	475	231	449	311	399	415	629	25
693	97	371	549	145	561	179	341	489	205	501	269	401	429	235	441	299	625	29
37	617	565	171	359	551	159	505	261	329	491	219	445	291	389	431	249	105	685
41	613	539	161	579	175	351	479	221	519	265	321	419	251	459	295	381	109	681
45	609	189	355	531	149	581	279	325	471	209	521	309	385	411	239	461	113	677
49	605	143	573	187	365	537	203	513	277	335	477	233	453	307	395	417	117	673
53	601	367	545	147	563	183	337	485	207	503	273	397	425	237	443	303	121	669
57	597	567	173	363	547	155	507	263	333	487	215	447	293	393	427	245	125	665
61	593	543	157	575	177	353	483	217	515	267	323	423	247	455	297	383	129	661
65	589	185	357	533	153	577	275	327	473	213	517	305	387	413	243	457	133	657
69	615	75	79	83	87	91	95	99	101	611	607	603	599	595	591	587	619	653
687	651	655	659	663	667	671	675	679	33	31	27	23	19	15	11	7	3	683

Example 19.2. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{181, 182, 183, \dots, 540, 541\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

200	216	214	212	210	208	206	204	202	525	526	528	530	532	534	536	538	540	198
541	232	504	502	500	498	496	494	492	491	236	238	240	242	244	246	248	234	181
539	217	249	466	278	367	445	279	436	323	352	415	294	406	338	382	385	505	183
537	219	368	457	250	459	271	353	427	280	429	316	383	397	295	399	331	503	185
535	221	460	264	361	458	262	430	309	346	428	292	400	324	376	398	307	501	187
533	223	451	263	472	265	354	421	293	442	310	339	391	308	412	325	369	499	189
531	225	277	355	444	256	473	322	340	414	286	443	337	370	384	301	413	497	191
529	227	251	465	276	365	448	281	435	321	350	418	296	405	336	380	388	495	193
527	229	366	455	253	461	270	351	425	283	431	315	381	395	298	401	330	493	195
199	489	463	266	360	456	260	433	311	345	426	290	403	326	375	396	305	233	523
201	487	450	261	470	268	356	420	291	440	313	341	390	306	410	328	371	235	521
203	485	275	358	446	255	471	320	343	416	285	441	335	373	386	300	411	237	519
205	483	252	467	274	363	449	282	437	319	348	419	297	407	334	378	389	239	517
207	481	364	453	254	462	272	349	423	284	432	317	379	393	299	402	332	241	515
209	479	464	267	362	454	258	434	312	347	424	288	404	327	377	394	303	243	513
211	477	452	259	468	269	357	422	289	438	314	342	392	304	408	329	372	245	511
213	475	273	359	447	257	469	318	344	417	287	439	333	374	387	302	409	247	509
215	488	218	220	222	224	226	228	230	231	486	484	482	480	478	476	474	490	507
524	506	508	510	512	514	516	518	520	197	196	194	192	190	188	186	184	182	522

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 19 given in Examples 19.1 and 19.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** and with equal sum blocks of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{19 \times 19} &:= 6859 = 19^3; & T_{361} &:= 19 \times 6859 = 130321 = 361^2 = 19^4; \\ S_{17 \times 17} &:= 6137; & T_{289} &:= 17 \times 6137 = 104329 = 323^2; \\ S_{15 \times 15} &:= 5415; & T_{225} &:= 15 \times 5415 = 81225 = 285^2; \\ S_{5 \times 5} &:= 1805; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 1805 = 9025 = 95^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 19.1 and 19.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 19, 19^2, 19^3, 19^4 \rangle$.

19.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 17 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (40, 399, 401) &\Rightarrow 401^2 - 40^2 = 399^2, \quad 401 - 40 = 19^2, \quad \text{Order 19, } S_{19 \times 19} := 8379, \quad T_{361} := 399^2, \\ E &= \{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\} \text{ or } E = \{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 19 with different entries. Below are these magic squares. Below are these two magic squares:

Example 19.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{81, 83, \dots, 799, 801\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

119	151	147	143	139	135	131	127	123	769	771	775	779	783	787	791	795	799	115
801	183	727	723	719	715	711	707	703	701	191	195	199	203	207	211	215	187	81
797	153	587	345	391	589	363	371	591	365	367	593	343	387	595	339	389	729	85
793	157	375	601	347	393	581	349	395	577	351	373	597	353	369	599	355	725	89
789	161	361	377	585	341	379	603	337	381	605	357	383	583	359	385	579	721	93
785	165	287	615	421	289	633	401	291	635	397	293	613	417	295	609	419	717	97
781	169	405	301	617	423	281	619	425	277	621	403	297	623	399	299	625	713	101
777	173	631	407	285	611	409	303	607	411	305	627	413	283	629	415	279	709	105
773	177	227	645	451	229	663	431	231	665	427	233	643	447	235	639	449	705	109
117	697	435	241	647	453	221	649	455	217	651	433	237	653	429	239	655	185	765
121	693	661	437	225	641	439	243	637	441	245	657	443	223	659	445	219	189	761
125	689	527	315	481	529	333	461	531	335	457	533	313	477	535	309	479	193	757
129	685	465	541	317	483	521	319	485	517	321	463	537	323	459	539	325	197	753
133	681	331	467	525	311	469	543	307	471	545	327	473	523	329	475	519	201	749
137	677	557	255	511	559	273	491	561	275	487	563	253	507	565	249	509	205	745
141	673	495	571	257	513	551	259	515	547	261	493	567	263	489	569	265	209	741
145	669	271	497	555	251	499	573	247	501	575	267	503	553	269	505	549	213	737
149	695	155	159	163	167	171	175	179	181	691	687	683	679	675	671	667	699	733
767	731	735	739	743	747	751	755	759	113	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	763

Example 19.4. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{261, 262, \dots, 620, 621\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

280	296	294	292	290	288	286	284	282	605	606	608	610	612	614	616	618	620	278
621	312	584	582	580	578	576	574	572	571	316	318	320	322	324	326	328	314	261
619	297	514	393	416	515	402	406	516	403	404	517	392	414	518	390	415	585	263
617	299	408	521	394	417	511	395	418	509	396	407	519	397	405	520	398	583	265
615	301	401	409	513	391	410	522	389	411	523	399	412	512	400	413	510	581	267
613	303	364	528	431	365	537	421	366	538	419	367	527	429	368	525	430	579	269
611	305	423	371	529	432	361	530	433	359	531	422	369	532	420	370	533	577	271
609	307	536	424	363	526	425	372	524	426	373	534	427	362	535	428	360	575	273
607	309	334	543	446	335	552	436	336	553	434	337	542	444	338	540	445	573	275
279	569	438	341	544	447	331	545	448	329	546	437	339	547	435	340	548	313	603
281	567	551	439	333	541	440	342	539	441	343	549	442	332	550	443	330	315	601
283	565	484	378	461	485	387	451	486	388	449	487	377	459	488	375	460	317	599
285	563	453	491	379	462	481	380	463	479	381	452	489	382	450	490	383	319	597
287	561	386	454	483	376	455	492	374	456	493	384	457	482	385	458	480	321	595
289	559	499	348	476	500	357	466	501	358	464	502	347	474	503	345	475	323	593
291	557	468	506	349	477	496	350	478	494	351	467	504	352	465	505	353	325	591
293	555	356	469	498	346	470	507	344	471	508	354	472	497	355	473	495	327	589
295	568	298	300	302	304	306	308	310	311	566	564	562	560	558	556	554	570	587
604	586	588	590	592	594	596	598	600	277	276	274	272	270	268	266	264	262	602

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 19 given in Examples 19.3 and 19.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** and with equal sum blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{19 \times 19} &:= 8379; & T_{361} &:= 19 \times 8379 = 159201 = 399^2; \\ S_{17 \times 17} &:= 7497; & T_{289} &:= 17 \times 7497 = 127449 = 357^2; \\ S_{15 \times 15} &:= 6615; & T_{225} &:= 15 \times 6615 = 99225 = 315^2; \\ S_{m_{3 \times 3}} &:= 1323; & T_{25} &:= 3 \times 1323 = 3969 = 63^2. \end{aligned}$$

Both the Examples 19.3 and 19.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (40,399,401)**, i.e., $40^2 + 399^2 = 401^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

19.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 17 given in List (15):

17.

$$\text{Order 19, } S_{19 \times 19} := 3724, T_{361} := 70756 = 266^2, E := \{16, 17, \dots, 375, 376\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 19.

Example 19.5. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{16, 17, 18, \dots, 375, 376\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

35	51	49	47	45	43	41	39	37	360	361	363	365	367	369	371	373	375	33
376	67	339	337	335	333	331	329	327	326	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	69	16
374	52	84	301	113	202	280	114	271	158	187	250	129	241	173	217	220	340	18
372	54	203	292	85	294	106	188	262	115	264	151	218	232	130	234	166	338	20
370	56	295	99	196	293	97	265	144	181	263	127	235	159	211	233	142	336	22
368	58	286	98	307	100	189	256	128	277	145	174	226	143	247	160	204	334	24
366	60	112	190	279	91	308	157	175	249	121	278	172	205	219	136	248	332	26
364	62	86	300	111	200	283	116	270	156	185	253	131	240	171	215	223	330	28
362	64	201	290	88	296	105	186	260	118	266	150	216	230	133	236	165	328	30
34	324	298	101	195	291	95	268	146	180	261	125	238	161	210	231	140	68	358
36	322	285	96	305	103	191	255	126	275	148	176	225	141	245	163	206	70	356
38	320	110	193	281	90	306	155	178	251	120	276	170	208	221	135	246	72	354
40	318	87	302	109	198	284	117	272	154	183	254	132	242	169	213	224	74	352
42	316	199	288	89	297	107	184	258	119	267	152	214	228	134	237	167	76	350
44	314	299	102	197	289	93	269	147	182	259	123	239	162	212	229	138	78	348
46	312	287	94	303	104	192	257	124	273	149	177	227	139	243	164	207	80	346
48	310	108	194	282	92	304	153	179	252	122	274	168	209	222	137	244	82	344
50	323	53	55	57	59	61	63	65	66	321	319	317	315	313	311	309	325	342
359	341	343	345	347	349	351	353	355	32	31	29	27	25	23	21	19	17	357

The magic square of order 19 given in Example 19.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner block of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with equal sum blocks of **pandiagonal** magic sums of order 5. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{19 \times 19} &:= 3724; & T_{361} &:= 19 \times 3724 = 70756 = 266^2; \\
 S_{17 \times 17} &:= 3332; & T_{289} &:= 17 \times 6137 = 56644 = 238^2; \\
 S_{15 \times 15} &:= 2940; & T_{225} &:= 15 \times 2940 = 44100 = 210^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 980; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 980 = 4900 = 70^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

20 Magic Squares of Order 20

This section brings magic squares of order 20 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

20.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 18 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 20, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 8000, \quad T_{400} := 160000 = 400^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 797, 799\} \text{ or } E := \{401/2, 403/2, \dots, 1195/2, 1199/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 20 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 20.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 20 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries 1, 3, 5, ..., 797, 799 is given by

		8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
	379	401	39	781	333	447	73	747	297	483	117	703	251	529	151	669	215	565	195	625	8000
8000	21	799	361	419	67	753	327	453	103	717	283	497	149	671	249	531	185	635	205	575	8000
8000	761	19	421	399	727	53	467	353	683	97	503	317	649	131	549	271	605	175	585	235	8000
8000	439	381	779	1	473	347	733	47	517	303	697	83	551	269	651	129	595	225	615	165	8000
8000	257	523	157	663	211	569	191	629	375	405	35	785	339	441	79	741	293	487	113	707	8000
8000	143	677	243	537	189	631	209	571	25	795	365	415	61	759	321	459	107	713	287	493	8000
8000	643	137	543	277	609	171	589	231	765	15	425	395	721	59	461	359	687	93	507	313	8000
8000	557	263	657	123	591	229	611	169	435	385	775	5	479	341	739	41	513	307	693	87	8000
8000	335	445	75	745	299	481	119	701	253	527	153	667	217	563	197	623	371	409	31	789	8000
8000	65	755	325	455	101	719	281	499	147	673	247	533	183	637	203	577	29	791	369	411	8000
8000	725	55	465	355	681	99	501	319	647	133	547	273	603	177	583	237	769	11	429	391	8000
8000	475	345	735	45	519	301	699	81	553	267	653	127	597	223	617	163	431	389	771	9	8000
8000	213	567	193	627	377	403	37	783	331	449	71	749	295	485	115	705	259	521	159	661	8000
8000	187	633	207	573	23	797	363	417	69	751	329	451	105	715	285	495	141	679	241	539	8000
8000	607	173	587	233	763	17	423	397	729	51	469	351	685	95	505	315	641	139	541	279	8000
8000	593	227	613	167	437	383	777	3	471	349	731	49	515	305	695	85	559	261	659	121	8000
8000	291	489	111	709	255	525	155	665	219	561	199	621	373	407	33	787	337	443	77	743	8000
8000	109	711	289	491	145	675	245	535	181	639	201	579	27	793	367	413	63	757	323	457	8000
8000	689	91	509	311	645	135	545	275	601	179	581	239	767	13	427	393	723	57	463	357	8000
8000	511	309	691	89	555	265	655	125	599	221	619	161	433	387	773	7	477	343	737	43	8000
	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000

Example 20.2. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 20 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{401/2, 403/2, \dots, 1195/2, 1199/2\}$ is given by

		8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000
	389.5	400.5	219.5	590.5	366.5	423.5	236.5	573.5	348.5	441.5	258.5	551.5	325.5	464.5	275.5	534.5	307.5	482.5	297.5	512.5	8000
8000	210.5	599.5	380.5	409.5	233.5	576.5	363.5	426.5	251.5	558.5	341.5	448.5	274.5	535.5	324.5	465.5	292.5	517.5	302.5	487.5	8000
8000	580.5	209.5	410.5	399.5	563.5	226.5	433.5	376.5	541.5	248.5	451.5	358.5	524.5	265.5	474.5	335.5	502.5	287.5	492.5	317.5	8000
8000	419.5	390.5	589.5	200.5	436.5	373.5	566.5	223.5	458.5	351.5	548.5	241.5	475.5	334.5	525.5	264.5	497.5	312.5	507.5	282.5	8000
8000	328.5	461.5	278.5	531.5	305.5	484.5	295.5	514.5	387.5	402.5	217.5	592.5	369.5	420.5	239.5	570.5	346.5	443.5	256.5	553.5	8000
8000	271.5	538.5	321.5	468.5	294.5	515.5	304.5	485.5	212.5	597.5	382.5	407.5	230.5	579.5	360.5	429.5	253.5	556.5	343.5	446.5	8000
8000	521.5	268.5	471.5	338.5	504.5	285.5	494.5	315.5	582.5	207.5	412.5	397.5	560.5	229.5	430.5	379.5	543.5	246.5	453.5	356.5	8000
8000	478.5	331.5	528.5	261.5	495.5	314.5	505.5	284.5	417.5	392.5	587.5	202.5	439.5	370.5	569.5	220.5	456.5	353.5	546.5	243.5	8000
8000	367.5	422.5	237.5	572.5	349.5	440.5	259.5	550.5	326.5	463.5	276.5	533.5	308.5	481.5	298.5	511.5	385.5	404.5	215.5	594.5	8000
8000	232.5	577.5	362.5	427.5	250.5	559.5	340.5	449.5	273.5	536.5	323.5	466.5	291.5	518.5	301.5	488.5	214.5	595.5	384.5	405.5	8000
8000	562.5	227.5	432.5	377.5	540.5	249.5	450.5	359.5	523.5	266.5	473.5	336.5	501.5	288.5	491.5	318.5	584.5	205.5	414.5	395.5	8000
8000	437.5	372.5	567.5	222.5	459.5	350.5	549.5	240.5	476.5	333.5	526.5	263.5	498.5	311.5	508.5	281.5	415.5	394.5	585.5	204.5	8000
8000	306.5	483.5	296.5	513.5	388.5	401.5	218.5	591.5	365.5	424.5	235.5	574.5	347.5	442.5	257.5	552.5	329.5	460.5	279.5	530.5	8000
8000	293.5	516.5	303.5	486.5	211.5	598.5	381.5	408.5	234.5	575.5	364.5	425.5	252.5	557.5	342.5	447.5	270.5	539.5	320.5	469.5	8000
8000	503.5	286.5	493.5	316.5	581.5	208.5	411.5	398.5	564.5	225.5	434.5	375.5	542.5	247.5	452.5	357.5	520.5	269.5	470.5	339.5	8000
8000	496.5	313.5	506.5	283.5	418.5	391.5	588.5	201.5	435.5	374.5	565.5	224.5	457.5	352.5	547.5	242.5	479.5	330.5	529.5	260.5	8000
8000	345.5	444.5	255.5	554.5	327.5	462.5	277.5	532.5	309.5	480.5	299.5	510.5	386.5	403.5	216.5	593.5	368.5	421.5	238.5	571.5	8000
8000	254.5	555.5	344.5	445.5	272.5	537.5	322.5	467.5	290.5	519.5	300.5	489.5	213.5	596.5	383.5	406.5	231.5	578.5	361.5	428.5	8000
8000	544.5	245.5	454.5	355.5	522.5	267.5	472.5	337.5	500.5	289.5	490.5	319.5	583.5	206.5	413.5	396.5	561.5	228.5	431.5	378.5	8000
8000	455.5	354.5	545.5	244.5	477.5	332.5	527.5	262.5	499.5	310.5	509.5	280.5	416.5	393.5	586.5	203.5	438.5	371.5	568.5	221.5	8000
	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000	8000

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 20 given in Examples 20.1 and 20.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 8000 = 20^3; \quad T_{400} := 160000 = 400^2 = 20^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1600; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1600 = 6400 = 80^2.$$

The Examples 20.1 and 20.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 20, 20^2, 20^3, 20^4 \rangle$.

20.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 18 given in List (10):

$$(42, 440, 442) \Rightarrow 442^2 - 42^2 = 440^2, 442 - 42 = 20^2, \text{ Order } 20, S_{20 \times 20} := 9680, T_{400} := 440^2,$$

$$E = \{85, 87, \dots, 881, 883\} \text{ or } E = \{569/2, 571/2, \dots, 1365/2, 1367/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 20 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares. Below are these magic squares.

Example 20.3. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 20 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries 85, 87, ..., 881, 883 is given by

		9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680
	97	353	449	705	801	107	363	459	715	811	85	341	437	693	789	111	367	463	719	815	9680
9680	609	865	161	257	513	619	875	171	267	523	597	853	149	245	501	623	879	175	271	527	9680
9680	321	417	673	769	225	331	427	683	779	235	309	405	661	757	213	335	431	687	783	239	9680
9680	833	129	385	481	577	843	139	395	491	587	821	117	373	469	565	847	143	399	495	591	9680
9680	545	641	737	193	289	555	651	747	203	299	533	629	725	181	277	559	655	751	207	303	9680
9680	87	343	439	695	791	109	365	461	717	813	99	355	451	707	803	105	361	457	713	809	9680
9680	599	855	151	247	503	621	877	173	269	525	611	867	163	259	515	617	873	169	265	521	9680
9680	311	407	663	759	215	333	429	685	781	237	323	419	675	771	227	329	425	681	777	233	9680
9680	823	119	375	471	567	845	141	397	493	589	835	131	387	483	579	841	137	393	489	585	9680
9680	535	631	727	183	279	557	653	749	205	301	547	643	739	195	291	553	649	745	201	297	9680
9680	115	371	467	723	819	89	345	441	697	793	103	359	455	711	807	93	349	445	701	797	9680
9680	627	883	179	275	531	601	857	153	249	505	615	871	167	263	519	605	861	157	253	509	9680
9680	339	435	691	787	243	313	409	665	761	217	327	423	679	775	231	317	413	669	765	221	9680
9680	851	147	403	499	595	825	121	377	473	569	839	135	391	487	583	829	125	381	477	573	9680
9680	563	659	755	211	307	537	633	729	185	281	551	647	743	199	295	541	637	733	189	285	9680
9680	101	357	453	709	805	95	351	447	703	799	113	369	465	721	817	91	347	443	699	795	9680
9680	613	869	165	261	517	607	863	159	255	511	625	881	177	273	529	603	859	155	251	507	9680
9680	325	421	677	773	229	319	415	671	767	223	337	433	689	785	241	315	411	667	763	219	9680
9680	837	133	389	485	581	831	127	383	479	575	849	145	401	497	593	827	123	379	475	571	9680
9680	549	645	741	197	293	543	639	735	191	287	561	657	753	209	305	539	635	731	187	283	9680
	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680

Example 20.4. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 20 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{569/2, 571/2, \dots, 1365/2, 1367/2\}$ is given by

		9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680
	290.5	418.5	466.5	594.5	642.5	295.5	423.5	471.5	599.5	647.5	284.5	412.5	460.5	588.5	636.5	297.5	425.5	473.5	601.5	649.5	9680
9680	546.5	674.5	322.5	370.5	498.5	551.5	679.5	327.5	375.5	503.5	540.5	668.5	316.5	364.5	492.5	553.5	681.5	329.5	377.5	505.5	9680
9680	402.5	450.5	578.5	626.5	354.5	407.5	455.5	583.5	631.5	359.5	396.5	444.5	572.5	620.5	348.5	409.5	457.5	585.5	633.5	361.5	9680
9680	658.5	306.5	434.5	482.5	530.5	663.5	311.5	439.5	487.5	535.5	652.5	300.5	428.5	476.5	524.5	665.5	313.5	441.5	489.5	537.5	9680
9680	514.5	562.5	610.5	338.5	386.5	519.5	567.5	615.5	343.5	391.5	508.5	556.5	604.5	332.5	380.5	521.5	569.5	617.5	345.5	393.5	9680
9680	285.5	413.5	461.5	589.5	637.5	296.5	424.5	472.5	600.5	648.5	291.5	419.5	467.5	595.5	643.5	294.5	422.5	470.5	598.5	646.5	9680
9680	541.5	669.5	317.5	365.5	493.5	552.5	680.5	328.5	376.5	504.5	547.5	675.5	323.5	371.5	499.5	550.5	678.5	326.5	374.5	502.5	9680
9680	397.5	445.5	573.5	621.5	349.5	408.5	456.5	584.5	632.5	360.5	403.5	451.5	579.5	627.5	355.5	406.5	454.5	582.5	630.5	358.5	9680
9680	653.5	301.5	429.5	477.5	525.5	664.5	312.5	440.5	488.5	536.5	659.5	307.5	435.5	483.5	531.5	662.5	310.5	438.5	486.5	534.5	9680
9680	509.5	557.5	605.5	333.5	381.5	520.5	568.5	616.5	344.5	392.5	515.5	563.5	611.5	339.5	387.5	518.5	566.5	614.5	342.5	390.5	9680
9680	299.5	427.5	475.5	603.5	651.5	286.5	414.5	462.5	590.5	638.5	293.5	421.5	469.5	597.5	645.5	288.5	416.5	464.5	592.5	640.5	9680
9680	555.5	683.5	331.5	379.5	507.5	542.5	670.5	318.5	366.5	494.5	549.5	677.5	325.5	373.5	501.5	544.5	672.5	320.5	368.5	496.5	9680
9680	411.5	459.5	587.5	635.5	363.5	398.5	446.5	574.5	622.5	350.5	405.5	453.5	581.5	629.5	357.5	400.5	448.5	576.5	624.5	352.5	9680
9680	667.5	315.5	443.5	491.5	539.5	654.5	302.5	430.5	478.5	526.5	661.5	309.5	437.5	485.5	533.5	656.5	304.5	432.5	480.5	528.5	9680
9680	523.5	571.5	619.5	347.5	395.5	510.5	558.5	606.5	334.5	382.5	517.5	565.5	613.5	341.5	389.5	512.5	560.5	608.5	336.5	384.5	9680
9680	292.5	420.5	468.5	596.5	644.5	289.5	417.5	465.5	593.5	641.5	298.5	426.5	474.5	602.5	650.5	287.5	415.5	463.5	591.5	639.5	9680
9680	548.5	676.5	324.5	372.5	500.5	545.5	673.5	321.5	369.5	497.5	554.5	682.5	330.5	378.5	506.5	543.5	671.5	319.5	367.5	495.5	9680
9680	404.5	452.5	580.5	628.5	356.5	401.5	449.5	577.5	625.5	353.5	410.5	458.5	586.5	634.5	362.5	399.5	447.5	575.5	623.5	351.5	9680
9680	660.5	308.5	436.5	484.5	532.5	657.5	305.5	433.5	481.5	529.5	666.5	314.5	442.5	490.5	538.5	655.5	303.5	431.5	479.5	527.5	9680
9680	516.5	564.5	612.5	340.5	388.5	513.5	561.5	609.5	337.5	385.5	522.5	570.5	618.5	346.5	394.5	511.5	559.5	607.5	335.5	383.5	9680
	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680	9680

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 20 given in Examples 20.3 and 20.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 9680; \quad T_{324} := 20 \times 9680 = 193600 = 440^2.$$

Both the Examples 20.3 and 20.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (42,440,442)**, i.e., $42^2 + 440^2 = 442^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

20.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 18 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 20, } S_{20 \times 20} := 4500, T_{400} := 90000 = 300^2, E := \{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 20 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 20.5. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 20 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$ is given by

		4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500
	214.5	225.5	44.5	415.5	191.5	248.5	61.5	398.5	173.5	266.5	83.5	376.5	150.5	289.5	100.5	359.5	132.5	307.5	122.5	337.5	4500
4500	35.5	424.5	205.5	234.5	58.5	401.5	188.5	251.5	76.5	383.5	166.5	273.5	99.5	360.5	149.5	290.5	117.5	342.5	127.5	312.5	4500
4500	405.5	34.5	235.5	224.5	388.5	51.5	258.5	201.5	366.5	73.5	276.5	183.5	349.5	90.5	299.5	160.5	327.5	112.5	317.5	142.5	4500
4500	244.5	215.5	414.5	25.5	261.5	198.5	391.5	48.5	283.5	176.5	373.5	66.5	300.5	159.5	350.5	89.5	322.5	137.5	332.5	107.5	4500
4500	153.5	286.5	103.5	356.5	130.5	309.5	120.5	339.5	212.5	227.5	42.5	417.5	194.5	245.5	64.5	395.5	171.5	268.5	81.5	378.5	4500
4500	96.5	363.5	146.5	293.5	119.5	340.5	129.5	310.5	37.5	422.5	207.5	232.5	55.5	404.5	185.5	254.5	78.5	381.5	168.5	271.5	4500
4500	346.5	93.5	296.5	163.5	329.5	110.5	319.5	140.5	407.5	32.5	237.5	222.5	385.5	54.5	255.5	204.5	368.5	71.5	278.5	181.5	4500
4500	303.5	156.5	353.5	86.5	320.5	139.5	330.5	109.5	242.5	217.5	412.5	27.5	264.5	195.5	394.5	45.5	281.5	178.5	371.5	68.5	4500
4500	192.5	247.5	62.5	397.5	174.5	265.5	84.5	375.5	151.5	288.5	101.5	358.5	133.5	306.5	123.5	336.5	210.5	229.5	40.5	419.5	4500
4500	57.5	402.5	187.5	252.5	75.5	384.5	165.5	274.5	98.5	361.5	148.5	291.5	116.5	343.5	126.5	313.5	39.5	420.5	209.5	230.5	4500
4500	387.5	52.5	257.5	202.5	365.5	74.5	275.5	184.5	348.5	91.5	298.5	161.5	326.5	113.5	316.5	143.5	409.5	30.5	239.5	220.5	4500
4500	262.5	197.5	392.5	47.5	284.5	175.5	374.5	65.5	301.5	158.5	351.5	88.5	323.5	136.5	333.5	106.5	240.5	219.5	410.5	29.5	4500
4500	131.5	308.5	121.5	338.5	213.5	226.5	43.5	416.5	190.5	249.5	60.5	399.5	172.5	267.5	82.5	377.5	154.5	285.5	104.5	355.5	4500
4500	118.5	341.5	128.5	311.5	36.5	423.5	206.5	233.5	59.5	400.5	189.5	250.5	77.5	382.5	167.5	272.5	95.5	364.5	145.5	294.5	4500
4500	328.5	111.5	318.5	141.5	406.5	33.5	236.5	223.5	389.5	50.5	259.5	200.5	367.5	72.5	277.5	182.5	345.5	94.5	295.5	164.5	4500
4500	321.5	138.5	331.5	108.5	243.5	216.5	413.5	26.5	260.5	199.5	390.5	49.5	282.5	177.5	372.5	67.5	304.5	155.5	354.5	85.5	4500
4500	170.5	269.5	80.5	379.5	152.5	287.5	102.5	357.5	134.5	305.5	124.5	335.5	211.5	228.5	41.5	418.5	193.5	246.5	63.5	396.5	4500
4500	79.5	380.5	169.5	270.5	97.5	362.5	147.5	292.5	115.5	344.5	125.5	314.5	38.5	421.5	208.5	231.5	56.5	403.5	186.5	253.5	4500
4500	369.5	70.5	279.5	180.5	347.5	92.5	297.5	162.5	325.5	114.5	315.5	144.5	408.5	31.5	238.5	221.5	386.5	53.5	256.5	203.5	4500
4500	280.5	179.5	370.5	69.5	302.5	157.5	352.5	87.5	324.5	135.5	334.5	105.5	241.5	218.5	411.5	28.5	263.5	196.5	393.5	46.5	4500
	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500

The magic square of order 20 given in Example 20.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 4500; \quad T_{400} := 90000 = 300^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 900; \quad T_{19006} := 3600 = 60^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

21 Magic Squares of Order 21

This section brings magic squares of order 21 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

21.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 19 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 21, \quad S_{21 \times 21} := 9261, \quad T_{441} := 194481 = 441^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 879, 881\} \text{ or } E := \{221, 222, \dots, 659, 661\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 21 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 21.1. For the *consecutive odd numbers* entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 879, 881\}$ a **block-wise** magic square of order 21 is given by

		9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	
	1	221	309	485	529	749	793	5	219	307	483	531	747	795	3	217	311	481	533	745	797	9261
9261	739	791	37	211	305	477	527	741	789	39	215	303	475	525	743	787	41	213	301	479	523	9261
9261	473	519	737	781	35	247	295	471	517	735	783	33	249	299	469	521	733	785	31	251	297	9261
9261	245	331	463	515	729	779	25	243	333	467	513	727	777	27	241	335	465	511	731	775	29	9261
9261	771	23	235	329	499	505	725	769	21	237	327	501	509	723	773	19	239	325	503	507	721	9261
9261	541	715	767	15	233	319	497	543	719	765	13	231	321	495	545	717	763	17	229	323	493	9261
9261	317	487	539	751	757	11	225	315	489	537	753	761	9	223	313	491	535	755	759	7	227	9261
9261	85	179	267	443	571	707	835	89	177	265	441	573	705	837	87	175	269	439	575	703	839	9261
9261	697	833	121	169	263	435	569	699	831	123	173	261	433	567	701	829	125	171	259	437	565	9261
9261	431	561	695	823	119	205	253	429	559	693	825	117	207	257	427	563	691	827	115	209	255	9261
9261	203	289	421	557	687	821	109	201	291	425	555	685	819	111	199	293	423	553	689	817	113	9261
9261	813	107	193	287	457	547	683	811	105	195	285	459	551	681	815	103	197	283	461	549	679	9261
9261	583	673	809	99	191	277	455	585	677	807	97	189	279	453	587	675	805	101	187	281	451	9261
9261	275	445	581	709	799	95	183	273	447	579	711	803	93	181	271	449	577	713	801	91	185	9261
9261	43	137	351	401	613	665	877	47	135	349	399	615	663	879	45	133	353	397	617	661	881	9261
9261	655	875	79	127	347	393	611	657	873	81	131	345	391	609	659	871	83	129	343	395	607	9261
9261	389	603	653	865	77	163	337	387	601	651	867	75	165	341	385	605	649	869	73	167	339	9261
9261	161	373	379	599	645	863	67	159	375	383	597	643	861	69	157	377	381	595	647	859	71	9261
9261	855	65	151	371	415	589	641	853	63	153	369	417	593	639	857	61	155	367	419	591	637	9261
9261	625	631	851	57	149	361	413	627	635	849	55	147	363	411	629	633	847	59	145	365	409	9261
9261	359	403	623	667	841	53	141	357	405	621	669	845	51	139	355	407	619	671	843	49	143	9261
	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261

Example 21.2. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{221, 222, 223, \dots, 660, 661\}$ a **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 21 is given by

		9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261
	221	331	375	463	485	595	617	223	330	374	462	486	594	618	222	329	376	461	487	593	619	9261
9261	590	616	239	326	373	459	484	591	615	240	328	372	458	483	592	614	241	327	371	460	482	9261
9261	457	480	589	611	238	344	368	456	479	588	612	237	345	370	455	481	587	613	236	346	369	9261
9261	343	386	452	478	585	610	233	342	387	454	477	584	609	234	341	388	453	476	586	608	235	9261
9261	606	232	338	385	470	473	583	605	231	339	384	471	475	582	607	230	340	383	472	474	581	9261
9261	491	578	604	228	337	380	469	492	580	603	227	336	381	468	493	579	602	229	335	382	467	9261
9261	379	464	490	596	599	226	333	378	465	489	597	601	225	332	377	466	488	598	600	224	334	9261
9261	263	310	354	442	506	574	638	265	309	353	441	507	573	639	264	308	355	440	508	572	640	9261
9261	569	637	281	305	352	438	505	570	636	282	307	351	437	504	571	635	283	306	350	439	503	9261
9261	436	501	568	632	280	323	347	435	500	567	633	279	324	349	434	502	566	634	278	325	348	9261
9261	322	365	431	499	564	631	275	321	366	433	498	563	630	276	320	367	432	497	565	629	277	9261
9261	627	274	317	364	449	494	562	626	273	318	363	450	496	561	628	272	319	362	451	495	560	9261
9261	512	557	625	270	316	359	448	513	559	624	269	315	360	447	514	558	623	271	314	361	446	9261
9261	358	443	511	575	620	268	312	357	444	510	576	622	267	311	356	445	509	577	621	266	313	9261
9261	242	289	396	421	527	553	659	244	288	395	420	528	552	660	243	287	397	419	529	551	661	9261
9261	548	658	260	284	394	417	526	549	657	261	286	393	416	525	550	656	262	285	392	418	524	9261
9261	415	522	547	653	259	302	389	414	521	546	654	258	303	391	413	523	545	655	257	304	390	9261
9261	301	407	410	520	543	652	254	300	408	412	519	542	651	255	299	409	411	518	544	650	256	9261
9261	648	253	296	406	428	515	541	647	252	297	405	429	517	540	649	251	298	404	430	516	539	9261
9261	533	536	646	249	295	401	427	534	538	645	248	294	402	426	535	537	644	250	293	403	425	9261
9261	400	422	532	554	641	247	291	399	423	531	555	643	246	290	398	424	530	556	642	245	292	9261
	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261	9261

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 21 given in Examples 21.1 and 21.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 9261; \quad T_{441} := 9261 \times 21 = 194481 = 441^2 = 21^4;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 3087; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 3087 = 21609 = 147^2.$$

The Examples 21.1 and 21.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 21, 21^2, 21^3, 21^4 \rangle$.

Example 21.4. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{309, 310, \dots, 748, 749\}$ a **block-wise** magic square of order 21 is given by

		11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109
	554	419	614	582	683	322	495	397	695	520	727	340	476	375	736	563	661	363	513	441	633	11109
11109	608	551	428	326	595	666	691	485	411	349	529	709	732	463	392	367	573	647	630	507	450	11109
11109	425	617	545	679	309	599	401	705	481	718	331	538	379	749	459	657	353	577	444	639	504	11109
11109	581	648	358	500	451	636	555	420	612	596	671	320	477	410	700	537	712	338	457	391	739	11109
11109	354	568	665	640	510	437	609	549	429	314	593	680	704	490	393	334	527	726	748	466	373	11109
11109	652	371	564	447	626	514	423	618	546	677	323	587	406	687	494	716	348	523	382	730	475	11109
11109	519	725	343	474	376	737	562	664	361	518	438	631	542	430	615	597	672	318	491	398	698	11109
11109	347	532	708	733	464	390	370	571	646	627	505	455	619	552	416	315	591	681	692	488	407	11109
11109	721	330	536	380	747	460	655	352	580	442	644	501	426	605	556	675	324	588	404	701	482	11109
11109	584	682	321	492	399	696	533	713	341	456	389	742	579	649	359	499	454	634	560	417	610	11109
11109	325	594	668	693	486	408	335	530	722	746	469	372	355	569	663	643	508	436	606	547	434	11109
11109	678	311	598	402	702	483	719	344	524	385	729	473	653	369	565	445	625	517	421	623	543	11109
11109	516	439	632	541	433	613	602	669	316	479	409	699	534	714	339	470	377	740	561	662	364	11109
11109	628	506	453	622	550	415	312	589	686	703	489	395	336	528	723	734	467	386	368	574	645	11109
11109	443	642	502	424	604	559	673	329	585	405	689	493	717	345	525	383	743	461	658	351	578	11109
11109	471	378	738	575	650	362	498	452	637	558	418	611	583	685	319	497	396	694	521	724	342	11109
11109	735	465	387	356	572	659	641	511	435	607	548	432	328	592	667	690	484	413	346	531	710	11109
11109	381	744	462	656	365	566	448	624	515	422	621	544	676	310	601	400	707	480	720	332	535	11109
11109	478	412	697	539	711	337	458	388	741	576	651	360	512	440	635	540	431	616	600	670	317	11109
11109	706	487	394	333	526	728	745	468	374	357	570	660	629	509	449	620	553	414	313	590	684	11109
11109	403	688	496	715	350	522	384	731	472	654	366	567	446	638	503	427	603	557	674	327	586	11109
	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109	11109

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 21 given in Examples 21.3 and 21.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 11109; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 11109 = 233289 = 483^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 1587; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 1587 = 4761 = 69^2.$$

Both the Examples 21.3 and 21.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (44,483,485)**, i.e., $44^2 + 483^2 = 485^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

21.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 19 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 21, } S_{21 \times 21} := 4725, \quad T_{441} := 99225 = 315^2, \quad E := \{5, 6, \dots, 444, 445\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 21.

Example 21.5. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{5, 6, 7, \dots, 444, 445\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 21 is given by

		4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725
	5	115	159	247	269	379	401	7	114	158	246	270	378	402	6	113	160	245	271	377	403	4725
4725	374	400	23	110	157	243	268	375	399	24	112	156	242	267	376	398	25	111	155	244	266	4725
4725	241	264	373	395	22	128	152	240	263	372	396	21	129	154	239	265	371	397	20	130	153	4725
4725	127	170	236	262	369	394	17	126	171	238	261	368	393	18	125	172	237	260	370	392	19	4725
4725	390	16	122	169	254	257	367	389	15	123	168	255	259	366	391	14	124	167	256	258	365	4725
4725	275	362	388	12	121	164	253	276	364	387	11	120	165	252	277	363	386	13	119	166	251	4725
4725	163	248	274	380	383	10	117	162	249	273	381	385	9	116	161	250	272	382	384	8	118	4725
4725	47	94	138	226	290	358	422	49	93	137	225	291	357	423	48	92	139	224	292	356	424	4725
4725	353	421	65	89	136	222	289	354	420	66	91	135	221	288	355	419	67	90	134	223	287	4725
4725	220	285	352	416	64	107	131	219	284	351	417	63	108	133	218	286	350	418	62	109	132	4725
4725	106	149	215	283	348	415	59	105	150	217	282	347	414	60	104	151	216	281	349	413	61	4725
4725	411	58	101	148	233	278	346	410	57	102	147	234	280	345	412	56	103	146	235	279	344	4725
4725	296	341	409	54	100	143	232	297	343	408	53	99	144	231	298	342	407	55	98	145	230	4725
4725	142	227	295	359	404	52	96	141	228	294	360	406	51	95	140	229	293	361	405	50	97	4725
4725	26	73	180	205	311	337	443	28	72	179	204	312	336	444	27	71	181	203	313	335	445	4725
4725	332	442	44	68	178	201	310	333	441	45	70	177	200	309	334	440	46	69	176	202	308	4725
4725	199	306	331	437	43	86	173	198	305	330	438	42	87	175	197	307	329	439	41	88	174	4725
4725	85	191	194	304	327	436	38	84	192	196	303	326	435	39	83	193	195	302	328	434	40	4725
4725	432	37	80	190	212	299	325	431	36	81	189	213	301	324	433	35	82	188	214	300	323	4725
4725	317	320	430	33	79	185	211	318	322	429	32	78	186	210	319	321	428	34	77	187	209	4725
4725	184	206	316	338	425	31	75	183	207	315	339	427	30	74	182	208	314	340	426	29	76	4725
	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725	4725

The magic square of order 21 given in Example 21.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{21 \times 21} = 4725 \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 4725 = 99225 = 315^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 1575; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 1575 = 11025 = 105^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

22 Magic Squares of Order 22

This section brings magic squares of order 22 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

22.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 20 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 22, \quad S_{22 \times 22} := 10648, \quad T_{484} := 234256 = 484^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 965, 967\} \text{ or } E := \{485/2, 487/2, \dots, 1447/2, 1451/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 22 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 22.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 965, 967\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 is given by

41	945	25	941	29	937	33	933	37	929	1	947	45	921	49	917	53	913	57	909	61	925
65	97	353	449	705	801	107	363	459	715	811	85	341	437	693	789	111	367	463	719	815	903
901	609	865	161	257	513	619	875	171	267	523	597	853	149	245	501	623	879	175	271	527	67
69	321	417	673	769	225	331	427	683	779	235	309	405	661	757	213	335	431	687	783	239	899
897	833	129	385	481	577	843	139	395	491	587	821	117	373	469	565	847	143	399	495	591	71
73	545	641	737	193	289	555	651	747	203	299	533	629	725	181	277	559	655	751	207	303	895
893	87	343	439	695	791	109	365	461	717	813	99	355	451	707	803	105	361	457	713	809	75
77	599	855	151	247	503	621	877	173	269	525	611	867	163	259	515	617	873	169	265	521	891
889	311	407	663	759	215	333	429	685	781	237	323	419	675	771	227	329	425	681	777	233	79
81	823	119	375	471	567	845	141	397	493	589	835	131	387	483	579	841	137	393	489	585	887
885	535	631	727	183	279	557	653	749	205	301	547	643	739	195	291	553	649	745	201	297	83
905	115	371	467	723	819	89	345	441	697	793	103	359	455	711	807	93	349	445	701	797	63
949	627	883	179	275	531	601	857	153	249	505	615	871	167	263	519	605	861	157	253	509	19
17	339	435	691	787	243	313	409	665	761	217	327	423	679	775	231	317	413	669	765	221	951
953	851	147	403	499	595	825	121	377	473	569	839	135	391	487	583	829	125	381	477	573	15
13	563	659	755	211	307	537	633	729	185	281	551	647	743	199	295	541	637	733	189	285	955
957	101	357	453	709	805	95	351	447	703	799	113	369	465	721	817	91	347	443	699	795	11
9	613	869	165	261	517	607	863	159	255	511	625	881	177	273	529	603	859	155	251	507	959
961	325	421	677	773	229	319	415	671	767	223	337	433	689	785	241	315	411	667	763	219	7
5	837	133	389	485	581	831	127	383	479	575	849	145	401	497	593	827	123	379	475	571	963
965	549	645	741	197	293	543	639	735	191	287	561	657	753	209	305	539	635	731	187	283	3
43	23	943	27	939	31	935	35	931	39	967	21	923	47	919	51	915	55	911	59	907	927

Example 22.2. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{485/2, 487/2, \dots, 1447/2, 1451/2\}$, a **block-bordered magic square of order 22** is given by

262.5	714.5	254.5	712.5	256.5	710.5	258.5	708.5	260.5	706.5	242.5	715.5	264.5	702.5	266.5	700.5	268.5	698.5	270.5	696.5	272.5	704.5
274.5	473.5	484.5	303.5	674.5	450.5	507.5	320.5	657.5	432.5	525.5	342.5	635.5	409.5	548.5	359.5	618.5	391.5	566.5	381.5	596.5	693.5
692.5	294.5	683.5	464.5	493.5	317.5	660.5	447.5	510.5	335.5	642.5	425.5	532.5	358.5	619.5	408.5	549.5	376.5	601.5	386.5	571.5	275.5
276.5	664.5	293.5	494.5	483.5	647.5	310.5	517.5	460.5	625.5	332.5	535.5	442.5	608.5	349.5	558.5	419.5	586.5	371.5	576.5	401.5	691.5
690.5	503.5	474.5	673.5	284.5	520.5	457.5	650.5	307.5	542.5	435.5	632.5	325.5	559.5	418.5	609.5	348.5	581.5	396.5	591.5	366.5	277.5
278.5	412.5	545.5	362.5	615.5	389.5	568.5	379.5	598.5	471.5	486.5	301.5	676.5	453.5	504.5	323.5	654.5	430.5	527.5	340.5	637.5	689.5
688.5	355.5	622.5	405.5	552.5	378.5	599.5	388.5	569.5	296.5	681.5	466.5	491.5	314.5	663.5	444.5	513.5	337.5	640.5	427.5	530.5	279.5
280.5	605.5	352.5	555.5	422.5	588.5	369.5	578.5	399.5	666.5	291.5	496.5	481.5	644.5	313.5	514.5	463.5	627.5	330.5	537.5	440.5	687.5
686.5	562.5	415.5	612.5	345.5	579.5	398.5	589.5	368.5	501.5	476.5	671.5	286.5	523.5	454.5	653.5	304.5	540.5	437.5	630.5	327.5	281.5
282.5	451.5	506.5	321.5	656.5	433.5	524.5	343.5	634.5	410.5	547.5	360.5	617.5	392.5	565.5	382.5	595.5	469.5	488.5	299.5	678.5	685.5
684.5	316.5	661.5	446.5	511.5	334.5	643.5	424.5	533.5	357.5	620.5	407.5	550.5	375.5	602.5	385.5	572.5	298.5	679.5	468.5	489.5	283.5
694.5	646.5	311.5	516.5	461.5	624.5	333.5	534.5	443.5	607.5	350.5	557.5	420.5	585.5	372.5	575.5	402.5	668.5	289.5	498.5	479.5	273.5
716.5	521.5	456.5	651.5	306.5	543.5	434.5	633.5	324.5	560.5	417.5	610.5	347.5	582.5	395.5	592.5	365.5	499.5	478.5	669.5	288.5	251.5
250.5	390.5	567.5	380.5	597.5	472.5	485.5	302.5	675.5	449.5	508.5	319.5	658.5	431.5	526.5	341.5	636.5	413.5	544.5	363.5	614.5	717.5
718.5	377.5	600.5	387.5	570.5	295.5	682.5	465.5	492.5	318.5	659.5	448.5	509.5	336.5	641.5	426.5	531.5	354.5	623.5	404.5	553.5	249.5
248.5	587.5	370.5	577.5	400.5	665.5	292.5	495.5	482.5	648.5	309.5	518.5	459.5	626.5	331.5	536.5	441.5	604.5	353.5	554.5	423.5	719.5
720.5	580.5	397.5	590.5	367.5	502.5	475.5	672.5	285.5	519.5	458.5	649.5	308.5	541.5	436.5	631.5	326.5	563.5	414.5	613.5	344.5	247.5
246.5	429.5	528.5	339.5	638.5	411.5	546.5	361.5	616.5	393.5	564.5	383.5	594.5	470.5	487.5	300.5	677.5	452.5	505.5	322.5	655.5	721.5
722.5	338.5	639.5	428.5	529.5	356.5	621.5	406.5	551.5	374.5	603.5	384.5	573.5	297.5	680.5	467.5	490.5	315.5	662.5	445.5	512.5	245.5
244.5	628.5	329.5	538.5	439.5	606.5	351.5	556.5	421.5	584.5	373.5	574.5	403.5	667.5	290.5	497.5	480.5	645.5	312.5	515.5	462.5	723.5
724.5	539.5	438.5	629.5	328.5	561.5	416.5	611.5	346.5	583.5	394.5	593.5	364.5	500.5	477.5	670.5	287.5	522.5	455.5	652.5	305.5	243.5
263.5	253.5	713.5	255.5	711.5	257.5	709.5	259.5	707.5	261.5	725.5	252.5	703.5	265.5	701.5	267.5	699.5	269.5	697.5	271.5	695.5	705.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 22 given in Examples 22.1 and 22.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic square of order 20 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with blocks of order 4. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of equal sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{22 \times 22} &:= 10648; & T_{484} &:= 22 \times 10648 = 234256 = 484^2 = 22^4; \\ S_{20 \times 20} &:= 9680; & T_{400} &:= 20 \times 9680 = 193600 = 440^2; \\ S_{4 \times 4} &:= 1936; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 1936 = 7744 = 88^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 22.1 and 22.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 22, 22^2, 22^3, 22^4 \rangle$.

22.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 20 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (46, 528, 530) &\Rightarrow 530^2 - 46^2 = 528^2, \quad 530 - 46 = 22^2, \quad \text{Order } 22, \quad S_{22 \times 22} := 12672, \quad T_{484} := 528^2, \\ E &= \{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\} \text{ or } E = \{669/2, 671/2, \dots, 1633/2, 1635/2\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 22 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 22.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{93, 95, \dots, 1057, 1059\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 is given by

133	1037	117	1033	121	1029	125	1025	129	1021	93	1039	137	1013	141	1009	145	1005	149	1001	153	1017
157	189	445	541	797	893	199	455	551	807	903	177	433	529	785	881	203	459	555	811	907	995
993	701	957	253	349	605	711	967	263	359	615	689	945	241	337	593	715	971	267	363	619	159
161	413	509	765	861	317	423	519	775	871	327	401	497	753	849	305	427	523	779	875	331	991
989	925	221	477	573	669	935	231	487	583	679	913	209	465	561	657	939	235	491	587	683	163
165	637	733	829	285	381	647	743	839	295	391	625	721	817	273	369	651	747	843	299	395	987
985	179	435	531	787	883	201	457	553	809	905	191	447	543	799	895	197	453	549	805	901	167
169	691	947	243	339	595	713	969	265	361	617	703	959	255	351	607	709	965	261	357	613	983
981	403	499	755	851	307	425	521	777	873	329	415	511	767	863	319	421	517	773	869	325	171
173	915	211	467	563	659	937	233	489	585	681	927	223	479	575	671	933	229	485	581	677	979
977	627	723	819	275	371	649	745	841	297	393	639	735	831	287	383	645	741	837	293	389	175
997	207	463	559	815	911	181	437	533	789	885	195	451	547	803	899	185	441	537	793	889	155
1041	719	975	271	367	623	693	949	245	341	597	707	963	259	355	611	697	953	249	345	601	111
109	431	527	783	879	335	405	501	757	853	309	419	515	771	867	323	409	505	761	857	313	1043
1045	943	239	495	591	687	917	213	469	565	661	931	227	483	579	675	921	217	473	569	665	107
105	655	751	847	303	399	629	725	821	277	373	643	739	835	291	387	633	729	825	281	377	1047
1049	193	449	545	801	897	187	443	539	795	891	205	461	557	813	909	183	439	535	791	887	103
101	705	961	257	353	609	699	955	251	347	603	717	973	269	365	621	695	951	247	343	599	1051
1053	417	513	769	865	321	411	507	763	859	315	429	525	781	877	333	407	503	759	855	311	99
97	929	225	481	577	673	923	219	475	571	667	941	237	493	589	685	919	215	471	567	663	1055
1057	641	737	833	289	385	635	731	827	283	379	653	749	845	301	397	631	727	823	279	375	95
135	115	1035	119	1031	123	1027	127	1023	131	1059	113	1015	139	1011	143	1007	147	1003	151	999	1019

Example 22.4. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{669/2, 671/2, \dots, 1633/2, 1635/2\}$, a **block-bordered magic square of order 22** is given by

354.5	806.5	346.5	804.5	348.5	802.5	350.5	800.5	352.5	798.5	334.5	807.5	356.5	794.5	358.5	792.5	360.5	790.5	362.5	788.5	364.5	796.5
366.5	382.5	510.5	558.5	686.5	734.5	387.5	515.5	563.5	691.5	739.5	376.5	504.5	552.5	680.5	728.5	389.5	517.5	565.5	693.5	741.5	785.5
784.5	638.5	766.5	414.5	462.5	590.5	643.5	771.5	419.5	467.5	595.5	632.5	760.5	408.5	456.5	584.5	645.5	773.5	421.5	469.5	597.5	367.5
368.5	494.5	542.5	670.5	718.5	446.5	499.5	547.5	675.5	723.5	451.5	488.5	536.5	664.5	712.5	440.5	501.5	549.5	677.5	725.5	453.5	783.5
782.5	750.5	398.5	526.5	574.5	622.5	755.5	403.5	531.5	579.5	627.5	744.5	392.5	520.5	568.5	616.5	757.5	405.5	533.5	581.5	629.5	369.5
370.5	606.5	654.5	702.5	430.5	478.5	611.5	659.5	707.5	435.5	483.5	600.5	648.5	696.5	424.5	472.5	613.5	661.5	709.5	437.5	485.5	781.5
780.5	377.5	505.5	553.5	681.5	729.5	388.5	516.5	564.5	692.5	740.5	383.5	511.5	559.5	687.5	735.5	386.5	514.5	562.5	690.5	738.5	371.5
372.5	633.5	761.5	409.5	457.5	585.5	644.5	772.5	420.5	468.5	596.5	639.5	767.5	415.5	463.5	591.5	642.5	770.5	418.5	466.5	594.5	779.5
778.5	489.5	537.5	665.5	713.5	441.5	500.5	548.5	676.5	724.5	452.5	495.5	543.5	671.5	719.5	447.5	498.5	546.5	674.5	722.5	450.5	373.5
374.5	745.5	393.5	521.5	569.5	617.5	756.5	404.5	532.5	580.5	628.5	751.5	399.5	527.5	575.5	623.5	754.5	402.5	530.5	578.5	626.5	777.5
776.5	601.5	649.5	697.5	425.5	473.5	612.5	660.5	708.5	436.5	484.5	607.5	655.5	703.5	431.5	479.5	610.5	658.5	706.5	434.5	482.5	375.5
786.5	391.5	519.5	567.5	695.5	743.5	378.5	506.5	554.5	682.5	730.5	385.5	513.5	561.5	689.5	737.5	380.5	508.5	556.5	684.5	732.5	365.5
808.5	647.5	775.5	423.5	471.5	599.5	634.5	762.5	410.5	458.5	586.5	641.5	769.5	417.5	465.5	593.5	636.5	764.5	412.5	460.5	588.5	343.5
342.5	503.5	551.5	679.5	727.5	455.5	490.5	538.5	666.5	714.5	442.5	497.5	545.5	673.5	721.5	449.5	492.5	540.5	668.5	716.5	444.5	809.5
810.5	759.5	407.5	535.5	583.5	631.5	746.5	394.5	522.5	570.5	618.5	753.5	401.5	529.5	577.5	625.5	748.5	396.5	524.5	572.5	620.5	341.5
340.5	615.5	663.5	711.5	439.5	487.5	602.5	650.5	698.5	426.5	474.5	609.5	657.5	705.5	433.5	481.5	604.5	652.5	700.5	428.5	476.5	811.5
812.5	384.5	512.5	560.5	688.5	736.5	381.5	509.5	557.5	685.5	733.5	390.5	518.5	566.5	694.5	742.5	379.5	507.5	555.5	683.5	731.5	339.5
338.5	640.5	768.5	416.5	464.5	592.5	637.5	765.5	413.5	461.5	589.5	646.5	774.5	422.5	470.5	598.5	635.5	763.5	411.5	459.5	587.5	813.5
814.5	496.5	544.5	672.5	720.5	448.5	493.5	541.5	669.5	717.5	445.5	502.5	550.5	678.5	726.5	454.5	491.5	539.5	667.5	715.5	443.5	337.5
336.5	752.5	400.5	528.5	576.5	624.5	749.5	397.5	525.5	573.5	621.5	758.5	406.5	534.5	582.5	630.5	747.5	395.5	523.5	571.5	619.5	815.5
816.5	608.5	656.5	704.5	432.5	480.5	605.5	653.5	701.5	429.5	477.5	614.5	662.5	710.5	438.5	486.5	603.5	651.5	699.5	427.5	475.5	335.5
355.5	345.5	805.5	347.5	803.5	349.5	801.5	351.5	799.5	353.5	817.5	344.5	795.5	357.5	793.5	359.5	791.5	361.5	789.5	363.5	787.5	797.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 22 given in Examples 22.3 and 22.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic square of order 20 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with blocks of order 5. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of different magic sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{22 \times 22} &:= 12672; & T_{484} &:= 22 \times 12672 = 278784 = 528^2; \\ S_{20 \times 20} &:= 11520; & T_{400} &:= 20 \times 230400 = 193600 = 480^2. \end{aligned}$$

Both the Examples 22.3 and 22.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (46,528,530)**, i.e., $46^2 + 528^2 = 530^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

22.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 20 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 22, } S_{22 \times 22} := 5632, T_{484} := 123904 = 352^2, E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 22 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 22.5. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 is given by

34.5	486.5	26.5	484.5	28.5	482.5	30.5	480.5	32.5	478.5	14.5	487.5	36.5	474.5	38.5	472.5	40.5	470.5	42.5	468.5	44.5	476.5
46.5	245.5	256.5	75.5	446.5	222.5	279.5	92.5	429.5	204.5	297.5	114.5	407.5	181.5	320.5	131.5	390.5	163.5	338.5	153.5	368.5	465.5
464.5	66.5	455.5	236.5	265.5	89.5	432.5	219.5	282.5	107.5	414.5	197.5	304.5	130.5	391.5	180.5	321.5	148.5	373.5	158.5	343.5	47.5
48.5	436.5	65.5	266.5	255.5	419.5	82.5	289.5	232.5	397.5	104.5	307.5	214.5	380.5	121.5	330.5	191.5	358.5	143.5	348.5	173.5	463.5
462.5	275.5	246.5	445.5	56.5	292.5	229.5	422.5	79.5	314.5	207.5	404.5	97.5	331.5	190.5	381.5	120.5	353.5	168.5	363.5	138.5	49.5
50.5	184.5	317.5	134.5	387.5	161.5	340.5	151.5	370.5	243.5	258.5	73.5	448.5	225.5	276.5	95.5	426.5	202.5	299.5	112.5	409.5	461.5
460.5	127.5	394.5	177.5	324.5	150.5	371.5	160.5	341.5	68.5	453.5	238.5	263.5	86.5	435.5	216.5	285.5	109.5	412.5	199.5	302.5	51.5
52.5	377.5	124.5	327.5	194.5	360.5	141.5	350.5	171.5	438.5	63.5	268.5	253.5	416.5	85.5	286.5	235.5	399.5	102.5	309.5	212.5	459.5
458.5	334.5	187.5	384.5	117.5	351.5	170.5	361.5	140.5	273.5	248.5	443.5	58.5	295.5	226.5	425.5	76.5	312.5	209.5	402.5	99.5	53.5
54.5	223.5	278.5	93.5	428.5	205.5	296.5	115.5	406.5	182.5	319.5	132.5	389.5	164.5	337.5	154.5	367.5	241.5	260.5	71.5	450.5	457.5
456.5	88.5	433.5	218.5	283.5	106.5	415.5	196.5	305.5	129.5	392.5	179.5	322.5	147.5	374.5	157.5	344.5	70.5	451.5	240.5	261.5	55.5
466.5	418.5	83.5	288.5	233.5	396.5	105.5	306.5	215.5	379.5	122.5	329.5	192.5	357.5	144.5	347.5	174.5	440.5	61.5	270.5	251.5	45.5
488.5	293.5	228.5	423.5	78.5	315.5	206.5	405.5	96.5	332.5	189.5	382.5	119.5	354.5	167.5	364.5	137.5	271.5	250.5	441.5	60.5	23.5
22.5	162.5	339.5	152.5	369.5	244.5	257.5	74.5	447.5	221.5	280.5	91.5	430.5	203.5	298.5	113.5	408.5	185.5	316.5	135.5	386.5	489.5
490.5	149.5	372.5	159.5	342.5	67.5	454.5	237.5	264.5	90.5	431.5	220.5	281.5	108.5	413.5	198.5	303.5	126.5	395.5	176.5	325.5	21.5
20.5	359.5	142.5	349.5	172.5	437.5	64.5	267.5	254.5	420.5	81.5	290.5	231.5	398.5	103.5	308.5	213.5	376.5	125.5	326.5	195.5	491.5
492.5	352.5	169.5	362.5	139.5	274.5	247.5	444.5	57.5	291.5	230.5	421.5	80.5	313.5	208.5	403.5	98.5	335.5	186.5	385.5	116.5	19.5
18.5	201.5	300.5	111.5	410.5	183.5	318.5	133.5	388.5	165.5	336.5	155.5	366.5	242.5	259.5	72.5	449.5	224.5	277.5	94.5	427.5	493.5
494.5	110.5	411.5	200.5	301.5	128.5	393.5	178.5	323.5	146.5	375.5	156.5	345.5	69.5	452.5	239.5	262.5	87.5	434.5	217.5	284.5	17.5
16.5	400.5	101.5	310.5	211.5	378.5	123.5	328.5	193.5	356.5	145.5	346.5	175.5	439.5	62.5	269.5	252.5	417.5	84.5	287.5	234.5	495.5
496.5	311.5	210.5	401.5	100.5	333.5	188.5	383.5	118.5	355.5	166.5	365.5	136.5	272.5	249.5	442.5	59.5	294.5	227.5	424.5	77.5	15.5
35.5	25.5	485.5	27.5	483.5	29.5	481.5	31.5	479.5	33.5	497.5	24.5	475.5	37.5	473.5	39.5	471.5	41.5	469.5	43.5	467.5	477.5

The magic square of order 22 given in Example 22.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 20 is **pandiagonal** with blocks of order 4 having equal magic sums. The magic squares of order 4 are **pandiagonal**. See below the details:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5632; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 5632 = 123904 = 352^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 5120; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 5120 = 102400 = 320^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1024; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1024 = 4096 = 64^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

23 Magic Squares of Order 23

This section brings magic squares of order 23 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

23.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 21 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 23, \quad \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 12167, \quad \mathbf{T}_{529} := 279841 = 529^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1055, 1057\} \text{ or } E := \{265, 266, \dots, 791, 793\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 23 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 23.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1055, 1057\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 is given by

1015	85	81	77	73	69	65	61	57	53	49	45	1021	1025	1029	1033	1037	1041	1045	1049	1053	1057	47
971	579	309	699	635	837	115	461	265	861	511	925	151	423	221	943	597	793	197	497	353	737	87
975	687	573	327	123	661	803	853	441	293	169	529	889	935	397	255	205	617	765	731	485	371	83
979	321	705	561	829	89	669	273	881	433	907	133	547	229	969	389	785	177	625	359	749	479	79
983	633	767	187	471	373	743	581	311	695	663	813	111	425	291	871	545	895	147	385	253	949	75
987	179	607	801	751	491	345	689	569	329	99	657	831	879	451	257	139	525	923	967	403	217	71
991	775	213	599	365	723	499	317	707	563	825	117	645	283	845	459	903	167	517	235	931	421	67
995	509	921	157	419	223	945	595	799	193	507	347	733	555	331	701	665	815	107	453	267	867	63
999	165	535	887	937	399	251	211	613	763	725	481	381	709	575	303	101	653	833	855	447	285	59
1003	913	131	543	231	965	391	781	175	631	355	759	473	323	681	583	821	119	647	279	873	435	55
1007	639	835	113	455	269	863	537	897	153	383	249	955	629	769	189	469	379	739	591	305	691	51
41	121	659	807	857	443	287	141	531	915	963	409	215	181	609	797	757	487	343	683	565	339	1017
39	827	93	667	275	875	437	909	159	519	241	929	417	777	209	601	361	721	505	313	717	557	1019
35	503	349	735	553	337	697	675	809	103	429	289	869	539	899	149	411	225	951	593	795	199	1023
31	727	483	377	715	571	301	95	649	843	877	449	261	143	527	917	939	405	243	207	619	761	1027
27	357	755	475	319	679	589	817	129	641	281	849	457	905	161	521	237	957	393	787	173	627	1031
23	413	227	947	621	771	195	467	375	745	587	307	693	637	841	109	465	263	859	513	919	155	1035
19	941	401	245	183	615	789	753	493	341	685	567	335	127	655	805	851	439	297	163	533	891	1039
15	233	959	395	783	201	603	367	719	501	315	713	559	823	91	673	271	885	431	911	135	541	1043
11	427	295	865	549	893	145	387	247	953	623	773	191	495	351	741	551	333	703	671	811	105	1047
7	883	445	259	137	523	927	961	407	219	185	611	791	729	489	369	711	577	299	97	651	839	1051
3	277	847	463	901	171	515	239	933	415	779	203	605	363	747	477	325	677	585	819	125	643	1055
1011	973	977	981	985	989	993	997	1001	1005	1009	1013	37	33	29	25	21	17	13	9	5	1	43

Example 23.2. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{265, 266, 267, \dots, 792, 793\}$ a **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 21 is given by

772	307	305	303	301	299	297	295	293	291	289	287	775	777	779	781	783	785	787	789	791	793	288
750	554	419	614	582	683	322	495	397	695	520	727	340	476	375	736	563	661	363	513	441	633	308
752	608	551	428	326	595	666	691	485	411	349	529	709	732	463	392	367	573	647	630	507	450	306
754	425	617	545	679	309	599	401	705	481	718	331	538	379	749	459	657	353	577	444	639	504	304
756	581	648	358	500	451	636	555	420	612	596	671	320	477	410	700	537	712	338	457	391	739	302
758	354	568	665	640	510	437	609	549	429	314	593	680	704	490	393	334	527	726	748	466	373	300
760	652	371	564	447	626	514	423	618	546	677	323	587	406	687	494	716	348	523	382	730	475	298
762	519	725	343	474	376	737	562	664	361	518	438	631	542	430	615	597	672	318	491	398	698	296
764	347	532	708	733	464	390	370	571	646	627	505	455	619	552	416	315	591	681	692	488	407	294
766	721	330	536	380	747	460	655	352	580	442	644	501	426	605	556	675	324	588	404	701	482	292
768	584	682	321	492	399	696	533	713	341	456	389	742	579	649	359	499	454	634	560	417	610	290
285	325	594	668	693	486	408	335	530	722	746	469	372	355	569	663	643	508	436	606	547	434	773
284	678	311	598	402	702	483	719	344	524	385	729	473	653	369	565	445	625	517	421	623	543	774
282	516	439	632	541	433	613	602	669	316	479	409	699	534	714	339	470	377	740	561	662	364	776
280	628	506	453	622	550	415	312	589	686	703	489	395	336	528	723	734	467	386	368	574	645	778
278	443	642	502	424	604	559	673	329	585	405	689	493	717	345	525	383	743	461	658	351	578	780
276	471	378	738	575	650	362	498	452	637	558	418	611	583	685	319	497	396	694	521	724	342	782
274	735	465	387	356	572	659	641	511	435	607	548	432	328	592	667	690	484	413	346	531	710	784
272	381	744	462	656	365	566	448	624	515	422	621	544	676	310	601	400	707	480	720	332	535	786
270	478	412	697	539	711	337	458	388	741	576	651	360	512	440	635	540	431	616	600	670	317	788
268	706	487	394	333	526	728	745	468	374	357	570	660	629	509	449	620	553	414	313	590	684	790
266	403	688	496	715	350	522	384	731	472	654	366	567	446	638	503	427	603	557	674	327	586	792
770	751	753	755	757	759	761	763	765	767	769	771	283	281	279	277	275	273	271	269	267	265	286

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 given in Examples 23.1 and 23.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 21 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with blocks of order 3. These blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares of equal sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{23 \times 23} &:= 12167; & T_{529} &:= 12167 \times 23 = 233289 = 529^2 \\ S_{21 \times 21} &:= 11109; & T_{441} &:= 11109 \times 21 = 279841 = 483^2 \\ Sm_{3 \times 3} &:= 1587; & T_9 &:= 4761 \times 3 = 279841 = 69^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 23.1 and 23.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 23, 23^2, 23^3, 23^4 \rangle$.

23.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 21 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (48, 575, 577) &\Rightarrow 577^2 - 48^2 = 575^2, \quad 577 - 48 = 23^2, \quad \text{Order } 23, \quad S_{23 \times 23} := 14375, \quad T_{529} := 575^2, \\ E &= \{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\} \text{ or } E = \{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 23 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 23.3. For the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{97, 99, \dots, 1151, 1153\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 is given by

1111	181	177	173	169	165	161	157	153	149	145	141	1117	1121	1125	1129	1133	1137	1141	1145	1149	1153	143
1067	185	405	493	669	713	933	977	189	403	491	667	715	931	979	187	401	495	665	717	929	981	183
1071	923	975	221	395	489	661	711	925	973	223	399	487	659	709	927	971	225	397	485	663	707	179
1075	657	703	921	965	219	431	479	655	701	919	967	217	433	483	653	705	917	969	215	435	481	175
1079	429	515	647	699	913	963	209	427	517	651	697	911	961	211	425	519	649	695	915	959	213	171
1083	955	207	419	513	683	689	909	953	205	421	511	685	693	907	957	203	423	509	687	691	905	167
1087	725	899	951	199	417	503	681	727	903	949	197	415	505	679	729	901	947	201	413	507	677	163
1091	501	671	723	935	941	195	409	499	673	721	937	945	193	407	497	675	719	939	943	191	411	159
1095	269	363	451	627	755	891	1019	273	361	449	625	757	889	1021	271	359	453	623	759	887	1023	155
1099	881	1017	305	353	447	619	753	883	1015	307	357	445	617	751	885	1013	309	355	443	621	749	151
1103	615	745	879	1007	303	389	437	613	743	877	1009	301	391	441	611	747	875	1011	299	393	439	147
137	387	473	605	741	871	1005	293	385	475	609	739	869	1003	295	383	477	607	737	873	1001	297	1113
135	997	291	377	471	641	731	867	995	289	379	469	643	735	865	999	287	381	467	645	733	863	1115
131	767	857	993	283	375	461	639	769	861	991	281	373	463	637	771	859	989	285	371	465	635	1119
127	459	629	765	893	983	279	367	457	631	763	895	987	277	365	455	633	761	897	985	275	369	1123
123	227	321	535	585	797	849	1061	231	319	533	583	799	847	1063	229	317	537	581	801	845	1065	1127
119	839	1059	263	311	531	577	795	841	1057	265	315	529	575	793	843	1055	267	313	527	579	791	1131
115	573	787	837	1049	261	347	521	571	785	835	1051	259	349	525	569	789	833	1053	257	351	523	1135
111	345	557	563	783	829	1047	251	343	559	567	781	827	1045	253	341	561	565	779	831	1043	255	1139
107	1039	249	335	555	599	773	825	1037	247	337	553	601	777	823	1041	245	339	551	603	775	821	1143
103	809	815	1035	241	333	545	597	811	819	1033	239	331	547	595	813	817	1031	243	329	549	593	1147
99	543	587	807	851	1025	237	325	541	589	805	853	1029	235	323	539	591	803	855	1027	233	327	1151
1107	1069	1073	1077	1081	1085	1089	1093	1097	1101	1105	1109	133	129	125	121	117	113	109	105	101	97	139

Example 23.4. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{361, 362, \dots, 888, 889\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 is given by

868	403	401	399	397	395	393	391	389	387	385	383	871	873	875	877	879	881	883	885	887	889	384
846	405	515	559	647	669	779	801	407	514	558	646	670	778	802	406	513	560	645	671	777	803	404
848	774	800	423	510	557	643	668	775	799	424	512	556	642	667	776	798	425	511	555	644	666	402
850	641	664	773	795	422	528	552	640	663	772	796	421	529	554	639	665	771	797	420	530	553	400
852	527	570	636	662	769	794	417	526	571	638	661	768	793	418	525	572	637	660	770	792	419	398
854	790	416	522	569	654	657	767	789	415	523	568	655	659	766	791	414	524	567	656	658	765	396
856	675	762	788	412	521	564	653	676	764	787	411	520	565	652	677	763	786	413	519	566	651	394
858	563	648	674	780	783	410	517	562	649	673	781	785	409	516	561	650	672	782	784	408	518	392
860	447	494	538	626	690	758	822	449	493	537	625	691	757	823	448	492	539	624	692	756	824	390
862	753	821	465	489	536	622	689	754	820	466	491	535	621	688	755	819	467	490	534	623	687	388
864	620	685	752	816	464	507	531	619	684	751	817	463	508	533	618	686	750	818	462	509	532	386
381	506	549	615	683	748	815	459	505	550	617	682	747	814	460	504	551	616	681	749	813	461	869
380	811	458	501	548	633	678	746	810	457	502	547	634	680	745	812	456	503	546	635	679	744	870
378	696	741	809	454	500	543	632	697	743	808	453	499	544	631	698	742	807	455	498	545	630	872
376	542	627	695	759	804	452	496	541	628	694	760	806	451	495	540	629	693	761	805	450	497	874
374	426	473	580	605	711	737	843	428	472	579	604	712	736	844	427	471	581	603	713	735	845	876
372	732	842	444	468	578	601	710	733	841	445	470	577	600	709	734	840	446	469	576	602	708	878
370	599	706	731	837	443	486	573	598	705	730	838	442	487	575	597	707	729	839	441	488	574	880
368	485	591	594	704	727	836	438	484	592	596	703	726	835	439	483	593	595	702	728	834	440	882
366	832	437	480	590	612	699	725	831	436	481	589	613	701	724	833	435	482	588	614	700	723	884
364	717	720	830	433	479	585	611	718	722	829	432	478	586	610	719	721	828	434	477	587	609	886
362	584	606	716	738	825	431	475	583	607	715	739	827	430	474	582	608	714	740	826	429	476	888
866	847	849	851	853	855	857	859	861	863	865	867	379	377	375	373	371	369	367	365	363	361	382

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 given in Examples 23.3 and 23.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 21 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with equal sum blocks of order 7. See below the details:

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 14375; \quad T_{529} := 14375 \times 23 = 330625 = 575^2$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 13125; \quad T_{441} := 13125 \times 21 = 275625 = 525^2$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 4375; \quad T_{49} := 4375 \times 7 = 30625 = 175^2.$$

Both the Examples 23.3 and 23.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (48, 575, 577)**, i.e., $48^2 + 575^2 = 577^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

23.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 21 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 23, } S_{23 \times 23} := 6647, \quad T_{529} := 152881 = 391^2, \quad E := \{25, 26, \dots, 552, 553\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 23.

Example 23.5. For the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $\{25, 26, 27, \dots, 552, 553\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 is given by

532	67	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	535	537	539	541	543	545	547	549	551	553	48
510	314	179	374	342	443	82	255	157	455	280	487	100	236	135	496	323	421	123	273	201	393	68
512	368	311	188	86	355	426	451	245	171	109	289	469	492	223	152	127	333	407	390	267	210	66
514	185	377	305	439	69	359	161	465	241	478	91	298	139	509	219	417	113	337	204	399	264	64
516	341	408	118	260	211	396	315	180	372	356	431	80	237	170	460	297	472	98	217	151	499	62
518	114	328	425	400	270	197	369	309	189	74	353	440	464	250	153	94	287	486	508	226	133	60
520	412	131	324	207	386	274	183	378	306	437	83	347	166	447	254	476	108	283	142	490	235	58
522	279	485	103	234	136	497	322	424	121	278	198	391	302	190	375	357	432	78	251	158	458	56
524	107	292	468	493	224	150	130	331	406	387	265	215	379	312	176	75	351	441	452	248	167	54
526	481	90	296	140	507	220	415	112	340	202	404	261	186	365	316	435	84	348	164	461	242	52
528	344	442	81	252	159	456	293	473	101	216	149	502	339	409	119	259	214	394	320	177	370	50
45	85	354	428	453	246	168	95	290	482	506	229	132	115	329	423	403	268	196	366	307	194	533
44	438	71	358	162	462	243	479	104	284	145	489	233	413	129	325	205	385	277	181	383	303	534
42	276	199	392	301	193	373	362	429	76	239	169	459	294	474	99	230	137	500	321	422	124	536
40	388	266	213	382	310	175	72	349	446	463	249	155	96	288	483	494	227	146	128	334	405	538
38	203	402	262	184	364	319	433	89	345	165	449	253	477	105	285	143	503	221	418	111	338	540
36	231	138	498	335	410	122	258	212	397	318	178	371	343	445	79	257	156	454	281	484	102	542
34	495	225	147	116	332	419	401	271	195	367	308	192	88	352	427	450	244	173	106	291	470	544
32	141	504	222	416	125	326	208	384	275	182	381	304	436	70	361	160	467	240	480	92	295	546
30	238	172	457	299	471	97	218	148	501	336	411	120	272	200	395	300	191	376	360	430	77	548
28	466	247	154	93	286	488	505	228	134	117	330	420	389	269	209	380	313	174	73	350	444	550
26	163	448	256	475	110	282	144	491	232	414	126	327	206	398	263	187	363	317	434	87	346	552
530	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	531	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	46

The magic square of order 23 given in Example 23.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive odd numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 21 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with blocks of order 3. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares of equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 6647; \quad T_{529} := 23 \times 6647 = 152881 = 391^2$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 6069; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 6069 = 127449 = 357^2$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 867; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 867 = 2601 = 51^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

24 Magic Squares of Order 24

This section brings magic squares of order 24 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

24.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 22 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 24, \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 13824, \quad T_{576} := 331776 = 576^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1149, 1151\} \text{ or } E := \{577/2, 579/2, \dots, 1723/2, 1727/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 24 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 24.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 24 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1149, 1151\}$ is given by

		13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	
	433	863	1	1007	435	861	3	1005	437	859	5	1003	439	857	7	1001	441	855	9	999	443	853	11	997	13824
13824	143	865	575	721	141	867	573	723	139	869	571	725	137	871	569	727	135	873	567	729	133	875	565	731	13824
13824	1151	145	719	289	1149	147	717	291	1147	149	715	293	1145	151	713	295	1143	153	711	297	1141	155	709	299	13824
13824	577	431	1009	287	579	429	1011	285	581	427	1013	283	583	425	1015	281	585	423	1017	279	587	421	1019	277	13824
13824	445	851	13	995	447	849	15	993	449	847	17	991	451	845	19	989	453	843	21	987	455	841	23	985	13824
13824	131	877	563	733	129	879	561	735	127	881	559	737	125	883	557	739	123	885	555	741	121	887	553	743	13824
13824	1139	157	707	301	1137	159	705	303	1135	161	703	305	1133	163	701	307	1131	165	699	309	1129	167	697	311	13824
13824	589	419	1021	275	591	417	1023	273	593	415	1025	271	595	413	1027	269	597	411	1029	267	599	409	1031	265	13824
13824	457	839	25	983	459	837	27	981	461	835	29	979	463	833	31	977	465	831	33	975	467	829	35	973	13824
13824	119	889	551	745	117	891	549	747	115	893	547	749	113	895	545	751	111	897	543	753	109	899	541	755	13824
13824	1127	169	695	313	1125	171	693	315	1123	173	691	317	1121	175	689	319	1119	177	687	321	1117	179	685	323	13824
13824	601	407	1033	263	603	405	1035	261	605	403	1037	259	607	401	1039	257	609	399	1041	255	611	397	1043	253	13824
13824	469	827	37	971	471	825	39	969	473	823	41	967	475	821	43	965	477	819	45	963	479	817	47	961	13824
13824	107	901	539	757	105	903	537	759	103	905	535	761	101	907	533	763	99	909	531	765	97	911	529	767	13824
13824	1115	181	683	325	1113	183	681	327	1111	185	679	329	1109	187	677	331	1107	189	675	333	1105	191	673	335	13824
13824	613	395	1045	251	615	393	1047	249	617	391	1049	247	619	389	1051	245	621	387	1053	243	623	385	1055	241	13824
13824	481	815	49	959	483	813	51	957	485	811	53	955	487	809	55	953	489	807	57	951	491	805	59	949	13824
13824	95	913	527	769	93	915	525	771	91	917	523	773	89	919	521	775	87	921	519	777	85	923	517	779	13824
13824	1103	193	671	337	1101	195	669	339	1099	197	667	341	1097	199	665	343	1095	201	663	345	1093	203	661	347	13824
13824	625	383	1057	239	627	381	1059	237	629	379	1061	235	631	377	1063	233	633	375	1065	231	635	373	1067	229	13824
13824	493	803	61	947	495	801	63	945	497	799	65	943	499	797	67	941	501	795	69	939	503	793	71	937	13824
13824	83	925	515	781	81	927	513	783	79	929	511	785	77	931	509	787	75	933	507	789	73	935	505	791	13824
13824	1091	205	659	349	1089	207	657	351	1087	209	655	353	1085	211	653	355	1083	213	651	357	1081	215	649	359	13824
13824	637	371	1069	227	639	369	1071	225	641	367	1073	223	643	365	1075	221	645	363	1077	219	647	361	1079	217	13824
	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824

Example 24.2. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 24 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{577/2, 579/2, \dots, 1723/2, 1727/2\}$ is given by

		13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	
	504.5	719.5	288.5	791.5	505.5	718.5	289.5	790.5	506.5	717.5	290.5	789.5	507.5	716.5	291.5	788.5	508.5	715.5	292.5	787.5	509.5	714.5	293.5	786.5	13824
13824	359.5	720.5	575.5	648.5	358.5	721.5	574.5	649.5	357.5	722.5	573.5	650.5	356.5	723.5	572.5	651.5	355.5	724.5	571.5	652.5	354.5	725.5	570.5	653.5	13824
13824	863.5	360.5	647.5	432.5	862.5	361.5	646.5	433.5	861.5	362.5	645.5	434.5	860.5	363.5	644.5	435.5	859.5	364.5	643.5	436.5	858.5	365.5	642.5	437.5	13824
13824	576.5	503.5	792.5	431.5	577.5	502.5	793.5	430.5	578.5	501.5	794.5	429.5	579.5	500.5	795.5	428.5	580.5	499.5	796.5	427.5	581.5	498.5	797.5	426.5	13824
13824	510.5	713.5	294.5	785.5	511.5	712.5	295.5	784.5	512.5	711.5	296.5	783.5	513.5	710.5	297.5	782.5	514.5	709.5	298.5	781.5	515.5	708.5	299.5	780.5	13824
13824	353.5	726.5	569.5	654.5	352.5	727.5	568.5	655.5	351.5	728.5	567.5	656.5	350.5	729.5	566.5	657.5	349.5	730.5	565.5	658.5	348.5	731.5	564.5	659.5	13824
13824	857.5	366.5	641.5	438.5	856.5	367.5	640.5	439.5	855.5	368.5	639.5	440.5	854.5	369.5	638.5	441.5	853.5	370.5	637.5	442.5	852.5	371.5	636.5	443.5	13824
13824	582.5	497.5	798.5	425.5	583.5	496.5	799.5	424.5	584.5	495.5	800.5	423.5	585.5	494.5	801.5	422.5	586.5	493.5	802.5	421.5	587.5	492.5	803.5	420.5	13824
13824	516.5	707.5	300.5	779.5	517.5	706.5	301.5	778.5	518.5	705.5	302.5	777.5	519.5	704.5	303.5	776.5	520.5	703.5	304.5	775.5	521.5	702.5	305.5	774.5	13824
13824	347.5	732.5	563.5	660.5	346.5	733.5	562.5	661.5	345.5	734.5	561.5	662.5	344.5	735.5	560.5	663.5	343.5	736.5	559.5	664.5	342.5	737.5	558.5	665.5	13824
13824	851.5	372.5	635.5	444.5	850.5	373.5	634.5	445.5	849.5	374.5	633.5	446.5	848.5	375.5	632.5	447.5	847.5	376.5	631.5	448.5	846.5	377.5	630.5	449.5	13824
13824	588.5	491.5	804.5	419.5	589.5	490.5	805.5	418.5	590.5	489.5	806.5	417.5	591.5	488.5	807.5	416.5	592.5	487.5	808.5	415.5	593.5	486.5	809.5	414.5	13824
13824	522.5	701.5	306.5	773.5	523.5	700.5	307.5	772.5	524.5	699.5	308.5	771.5	525.5	698.5	309.5	770.5	526.5	697.5	310.5	769.5	527.5	696.5	311.5	768.5	13824
13824	341.5	738.5	557.5	666.5	340.5	739.5	556.5	667.5	339.5	740.5	555.5	668.5	338.5	741.5	554.5	669.5	337.5	742.5	553.5	670.5	336.5	743.5	552.5	671.5	13824
13824	845.5	378.5	629.5	450.5	844.5	379.5	628.5	451.5	843.5	380.5	627.5	452.5	842.5	381.5	626.5	453.5	841.5	382.5	625.5	454.5	840.5	383.5	624.5	455.5	13824
13824	594.5	485.5	810.5	413.5	595.5	484.5	811.5	412.5	596.5	483.5	812.5	411.5	597.5	482.5	813.5	410.5	598.5	481.5	814.5	409.5	599.5	480.5	815.5	408.5	13824
13824	528.5	695.5	312.5	767.5	529.5	694.5	313.5	766.5	530.5	693.5	314.5	765.5	531.5	692.5	315.5	764.5	532.5	691.5	316.5	763.5	533.5	690.5	317.5	762.5	13824
13824	335.5	744.5	551.5	672.5	334.5	745.5	550.5	673.5	333.5	746.5	549.5	674.5	332.5	747.5	548.5	675.5	331.5	748.5	547.5	676.5	330.5	749.5	546.5	677.5	13824
13824	839.5	384.5	623.5	456.5	838.5	385.5	622.5	457.5	837.5	386.5	621.5	458.5	836.5	387.5	620.5	459.5	835.5	388.5	619.5	460.5	834.5	389.5	618.5	461.5	13824
13824	600.5	479.5	816.5	407.5	601.5	478.5	817.5	406.5	602.5	477.5	818.5	405.5	603.5	476.5	819.5	404.5	604.5	475.5	820.5	403.5	605.5	474.5	821.5	402.5	13824
13824	534.5	689.5	318.5	761.5	535.5	688.5	319.5	760.5	536.5	687.5	320.5	759.5	537.5	686.5	321.5	758.5	538.5	685.5	322.5	757.5	539.5	684.5	323.5	756.5	13824
13824	329.5	750.5	545.5	678.5	328.5	751.5	544.5	679.5	327.5	752.5	543.5	680.5	326.5	753.5	542.5	681.5	325.5	754.5	541.5	682.5	324.5	755.5	540.5	683.5	13824
13824	833.5	390.5	617.5	462.5	832.5	391.5	616.5	463.5	831.5	392.5	615.5	464.5	830.5	393.5	614.5	465.5	829.5	394.5	613.5	466.5	828.5	395.5	612.5	467.5	13824
13824	606.5	473.5	822.5	401.5	607.5	472.5	823.5	400.5	608.5	471.5	824.5	399.5	609.5	470.5	825.5	398.5	610.5	469.5	826.5	397.5	611.5	468.5	827.5	396.5	13824
	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824	13824

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 24 given in Examples 24.1 and 24.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 13824 = 24^3; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 13824 = 331776 = 576^2 = 24^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 2304; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 2304 = 9216 = 96^2.$$

The Examples 24.1 and 24.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 24, 24^2, 24^3, 24^4 \rangle$.

24.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 22 given in List (10):

$$(50, 624, 626) \Rightarrow 626^2 - 50^2 = 624^2, 626 - 50 = 24^2, \text{ Order } 24, S_{24 \times 24} := 16224, T_{576} := 624^2,$$

$$E = \{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\} \text{ or } E = \{777/2, 779/2, \dots, 1925/2, 1927/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 24 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 24.3. A *block-wise* magic square of order 24 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries

$\{101, 103, \dots, 1249, 1251\}$ is given by

																								16224
101	1189	1187	1125	163	291	103	1191	1185	1127	161	289	105	1193	1183	1129	159	287	107	1195	1181	1131	157	285	16224
1059	355	995	357	421	869	1057	353	993	359	423	871	1055	351	991	361	425	873	1053	349	989	363	427	875	16224
867	805	549	611	739	485	865	807	551	609	737	487	863	809	553	607	735	489	861	811	555	605	733	491	16224
675	547	741	803	613	677	673	545	743	801	615	679	671	543	745	799	617	681	669	541	747	797	619	683	16224
293	931	419	933	997	483	295	929	417	935	999	481	297	927	415	937	1001	479	299	925	413	939	1003	477	16224
1061	229	165	227	1123	1251	1063	231	167	225	1121	1249	1065	233	169	223	1119	1247	1067	235	171	221	1117	1245	16224
109	1197	1179	1133	155	283	111	1199	1177	1135	153	281	113	1201	1175	1137	151	279	115	1203	1173	1139	149	277	16224
1051	347	987	365	429	877	1049	345	985	367	431	879	1047	343	983	369	433	881	1045	341	981	371	435	883	16224
859	813	557	603	731	493	857	815	559	601	729	495	855	817	561	599	727	497	853	819	563	597	725	499	16224
667	539	749	795	621	685	665	537	751	793	623	687	663	535	753	791	625	689	661	533	755	789	627	691	16224
301	923	411	941	1005	475	303	921	409	943	1007	473	305	919	407	945	1009	471	307	917	405	947	1011	469	16224
1069	237	173	219	1115	1243	1071	239	175	217	1113	1241	1073	241	177	215	1111	1239	1075	243	179	213	1109	1237	16224
117	1205	1171	1141	147	275	119	1207	1169	1143	145	273	121	1209	1167	1145	143	271	123	1211	1165	1147	141	269	16224
1043	339	979	373	437	885	1041	337	977	375	439	887	1039	335	975	377	441	889	1037	333	973	379	443	891	16224
851	821	565	595	723	501	849	823	567	593	721	503	847	825	569	591	719	505	845	827	571	589	717	507	16224
659	531	757	787	629	693	657	529	759	785	631	695	655	527	761	783	633	697	653	525	763	781	635	699	16224
309	915	403	949	1013	467	311	913	401	951	1015	465	313	911	399	953	1017	463	315	909	397	955	1019	461	16224
1077	245	181	211	1107	1235	1079	247	183	209	1105	1233	1081	249	185	207	1103	1231	1083	251	187	205	1101	1229	16224
125	1213	1163	1149	139	267	127	1215	1161	1151	137	265	129	1217	1159	1153	135	263	131	1219	1157	1155	133	261	16224
1035	331	971	381	445	893	1033	329	969	383	447	895	1031	327	967	385	449	897	1029	325	965	387	451	899	16224
843	829	573	587	715	509	841	831	575	585	713	511	839	833	577	583	711	513	837	835	579	581	709	515	16224
651	523	765	779	637	701	649	521	767	777	639	703	647	519	769	775	641	705	645	517	771	773	643	707	16224
317	907	395	957	1021	459	319	905	393	959	1023	457	321	903	391	961	1025	455	323	901	389	963	1027	453	16224
1085	253	189	203	1099	1227	1087	255	191	201	1097	1225	1089	257	193	199	1095	1223	1091	259	195	197	1093	1221	16224
16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224

Example 24.4. A *block-wise* magic square of order 24 for *consecutive fraction numbers* entries $\{777/2, 779/2, \dots, 1925/2, 1927/2\}$ is given by

																								16224
388.5	932.5	931.5	900.5	419.5	483.5	389.5	933.5	930.5	901.5	418.5	482.5	390.5	934.5	929.5	902.5	417.5	481.5	391.5	935.5	928.5	903.5	416.5	480.5	16224
867.5	515.5	835.5	516.5	548.5	772.5	866.5	514.5	834.5	517.5	549.5	773.5	865.5	513.5	833.5	518.5	550.5	774.5	864.5	512.5	832.5	519.5	551.5	775.5	16224
771.5	740.5	612.5	643.5	707.5	580.5	770.5	741.5	613.5	642.5	706.5	581.5	769.5	742.5	614.5	641.5	705.5	582.5	768.5	743.5	615.5	640.5	704.5	583.5	16224
675.5	611.5	708.5	739.5	644.5	676.5	674.5	610.5	709.5	738.5	645.5	677.5	673.5	609.5	710.5	737.5	646.5	678.5	672.5	608.5	711.5	736.5	647.5	679.5	16224
484.5	803.5	547.5	804.5	836.5	579.5	485.5	802.5	546.5	805.5	837.5	578.5	486.5	801.5	545.5	806.5	838.5	577.5	487.5	800.5	544.5	807.5	839.5	576.5	16224
868.5	452.5	420.5	451.5	899.5	963.5	869.5	453.5	421.5	450.5	898.5	962.5	870.5	454.5	422.5	449.5	897.5	961.5	871.5	455.5	423.5	448.5	896.5	960.5	16224
392.5	936.5	927.5	904.5	415.5	479.5	393.5	937.5	926.5	905.5	414.5	478.5	394.5	938.5	925.5	906.5	413.5	477.5	395.5	939.5	924.5	907.5	412.5	476.5	16224
863.5	511.5	831.5	520.5	552.5	776.5	862.5	510.5	830.5	521.5	553.5	777.5	861.5	509.5	829.5	522.5	554.5	778.5	860.5	508.5	828.5	523.5	555.5	779.5	16224
767.5	744.5	616.5	639.5	703.5	584.5	766.5	745.5	617.5	638.5	702.5	585.5	765.5	746.5	618.5	637.5	701.5	586.5	764.5	747.5	619.5	636.5	700.5	587.5	16224
671.5	607.5	712.5	735.5	648.5	680.5	670.5	606.5	713.5	734.5	649.5	681.5	669.5	605.5	714.5	733.5	650.5	682.5	668.5	604.5	715.5	732.5	651.5	683.5	16224
488.5	799.5	543.5	808.5	840.5	575.5	489.5	798.5	542.5	809.5	841.5	574.5	490.5	797.5	541.5	810.5	842.5	573.5	491.5	796.5	540.5	811.5	843.5	572.5	16224
872.5	456.5	424.5	447.5	895.5	959.5	873.5	457.5	425.5	446.5	894.5	958.5	874.5	458.5	426.5	445.5	893.5	957.5	875.5	459.5	427.5	444.5	892.5	956.5	16224
396.5	940.5	923.5	908.5	411.5	475.5	397.5	941.5	922.5	909.5	410.5	474.5	398.5	942.5	921.5	910.5	409.5	473.5	399.5	943.5	920.5	911.5	408.5	472.5	16224
859.5	507.5	827.5	524.5	556.5	780.5	858.5	506.5	826.5	525.5	557.5	781.5	857.5	505.5	825.5	526.5	558.5	782.5	856.5	504.5	824.5	527.5	559.5	783.5	16224
763.5	748.5	620.5	635.5	699.5	588.5	762.5	749.5	621.5	634.5	698.5	589.5	761.5	750.5	622.5	633.5	697.5	590.5	760.5	751.5	623.5	632.5	696.5	591.5	16224
667.5	603.5	716.5	731.5	652.5	684.5	666.5	602.5	717.5	730.5	653.5	685.5	665.5	601.5	718.5	729.5	654.5	686.5	664.5	600.5	719.5	728.5	655.5	687.5	16224
492.5	795.5	539.5	812.5	844.5	571.5	493.5	794.5	538.5	813.5	845.5	570.5	494.5	793.5	537.5	814.5	846.5	569.5	495.5	792.5	536.5	815.5	847.5	568.5	16224
876.5	460.5	428.5	443.5	891.5	955.5	877.5	461.5	429.5	442.5	890.5	954.5	878.5	462.5	430.5	441.5	889.5	953.5	879.5	463.5	431.5	440.5	888.5	952.5	16224
400.5	944.5	919.5	912.5	407.5	471.5	401.5	945.5	918.5	913.5	406.5	470.5	402.5	946.5	917.5	914.5	405.5	469.5	403.5	947.5	916.5	915.5	404.5	468.5	16224
855.5	503.5	823.5	528.5	560.5	784.5	854.5	502.5	822.5	529.5	561.5	785.5	853.5	501.5	821.5	530.5	562.5	786.5	852.5	500.5	820.5	531.5	563.5	787.5	16224
759.5	752.5	624.5	631.5	695.5	592.5	758.5	753.5	625.5	630.5	694.5	593.5	757.5	754.5	626.5	629.5	693.5	594.5	756.5	755.5	627.5	628.5	692.5	595.5	16224
663.5	599.5	720.5	727.5	656.5	688.5	662.5	598.5	721.5	726.5	657.5	689.5	661.5	597.5	722.5	725.5	658.5	690.5	660.5	596.5	723.5	724.5	659.5	691.5	16224
496.5	791.5	535.5	816.5	848.5	567.5	497.5	790.5	534.5	817.5	849.5	566.5	498.5	789.5	533.5	818.5	850.5	565.5	499.5	788.5	532.5	819.5	851.5	564.5	16224
880.5	464.5	432.5	439.5	887.5	951.5	881.5	465.5	433.5	438.5	886.5	950.5	882.5	466.5	434.5	437.5	885.5	949.5	883.5	467.5	435.5	436.5	884.5	948.5	16224
16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224	16224

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 24 given in Examples 24.3 and 24.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 16224; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 16224 = 389376 = 576^2 = 624^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 4056; \quad T_3 := 6 \times 4056 = 24336 = 156^2.$$

Both the Examples 24.3 and 24.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (50,624,626)**, i.e., $50^2 + 624^2 = 626^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

24.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 22 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 24, } S_{24 \times 24} := 6936, \quad T_{576} := 166464 = 408^2, \quad E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 24 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 24.5. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 24 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$ is given by

		6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	
	217.5	432.5	1.5	504.5	218.5	431.5	2.5	503.5	219.5	430.5	3.5	502.5	220.5	429.5	4.5	501.5	221.5	428.5	5.5	500.5	222.5	427.5	6.5	499.5	6936
6936	72.5	433.5	288.5	361.5	71.5	434.5	287.5	362.5	70.5	435.5	286.5	363.5	69.5	436.5	285.5	364.5	68.5	437.5	284.5	365.5	67.5	438.5	283.5	366.5	6936
6936	576.5	73.5	360.5	145.5	575.5	74.5	359.5	146.5	574.5	75.5	358.5	147.5	573.5	76.5	357.5	148.5	572.5	77.5	356.5	149.5	571.5	78.5	355.5	150.5	6936
6936	289.5	216.5	505.5	144.5	290.5	215.5	506.5	143.5	291.5	214.5	507.5	142.5	292.5	213.5	508.5	141.5	293.5	212.5	509.5	140.5	294.5	211.5	510.5	139.5	6936
6936	223.5	426.5	7.5	498.5	224.5	425.5	8.5	497.5	225.5	424.5	9.5	496.5	226.5	423.5	10.5	495.5	227.5	422.5	11.5	494.5	228.5	421.5	12.5	493.5	6936
6936	66.5	439.5	282.5	367.5	65.5	440.5	281.5	368.5	64.5	441.5	280.5	369.5	63.5	442.5	279.5	370.5	62.5	443.5	278.5	371.5	61.5	444.5	277.5	372.5	6936
6936	570.5	79.5	354.5	151.5	569.5	80.5	353.5	152.5	568.5	81.5	352.5	153.5	567.5	82.5	351.5	154.5	566.5	83.5	350.5	155.5	565.5	84.5	349.5	156.5	6936
6936	295.5	210.5	511.5	138.5	296.5	209.5	512.5	137.5	297.5	208.5	513.5	136.5	298.5	207.5	514.5	135.5	299.5	206.5	515.5	134.5	300.5	205.5	516.5	133.5	6936
6936	229.5	420.5	13.5	492.5	230.5	419.5	14.5	491.5	231.5	418.5	15.5	490.5	232.5	417.5	16.5	489.5	233.5	416.5	17.5	488.5	234.5	415.5	18.5	487.5	6936
6936	60.5	445.5	276.5	373.5	59.5	446.5	275.5	374.5	58.5	447.5	274.5	375.5	57.5	448.5	273.5	376.5	56.5	449.5	272.5	377.5	55.5	450.5	271.5	378.5	6936
6936	564.5	85.5	348.5	157.5	563.5	86.5	347.5	158.5	562.5	87.5	346.5	159.5	561.5	88.5	345.5	160.5	560.5	89.5	344.5	161.5	559.5	90.5	343.5	162.5	6936
6936	301.5	204.5	517.5	132.5	302.5	203.5	518.5	131.5	303.5	202.5	519.5	130.5	304.5	201.5	520.5	129.5	305.5	200.5	521.5	128.5	306.5	199.5	522.5	127.5	6936
6936	235.5	414.5	19.5	486.5	236.5	413.5	20.5	485.5	237.5	412.5	21.5	484.5	238.5	411.5	22.5	483.5	239.5	410.5	23.5	482.5	240.5	409.5	24.5	481.5	6936
6936	54.5	451.5	270.5	379.5	53.5	452.5	269.5	380.5	52.5	453.5	268.5	381.5	51.5	454.5	267.5	382.5	50.5	455.5	266.5	383.5	49.5	456.5	265.5	384.5	6936
6936	558.5	91.5	342.5	163.5	557.5	92.5	341.5	164.5	556.5	93.5	340.5	165.5	555.5	94.5	339.5	166.5	554.5	95.5	338.5	167.5	553.5	96.5	337.5	168.5	6936
6936	307.5	198.5	523.5	126.5	308.5	197.5	524.5	125.5	309.5	196.5	525.5	124.5	310.5	195.5	526.5	123.5	311.5	194.5	527.5	122.5	312.5	193.5	528.5	121.5	6936
6936	241.5	408.5	25.5	480.5	242.5	407.5	26.5	479.5	243.5	406.5	27.5	478.5	244.5	405.5	28.5	477.5	245.5	404.5	29.5	476.5	246.5	403.5	30.5	475.5	6936
6936	48.5	457.5	264.5	385.5	47.5	458.5	263.5	386.5	46.5	459.5	262.5	387.5	45.5	460.5	261.5	388.5	44.5	461.5	260.5	389.5	43.5	462.5	259.5	390.5	6936
6936	552.5	97.5	336.5	169.5	551.5	98.5	335.5	170.5	550.5	99.5	334.5	171.5	549.5	100.5	333.5	172.5	548.5	101.5	332.5	173.5	547.5	102.5	331.5	174.5	6936
6936	313.5	192.5	529.5	120.5	314.5	191.5	530.5	119.5	315.5	190.5	531.5	118.5	316.5	189.5	532.5	117.5	317.5	188.5	533.5	116.5	318.5	187.5	534.5	115.5	6936
6936	247.5	402.5	31.5	474.5	248.5	401.5	32.5	473.5	249.5	400.5	33.5	472.5	250.5	399.5	34.5	471.5	251.5	398.5	35.5	470.5	252.5	397.5	36.5	469.5	6936
6936	42.5	463.5	258.5	391.5	41.5	464.5	257.5	392.5	40.5	465.5	256.5	393.5	39.5	466.5	255.5	394.5	38.5	467.5	254.5	395.5	37.5	468.5	253.5	396.5	6936
6936	546.5	103.5	330.5	175.5	545.5	104.5	329.5	176.5	544.5	105.5	328.5	177.5	543.5	106.5	327.5	178.5	542.5	107.5	326.5	179.5	541.5	108.5	325.5	180.5	6936
6936	319.5	186.5	535.5	114.5	320.5	185.5	536.5	113.5	321.5	184.5	537.5	112.5	322.5	183.5	538.5	111.5	323.5	182.5	539.5	110.5	324.5	181.5	540.5	109.5	6936
	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936	6936

The magic square of order 24 given in Example 24.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 6936; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 6936 = 166464 = 408^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 1156; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1156 = 4624 = 68^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

25 Magic Squares of Order 25

This section brings magic squares of order 25 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

25.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 23 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 25, \quad \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 15625, \quad \mathbf{T}_{625} := 390625 = 625^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1247, 1249\} \text{ or } E := \{313, 314, \dots, 935, 937\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 25 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 25.2. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{313, 314, 315, \dots, 936, 937\}$ a **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 25 is given by

		15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	
	313	481	619	787	925	755	893	436	449	592	547	585	723	866	404	859	377	515	678	696	651	789	832	345	508	15625
15625	769	937	325	463	631	461	599	742	905	418	873	391	554	572	735	665	703	846	384	527	357	495	658	801	814	15625
15625	475	613	781	919	337	892	430	443	611	749	579	722	885	398	541	371	534	677	690	853	808	826	339	507	645	15625
15625	931	319	487	625	763	593	761	899	417	455	410	548	566	729	872	702	840	378	521	684	489	657	795	833	351	15625
15625	637	775	913	331	469	424	442	605	743	911	716	879	397	560	573	528	671	709	852	365	820	358	501	639	807	15625
15625	847	385	523	666	704	659	802	815	353	496	326	464	632	770	933	738	906	419	462	600	555	568	736	874	392	15625
15625	673	691	854	372	535	340	503	646	809	827	782	920	333	476	614	444	612	750	888	431	886	399	542	580	718	15625
15625	379	522	685	698	841	796	834	352	490	653	483	626	764	932	320	900	413	456	594	762	567	730	868	411	549	15625
15625	710	848	366	529	672	502	640	803	821	359	914	332	470	633	776	606	744	912	425	438	393	561	574	717	880	15625
15625	516	679	697	860	373	828	346	509	652	790	620	783	926	314	482	437	450	588	756	894	724	867	405	543	586	15625
15625	751	889	432	445	608	538	581	719	887	400	855	368	536	674	692	647	810	823	341	504	334	477	615	778	921	15625
15625	457	595	758	901	414	869	412	550	563	731	686	699	842	380	518	348	491	654	797	835	765	928	321	484	627	15625
15625	908	426	439	607	745	575	713	881	394	562	367	530	668	711	849	804	822	360	498	641	471	634	777	915	328	15625
15625	589	757	895	433	451	406	544	587	725	863	693	861	374	517	680	510	648	791	829	347	927	315	478	621	784	15625
15625	420	458	601	739	907	737	875	388	556	569	524	667	705	843	386	816	354	497	660	798	628	771	934	327	465	15625
15625	655	793	836	349	492	322	485	623	766	929	759	902	415	453	596	551	564	732	870	408	838	381	519	687	700	15625
15625	361	499	642	805	818	773	916	329	472	635	440	603	746	909	427	882	395	558	576	714	669	712	850	363	531	15625
15625	792	830	343	511	649	479	622	785	923	316	896	434	452	590	753	583	726	864	407	545	375	513	681	694	862	15625
15625	493	661	799	817	355	935	323	466	629	772	602	740	903	421	459	389	557	570	733	876	706	844	387	525	663	15625
15625	824	342	505	643	811	616	779	922	335	473	428	446	609	752	890	720	883	401	539	582	537	675	688	856	369	15625
15625	559	577	715	878	396	851	364	532	670	708	638	806	819	362	500	330	468	636	774	917	747	910	423	441	604	15625
15625	865	403	546	584	727	682	695	858	376	514	344	512	650	788	831	786	924	317	480	618	448	591	754	897	435	15625
15625	571	734	877	390	553	383	526	664	707	845	800	813	356	494	662	467	630	768	936	324	904	422	460	598	741	15625
15625	402	540	578	721	884	689	857	370	533	676	506	644	812	825	338	918	336	474	617	780	610	748	891	429	447	15625
15625	728	871	409	552	565	520	683	701	839	382	837	350	488	656	794	624	767	930	318	486	416	454	597	760	898	15625
	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625	15625

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 25 given in Examples 25.1 and 25.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 5 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 15625; \quad T_{625} := 15625 \times 25 = 390625 = 625^2 = 25^4;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 3125; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 3125 = 15625 = 125^2.$$

Both the Examples 25.1 and 25.2 satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 25, 25^2, 25^3, 25^4 \rangle$. It is also **bimagic** square with **bimagic** sums, $Sb_{25 \times 25} = 13020825$ and $Sb_{25 \times 25} = 10563175$ respectively.

Remark 25.1. We observe from the Examples 25.1 and 25.2 are both **bimagic** squares with same magic sums, and different **bimagic sums**.

25.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 23 given in List (10):

$$(52, 675, 677) \Rightarrow 677^2 - 52^2 = 675^2, \quad 677 - 52 = 25^2, \quad \text{Order 25}, \quad S_{25 \times 25} := 18225, \quad T_{625} := 675^2,$$

$$E = \{105, 107, \dots, 1351, 1353\} \text{ or } E = \{417, 418, \dots, 1040, 1041\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 25 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 25 given in Examples 25.3 and 25.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 5 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal sums. See below the details:

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 18225; \quad T_{625} := 18225 \times 25 = 455625 = 675^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 3645; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 3645 = 18225 = 135^2.$$

Both the Examples 25.3 and 25.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (52,675,677)**, i.e., $52^2 + 675^2 = 677^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**. Both the Examples 25.3 and 25.4 are **bimagic** squares with **bimagic** sums $Sb_{25 \times 25} = 16541225$ and $Sb_{25 \times 25} = 14099825$ respectively.

Remark 25.2. *We observe from the Examples 25.2 and 25.5 are with same magic sums and different **bimagic sums**.*

25.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 23 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 25, } S_{25 \times 25} := 8100, \quad T_{625} := 202500 = 450^2, \quad E := \{12, 13, \dots, 635, 636\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 25 with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

26 Magic Squares of Order 26

This section brings magic squares of order 26 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

26.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 24 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 26, \quad S_{26 \times 26} := 17576, \quad T_{676} := 456976 = 676^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1349, 1351\} \text{ or } E := \{677/2, 679/2, \dots, 2023/2, 2027/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 26 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 26.1. For the **consecutive odd numbers entries** $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1349, 1351\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 is given by

49	1325	29	1321	33	1317	37	1313	41	1309	45	1305	1	1327	53	1297	57	1293	61	1289	65	1285	69	1281	73	1301
77	533	963	101	1107	535	961	103	1105	537	959	105	1103	539	957	107	1101	541	955	109	1099	543	953	111	1097	1275
1273	243	965	675	821	241	967	673	823	239	969	671	825	237	971	669	827	235	973	667	829	233	975	665	831	79
81	1251	245	819	389	1249	247	817	391	1247	249	815	393	1245	251	813	395	1243	253	811	397	1241	255	809	399	1271
1269	677	531	1109	387	679	529	1111	385	681	527	1113	383	683	525	1115	381	685	523	1117	379	687	521	1119	377	83
85	545	951	113	1095	547	949	115	1093	549	947	117	1091	551	945	119	1089	553	943	121	1087	555	941	123	1085	1267
1265	231	977	663	833	229	979	661	835	227	981	659	837	225	983	657	839	223	985	655	841	221	987	653	843	87
89	1239	257	807	401	1237	259	805	403	1235	261	803	405	1233	263	801	407	1231	265	799	409	1229	267	797	411	1263
1261	689	519	1121	375	691	517	1123	373	693	515	1125	371	695	513	1127	369	697	511	1129	367	699	509	1131	365	91
93	557	939	125	1083	559	937	127	1081	561	935	129	1079	563	933	131	1077	565	931	133	1075	567	929	135	1073	1259
1257	219	989	651	845	217	991	649	847	215	993	647	849	213	995	645	851	211	997	643	853	209	999	641	855	95
97	1227	269	795	413	1225	271	793	415	1223	273	791	417	1221	275	789	419	1219	277	787	421	1217	279	785	423	1255
1253	701	507	1133	363	703	505	1135	361	705	503	1137	359	707	501	1139	357	709	499	1141	355	711	497	1143	353	99
1277	569	927	137	1071	571	925	139	1069	573	923	141	1067	575	921	143	1065	577	919	145	1063	579	917	147	1061	75
1329	207	1001	639	857	205	1003	637	859	203	1005	635	861	201	1007	633	863	199	1009	631	865	197	1011	629	867	23
21	1215	281	783	425	1213	283	781	427	1211	285	779	429	1209	287	777	431	1207	289	775	433	1205	291	773	435	1331
1333	713	495	1145	351	715	493	1147	349	717	491	1149	347	719	489	1151	345	721	487	1153	343	723	485	1155	341	19
17	581	915	149	1059	583	913	151	1057	585	911	153	1055	587	909	155	1053	589	907	157	1051	591	905	159	1049	1335
1337	195	1013	627	869	193	1015	625	871	191	1017	623	873	189	1019	621	875	187	1021	619	877	185	1023	617	879	15
13	1203	293	771	437	1201	295	769	439	1199	297	767	441	1197	299	765	443	1195	301	763	445	1193	303	761	447	1339
1341	725	483	1157	339	727	481	1159	337	729	479	1161	335	731	477	1163	333	733	475	1165	331	735	473	1167	329	11
9	593	903	161	1047	595	901	163	1045	597	899	165	1043	599	897	167	1041	601	895	169	1039	603	893	171	1037	1343
1345	183	1025	615	881	181	1027	613	883	179	1029	611	885	177	1031	609	887	175	1033	607	889	173	1035	605	891	7
5	1191	305	759	449	1189	307	757	451	1187	309	755	453	1185	311	753	455	1183	313	751	457	1181	315	749	459	1347
1349	737	471	1169	327	739	469	1171	325	741	467	1173	323	743	465	1175	321	745	463	1177	319	747	461	1179	317	3
51	27	1323	31	1319	35	1315	39	1311	43	1307	47	1351	25	1299	55	1295	59	1291	63	1287	67	1283	71	1279	1303

Example 26.2. For the consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{677/2, 679/2, \dots, 2023/2, 2027/2\}$, a block-bordered magic square of order 26 is given by

362.5	1000.5	352.5	998.5	354.5	996.5	356.5	994.5	358.5	992.5	360.5	990.5	338.5	1001.5	364.5	986.5	366.5	984.5	368.5	982.5	370.5	980.5	372.5	978.5	374.5	988.5
376.5	604.5	819.5	388.5	891.5	605.5	818.5	389.5	890.5	606.5	817.5	390.5	889.5	607.5	816.5	391.5	888.5	608.5	815.5	392.5	887.5	609.5	814.5	393.5	886.5	975.5
974.5	459.5	820.5	675.5	748.5	458.5	821.5	674.5	749.5	457.5	822.5	673.5	750.5	456.5	823.5	672.5	751.5	455.5	824.5	671.5	752.5	454.5	825.5	670.5	753.5	377.5
378.5	963.5	460.5	747.5	532.5	962.5	461.5	746.5	533.5	961.5	462.5	745.5	534.5	960.5	463.5	744.5	535.5	959.5	464.5	743.5	536.5	958.5	465.5	742.5	537.5	973.5
972.5	676.5	603.5	892.5	531.5	677.5	602.5	893.5	530.5	678.5	601.5	894.5	529.5	679.5	600.5	895.5	528.5	680.5	599.5	896.5	527.5	681.5	598.5	897.5	526.5	379.5
380.5	610.5	813.5	394.5	885.5	611.5	812.5	395.5	884.5	612.5	811.5	396.5	883.5	613.5	810.5	397.5	882.5	614.5	809.5	398.5	881.5	615.5	808.5	399.5	880.5	971.5
970.5	453.5	826.5	669.5	754.5	452.5	827.5	668.5	755.5	451.5	828.5	667.5	756.5	450.5	829.5	666.5	757.5	449.5	830.5	665.5	758.5	448.5	831.5	664.5	759.5	381.5
382.5	957.5	466.5	741.5	538.5	956.5	467.5	740.5	539.5	955.5	468.5	739.5	540.5	954.5	469.5	738.5	541.5	953.5	470.5	737.5	542.5	952.5	471.5	736.5	543.5	969.5
968.5	682.5	597.5	898.5	525.5	683.5	596.5	899.5	524.5	684.5	595.5	900.5	523.5	685.5	594.5	901.5	522.5	686.5	593.5	902.5	521.5	687.5	592.5	903.5	520.5	383.5
384.5	616.5	807.5	400.5	879.5	617.5	806.5	401.5	878.5	618.5	805.5	402.5	877.5	619.5	804.5	403.5	876.5	620.5	803.5	404.5	875.5	621.5	802.5	405.5	874.5	967.5
966.5	447.5	832.5	663.5	760.5	446.5	833.5	662.5	761.5	445.5	834.5	661.5	762.5	444.5	835.5	660.5	763.5	443.5	836.5	659.5	764.5	442.5	837.5	658.5	765.5	385.5
386.5	951.5	472.5	735.5	544.5	950.5	473.5	734.5	545.5	949.5	474.5	733.5	546.5	948.5	475.5	732.5	547.5	947.5	476.5	731.5	548.5	946.5	477.5	730.5	549.5	965.5
964.5	688.5	591.5	904.5	519.5	689.5	590.5	905.5	518.5	690.5	589.5	906.5	517.5	691.5	588.5	907.5	516.5	692.5	587.5	908.5	515.5	693.5	586.5	909.5	514.5	387.5
376.5	622.5	801.5	406.5	873.5	623.5	800.5	407.5	872.5	624.5	799.5	408.5	871.5	625.5	798.5	409.5	870.5	626.5	797.5	410.5	869.5	627.5	796.5	411.5	868.5	375.5
1002.5	441.5	838.5	657.5	766.5	440.5	839.5	656.5	767.5	439.5	840.5	655.5	768.5	438.5	841.5	654.5	769.5	437.5	842.5	653.5	770.5	436.5	843.5	652.5	771.5	349.5
348.5	945.5	478.5	729.5	550.5	944.5	479.5	728.5	551.5	943.5	480.5	727.5	552.5	942.5	481.5	726.5	553.5	941.5	482.5	725.5	554.5	940.5	483.5	724.5	555.5	1003.5
1004.5	694.5	585.5	910.5	513.5	695.5	584.5	911.5	512.5	696.5	583.5	912.5	511.5	697.5	582.5	913.5	510.5	698.5	581.5	914.5	509.5	699.5	580.5	915.5	508.5	347.5
346.5	628.5	795.5	412.5	867.5	629.5	794.5	413.5	866.5	630.5	793.5	414.5	865.5	631.5	792.5	415.5	864.5	632.5	791.5	416.5	863.5	633.5	790.5	417.5	862.5	1005.5
1006.5	435.5	844.5	651.5	772.5	434.5	845.5	650.5	773.5	433.5	846.5	649.5	774.5	432.5	847.5	648.5	775.5	431.5	848.5	647.5	776.5	430.5	849.5	646.5	777.5	345.5
344.5	939.5	484.5	723.5	556.5	938.5	485.5	722.5	557.5	937.5	486.5	721.5	558.5	936.5	487.5	720.5	559.5	935.5	488.5	719.5	560.5	934.5	489.5	718.5	561.5	1007.5
1008.5	700.5	579.5	916.5	507.5	701.5	578.5	917.5	506.5	702.5	577.5	918.5	505.5	703.5	576.5	919.5	504.5	704.5	575.5	920.5	503.5	705.5	574.5	921.5	502.5	343.5
342.5	634.5	789.5	418.5	861.5	635.5	788.5	419.5	860.5	636.5	787.5	420.5	859.5	637.5	786.5	421.5	858.5	638.5	785.5	422.5	857.5	639.5	784.5	423.5	856.5	1009.5
1010.5	429.5	850.5	645.5	778.5	428.5	851.5	644.5	779.5	427.5	852.5	643.5	780.5	426.5	853.5	642.5	781.5	425.5	854.5	641.5	782.5	424.5	855.5	640.5	783.5	341.5
340.5	933.5	490.5	717.5	562.5	932.5	491.5	716.5	563.5	931.5	492.5	715.5	564.5	930.5	493.5	714.5	565.5	929.5	494.5	713.5	566.5	928.5	495.5	712.5	567.5	1011.5
1012.5	706.5	573.5	922.5	501.5	707.5	572.5	923.5	500.5	708.5	571.5	924.5	499.5	709.5	570.5	925.5	498.5	710.5	569.5	926.5	497.5	711.5	568.5	927.5	496.5	339.5
363.5	351.5	999.5	353.5	997.5	355.5	995.5	357.5	993.5	359.5	991.5	361.5	1013.5	350.5	987.5	365.5	985.5	367.5	983.5	369.5	981.5	371.5	979.5	373.5	977.5	989.5

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 26 given in Examples 26.1 and 26.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic squares of order 24 is **block-wise pandiagonal**. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{26 \times 26} &= 17576; & T_{676} &:= 26 \times 17576 = 456976 = 676^2 = 26^4; \\ S_{24 \times 24} &= 16224; & T_{576} &:= 24 \times 17576 = 389376 = 624^2; \\ S_{4 \times 4} &= 2704; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 2704 = 10816 = 104^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 26.1 and 26.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 26, 26^2, 26^3, 26^4 \rangle$.

26.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 24 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (54, 728, 730) &\Rightarrow 730^2 - 54^2 = 728^2, \quad 730 - 54 = 26^2, \quad \text{Order } 26, \quad S_{26 \times 26} := 20384, \quad T_{676} := 728^2, \\ E &= \{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\} \text{ or } E = \{893/2, 895/2, \dots, 2241/2, 2243/2\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 24 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 26.3. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{109, 111, \dots, 1457, 1459\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 is given by

157	1433	137	1429	141	1425	145	1421	149	1417	153	1413	109	1435	161	1405	165	1401	169	1397	173	1393	177	1389	181	1409
185	209	1297	1295	1233	271	399	211	1299	1293	1235	269	397	213	1301	1291	1237	267	395	215	1303	1289	1239	265	393	1383
1381	1167	463	1103	465	529	977	1165	461	1101	467	531	979	1163	459	1099	469	533	981	1161	457	1097	471	535	983	187
189	975	913	657	719	847	593	973	915	659	717	845	595	971	917	661	715	843	597	969	919	663	713	841	599	1379
1377	783	655	849	911	721	785	781	653	851	909	723	787	779	651	853	907	725	789	777	649	855	905	727	791	191
193	401	1039	527	1041	1105	591	403	1037	525	1043	1107	589	405	1035	523	1045	1109	587	407	1033	521	1047	1111	585	1375
1373	1169	337	273	335	1231	1359	1171	339	275	333	1229	1357	1173	341	277	331	1227	1355	1175	343	279	329	1225	1353	195
197	217	1305	1287	1241	263	391	219	1307	1285	1243	261	389	221	1309	1283	1245	259	387	223	1311	1281	1247	257	385	1371
1369	1159	455	1095	473	537	985	1157	453	1093	475	539	987	1155	451	1091	477	541	989	1153	449	1089	479	543	991	199
201	967	921	665	711	839	601	965	923	667	709	837	603	963	925	669	707	835	605	961	927	671	705	833	607	1367
1365	775	647	857	903	729	793	773	645	859	901	731	795	771	643	861	899	733	797	769	641	863	897	735	799	203
205	409	1031	519	1049	1113	583	411	1029	517	1051	1115	581	413	1027	515	1053	1117	579	415	1025	513	1055	1119	577	1363
1361	1177	345	281	327	1223	1351	1179	347	283	325	1221	1349	1181	349	285	323	1219	1347	1183	351	287	321	1217	1345	207
1385	225	1313	1279	1249	255	383	227	1315	1277	1251	253	381	229	1317	1275	1253	251	379	231	1319	1273	1255	249	377	183
1437	1151	447	1087	481	545	993	1149	445	1085	483	547	995	1147	443	1083	485	549	997	1145	441	1081	487	551	999	131
129	959	929	673	703	831	609	957	931	675	701	829	611	955	933	677	699	827	613	953	935	679	697	825	615	1439
1441	767	639	865	895	737	801	765	637	867	893	739	803	763	635	869	891	741	805	761	633	871	889	743	807	127
125	417	1023	511	1057	1121	575	419	1021	509	1059	1123	573	421	1019	507	1061	1125	571	423	1017	505	1063	1127	569	1443
1445	1185	353	289	319	1215	1343	1187	355	291	317	1213	1341	1189	357	293	315	1211	1339	1191	359	295	313	1209	1337	123
121	233	1321	1271	1257	247	375	235	1323	1269	1259	245	373	237	1325	1267	1261	243	371	239	1327	1265	1263	241	369	1447
1449	1143	439	1079	489	553	1001	1141	437	1077	491	555	1003	1139	435	1075	493	557	1005	1137	433	1073	495	559	1007	119
117	951	937	681	695	823	617	949	939	683	693	821	619	947	941	685	691	819	621	945	943	687	689	817	623	1451
1453	759	631	873	887	745	809	757	629	875	885	747	811	755	627	877	883	749	813	753	625	879	881	751	815	115
113	425	1015	503	1065	1129	567	427	1013	501	1067	1131	565	429	1011	499	1069	1133	563	431	1009	497	1071	1135	561	1455
1457	1193	361	297	311	1207	1335	1195	363	299	309	1205	1333	1197	365	301	307	1203	1331	1199	367	303	305	1201	1329	111
159	135	1431	139	1427	143	1423	147	1419	151	1415	155	1459	133	1407	163	1403	167	1399	171	1395	175	1391	179	1387	1411

Example 26.4. For the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{893/2, 895/2, \dots, 2241/2, 2243/2\}$, a **block-bordered magic square of order 26** is given by

470.5	1108.5	460.5	1106.5	462.5	1104.5	464.5	1102.5	466.5	1100.5	468.5	1098.5	446.5	1109.5	472.5	1094.5	474.5	1092.5	476.5	1090.5	478.5	1088.5	480.5	1086.5	482.5	1096.5
484.5	496.5	1040.5	1039.5	1008.5	527.5	591.5	497.5	1041.5	1038.5	1009.5	526.5	590.5	498.5	1042.5	1037.5	1010.5	525.5	589.5	499.5	1043.5	1036.5	1011.5	524.5	588.5	1083.5
1082.5	975.5	623.5	943.5	624.5	656.5	880.5	974.5	622.5	942.5	625.5	657.5	881.5	973.5	621.5	941.5	626.5	658.5	882.5	972.5	620.5	940.5	627.5	659.5	883.5	485.5
486.5	879.5	848.5	720.5	751.5	815.5	688.5	878.5	849.5	721.5	750.5	814.5	689.5	877.5	850.5	722.5	749.5	813.5	690.5	876.5	851.5	723.5	748.5	812.5	691.5	1081.5
1080.5	783.5	719.5	816.5	847.5	752.5	784.5	782.5	718.5	817.5	846.5	753.5	785.5	781.5	717.5	818.5	845.5	754.5	786.5	780.5	716.5	819.5	844.5	755.5	787.5	487.5
488.5	592.5	911.5	655.5	912.5	944.5	687.5	593.5	910.5	654.5	913.5	945.5	686.5	594.5	909.5	653.5	914.5	946.5	685.5	595.5	908.5	652.5	915.5	947.5	684.5	1079.5
1078.5	976.5	560.5	528.5	559.5	1007.5	1071.5	977.5	561.5	529.5	558.5	1006.5	1070.5	978.5	562.5	530.5	557.5	1005.5	1069.5	979.5	563.5	531.5	556.5	1004.5	1068.5	489.5
490.5	500.5	1044.5	1035.5	1012.5	523.5	587.5	501.5	1045.5	1034.5	1013.5	522.5	586.5	502.5	1046.5	1033.5	1014.5	521.5	585.5	503.5	1047.5	1032.5	1015.5	520.5	584.5	1077.5
1076.5	971.5	619.5	939.5	628.5	660.5	884.5	970.5	618.5	938.5	629.5	661.5	885.5	969.5	617.5	937.5	630.5	662.5	886.5	968.5	616.5	936.5	631.5	663.5	887.5	491.5
492.5	875.5	852.5	724.5	747.5	811.5	692.5	874.5	853.5	725.5	746.5	810.5	693.5	873.5	854.5	726.5	745.5	809.5	694.5	872.5	855.5	727.5	744.5	808.5	695.5	1075.5
1074.5	779.5	715.5	820.5	843.5	756.5	788.5	778.5	714.5	821.5	842.5	757.5	789.5	777.5	713.5	822.5	841.5	758.5	790.5	776.5	712.5	823.5	840.5	759.5	791.5	493.5
494.5	596.5	907.5	651.5	916.5	948.5	683.5	597.5	906.5	650.5	917.5	949.5	682.5	598.5	905.5	649.5	918.5	950.5	681.5	599.5	904.5	648.5	919.5	951.5	680.5	1073.5
1072.5	980.5	564.5	532.5	555.5	1003.5	1067.5	981.5	565.5	533.5	554.5	1002.5	1066.5	982.5	566.5	534.5	553.5	1001.5	1065.5	983.5	567.5	535.5	552.5	1000.5	1064.5	495.5
1084.5	504.5	1048.5	1031.5	1016.5	519.5	583.5	505.5	1049.5	1030.5	1017.5	518.5	582.5	506.5	1050.5	1029.5	1018.5	517.5	581.5	507.5	1051.5	1028.5	1019.5	516.5	580.5	483.5
1110.5	967.5	615.5	935.5	632.5	664.5	888.5	966.5	614.5	934.5	633.5	665.5	889.5	965.5	613.5	933.5	634.5	666.5	890.5	964.5	612.5	932.5	635.5	667.5	891.5	457.5
456.5	871.5	856.5	728.5	743.5	807.5	696.5	870.5	857.5	729.5	742.5	806.5	697.5	869.5	858.5	730.5	741.5	805.5	698.5	868.5	859.5	731.5	740.5	804.5	699.5	1111.5
1112.5	775.5	711.5	824.5	839.5	760.5	792.5	774.5	710.5	825.5	838.5	761.5	793.5	773.5	709.5	826.5	837.5	762.5	794.5	772.5	708.5	827.5	836.5	763.5	795.5	455.5
454.5	600.5	903.5	647.5	920.5	952.5	679.5	601.5	902.5	646.5	921.5	953.5	678.5	602.5	901.5	645.5	922.5	954.5	677.5	603.5	900.5	644.5	923.5	955.5	676.5	1113.5
1114.5	984.5	568.5	536.5	551.5	999.5	1063.5	985.5	569.5	537.5	550.5	998.5	1062.5	986.5	570.5	538.5	549.5	997.5	1061.5	987.5	571.5	539.5	548.5	996.5	1060.5	453.5
452.5	508.5	1052.5	1027.5	1020.5	515.5	579.5	509.5	1053.5	1026.5	1021.5	514.5	578.5	510.5	1054.5	1025.5	1022.5	513.5	577.5	511.5	1055.5	1024.5	1023.5	512.5	576.5	1115.5
1116.5	963.5	611.5	931.5	636.5	668.5	892.5	962.5	610.5	930.5	637.5	669.5	893.5	961.5	609.5	929.5	638.5	670.5	894.5	960.5	608.5	928.5	639.5	671.5	895.5	451.5
450.5	867.5	860.5	732.5	739.5	803.5	700.5	866.5	861.5	733.5	738.5	802.5	701.5	865.5	862.5	734.5	737.5	801.5	702.5	864.5	863.5	735.5	736.5	800.5	703.5	1117.5
1118.5	771.5	707.5	828.5	835.5	764.5	796.5	770.5	706.5	829.5	834.5	765.5	797.5	769.5	705.5	830.5	833.5	766.5	798.5	768.5	704.5	831.5	832.5	767.5	799.5	449.5
448.5	604.5	899.5	643.5	924.5	956.5	675.5	605.5	898.5	642.5	925.5	957.5	674.5	606.5	897.5	641.5	926.5	958.5	673.5	607.5	896.5	640.5	927.5	959.5	672.5	1119.5
1120.5	988.5	572.5	540.5	547.5	995.5	1059.5	989.5	573.5	541.5	546.5	994.5	1058.5	990.5	574.5	542.5	545.5	993.5	1057.5	991.5	575.5	543.5	544.5	992.5	1056.5	447.5
471.5	459.5	1107.5	461.5	1105.5	463.5	1103.5	465.5	1101.5	467.5	1099.5	469.5	1121.5	458.5	1095.5	473.5	1093.5	475.5	1091.5	477.5	1089.5	479.5	1087.5	481.5	1085.5	1097.5

It is **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 given in Examples 26.3 and 26.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The inner magic square of order 24 is with blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{26 \times 26} = 20384; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 20384 = 529984 = 728^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} = 18816; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 18816 = 451584 = 672^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 4704; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 4704 = 28224 = 168^2.$$

Both the Examples 26.3 and 26.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (54, 728, 730)**, i.e., $54^2 + 728^2 = 730^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

26.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 24 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 26, } S_{26 \times 26} := 9386, T_{676} := 244036 = 494^2, E := \{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 26 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 26.5. For the consecutive fraction numbers entries $:= \{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 is given by

47.5	685.5	37.5	683.5	39.5	681.5	41.5	679.5	43.5	677.5	45.5	675.5	23.5	686.5	49.5	671.5	51.5	669.5	53.5	667.5	55.5	665.5	57.5	663.5	59.5	673.5
61.5	289.5	504.5	73.5	576.5	290.5	503.5	74.5	575.5	291.5	502.5	75.5	574.5	292.5	501.5	76.5	573.5	293.5	500.5	77.5	572.5	294.5	499.5	78.5	571.5	660.5
659.5	144.5	505.5	360.5	433.5	143.5	506.5	359.5	434.5	142.5	507.5	358.5	435.5	141.5	508.5	357.5	436.5	140.5	509.5	356.5	437.5	139.5	510.5	355.5	438.5	62.5
63.5	648.5	145.5	432.5	217.5	647.5	146.5	431.5	218.5	646.5	147.5	430.5	219.5	645.5	148.5	429.5	220.5	644.5	149.5	428.5	221.5	643.5	150.5	427.5	222.5	658.5
657.5	361.5	288.5	577.5	216.5	362.5	287.5	578.5	215.5	363.5	286.5	579.5	214.5	364.5	285.5	580.5	213.5	365.5	284.5	581.5	212.5	366.5	283.5	582.5	211.5	64.5
65.5	295.5	498.5	79.5	570.5	296.5	497.5	80.5	569.5	297.5	496.5	81.5	568.5	298.5	495.5	82.5	567.5	299.5	494.5	83.5	566.5	300.5	493.5	84.5	565.5	656.5
655.5	138.5	511.5	354.5	439.5	137.5	512.5	353.5	440.5	136.5	513.5	352.5	441.5	135.5	514.5	351.5	442.5	134.5	515.5	350.5	443.5	133.5	516.5	349.5	444.5	66.5
67.5	642.5	151.5	426.5	223.5	641.5	152.5	425.5	224.5	640.5	153.5	424.5	225.5	639.5	154.5	423.5	226.5	638.5	155.5	422.5	227.5	637.5	156.5	421.5	228.5	654.5
653.5	367.5	282.5	583.5	210.5	368.5	281.5	584.5	209.5	369.5	280.5	585.5	208.5	370.5	279.5	586.5	207.5	371.5	278.5	587.5	206.5	372.5	277.5	588.5	205.5	68.5
69.5	301.5	492.5	85.5	564.5	302.5	491.5	86.5	563.5	303.5	490.5	87.5	562.5	304.5	489.5	88.5	561.5	305.5	488.5	89.5	560.5	306.5	487.5	90.5	559.5	652.5
651.5	132.5	517.5	348.5	445.5	131.5	518.5	347.5	446.5	130.5	519.5	346.5	447.5	129.5	520.5	345.5	448.5	128.5	521.5	344.5	449.5	127.5	522.5	343.5	450.5	70.5
71.5	636.5	157.5	420.5	229.5	635.5	158.5	419.5	230.5	634.5	159.5	418.5	231.5	633.5	160.5	417.5	232.5	632.5	161.5	416.5	233.5	631.5	162.5	415.5	234.5	650.5
649.5	373.5	276.5	589.5	204.5	374.5	275.5	590.5	203.5	375.5	274.5	591.5	202.5	376.5	273.5	592.5	201.5	377.5	272.5	593.5	200.5	378.5	271.5	594.5	199.5	72.5
661.5	307.5	486.5	91.5	558.5	308.5	485.5	92.5	557.5	309.5	484.5	93.5	556.5	310.5	483.5	94.5	555.5	311.5	482.5	95.5	554.5	312.5	481.5	96.5	553.5	60.5
687.5	126.5	523.5	342.5	451.5	125.5	524.5	341.5	452.5	124.5	525.5	340.5	453.5	123.5	526.5	339.5	454.5	122.5	527.5	338.5	455.5	121.5	528.5	337.5	456.5	34.5
33.5	630.5	163.5	414.5	235.5	629.5	164.5	413.5	236.5	628.5	165.5	412.5	237.5	627.5	166.5	411.5	238.5	626.5	167.5	410.5	239.5	625.5	168.5	409.5	240.5	688.5
689.5	379.5	270.5	595.5	198.5	380.5	269.5	596.5	197.5	381.5	268.5	597.5	196.5	382.5	267.5	598.5	195.5	383.5	266.5	599.5	194.5	384.5	265.5	600.5	193.5	32.5
31.5	313.5	480.5	97.5	552.5	314.5	479.5	98.5	551.5	315.5	478.5	99.5	550.5	316.5	477.5	100.5	549.5	317.5	476.5	101.5	548.5	318.5	475.5	102.5	547.5	690.5
691.5	120.5	529.5	336.5	457.5	119.5	530.5	335.5	458.5	118.5	531.5	334.5	459.5	117.5	532.5	333.5	460.5	116.5	533.5	332.5	461.5	115.5	534.5	331.5	462.5	30.5
29.5	624.5	169.5	408.5	241.5	623.5	170.5	407.5	242.5	622.5	171.5	406.5	243.5	621.5	172.5	405.5	244.5	620.5	173.5	404.5	245.5	619.5	174.5	403.5	246.5	692.5
693.5	385.5	264.5	601.5	192.5	386.5	263.5	602.5	191.5	387.5	262.5	603.5	190.5	388.5	261.5	604.5	189.5	389.5	260.5	605.5	188.5	390.5	259.5	606.5	187.5	28.5
27.5	319.5	474.5	103.5	546.5	320.5	473.5	104.5	545.5	321.5	472.5	105.5	544.5	322.5	471.5	106.5	543.5	323.5	470.5	107.5	542.5	324.5	469.5	108.5	541.5	694.5
695.5	114.5	535.5	330.5	463.5	113.5	536.5	329.5	464.5	112.5	537.5	328.5	465.5	111.5	538.5	327.5	466.5	110.5	539.5	326.5	467.5	109.5	540.5	325.5	468.5	26.5
25.5	618.5	175.5	402.5	247.5	617.5	176.5	401.5	248.5	616.5	177.5	400.5	249.5	615.5	178.5	399.5	250.5	614.5	179.5	398.5	251.5	613.5	180.5	397.5	252.5	696.5
697.5	391.5	258.5	607.5	186.5	392.5	257.5	608.5	185.5	393.5	256.5	609.5	184.5	394.5	255.5	610.5	183.5	395.5	254.5	611.5	182.5	396.5	253.5	612.5	181.5	24.5
48.5	36.5	684.5	38.5	682.5	40.5	680.5	42.5	678.5	44.5	676.5	46.5	674.5	48.5	672.5	50.5	670.5	52.5	668.5	54.5	666.5	56.5	664.5	58.5	662.5	674.5

The magic square of order 26 given in Example 26.5 is **block-bordered** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The inner magic squares of order 26 is **pandiagonal**. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{26 \times 26} = 9386; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 9386 = 244036 = 494^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} = 8664; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 8664 = 207936 = 456^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 1444; \quad T_{16} := 6 \times 1444 = 5776 = 76^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

27 Magic Squares of Order 27

This section brings magic squares of order 27 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

27.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 25 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 27, \quad \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 19683, \quad \mathbf{T}_{729} := 531441 = 729^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1455, 1457\} \text{ or } E := \{365, 366, \dots, 1091, 1093\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 27 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 27 given in Examples 27.1 and 27.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 19683; \quad T_{625} := 27 \times 19683 = 31441 = 729^2 = 27^4;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 2187; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 2187 = 6561 = 81^2.$$

The Examples 27.1 and 27.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 27, 27^2, 27^3, 27^4 \rangle$.

27.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 25 given in List (10):

$$(56, 783, 785) \Rightarrow 785^2 - 56^2 = 783^2, \quad 785 - 56 = 27^2, \quad \text{Order } 27, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 22707, \quad T_{729} := 783^2,$$

$$E = \{113, 115, \dots, 1567, 1569\} \text{ or } E = \{477, 478, \dots, 1204, 1205\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 25 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 27 given in Examples 27.3 and 27.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. See below the details:

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 22707; \quad T_{729} := 27 \times 22707 = 613089 = 783^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 2523; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 2523 = 7569 = 87^2.$$

Both the Examples 27.3 and 27.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (56,783,785)**, i.e., $56^2 + 783^2 = 785^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

27.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the 25 expression given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 27, } S_{27 \times 27} := 10800, \quad T_{729} := 291600 = 540^2, \quad E := \{36, 37, \dots, 763, 764\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 27.

28 Magic Squares of Order 28

This section brings magic squares of order 28 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

28.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 26 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 28, \quad S_{28 \times 28} := 21952, \quad T_{784} := 614656 = 784^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1565, 1567\} \text{ or } E := \{785/2, 787/2, \dots, 2347/2, 2351/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 28 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 28.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 28 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries 1, 3, 5, ..., 1565, 1567 is given by

589	1175	1	1371	591	1173	3	1369	593	1171	5	1367	595	1169	7	1365	597	1167	9	1363	599	1165	11	1361	601	1163	13	1359
195	1177	783	981	193	1179	781	983	191	1181	779	985	189	1183	777	987	187	1185	775	989	185	1187	773	991	183	1189	771	993
1567	197	979	393	1565	199	977	395	1563	201	975	397	1561	203	973	399	1559	205	971	401	1557	207	969	403	1555	209	967	405
785	587	1373	391	787	585	1375	389	789	583	1377	387	791	581	1379	385	793	579	1381	383	795	577	1383	381	797	575	1385	379
603	1161	15	1357	605	1159	17	1355	607	1157	19	1353	609	1155	21	1351	611	1153	23	1349	613	1151	25	1347	615	1149	27	1345
181	1191	769	995	179	1193	767	997	177	1195	765	999	175	1197	763	1001	173	1199	761	1003	171	1201	759	1005	169	1203	757	1007
1553	211	965	407	1551	213	963	409	1549	215	961	411	1547	217	959	413	1545	219	957	415	1543	221	955	417	1541	223	953	419
799	573	1387	377	801	571	1389	375	803	569	1391	373	805	567	1393	371	807	565	1395	369	809	563	1397	367	811	561	1399	365
617	1147	29	1343	619	1145	31	1341	621	1143	33	1339	623	1141	35	1337	625	1139	37	1335	627	1137	39	1333	629	1135	41	1331
167	1205	755	1009	165	1207	753	1011	163	1209	751	1013	161	1211	749	1015	159	1213	747	1017	157	1215	745	1019	155	1217	743	1021
1539	225	951	421	1537	227	949	423	1535	229	947	425	1533	231	945	427	1531	233	943	429	1529	235	941	431	1527	237	939	433
813	559	1401	363	815	557	1403	361	817	555	1405	359	819	553	1407	357	821	551	1409	355	823	549	1411	353	825	547	1413	351
631	1133	43	1329	633	1131	45	1327	635	1129	47	1325	637	1127	49	1323	639	1125	51	1321	641	1123	53	1319	643	1121	55	1317
153	1219	741	1023	151	1221	739	1025	149	1223	737	1027	147	1225	735	1029	145	1227	733	1031	143	1229	731	1033	141	1231	729	1035
1525	239	937	435	1523	241	935	437	1521	243	933	439	1519	245	931	441	1517	247	929	443	1515	249	927	445	1513	251	925	447
827	545	1415	349	829	543	1417	347	831	541	1419	345	833	539	1421	343	835	537	1423	341	837	535	1425	339	839	533	1427	337
645	1119	57	1315	647	1117	59	1313	649	1115	61	1311	651	1113	63	1309	653	1111	65	1307	655	1109	67	1305	657	1107	69	1303
139	1233	727	1037	137	1235	725	1039	135	1237	723	1041	133	1239	721	1043	131	1241	719	1045	129	1243	717	1047	127	1245	715	1049
1511	253	923	449	1509	255	921	451	1507	257	919	453	1505	259	917	455	1503	261	915	457	1501	263	913	459	1499	265	911	461
841	531	1429	335	843	529	1431	333	845	527	1433	331	847	525	1435	329	849	523	1437	327	851	521	1439	325	853	519	1441	323
659	1105	71	1301	661	1103	73	1299	663	1101	75	1297	665	1099	77	1295	667	1097	79	1293	669	1095	81	1291	671	1093	83	1289
125	1247	713	1051	123	1249	711	1053	121	1251	709	1055	119	1253	707	1057	117	1255	705	1059	115	1257	703	1061	113	1259	701	1063
1497	267	909	463	1495	269	907	465	1493	271	905	467	1491	273	903	469	1489	275	901	471	1487	277	899	473	1485	279	897	475
855	517	1443	321	857	515	1445	319	859	513	1447	317	861	511	1449	315	863	509	1451	313	865	507	1453	311	867	505	1455	309
673	1091	85	1287	675	1089	87	1285	677	1087	89	1283	679	1085	91	1281	681	1083	93	1279	683	1081	95	1277	685	1079	97	1275
111	1261	699	1065	109	1263	697	1067	107	1265	695	1069	105	1267	693	1071	103	1269	691	1073	101	1271	689	1075	99	1273	687	1077
1483	281	895	477	1481	283	893	479	1479	285	891	481	1477	287	889	483	1475	289	887	485	1473	291	885	487	1471	293	883	489
869	503	1457	307	871	501	1459	305	873	499	1461	303	875	497	1463	301	877	495	1465	299	879	493	1467	297	881	491	1469	295

Example 28.2. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 28 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{785/2, 787/2, \dots, 2347/2, 2351/2\}$ is given by

686.5	979.5	392.5	1077.5	687.5	978.5	393.5	1076.5	688.5	977.5	394.5	1075.5	689.5	976.5	395.5	1074.5	690.5	975.5	396.5	1073.5	691.5	974.5	397.5	1072.5	692.5	973.5	398.5	1071.5
489.5	980.5	783.5	882.5	488.5	981.5	782.5	883.5	487.5	982.5	781.5	884.5	486.5	983.5	780.5	885.5	485.5	984.5	779.5	886.5	484.5	985.5	778.5	887.5	483.5	986.5	777.5	888.5
1175.5	490.5	881.5	588.5	1174.5	491.5	880.5	589.5	1173.5	492.5	879.5	590.5	1172.5	493.5	878.5	591.5	1171.5	494.5	877.5	592.5	1170.5	495.5	876.5	593.5	1169.5	496.5	875.5	594.5
784.5	685.5	1078.5	587.5	785.5	684.5	1079.5	586.5	786.5	683.5	1080.5	585.5	787.5	682.5	1081.5	584.5	788.5	681.5	1082.5	583.5	789.5	680.5	1083.5	582.5	790.5	679.5	1084.5	581.5
693.5	972.5	399.5	1070.5	694.5	971.5	400.5	1069.5	695.5	970.5	401.5	1068.5	696.5	969.5	402.5	1067.5	697.5	968.5	403.5	1066.5	698.5	967.5	404.5	1065.5	699.5	966.5	405.5	1064.5
482.5	987.5	776.5	889.5	481.5	988.5	775.5	890.5	480.5	989.5	774.5	891.5	479.5	990.5	773.5	892.5	478.5	991.5	772.5	893.5	477.5	992.5	771.5	894.5	476.5	993.5	770.5	895.5
1168.5	497.5	874.5	595.5	1167.5	498.5	873.5	596.5	1166.5	499.5	872.5	597.5	1165.5	500.5	871.5	598.5	1164.5	501.5	870.5	599.5	1163.5	502.5	869.5	600.5	1162.5	503.5	868.5	601.5
791.5	678.5	1085.5	580.5	792.5	677.5	1086.5	579.5	793.5	676.5	1087.5	578.5	794.5	675.5	1088.5	577.5	795.5	674.5	1089.5	576.5	796.5	673.5	1090.5	575.5	797.5	672.5	1091.5	574.5
700.5	965.5	406.5	1063.5	701.5	964.5	407.5	1062.5	702.5	963.5	408.5	1061.5	703.5	962.5	409.5	1060.5	704.5	961.5	410.5	1059.5	705.5	960.5	411.5	1058.5	706.5	959.5	412.5	1057.5
475.5	994.5	769.5	896.5	474.5	995.5	768.5	897.5	473.5	996.5	767.5	898.5	472.5	997.5	766.5	899.5	471.5	998.5	765.5	900.5	470.5	999.5	764.5	901.5	469.5	1000.5	763.5	902.5
1161.5	504.5	867.5	602.5	1160.5	505.5	866.5	603.5	1159.5	506.5	865.5	604.5	1158.5	507.5	864.5	605.5	1157.5	508.5	863.5	606.5	1156.5	509.5	862.5	607.5	1155.5	510.5	861.5	608.5
798.5	671.5	1092.5	573.5	799.5	670.5	1093.5	572.5	800.5	669.5	1094.5	571.5	801.5	668.5	1095.5	570.5	802.5	667.5	1096.5	569.5	803.5	666.5	1097.5	568.5	804.5	665.5	1098.5	567.5
707.5	958.5	413.5	1056.5	708.5	957.5	414.5	1055.5	709.5	956.5	415.5	1054.5	710.5	955.5	416.5	1053.5	711.5	954.5	417.5	1052.5	712.5	953.5	418.5	1051.5	713.5	952.5	419.5	1050.5
468.5	1001.5	762.5	903.5	467.5	1002.5	761.5	904.5	466.5	1003.5	760.5	905.5	465.5	1004.5	759.5	906.5	464.5	1005.5	758.5	907.5	463.5	1006.5	757.5	908.5	462.5	1007.5	756.5	909.5
1154.5	511.5	860.5	609.5	1153.5	512.5	859.5	610.5	1152.5	513.5	858.5	611.5	1151.5	514.5	857.5	612.5	1150.5	515.5	856.5	613.5	1149.5	516.5	855.5	614.5	1148.5	517.5	854.5	615.5
805.5	664.5	1099.5	566.5	806.5	663.5	1100.5	565.5	807.5	662.5	1101.5	564.5	808.5	661.5	1102.5	563.5	809.5	660.5	1103.5	562.5	810.5	659.5	1104.5	561.5	811.5	658.5	1105.5	560.5
714.5	951.5	420.5	1049.5	715.5	950.5	421.5	1048.5	716.5	949.5	422.5	1047.5	717.5	948.5	423.5	1046.5	718.5	947.5	424.5	1045.5	719.5	946.5	425.5	1044.5	720.5	945.5	426.5	1043.5
461.5	1008.5	755.5	910.5	460.5	1009.5	754.5	911.5	459.5	1010.5	753.5	912.5	458.5	1011.5	752.5	913.5	457.5	1012.5	751.5	914.5	456.5	1013.5	750.5	915.5	455.5	1014.5	749.5	916.5
1147.5	518.5	853.5	616.5	1146.5	519.5	852.5	617.5	1145.5	520.5	851.5	618.5	1144.5	521.5	850.5	619.5	1143.5	522.5	849.5	620.5	1142.5	523.5	848.5	621.5	1141.5	524.5	847.5	622.5
812.5	657.5	1106.5	559.5	813.5	656.5	1107.5	558.5	814.5	655.5	1108.5	557.5	815.5	654.5	1109.5	556.5	816.5	653.5	1110.5	555.5	817.5	652.5	1111.5	554.5	818.5	651.5	1112.5	553.5
721.5	944.5	427.5	1042.5	722.5	943.5	428.5	1041.5	723.5	942.5	429.5	1040.5	724.5	941.5	430.5	1039.5	725.5	940.5	431.5	1038.5	726.5	939.5	432.5	1037.5	727.5	938.5	433.5	1036.5
454.5	1015.5	748.5	917.5	453.5	1016.5	747.5	918.5	452.5	1017.5	746.5	919.5	451.5	1018.5	745.5	920.5	450.5	1019.5	744.5	921.5	449.5	1020.5	743.5	922.5	448.5	1021.5	742.5	923.5
1140.5	525.5	846.5	623.5	1139.5	526.5	845.5	624.5	1138.5	527.5	844.5	625.5	1137.5	528.5	843.5	626.5	1136.5	529.5	842.5	627.5	1135.5	530.5	841.5	628.5	1134.5	531.5	840.5	629.5
819.5	650.5	1113.5	552.5	820.5	649.5	1114.5	551.5	821.5	648.5	1115.5	550.5	822.5	647.5	1116.5	549.5	823.5	646.5	1117.5	548.5	824.5	645.5	1118.5	547.5	825.5	644.5	1119.5	546.5
728.5	937.5	434.5	1035.5	729.5	936.5	435.5	1034.5	730.5	935.5	436.5	1033.5	731.5	934.5	437.5	1032.5	732.5	933.5	438.5	1031.5	733.5	932.5	439.5	1030.5	734.5	931.5	440.5	1029.5
447.5	1022.5	741.5	924.5	446.5	1023.5	740.5	925.5	445.5	1024.5	739.5	926.5	444.5	1025.5	738.5	927.5	443.5	1026.5	737.5	928.5	442.5	1027.5	736.5	929.5	441.5	1028.5	735.5	930.5
1133.5	532.5	839.5	630.5	1132.5	533.5	838.5	631.5	1131.5	534.5	837.5	632.5	1130.5	535.5	836.5	633.5	1129.5	536.5	835.5	634.5	1128.5	537.5	834.5	635.5	1127.5	538.5	833.5	636.5
826.5	643.5	1120.5	545.5	827.5	642.5	1121.5	544.5	828.5	641.5	1122.5	543.5	829.5	640.5	1123.5	542.5	830.5	639.5	1124.5	541.5	831.5	638.5	1125.5	540.5	832.5	637.5	1126.5	539.5

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 28 given in Examples 28.1 and 28.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. Block of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares equal of magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 21952 = 28^3; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 21952 = 614656 = 784^2 = 28^4;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 3136; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 3136 = 12544 = 112^2.$$

The Examples 28.1 and 28.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 28, 28^2, 28^3, 28^4 \rangle$.

28.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 26 given in List (10):

$$(58, 840, 842) \Rightarrow 842^2 - 58^2 = 840^2, 842 - 58 = 28^2, \text{ Order } 28, S_{28 \times 28} := 25200, T_{784} := 840^2,$$

$$E = \{117, 119, \dots, 1681, 1683\} \text{ or } E = \{1017/2, 1019/2, \dots, 2581/2, 2583/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 28 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 28.3. A *block-wise pandiagonal magic square of order 28 for consecutive odd numbers entries 117, 119, ..., 1681, 1683* is given by

129	385	641	897	1153	1409	1665	139	395	651	907	1163	1419	1675	117	373	629	885	1141	1397	1653	143	399	655	911	1167	1423	1679
1377	1633	321	353	609	865	1121	1387	1643	331	363	619	875	1131	1365	1621	309	341	597	853	1109	1391	1647	335	367	623	879	1135
833	1089	1345	1601	289	545	577	843	1099	1355	1611	299	555	587	821	1077	1333	1589	277	533	565	847	1103	1359	1615	303	559	591
513	769	801	1057	1313	1569	257	523	779	811	1067	1323	1579	267	501	757	789	1045	1301	1557	245	527	783	815	1071	1327	1583	271
1537	225	481	737	993	1025	1281	1547	235	491	747	1003	1035	1291	1525	213	469	725	981	1013	1269	1551	239	495	751	1007	1039	1295
1217	1249	1505	193	449	705	961	1227	1259	1515	203	459	715	971	1205	1237	1493	181	437	693	949	1231	1263	1519	207	463	719	975
673	929	1185	1441	1473	161	417	683	939	1195	1451	1483	171	427	661	917	1173	1429	1461	149	405	687	943	1199	1455	1487	175	431
119	375	631	887	1143	1399	1655	141	397	653	909	1165	1421	1677	131	387	643	899	1155	1411	1667	137	393	649	905	1161	1417	1673
1367	1623	311	343	599	855	1111	1389	1645	333	365	621	877	1133	1379	1635	323	355	611	867	1123	1385	1641	329	361	617	873	1129
823	1079	1335	1591	279	535	567	845	1101	1357	1613	301	557	589	835	1091	1347	1603	291	547	579	841	1097	1353	1609	297	553	585
503	759	791	1047	1303	1559	247	525	781	813	1069	1325	1581	269	515	771	803	1059	1315	1571	259	521	777	809	1065	1321	1577	265
1527	215	471	727	983	1015	1271	1549	237	493	749	1005	1037	1293	1539	227	483	739	995	1027	1283	1545	233	489	745	1001	1033	1289
1207	1239	1495	183	439	695	951	1229	1261	1517	205	461	717	973	1219	1251	1507	195	451	707	963	1225	1257	1513	201	457	713	969
663	919	1175	1431	1463	151	407	685	941	1197	1453	1485	173	429	675	931	1187	1443	1475	163	419	681	937	1193	1449	1481	169	425
147	403	659	915	1171	1427	1683	121	377	633	889	1145	1401	1657	135	391	647	903	1159	1415	1671	125	381	637	893	1149	1405	1661
1395	1651	339	371	627	883	1139	1369	1625	313	345	601	857	1113	1383	1639	327	359	615	871	1127	1373	1629	317	349	605	861	1117
851	1107	1363	1619	307	563	595	825	1081	1337	1593	281	537	569	839	1095	1351	1607	295	551	583	829	1085	1341	1597	285	541	573
531	787	819	1075	1331	1587	275	505	761	793	1049	1305	1561	249	519	775	807	1063	1319	1575	263	509	765	797	1053	1309	1565	253
1555	243	499	755	1011	1043	1299	1529	217	473	729	985	1017	1273	1543	231	487	743	999	1031	1287	1533	221	477	733	989	1021	1277
1235	1267	1523	211	467	723	979	1209	1241	1497	185	441	697	953	1223	1255	1511	199	455	711	967	1213	1245	1501	189	445	701	957
691	947	1203	1459	1491	179	435	665	921	1177	1433	1465	153	409	679	935	1191	1447	1479	167	423	669	925	1181	1437	1469	157	413
133	389	645	901	1157	1413	1669	127	383	639	895	1151	1407	1663	145	401	657	913	1169	1425	1681	123	379	635	891	1147	1403	1659
1381	1637	325	357	613	869	1125	1375	1631	319	351	607	863	1119	1393	1649	337	369	625	881	1137	1371	1627	315	347	603	859	1115
837	1093	1349	1605	293	549	581	831	1087	1343	1599	287	543	575	849	1105	1361	1617	305	561	593	827	1083	1339	1595	283	539	571
517	773	805	1061	1317	1573	261	511	767	799	1055	1311	1567	255	529	785	817	1073	1329	1585	273	507	763	795	1051	1307	1563	251
1541	229	485	741	997	1029	1285	1535	223	479	735	991	1023	1279	1553	241	497	753	1009	1041	1297	1531	219	475	731	987	1019	1275
1221	1253	1509	197	453	709	965	1215	1247	1503	191	447	703	959	1233	1265	1521	209	465	721	977	1211	1243	1499	187	443	699	955
677	933	1189	1445	1477	165	421	671	927	1183	1439	1471	159	415	689	945	1201	1457	1489	177	433	667	923	1179	1435	1467	155	411

Example 28.4. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 28 for **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $1017/2, 1019/2, \dots, 2581/2, 2583/2$ is given by

514.5	642.5	770.5	898.5	1026.5	1154.5	1282.5	519.5	647.5	775.5	903.5	1031.5	1159.5	1287.5	508.5	636.5	764.5	892.5	1020.5	1148.5	1276.5	521.5	649.5	777.5	905.5	1033.5	1161.5	1289.5
1138.5	1266.5	610.5	626.5	754.5	882.5	1010.5	1143.5	1271.5	615.5	631.5	759.5	887.5	1015.5	1132.5	1260.5	604.5	620.5	748.5	876.5	1004.5	1145.5	1273.5	617.5	633.5	761.5	889.5	1017.5
866.5	994.5	1122.5	1250.5	594.5	722.5	738.5	871.5	999.5	1127.5	1255.5	599.5	727.5	743.5	860.5	988.5	1116.5	1244.5	588.5	716.5	732.5	873.5	1001.5	1129.5	1257.5	601.5	729.5	745.5
706.5	834.5	850.5	978.5	1106.5	1234.5	578.5	711.5	839.5	855.5	983.5	1111.5	1239.5	583.5	700.5	828.5	844.5	972.5	1100.5	1228.5	572.5	713.5	841.5	857.5	985.5	1113.5	1241.5	585.5
1218.5	562.5	690.5	818.5	946.5	962.5	1090.5	1223.5	567.5	695.5	823.5	951.5	967.5	1095.5	1212.5	556.5	684.5	812.5	940.5	956.5	1084.5	1225.5	569.5	697.5	825.5	953.5	969.5	1097.5
1058.5	1074.5	1202.5	546.5	674.5	802.5	930.5	1063.5	1079.5	1207.5	551.5	679.5	807.5	935.5	1052.5	1068.5	1196.5	540.5	668.5	796.5	924.5	1065.5	1081.5	1209.5	553.5	681.5	809.5	937.5
786.5	914.5	1042.5	1170.5	1186.5	530.5	658.5	791.5	919.5	1047.5	1175.5	1191.5	535.5	663.5	780.5	908.5	1036.5	1164.5	1180.5	524.5	652.5	793.5	921.5	1049.5	1177.5	1193.5	537.5	665.5
509.5	637.5	765.5	893.5	1021.5	1149.5	1277.5	520.5	648.5	776.5	904.5	1032.5	1160.5	1288.5	515.5	643.5	771.5	899.5	1027.5	1155.5	1283.5	518.5	646.5	774.5	902.5	1030.5	1158.5	1286.5
1133.5	1261.5	605.5	621.5	749.5	877.5	1005.5	1144.5	1272.5	616.5	632.5	760.5	888.5	1016.5	1139.5	1267.5	611.5	627.5	755.5	883.5	1011.5	1142.5	1270.5	614.5	630.5	758.5	886.5	1014.5
861.5	989.5	1117.5	1245.5	589.5	717.5	733.5	872.5	1000.5	1128.5	1256.5	600.5	728.5	744.5	867.5	995.5	1123.5	1251.5	595.5	723.5	739.5	870.5	998.5	1126.5	1254.5	598.5	726.5	742.5
701.5	829.5	845.5	973.5	1101.5	1229.5	573.5	712.5	840.5	856.5	984.5	1112.5	1240.5	584.5	707.5	835.5	851.5	979.5	1107.5	1235.5	579.5	710.5	838.5	854.5	982.5	1110.5	1238.5	582.5
1213.5	557.5	685.5	813.5	941.5	957.5	1085.5	1224.5	568.5	696.5	824.5	952.5	968.5	1096.5	1219.5	563.5	691.5	819.5	947.5	963.5	1091.5	1222.5	566.5	694.5	822.5	950.5	966.5	1094.5
1053.5	1069.5	1197.5	541.5	669.5	797.5	925.5	1064.5	1080.5	1208.5	552.5	680.5	808.5	936.5	1059.5	1075.5	1203.5	547.5	675.5	803.5	931.5	1062.5	1078.5	1206.5	550.5	678.5	806.5	934.5
781.5	909.5	1037.5	1165.5	1181.5	525.5	653.5	792.5	920.5	1048.5	1176.5	1192.5	536.5	664.5	787.5	915.5	1043.5	1171.5	1187.5	531.5	659.5	790.5	918.5	1046.5	1174.5	1190.5	534.5	662.5
523.5	651.5	779.5	907.5	1035.5	1163.5	1291.5	510.5	638.5	766.5	894.5	1022.5	1150.5	1278.5	517.5	645.5	773.5	901.5	1029.5	1157.5	1285.5	512.5	640.5	768.5	896.5	1024.5	1152.5	1280.5
1147.5	1275.5	619.5	635.5	763.5	891.5	1019.5	1134.5	1262.5	606.5	622.5	750.5	878.5	1006.5	1141.5	1269.5	613.5	629.5	757.5	885.5	1013.5	1136.5	1264.5	608.5	624.5	752.5	880.5	1008.5
875.5	1003.5	1131.5	1259.5	603.5	731.5	747.5	862.5	990.5	1118.5	1246.5	590.5	718.5	734.5	869.5	997.5	1125.5	1253.5	597.5	725.5	741.5	864.5	992.5	1120.5	1248.5	592.5	720.5	736.5
715.5	843.5	859.5	987.5	1115.5	1243.5	587.5	702.5	830.5	846.5	974.5	1102.5	1230.5	574.5	709.5	837.5	853.5	981.5	1109.5	1237.5	581.5	704.5	832.5	848.5	976.5	1104.5	1232.5	576.5
1227.5	571.5	699.5	827.5	955.5	971.5	1099.5	1214.5	558.5	686.5	814.5	942.5	958.5	1086.5	1221.5	565.5	693.5	821.5	949.5	965.5	1093.5	1216.5	560.5	688.5	816.5	944.5	960.5	1088.5
1067.5	1083.5	1211.5	555.5	683.5	811.5	939.5	1054.5	1070.5	1198.5	542.5	670.5	798.5	926.5	1061.5	1077.5	1205.5	549.5	677.5	805.5	933.5	1056.5	1072.5	1200.5	544.5	672.5	800.5	928.5
795.5	923.5	1051.5	1179.5	1195.5	539.5	667.5	782.5	910.5	1038.5	1166.5	1182.5	526.5	654.5	789.5	917.5	1045.5	1173.5	1189.5	533.5	661.5	784.5	912.5	1040.5	1168.5	1184.5	528.5	656.5
516.5	644.5	772.5	900.5	1028.5	1156.5	1284.5	513.5	641.5	769.5	897.5	1025.5	1153.5	1281.5	522.5	650.5	778.5	906.5	1034.5	1162.5	1290.5	511.5	639.5	767.5	895.5	1023.5	1151.5	1279.5
1140.5	1268.5	612.5	628.5	756.5	884.5	1012.5	1137.5	1265.5	609.5	625.5	753.5	881.5	1009.5	1146.5	1274.5	618.5	634.5	762.5	890.5	1018.5	1135.5	1263.5	607.5	623.5	751.5	879.5	1007.5
868.5	996.5	1124.5	1252.5	596.5	724.5	740.5	865.5	993.5	1121.5	1249.5	593.5	721.5	737.5	874.5	1002.5	1130.5	1258.5	602.5	730.5	746.5	863.5	991.5	1119.5	1247.5	591.5	719.5	735.5
708.5	836.5	852.5	980.5	1108.5	1236.5	580.5	705.5	833.5	849.5	977.5	1105.5	1233.5	577.5	714.5	842.5	858.5	986.5	1114.5	1242.5	586.5	703.5	831.5	847.5	975.5	1103.5	1231.5	575.5
1220.5	564.5	692.5	820.5	948.5	964.5	1092.5	1217.5	561.5	689.5	817.5	945.5	961.5	1089.5	1226.5	570.5	698.5	826.5	954.5	970.5	1098.5	1215.5	559.5	687.5	815.5	943.5	959.5	1087.5
1060.5	1076.5	1204.5	548.5	676.5	804.5	932.5	1057.5	1073.5	1201.5	545.5	673.5	801.5	929.5	1066.5	1082.5	1210.5	554.5	682.5	810.5	938.5	1055.5	1071.5	1199.5	543.5	671.5	799.5	927.5
788.5	916.5	1044.5	1172.5	1188.5	532.5	660.5	785.5	913.5	1041.5	1169.5	1185.5	529.5	657.5	794.5	922.5	1050.5	1178.5	1194.5	538.5	666.5	783.5	911.5	1039.5	1167.5	1183.5	527.5	655.5

The **block-wise pandiagonal** magic squares of order 28 given in Examples 28.3 and 28.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. Block of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares equal of magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 25200; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 25200 = 705600 = 840^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 6300; \quad T_{16} := 7 \times 6300 = 176400 = 420^2.$$

Both the Examples 28.3 and 28.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (58,840,842)**, i.e., $58^2 + 840^2 = 842^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

28.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 26 given in List (15):

Order 28, $S_{28 \times 28} := 11200$, $T_{784} := 313600 = 560^2$, $E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 28 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 28.5. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 28 for **consecutive fractional numbers** entries $\{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$ is given by

302.5	595.5	8.5	693.5	303.5	594.5	9.5	692.5	304.5	593.5	10.5	691.5	305.5	592.5	11.5	690.5	306.5	591.5	12.5	689.5	307.5	590.5	13.5	688.5	308.5	589.5	14.5	687.5
105.5	596.5	399.5	498.5	104.5	597.5	398.5	499.5	103.5	598.5	397.5	500.5	102.5	599.5	396.5	501.5	101.5	600.5	395.5	502.5	100.5	601.5	394.5	503.5	99.5	602.5	393.5	504.5
791.5	106.5	497.5	204.5	790.5	107.5	496.5	205.5	789.5	108.5	495.5	206.5	788.5	109.5	494.5	207.5	787.5	110.5	493.5	208.5	786.5	111.5	492.5	209.5	785.5	112.5	491.5	210.5
400.5	301.5	694.5	203.5	401.5	300.5	695.5	202.5	402.5	299.5	696.5	201.5	403.5	298.5	697.5	200.5	404.5	297.5	698.5	199.5	405.5	296.5	699.5	198.5	406.5	295.5	700.5	197.5
309.5	588.5	15.5	686.5	310.5	587.5	16.5	685.5	311.5	586.5	17.5	684.5	312.5	585.5	18.5	683.5	313.5	584.5	19.5	682.5	314.5	583.5	20.5	681.5	315.5	582.5	21.5	680.5
98.5	603.5	392.5	505.5	97.5	604.5	391.5	506.5	96.5	605.5	390.5	507.5	95.5	606.5	389.5	508.5	94.5	607.5	388.5	509.5	93.5	608.5	387.5	510.5	92.5	609.5	386.5	511.5
784.5	113.5	490.5	211.5	783.5	114.5	489.5	212.5	782.5	115.5	488.5	213.5	781.5	116.5	487.5	214.5	780.5	117.5	486.5	215.5	779.5	118.5	485.5	216.5	778.5	119.5	484.5	217.5
407.5	294.5	701.5	196.5	408.5	293.5	702.5	195.5	409.5	292.5	703.5	194.5	410.5	291.5	704.5	193.5	411.5	290.5	705.5	192.5	412.5	289.5	706.5	191.5	413.5	288.5	707.5	190.5
316.5	581.5	22.5	679.5	317.5	580.5	23.5	678.5	318.5	579.5	24.5	677.5	319.5	578.5	25.5	676.5	320.5	577.5	26.5	675.5	321.5	576.5	27.5	674.5	322.5	575.5	28.5	673.5
91.5	610.5	385.5	512.5	90.5	611.5	384.5	513.5	89.5	612.5	383.5	514.5	88.5	613.5	382.5	515.5	87.5	614.5	381.5	516.5	86.5	615.5	380.5	517.5	85.5	616.5	379.5	518.5
777.5	120.5	483.5	218.5	776.5	121.5	482.5	219.5	775.5	122.5	481.5	220.5	774.5	123.5	480.5	221.5	773.5	124.5	479.5	222.5	772.5	125.5	478.5	223.5	771.5	126.5	477.5	224.5
414.5	287.5	708.5	189.5	415.5	286.5	709.5	188.5	416.5	285.5	710.5	187.5	417.5	284.5	711.5	186.5	418.5	283.5	712.5	185.5	419.5	282.5	713.5	184.5	420.5	281.5	714.5	183.5
323.5	574.5	29.5	672.5	324.5	573.5	30.5	671.5	325.5	572.5	31.5	670.5	326.5	571.5	32.5	669.5	327.5	570.5	33.5	668.5	328.5	569.5	34.5	667.5	329.5	568.5	35.5	666.5
84.5	617.5	378.5	519.5	83.5	618.5	377.5	520.5	82.5	619.5	376.5	521.5	81.5	620.5	375.5	522.5	80.5	621.5	374.5	523.5	79.5	622.5	373.5	524.5	78.5	623.5	372.5	525.5
770.5	127.5	476.5	225.5	769.5	128.5	475.5	226.5	768.5	129.5	474.5	227.5	767.5	130.5	473.5	228.5	766.5	131.5	472.5	229.5	765.5	132.5	471.5	230.5	764.5	133.5	470.5	231.5
421.5	280.5	715.5	182.5	422.5	279.5	716.5	181.5	423.5	278.5	717.5	180.5	424.5	277.5	718.5	179.5	425.5	276.5	719.5	178.5	426.5	275.5	720.5	177.5	427.5	274.5	721.5	176.5
330.5	567.5	36.5	665.5	331.5	566.5	37.5	664.5	332.5	565.5	38.5	663.5	333.5	564.5	39.5	662.5	334.5	563.5	40.5	661.5	335.5	562.5	41.5	660.5	336.5	561.5	42.5	659.5
77.5	624.5	371.5	526.5	76.5	625.5	370.5	527.5	75.5	626.5	369.5	528.5	74.5	627.5	368.5	529.5	73.5	628.5	367.5	530.5	72.5	629.5	366.5	531.5	71.5	630.5	365.5	532.5
763.5	134.5	469.5	232.5	762.5	135.5	468.5	233.5	761.5	136.5	467.5	234.5	760.5	137.5	466.5	235.5	759.5	138.5	465.5	236.5	758.5	139.5	464.5	237.5	757.5	140.5	463.5	238.5
428.5	273.5	722.5	175.5	429.5	272.5	723.5	174.5	430.5	271.5	724.5	173.5	431.5	270.5	725.5	172.5	432.5	269.5	726.5	171.5	433.5	268.5	727.5	170.5	434.5	267.5	728.5	169.5
337.5	560.5	43.5	658.5	338.5	559.5	44.5	657.5	339.5	558.5	45.5	656.5	340.5	557.5	46.5	655.5	341.5	556.5	47.5	654.5	342.5	555.5	48.5	653.5	343.5	554.5	49.5	652.5
70.5	631.5	364.5	533.5	69.5	632.5	363.5	534.5	68.5	633.5	362.5	535.5	67.5	634.5	361.5	536.5	66.5	635.5	360.5	537.5	65.5	636.5	359.5	538.5	64.5	637.5	358.5	539.5
756.5	141.5	462.5	239.5	755.5	142.5	461.5	240.5	754.5	143.5	460.5	241.5	753.5	144.5	459.5	242.5	752.5	145.5	458.5	243.5	751.5	146.5	457.5	244.5	750.5	147.5	456.5	245.5
435.5	266.5	729.5	168.5	436.5	265.5	730.5	167.5	437.5	264.5	731.5	166.5	438.5	263.5	732.5	165.5	439.5	262.5	733.5	164.5	440.5	261.5	734.5	163.5	441.5	260.5	735.5	162.5
344.5	553.5	50.5	651.5	345.5	552.5	51.5	650.5	346.5	551.5	52.5	649.5	347.5	550.5	53.5	648.5	348.5	549.5	54.5	647.5	349.5	548.5	55.5	646.5	350.5	547.5	56.5	645.5
63.5	638.5	357.5	540.5	62.5	639.5	356.5	541.5	61.5	640.5	355.5	542.5	60.5	641.5	354.5	543.5	59.5	642.5	353.5	544.5	58.5	643.5	352.5	545.5	57.5	644.5	351.5	546.5
749.5	148.5	455.5	246.5	748.5	149.5	454.5	247.5	747.5	150.5	453.5	248.5	746.5	151.5	452.5	249.5	745.5	152.5	451.5	250.5	744.5	153.5	450.5	251.5	743.5	154.5	449.5	252.5
442.5	259.5	736.5	161.5	443.5	258.5	737.5	160.5	444.5	257.5	738.5	159.5	445.5	256.5	739.5	158.5	446.5	255.5	740.5	157.5	447.5	254.5	741.5	156.5	448.5	253.5	742.5	155.5

The magic square of order 28 given in Example 28.5 is **block-wise pandiagonal** with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 11200; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 11200 = 313600 = 560^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 1600; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1600 = 6400 = 80^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

29 Magic Squares of Order 29

This section brings magic squares of order 29 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

29.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 27 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 29, \quad \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 24389, \quad \mathbf{T}_{841} := 707281 = 841^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1679, 1681\} \text{ or } E := \{421, 422, \dots, 1259, 1261\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 29 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 29.1. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1679, 1681\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 is given by

1627	1571	1575	1579	1583	1587	1591	1595	1599	1603	1607	1611	1615	1619	53	51	47	43	39	35	31	27	23	19	15	11	7	3	1623
109	1355	1009	159	1383	979	161	1363	1013	147	1385	987	151	1395	989	139	1397	999	127	1371	1021	131	1405	1001	117	1375	1029	119	1573
105	145	1401	977	115	1403	1005	149	1389	985	123	1393	1007	125	1381	1017	135	1369	1019	157	1373	993	137	1359	1027	165	1361	997	1577
101	1023	113	1387	1025	141	1357	1011	121	1391	1015	143	1365	1003	153	1367	991	155	1377	995	129	1399	981	163	1379	983	133	1407	1581
97	1409	199	915	1437	169	917	1417	203	903	1439	177	907	1449	179	895	1451	189	883	1425	211	887	1459	191	873	1429	219	875	1585
93	901	1455	167	871	1457	195	905	1443	175	879	1447	197	881	1435	207	891	1423	209	913	1427	183	893	1413	217	921	1415	187	1589
89	213	869	1441	215	897	1411	201	877	1445	205	899	1419	193	909	1421	181	911	1431	185	885	1453	171	919	1433	173	889	1461	1593
85	1031	1117	375	1059	1087	377	1039	1121	363	1061	1095	367	1071	1097	355	1073	1107	343	1047	1129	347	1081	1109	333	1051	1137	335	1597
81	361	1077	1085	331	1079	1113	365	1065	1093	339	1069	1115	341	1057	1125	351	1045	1127	373	1049	1101	353	1035	1135	381	1037	1105	1601
77	1131	329	1063	1133	357	1033	1119	337	1067	1123	359	1041	1111	369	1043	1099	371	1053	1103	345	1075	1089	379	1055	1091	349	1083	1605
73	1139	415	969	1167	385	971	1147	419	957	1169	393	961	1179	395	949	1181	405	937	1155	427	941	1189	407	927	1159	435	929	1609
69	955	1185	383	925	1187	411	959	1173	391	933	1177	413	935	1165	423	945	1153	425	967	1157	399	947	1143	433	975	1145	403	1613
65	429	923	1171	431	951	1141	417	931	1175	421	953	1149	409	963	1151	397	965	1161	401	939	1183	387	973	1163	389	943	1191	1617
61	815	469	1239	843	439	1241	823	473	1227	845	447	1231	855	449	1219	857	459	1207	831	481	1211	865	461	1197	835	489	1199	1621
57	1225	861	437	1195	863	465	1229	849	445	1203	853	467	1205	841	477	1215	829	479	1237	833	453	1217	819	487	1245	821	457	1625
1633	483	1193	847	485	1221	817	471	1201	851	475	1223	825	463	1233	827	451	1235	837	455	1209	859	441	1243	839	443	1213	867	49
1637	491	739	1293	519	709	1295	499	743	1281	521	717	1285	531	719	1273	533	729	1261	507	751	1265	541	731	1251	511	759	1253	45
1641	1279	537	707	1249	539	735	1283	525	715	1257	529	737	1259	517	747	1269	505	749	1291	509	723	1271	495	757	1299	497	727	41
1645	753	1247	523	755	1275	493	741	1255	527	745	1277	501	733	1287	503	721	1289	513	725	1263	535	711	1297	515	713	1267	543	37
1649	599	1333	591	627	1303	593	607	1337	579	629	1311	583	639	1313	571	641	1323	559	615	1345	563	649	1325	549	619	1353	551	33
1653	577	645	1301	547	647	1329	581	633	1309	555	637	1331	557	625	1341	567	613	1343	589	617	1317	569	603	1351	597	605	1321	29
1657	1347	545	631	1349	573	601	1335	553	635	1339	575	609	1327	585	611	1315	587	621	1319	561	643	1305	595	623	1307	565	651	25
1661	221	793	1509	249	763	1511	229	797	1497	251	771	1501	261	773	1489	263	783	1477	237	805	1481	271	785	1467	241	813	1469	21
1665	1495	267	761	1465	269	789	1499	255	769	1473	259	791	1475	247	801	1485	235	803	1507	239	777	1487	225	811	1515	227	781	17
1669	807	1463	253	809	1491	223	795	1471	257	799	1493	231	787	1503	233	775	1505	243	779	1479	265	765	1513	245	767	1483	273	13
1673	275	1549	699	303	1519	701	283	1553	687	305	1527	691	315	1529	679	317	1539	667	291	1561	671	325	1541	657	295	1569	659	9
1677	685	321	1517	655	323	1545	689	309	1525	663	313	1547	665	301	1557	675	289	1559	697	293	1533	677	279	1567	705	281	1537	5
1681	1563	653	307	1565	681	277	1551	661	311	1555	683	285	1543	693	287	1531	695	297	1535	669	319	1521	703	299	1523	673	327	1
59	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	79	75	71	67	63	1629	1631	1635	1639	1643	1647	1651	1655	1659	1663	1667	1671	1675	1679	55

Example 29.2. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{421, 422, 423, \dots, 1260, 1261\}$ a **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 27 is given by

1234	1206	1208	1210	1212	1214	1216	1218	1220	1222	1224	1226	1228	1230	447	446	444	442	440	438	436	434	432	430	428	426	424	422	1232
475	1098	925	500	1112	910	501	1102	927	494	1113	914	496	1118	915	490	1119	920	484	1106	931	486	1123	921	479	1108	935	480	1207
473	493	1121	909	478	1122	923	495	1115	913	482	1117	924	483	1111	929	488	1105	930	499	1107	917	489	1100	934	503	1101	919	1209
471	932	477	1114	933	491	1099	926	481	1116	928	492	1103	922	497	1104	916	498	1109	918	485	1120	911	502	1110	912	487	1124	1211
469	1125	520	878	1139	505	879	1129	522	872	1140	509	874	1145	510	868	1146	515	862	1133	526	864	1150	516	857	1135	530	858	1213
467	871	1148	504	856	1149	518	873	1142	508	860	1144	519	861	1138	524	866	1132	525	877	1134	512	867	1127	529	881	1128	514	1215
465	527	855	1141	528	869	1126	521	859	1143	523	870	1130	517	875	1131	511	876	1136	513	863	1147	506	880	1137	507	865	1151	1217
463	936	979	608	950	964	609	940	981	602	951	968	604	956	969	598	957	974	592	944	985	594	961	975	587	946	989	588	1219
461	601	959	963	586	960	977	603	953	967	590	955	978	591	949	983	596	943	984	607	945	971	597	938	988	611	939	973	1221
459	986	585	952	987	599	937	980	589	954	982	600	941	976	605	942	970	606	947	972	593	958	965	610	948	966	595	962	1223
457	990	628	905	1004	613	906	994	630	899	1005	617	901	1010	618	895	1011	623	889	998	634	891	1015	624	884	1000	638	885	1225
455	898	1013	612	883	1014	626	900	1007	616	887	1009	627	888	1003	632	893	997	633	904	999	620	894	992	637	908	993	622	1227
453	635	882	1006	636	896	991	629	886	1008	631	897	995	625	902	996	619	903	1001	621	890	1012	614	907	1002	615	892	1016	1229
451	828	655	1040	842	640	1041	832	657	1034	843	644	1036	848	645	1030	849	650	1024	836	661	1026	853	651	1019	838	665	1020	1231
449	1033	851	639	1018	852	653	1035	845	643	1022	847	654	1023	841	659	1028	835	660	1039	837	647	1029	830	664	1043	831	649	1233
1237	662	1017	844	663	1031	829	656	1021	846	658	1032	833	652	1037	834	646	1038	839	648	1025	850	641	1042	840	642	1027	854	445
1239	666	790	1067	680	775	1068	670	792	1061	681	779	1063	686	780	1057	687	785	1051	674	796	1053	691	786	1046	676	800	1047	443
1241	1060	689	774	1045	690	788	1062	683	778	1049	685	789	1050	679	794	1055	673	795	1066	675	782	1056	668	799	1070	669	784	441
1243	797	1044	682	798	1058	667	791	1048	684	793	1059	671	787	1064	672	781	1065	677	783	1052	688	776	1069	678	777	1054	692	439
1245	720	1087	716	734	1072	717	724	1089	710	735	1076	712	740	1077	706	741	1082	700	728	1093	702	745	1083	695	730	1097	696	437
1247	709	743	1071	694	744	1085	711	737	1075	698	739	1086	699	733	1091	704	727	1092	715	729	1079	705	722	1096	719	723	1081	435
1249	1094	693	736	1095	707	721	1088	697	738	1090	708	725	1084	713	726	1078	714	731	1080	701	742	1073	718	732	1074	703	746	433
1251	531	817	1175	545	802	1176	535	819	1169	546	806	1171	551	807	1165	552	812	1159	539	823	1161	556	813	1154	541	827	1155	431
1253	1168	554	801	1153	555	815	1170	548	805	1157	550	816	1158	544	821	1163	538	822	1174	540	809	1164	533	826	1178	534	811	429
1255	824	1152	547	825	1166	532	818	1156	549	820	1167	536	814	1172	537	808	1173	542	810	1160	553	803	1177	543	804	1162	557	427
1257	558	1195	770	572	1180	771	562	1197	764	573	1184	766	578	1185	760	579	1190	754	566	1201	756	583	1191	749	568	1205	750	425
1259	763	581	1179	748	582	1193	765	575	1183	752	577	1194	753	571	1199	758	565	1200	769	567	1187	759	560	1204	773	561	1189	423
1261	1202	747	574	1203	761	559	1196	751	576	1198	762	563	1192	767	564	1186	768	569	1188	755	580	1181	772	570	1182	757	584	421
450	476	474	472	470	468	466	464	462	460	458	456	454	452	1235	1236	1238	1240	1242	1244	1246	1248	1250	1252	1254	1256	1258	1260	448

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given in Examples 29.1 and 29.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The magic square of order 27 is **block-wise pandiagonal**. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{29 \times 29} &= 24389 = 29^3; & T_{841} &:= 29 \times 24389 = 707281 = 841^2 = 29^4; \\ S_{27 \times 27} &= 22707; & T_{729} &:= 27 \times 22707 = 613089 = 783^2; \\ Sm_{3 \times 3} &= 2523; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 2523 = 7569 = 87^2. \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 29.1 and 29.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 29, 29^2, 29^3, 29^4 \rangle$.

29.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 27 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (60, 899, 901) &\Rightarrow 901^2 - 60^2 = 899^2, \quad 901 - 60 = 29^2, \quad \text{Order } 29, \quad S_{29 \times 29} := 27869, \quad T_{841} := 899^2, \\ E &= \{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\} \text{ or } E = \{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 29 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 29.3. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{121, 123, \dots, 1799, 1801\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 is given by

1747	1691	1695	1699	1703	1707	1711	1715	1719	1723	1727	1731	1735	1739	173	171	167	163	159	155	151	147	143	139	135	131	127	123	1743
229	1475	1129	279	1503	1099	281	1483	1133	267	1505	1107	271	1515	1109	259	1517	1119	247	1491	1141	251	1525	1121	237	1495	1149	239	1693
225	265	1521	1097	235	1523	1125	269	1509	1105	243	1513	1127	245	1501	1137	255	1489	1139	277	1493	1113	257	1479	1147	285	1481	1117	1697
221	1143	233	1507	1145	261	1477	1131	241	1511	1135	263	1485	1123	273	1487	1111	275	1497	1115	249	1519	1101	283	1499	1103	253	1527	1701
217	1529	319	1035	1557	289	1037	1537	323	1023	1559	297	1027	1569	299	1015	1571	309	1003	1545	331	1007	1579	311	993	1549	339	995	1705
213	1021	1575	287	991	1577	315	1025	1563	295	999	1567	317	1001	1555	327	1011	1543	329	1033	1547	303	1013	1533	337	1041	1535	307	1709
209	333	989	1561	335	1017	1531	321	997	1565	325	1019	1539	313	1029	1541	301	1031	1551	305	1005	1573	291	1039	1553	293	1009	1581	1713
205	1151	1237	495	1179	1207	497	1159	1241	483	1181	1215	487	1191	1217	475	1193	1227	463	1167	1249	467	1201	1229	453	1171	1257	455	1717
201	481	1197	1205	451	1199	1233	485	1185	1213	459	1189	1235	461	1177	1245	471	1165	1247	493	1169	1221	473	1155	1255	501	1157	1225	1721
197	1251	449	1183	1253	477	1153	1239	457	1187	1243	479	1161	1231	489	1163	1219	491	1173	1223	465	1195	1209	499	1175	1211	469	1203	1725
193	1259	535	1089	1287	505	1091	1267	539	1077	1289	513	1081	1299	515	1069	1301	525	1057	1275	547	1061	1309	527	1047	1279	555	1049	1729
189	1075	1305	503	1045	1307	531	1079	1293	511	1053	1297	533	1055	1285	543	1065	1273	545	1087	1277	519	1067	1263	553	1095	1265	523	1733
185	549	1043	1291	551	1071	1261	537	1051	1295	541	1073	1269	529	1083	1271	517	1085	1281	521	1059	1303	507	1093	1283	509	1063	1311	1737
181	935	589	1359	963	559	1361	943	593	1347	965	567	1351	975	569	1339	977	579	1327	951	601	1331	985	581	1317	955	609	1319	1741
177	1345	981	557	1315	983	585	1349	969	565	1323	973	587	1325	961	597	1335	949	599	1357	953	573	1337	939	607	1365	941	577	1745
1753	603	1313	967	605	1341	937	591	1321	971	595	1343	945	583	1353	947	571	1355	957	575	1329	979	561	1363	959	563	1333	987	169
1757	611	859	1413	639	829	1415	619	863	1401	641	837	1405	651	839	1393	653	849	1381	627	871	1385	661	851	1371	631	879	1373	165
1761	1399	657	827	1369	659	855	1403	645	835	1377	649	857	1379	637	867	1389	625	869	1411	629	843	1391	615	877	1419	617	847	161
1765	873	1367	643	875	1395	613	861	1375	647	865	1397	621	853	1407	623	841	1409	633	845	1383	655	831	1417	635	833	1387	663	157
1769	719	1453	711	747	1423	713	727	1457	699	749	1431	703	759	1433	691	761	1443	679	735	1465	683	769	1445	669	739	1473	671	153
1773	697	765	1421	667	767	1449	701	753	1429	675	757	1451	677	745	1461	687	733	1463	709	737	1437	689	723	1471	717	725	1441	149
1777	1467	665	751	1469	693	721	1455	673	755	1459	695	729	1447	705	731	1435	707	741	1439	681	763	1425	715	743	1427	685	771	145
1781	341	913	1629	369	883	1631	349	917	1617	371	891	1621	381	893	1609	383	903	1597	357	925	1601	391	905	1587	361	933	1589	141
1785	1615	387	881	1585	389	909	1619	375	889	1593	379	911	1595	367	921	1605	355	923	1627	359	897	1607	345	931	1635	347	901	137
1789	927	1583	373	929	1611	343	915	1591	377	919	1613	351	907	1623	353	895	1625	363	899	1599	385	885	1633	365	887	1603	393	133
1793	395	1669	819	423	1639	821	403	1673	807	425	1647	811	435	1649	799	437	1659	787	411	1681	791	445	1661	777	415	1689	779	129
1797	805	441	1637	775	443	1665	809	429	1645	783	433	1667	785	421	1677	795	409	1679	817	413	1653	797	399	1687	825	401	1657	125
1801	1683	773	427	1685	801	397	1671	781	431	1675	803	405	1663	813	407	1651	815	417	1655	789	439	1641	823	419	1643	793	447	121
179	231	227	223	219	215	211	207	203	199	195	191	187	183	1749	1751	1755	1759	1763	1767	1771	1775	1779	1783	1787	1791	1795	1799	175

Example 29.4. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{541, 542, \dots, 1380, 1381\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 is given by

1354	1326	1328	1330	1332	1334	1336	1338	1340	1342	1344	1346	1348	1350	567	566	564	562	560	558	556	554	552	550	548	546	544	542	1352
595	1218	1045	620	1232	1030	621	1222	1047	614	1233	1034	616	1238	1035	610	1239	1040	604	1226	1051	606	1243	1041	599	1228	1055	600	1327
593	613	1241	1029	598	1242	1043	615	1235	1033	602	1237	1044	603	1231	1049	608	1225	1050	619	1227	1037	609	1220	1054	623	1221	1039	1329
591	1052	597	1234	1053	611	1219	1046	601	1236	1048	612	1223	1042	617	1224	1036	618	1229	1038	605	1240	1031	622	1230	1032	607	1244	1331
589	1245	640	998	1259	625	999	1249	642	992	1260	629	994	1265	630	988	1266	635	982	1253	646	984	1270	636	977	1255	650	978	1333
587	991	1268	624	976	1269	638	993	1262	628	980	1264	639	981	1258	644	986	1252	645	997	1254	632	987	1247	649	1001	1248	634	1335
585	647	975	1261	648	989	1246	641	979	1263	643	990	1250	637	995	1251	631	996	1256	633	983	1267	626	1000	1257	627	985	1271	1337
583	1056	1099	728	1070	1084	729	1060	1101	722	1071	1088	724	1076	1089	718	1077	1094	712	1064	1105	714	1081	1095	707	1066	1109	708	1339
581	721	1079	1083	706	1080	1097	723	1073	1087	710	1075	1098	711	1069	1103	716	1063	1104	727	1065	1091	717	1058	1108	731	1059	1093	1341
579	1106	705	1072	1107	719	1057	1100	709	1074	1102	720	1061	1096	725	1062	1090	726	1067	1092	713	1078	1085	730	1068	1086	715	1082	1343
577	1110	748	1025	1124	733	1026	1114	750	1019	1125	737	1021	1130	738	1015	1131	743	1009	1118	754	1011	1135	744	1004	1120	758	1005	1345
575	1018	1133	732	1003	1134	746	1020	1127	736	1007	1129	747	1008	1123	752	1013	1117	753	1024	1119	740	1014	1112	757	1028	1113	742	1347
573	755	1002	1126	756	1016	1111	749	1006	1128	751	1017	1115	745	1022	1116	739	1023	1121	741	1010	1132	734	1027	1122	735	1012	1136	1349
571	948	775	1160	962	760	1161	952	777	1154	963	764	1156	968	765	1150	969	770	1144	956	781	1146	973	771	1139	958	785	1140	1351
569	1153	971	759	1138	972	773	1155	965	763	1142	967	774	1143	961	779	1148	955	780	1159	957	767	1149	950	784	1163	951	769	1353
1357	782	1137	964	783	1151	949	776	1141	966	778	1152	953	772	1157	954	766	1158	959	768	1145	970	761	1162	960	762	1147	974	565
1359	786	910	1187	800	895	1188	790	912	1181	801	899	1183	806	900	1177	807	905	1171	794	916	1173	811	906	1166	796	920	1167	563
1361	1180	809	894	1165	810	908	1182	803	898	1169	805	909	1170	799	914	1175	793	915	1186	795	902	1176	788	919	1190	789	904	561
1363	917	1164	802	918	1178	787	911	1168	804	913	1179	791	907	1184	792	901	1185	797	903	1172	808	896	1189	798	897	1174	812	559
1365	840	1207	836	854	1192	837	844	1209	830	855	1196	832	860	1197	826	861	1202	820	848	1213	822	865	1203	815	850	1217	816	557
1367	829	863	1191	814	864	1205	831	857	1195	818	859	1206	819	853	1211	824	847	1212	835	849	1199	825	842	1216	839	843	1201	555
1369	1214	813	856	1215	827	841	1208	817	858	1210	828	845	1204	833	846	1198	834	851	1200	821	862	1193	838	852	1194	823	866	553
1371	651	937	1295	665	922	1296	655	939	1289	666	926	1291	671	927	1285	672	932	1279	659	943	1281	676	933	1274	661	947	1275	551
1373	1288	674	921	1273	675	935	1290	668	925	1277	670	936	1278	664	941	1283	658	942	1294	660	929	1284	653	946	1298	654	931	549
1375	944	1272	667	945	1286	652	938	1276	669	940	1287	656	934	1292	657	928	1293	662	930	1280	673	923	1297	663	924	1282	677	547
1377	678	1315	890	692	1300	891	682	1317	884	693	1304	886	698	1305	880	699	1310	874	686	1321	876	703	1311	869	688	1325	870	545
1379	883	701	1299	868	702	1313	885	695	1303	872	697	1314	873	691	1319	878	685	1320	889	687	1307	879	680	1324	893	681	1309	543
1381	1322	867	694	1323	881	679	1316	871	696	1318	882	683	1312	887	684	1306	888	689	1308	875	700	1301	892	690	1302	877	704	541
570	596	594	592	590	588	586	584	582	580	578	576	574	572	1355	1356	1358	1360	1362	1364	1366	1368	1370	1372	1374	1376	1378	1380	568

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given in Examples 29.3 and 29.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. In both the examples, the magic sums are equal. The magic square of order 27 is **block-wise pandiagonal**. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$\begin{aligned}S_{29 \times 29} &= 27869; & T_{841} &:= 29 \times 27869 = 808201 = 899^2; \\S_{27 \times 27} &= 25947; & T_{729} &:= 27 \times 25947 = 700569 = 837^2; \\Sm_{3 \times 3} &= 2883; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 2883 = 8649 = 93^2.\end{aligned}$$

Both the Examples 29.3 and 29.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (60,899,901)**, i.e., $60^2 + 899^2 = 901^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

29.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 27 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 29, } S_{29 \times 29} := 12789, T_{841} := 370881 = 609^2, E := \{21, 22, \dots, 860, 861\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 29 for consecutive **natural numbers entries**.

Example 29.5. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{21, 22, 23, \dots, 860, 861\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 is given by

834	806	808	810	812	814	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	47	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	832
75	698	525	100	712	510	101	702	527	94	713	514	96	718	515	90	719	520	84	706	531	86	723	521	79	708	535	80	807
73	93	721	509	78	722	523	95	715	513	82	717	524	83	711	529	88	705	530	99	707	517	89	700	534	103	701	519	809
71	532	77	714	533	91	699	526	81	716	528	92	703	522	97	704	516	98	709	518	85	720	511	102	710	512	87	724	811
69	725	120	478	739	105	479	729	122	472	740	109	474	745	110	468	746	115	462	733	126	464	750	116	457	735	130	458	813
67	471	748	104	456	749	118	473	742	108	460	744	119	461	738	124	466	732	125	477	734	112	467	727	129	481	728	114	815
65	127	455	741	128	469	726	121	459	743	123	470	730	117	475	731	111	476	736	113	463	747	106	480	737	107	465	751	817
63	536	579	208	550	564	209	540	581	202	551	568	204	556	569	198	557	574	192	544	585	194	561	575	187	546	589	188	819
61	201	559	563	186	560	577	203	553	567	190	555	578	191	549	583	196	543	584	207	545	571	197	538	588	211	539	573	821
59	586	185	552	587	199	537	580	189	554	582	200	541	576	205	542	570	206	547	572	193	558	565	210	548	566	195	562	823
57	590	228	505	604	213	506	594	230	499	605	217	501	610	218	495	611	223	489	598	234	491	615	224	484	600	238	485	825
55	498	613	212	483	614	226	500	607	216	487	609	227	488	603	232	493	597	233	504	599	220	494	592	237	508	593	222	827
53	235	482	606	236	496	591	229	486	608	231	497	595	225	502	596	219	503	601	221	490	612	214	507	602	215	492	616	829
51	428	255	640	442	240	641	432	257	634	443	244	636	448	245	630	449	250	624	436	261	626	453	251	619	438	265	620	831
49	633	451	239	618	452	253	635	445	243	622	447	254	623	441	259	628	435	260	639	437	247	629	430	264	643	431	249	833
837	262	617	444	263	631	429	256	621	446	258	63	433	252	637	434	246	638	439	248	625	450	241	642	440	242	627	454	45
839	266	390	667	280	375	668	270	392	661	281	379	663	286	380	657	287	385	651	274	396	653	291	386	646	276	400	647	43
841	660	289	374	645	290	388	662	283	378	649	285	389	650	279	394	655	273	395	666	275	382	656	268	399	670	269	384	41
843	397	644	282	398	658	267	391	648	284	393	659	271	387	664	272	381	665	277	383	652	288	376	669	278	377	654	292	39
845	320	687	316	334	672	317	324	689	310	335	676	312	340	677	306	341	682	300	328	693	302	345	683	295	330	697	296	37
847	309	343	671	294	344	685	311	337	675	298	339	686	299	333	691	304	327	692	315	329	679	305	322	696	319	323	681	35
849	694	293	336	695	307	321	688	297	338	690	308	325	684	313	326	678	314	331	680	301	342	673	318	332	674	303	346	33
851	131	417	775	145	402	776	135	419	769	146	406	771	151	407	765	152	412	759	139	423	761	156	413	754	141	427	755	31
853	768	154	401	753	155	415	770	148	405	757	150	416	758	144	421	763	138	422	774	140	409	764	133	426	778	134	411	29
855	424	752	147	425	766	132	418	756	149	420	767	136	414	772	137	408	773	142	410	760	153	403	777	143	404	762	157	27
857	158	795	370	172	780	371	162	797	364	173	784	366	178	785	360	179	790	354	166	801	356	183	791	349	168	805	350	25
859	363	181	779	348	182	793	365	175	783	352	177	794	353	171	799	358	165	800	369	167	787	359	160	804	373	161	789	23
861	802	347	174	803	361	159	796	351	176	798	362	163	792	367	164	786	368	169	788	355	180	781	372	170	782	357	184	21
50	76	74	72	70	68	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	835	836	838	840	842	844	846	848	850	852	854	856	858	860	48

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given in Example 29.5 is with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. This magic square of order 29 is a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The magic square of order 27 is **block-wise pandiagonal**. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{29 \times 29} = 12789; \quad T_{841} := 29 \times 12789 = 370881 = 609^2;$$

$$S_{27 \times 27} = 11907; \quad T_{729} := 27 \times 11907 = 321489 = 567^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 1323; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 1323 = 3969 = 63^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

30 Magic Squares of Order 30

This section brings magic squares of order 30 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10). Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

30.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 28 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 30, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 27000, \quad T_{900} := 810000 = 900^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1797, 1799\} \text{ or } E := \{901/2, 903/2, \dots, 2695/2, 2699/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 30 with different entries. One of them one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 30.1. A *block-wise* magic square of order 30 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1797, 1799\}$ is given by

1	1701	1699	1601	99	299	3	1703	1697	1603	97	297	5	1705	1695	1605	95	295	7	1707	1693	1607	93	293	9	1709	1691	1609	91	291
1499	399	1399	401	501	1201	1497	397	1397	403	503	1203	1495	395	1395	405	505	1205	1493	393	1393	407	507	1207	1491	391	1391	409	509	1209
1199	1101	701	799	999	601	1197	1103	703	797	997	603	1195	1105	705	795	995	605	1193	1107	707	793	993	607	1191	1109	709	791	991	609
899	699	1001	1099	801	901	897	697	1003	1097	803	903	895	695	1005	1095	805	905	893	693	1007	1093	807	907	891	691	1009	1091	809	909
301	1299	499	1301	1401	599	303	1297	497	1303	1403	597	305	1295	495	1305	1405	595	307	1293	493	1307	1407	593	309	1291	491	1309	1409	591
1501	201	101	199	1599	1799	1503	203	103	197	1597	1797	1505	205	105	195	1595	1795	1507	207	107	193	1593	1793	1509	209	109	191	1591	1791
11	1711	1689	1611	89	289	13	1713	1687	1613	87	287	15	1715	1685	1615	85	285	17	1717	1683	1617	83	283	19	1719	1681	1619	81	281
1489	389	1389	411	511	1211	1487	387	1387	413	513	1213	1485	385	1385	415	515	1215	1483	383	1383	417	517	1217	1481	381	1381	419	519	1219
1189	1111	711	789	989	611	1187	1113	713	787	987	613	1185	1115	715	785	985	615	1183	1117	717	783	983	617	1181	1119	719	781	981	619
889	689	1011	1089	811	911	887	687	1013	1087	813	913	885	685	1015	1085	815	915	883	683	1017	1083	817	917	881	681	1019	1081	819	919
311	1289	489	1311	1411	589	313	1287	487	1313	1413	587	315	1285	485	1315	1415	585	317	1283	483	1317	1417	583	319	1281	481	1319	1419	581
1511	211	111	189	1589	1789	1513	213	113	187	1587	1787	1515	215	115	185	1585	1785	1517	217	117	183	1583	1783	1519	219	119	181	1581	1781
21	1721	1679	1621	79	279	23	1723	1677	1623	77	277	25	1725	1675	1625	75	275	27	1727	1673	1627	73	273	29	1729	1671	1629	71	271
1479	379	1379	421	521	1221	1477	377	1377	423	523	1223	1475	375	1375	425	525	1225	1473	373	1373	427	527	1227	1471	371	1371	429	529	1229
1179	1121	721	779	979	621	1177	1123	723	777	977	623	1175	1125	725	775	975	625	1173	1127	727	773	973	627	1171	1129	729	771	971	629
879	679	1021	1079	821	921	877	677	1023	1077	823	923	875	675	1025	1075	825	925	873	673	1027	1073	827	927	871	671	1029	1071	829	929
321	1279	479	1321	1421	579	323	1277	477	1323	1423	577	325	1275	475	1325	1425	575	327	1273	473	1327	1427	573	329	1271	471	1329	1429	571
1521	221	121	179	1579	1779	1523	223	123	177	1577	1777	1525	225	125	175	1575	1775	1527	227	127	173	1573	1773	1529	229	129	171	1571	1771
31	1731	1669	1631	69	269	33	1733	1667	1633	67	267	35	1735	1665	1635	65	265	37	1737	1663	1637	63	263	39	1739	1661	1639	61	261
1469	369	1369	431	531	1231	1467	367	1367	433	533	1233	1465	365	1365	435	535	1235	1463	363	1363	437	537	1237	1461	361	1361	439	539	1239
1169	1131	731	769	969	631	1167	1133	733	767	967	633	1165	1135	735	765	965	635	1163	1137	737	763	963	637	1161	1139	739	761	961	639
869	669	1031	1069	831	931	867	667	1033	1067	833	933	865	665	1035	1065	835	935	863	663	1037	1063	837	937	861	661	1039	1061	839	939
331	1269	469	1331	1431	569	333	1267	467	1333	1433	567	335	1265	465	1335	1435	565	337	1263	463	1337	1437	563	339	1261	461	1339	1439	561
1531	231	131	169	1569	1769	1533	233	133	167	1567	1767	1535	235	135	165	1565	1765	1537	237	137	163	1563	1763	1539	239	139	161	1561	1761
41	1741	1659	1641	59	259	43	1743	1657	1643	57	257	45	1745	1655	1645	55	255	47	1747	1653	1647	53	253	49	1749	1651	1649	51	251
1459	359	1359	441	541	1241	1457	357	1357	443	543	1243	1455	355	1355	445	545	1245	1453	353	1353	447	547	1247	1451	351	1351	449	549	1249
1159	1141	741	759	959	641	1157	1143	743	757	957	643	1155	1145	745	755	955	645	1153	1147	747	753	953	647	1151	1149	749	751	951	649
859	659	1041	1059	841	941	857	657	1043	1057	843	943	855	655	1045	1055	845	945	853	653	1047	1053	847	947	851	651	1049	1051	849	949
341	1259	459	1341	1441	559	343	1257	457	1343	1443	557	345	1255	455	1345	1445	555	347	1253	453	1347	1447	553	349	1251	451	1349	1449	551
1541	241	141	159	1559	1759	1543	243	143	157	1557	1757	1545	245	145	155	1555	1755	1547	247	147	153	1553	1753	1549	249	149	151	1551	1751

Example 30.2. A **block-wise** magic square of order 30 for the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{901/2, 903/2, \dots, 2695/2, 2699/2\}$ is given by

450.5	1300.5	1299.5	1250.5	499.5	599.5	451.5	1301.5	1298.5	1251.5	498.5	598.5	452.5	1302.5	1297.5	1252.5	497.5	597.5	453.5	1303.5	1296.5	1253.5	496.5	596.5	454.5	1304.5	1295.5	1254.5	495.5	595.5
1199.5	649.5	1149.5	650.5	700.5	1050.5	1198.5	648.5	1148.5	651.5	701.5	1051.5	1197.5	647.5	1147.5	652.5	702.5	1052.5	1196.5	646.5	1146.5	653.5	703.5	1053.5	1195.5	645.5	1145.5	654.5	704.5	1054.5
1049.5	1000.5	800.5	849.5	949.5	750.5	1048.5	1001.5	801.5	848.5	948.5	751.5	1047.5	1002.5	802.5	847.5	947.5	752.5	1046.5	1003.5	803.5	846.5	946.5	753.5	1045.5	1004.5	804.5	845.5	945.5	754.5
899.5	799.5	950.5	999.5	850.5	900.5	898.5	798.5	951.5	998.5	851.5	901.5	897.5	797.5	952.5	997.5	852.5	902.5	896.5	796.5	953.5	996.5	853.5	903.5	895.5	795.5	954.5	995.5	854.5	904.5
600.5	1099.5	699.5	1100.5	1150.5	749.5	601.5	1098.5	698.5	1101.5	1151.5	748.5	602.5	1097.5	697.5	1102.5	1152.5	747.5	603.5	1096.5	696.5	1103.5	1153.5	746.5	604.5	1095.5	695.5	1104.5	1154.5	745.5
1200.5	550.5	500.5	549.5	1249.5	1349.5	1201.5	551.5	501.5	548.5	1248.5	1348.5	1202.5	552.5	502.5	547.5	1247.5	1347.5	1203.5	553.5	503.5	546.5	1246.5	1346.5	1204.5	554.5	504.5	545.5	1245.5	1345.5
455.5	1305.5	1294.5	1255.5	494.5	594.5	456.5	1306.5	1293.5	1256.5	493.5	593.5	457.5	1307.5	1292.5	1257.5	492.5	592.5	458.5	1308.5	1291.5	1258.5	491.5	591.5	459.5	1309.5	1290.5	1259.5	490.5	590.5
1194.5	644.5	1144.5	655.5	705.5	1055.5	1193.5	643.5	1143.5	656.5	706.5	1056.5	1192.5	642.5	1142.5	657.5	707.5	1057.5	1191.5	641.5	1141.5	658.5	708.5	1058.5	1190.5	640.5	1140.5	659.5	709.5	1059.5
1044.5	1005.5	805.5	844.5	944.5	755.5	1043.5	1006.5	806.5	843.5	943.5	756.5	1042.5	1007.5	807.5	842.5	942.5	757.5	1041.5	1008.5	808.5	841.5	941.5	758.5	1040.5	1009.5	809.5	840.5	940.5	759.5
894.5	794.5	955.5	994.5	855.5	905.5	893.5	793.5	956.5	993.5	856.5	906.5	892.5	792.5	957.5	992.5	857.5	907.5	891.5	791.5	958.5	991.5	858.5	908.5	890.5	790.5	959.5	990.5	859.5	909.5
605.5	1094.5	694.5	1105.5	1155.5	744.5	606.5	1093.5	693.5	1106.5	1156.5	743.5	607.5	1092.5	692.5	1107.5	1157.5	742.5	608.5	1091.5	691.5	1108.5	1158.5	741.5	609.5	1090.5	690.5	1109.5	1159.5	740.5
1205.5	555.5	505.5	544.5	1244.5	1344.5	1206.5	556.5	506.5	543.5	1243.5	1343.5	1207.5	557.5	507.5	542.5	1242.5	1342.5	1208.5	558.5	508.5	541.5	1241.5	1341.5	1209.5	559.5	509.5	540.5	1240.5	1340.5
460.5	1310.5	1289.5	1260.5	489.5	589.5	461.5	1311.5	1288.5	1261.5	488.5	588.5	462.5	1312.5	1287.5	1262.5	487.5	587.5	463.5	1313.5	1286.5	1263.5	486.5	586.5	464.5	1314.5	1285.5	1264.5	485.5	585.5
1189.5	639.5	1139.5	660.5	710.5	1060.5	1188.5	638.5	1138.5	661.5	711.5	1061.5	1187.5	637.5	1137.5	662.5	712.5	1062.5	1186.5	636.5	1136.5	663.5	713.5	1063.5	1185.5	635.5	1135.5	664.5	714.5	1064.5
1039.5	1010.5	810.5	839.5	939.5	760.5	1038.5	1011.5	811.5	838.5	938.5	761.5	1037.5	1012.5	812.5	837.5	937.5	762.5	1036.5	1013.5	813.5	836.5	936.5	763.5	1035.5	1014.5	814.5	835.5	935.5	764.5
889.5	789.5	960.5	989.5	860.5	910.5	888.5	788.5	961.5	988.5	861.5	911.5	887.5	787.5	962.5	987.5	862.5	912.5	886.5	786.5	963.5	986.5	863.5	913.5	885.5	785.5	964.5	985.5	864.5	914.5
610.5	1089.5	689.5	1110.5	1160.5	739.5	611.5	1088.5	688.5	1111.5	1161.5	738.5	612.5	1087.5	687.5	1112.5	1162.5	737.5	613.5	1086.5	686.5	1113.5	1163.5	736.5	614.5	1085.5	685.5	1114.5	1164.5	735.5
1210.5	560.5	510.5	539.5	1239.5	1339.5	1211.5	561.5	511.5	538.5	1238.5	1338.5	1212.5	562.5	512.5	537.5	1237.5	1337.5	1213.5	563.5	513.5	536.5	1236.5	1336.5	1214.5	564.5	514.5	535.5	1235.5	1335.5
465.5	1315.5	1284.5	1265.5	484.5	584.5	466.5	1316.5	1283.5	1266.5	483.5	583.5	467.5	1317.5	1282.5	1267.5	482.5	582.5	468.5	1318.5	1281.5	1268.5	481.5	581.5	469.5	1319.5	1280.5	1269.5	480.5	580.5
1184.5	634.5	1134.5	665.5	715.5	1065.5	1183.5	633.5	1133.5	666.5	716.5	1066.5	1182.5	632.5	1132.5	667.5	717.5	1067.5	1181.5	631.5	1131.5	668.5	718.5	1068.5	1180.5	630.5	1130.5	669.5	719.5	1069.5
1034.5	1015.5	815.5	834.5	934.5	765.5	1033.5	1016.5	816.5	833.5	933.5	766.5	1032.5	1017.5	817.5	832.5	932.5	767.5	1031.5	1018.5	818.5	831.5	931.5	768.5	1030.5	1019.5	819.5	830.5	930.5	769.5
884.5	784.5	965.5	984.5	865.5	915.5	883.5	783.5	966.5	983.5	866.5	916.5	882.5	782.5	967.5	982.5	867.5	917.5	881.5	781.5	968.5	981.5	868.5	918.5	880.5	780.5	969.5	980.5	869.5	919.5
615.5	1084.5	684.5	1115.5	1165.5	734.5	616.5	1083.5	683.5	1116.5	1166.5	733.5	617.5	1082.5	682.5	1117.5	1167.5	732.5	618.5	1081.5	681.5	1118.5	1168.5	731.5	619.5	1080.5	680.5	1119.5	1169.5	730.5
1215.5	565.5	515.5	534.5	1234.5	1334.5	1216.5	566.5	516.5	533.5	1233.5	1333.5	1217.5	567.5	517.5	532.5	1232.5	1332.5	1218.5	568.5	518.5	531.5	1231.5	1331.5	1219.5	569.5	519.5	530.5	1230.5	1330.5
470.5	1320.5	1279.5	1270.5	479.5	579.5	471.5	1321.5	1278.5	1271.5	478.5	578.5	472.5	1322.5	1277.5	1272.5	477.5	577.5	473.5	1323.5	1276.5	1273.5	476.5	576.5	474.5	1324.5	1275.5	1274.5	475.5	575.5
1179.5	629.5	1129.5	670.5	720.5	1070.5	1178.5	628.5	1128.5	671.5	721.5	1071.5	1177.5	627.5	1127.5	672.5	722.5	1072.5	1176.5	626.5	1126.5	673.5	723.5	1073.5	1175.5	625.5	1125.5	674.5	724.5	1074.5
1029.5	1020.5	820.5	829.5	929.5	770.5	1028.5	1021.5	821.5	828.5	928.5	771.5	1027.5	1022.5	822.5	827.5	927.5	772.5	1026.5	1023.5	823.5	826.5	926.5	773.5	1025.5	1024.5	824.5	825.5	925.5	774.5
879.5	779.5	970.5	979.5	870.5	920.5	878.5	778.5	971.5	978.5	871.5	921.5	877.5	777.5	972.5	977.5	872.5	922.5	876.5	776.5	973.5	976.5	873.5	923.5	875.5	775.5	974.5	975.5	874.5	924.5
620.5	1079.5	679.5	1120.5	1170.5	729.5	621.5	1078.5	678.5	1121.5	1171.5	728.5	622.5	1077.5	677.5	1122.5	1172.5	727.5	623.5	1076.5	676.5	1123.5	1173.5	726.5	624.5	1075.5	675.5	1124.5	1174.5	725.5
1220.5	570.5	520.5	529.5	1229.5	1329.5	1221.5	571.5	521.5	528.5	1228.5	1328.5	1222.5	572.5	522.5	527.5	1227.5	1327.5	1223.5	573.5	523.5	526.5	1226.5	1326.5	1224.5	574.5	524.5	525.5	1225.5	1325.5

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 30 given in Examples 30.1 and 30.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. Both the examples are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 6 are equal sum magic squares. See below the details:

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 27000 = 30^3; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 27000 = 810000 = 900^2 = 30^4;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 5400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 5400 = 32400 = 180^2.$$

The Examples 30.1 and 30.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 30, 30^2, 30^3, 30^4 \rangle$.

30.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 28 given in List (10):

$$(62,960,962) \Rightarrow 962^2 - 62^2 = 960^2, 962 - 62 = 30^2, \text{ Order } 30, S_{30 \times 30} := 30720, T_{900} := 960^2,$$

$$E = \{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\} \text{ or } E = \{1149/2, 1151/2, \dots, 2945/2, 2947/2\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 30 with different entries. One of them is one is with **fraction numbers**. Below are these magic squares.

Example 30.3. A *block-wise* magic square of order 30 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $\{125, 127, \dots, 1921, 1923\}$ is given by

125	701	917	1493	1709	169	745	961	1537	1753	179	755	971	1547	1763	191	767	983	1559	1775	157	733	949	1525	1741	139	715	931	1507	1723
1277	1853	269	485	1061	1321	1897	313	529	1105	1331	1907	323	539	1115	1343	1919	335	551	1127	1309	1885	301	517	1093	1291	1867	283	499	1075
629	845	1421	1637	413	673	889	1465	1681	457	683	899	1475	1691	467	695	911	1487	1703	479	661	877	1453	1669	445	643	859	1435	1651	427
1781	197	773	989	1205	1825	241	817	1033	1249	1835	251	827	1043	1259	1847	263	839	1055	1271	1813	229	805	1021	1237	1795	211	787	1003	1219
1133	1349	1565	341	557	1177	1393	1609	385	601	1187	1403	1619	395	611	1199	1415	1631	407	623	1165	1381	1597	373	589	1147	1363	1579	355	571
181	757	973	1549	1765	137	713	929	1505	1721	193	769	985	1561	1777	151	727	943	1519	1735	165	741	957	1533	1749	133	709	925	1501	1717
1333	1909	325	541	1117	1289	1865	281	497	1073	1345	1921	337	553	1129	1303	1879	295	511	1087	1317	1893	309	525	1101	1285	1861	277	493	1069
685	901	1477	1693	469	641	857	1433	1649	425	697	913	1489	1705	481	655	871	1447	1663	439	669	885	1461	1677	453	637	853	1429	1645	421
1837	253	829	1045	1261	1793	209	785	1001	1217	1849	265	841	1057	1273	1807	223	799	1015	1231	1821	237	813	1029	1245	1789	205	781	997	1213
1189	1405	1621	397	613	1145	1361	1577	353	569	1201	1417	1633	409	625	1159	1375	1591	367	583	1173	1389	1605	381	597	1141	1357	1573	349	565
147	723	939	1515	1731	135	711	927	1503	1719	149	725	941	1517	1733	177	753	969	1545	1761	185	761	977	1553	1769	167	743	959	1535	1751
1299	1875	291	507	1083	1287	1863	279	495	1071	1301	1877	293	509	1085	1329	1905	321	537	1113	1337	1913	329	545	1121	1319	1895	311	527	1103
651	867	1443	1659	435	639	855	1431	1647	423	653	869	1445	1661	437	681	897	1473	1689	465	689	905	1481	1697	473	671	887	1463	1679	455
1803	219	795	1011	1227	1791	207	783	999	1215	1805	221	797	1013	1229	1833	249	825	1041	1257	1841	257	833	1049	1265	1823	239	815	1031	1247
1155	1371	1587	363	579	1143	1359	1575	351	567	1157	1373	1589	365	581	1185	1401	1617	393	609	1193	1409	1625	401	617	1175	1391	1607	383	599
187	763	979	1555	1771	155	731	947	1523	1739	131	707	923	1499	1715	171	747	963	1539	1755	143	719	935	1511	1727	173	749	965	1541	1757
1339	1915	331	547	1123	1307	1883	299	515	1091	1283	1859	275	491	1067	1323	1899	315	531	1107	1295	1871	287	503	1079	1325	1901	317	533	1109
691	907	1483	1699	475	659	875	1451	1667	443	635	851	1427	1643	419	675	891	1467	1683	459	647	863	1439	1655	431	677	893	1469	1685	461
1843	259	835	1051	1267	1811	227	803	1019	1235	1787	203	779	995	1211	1827	243	819	1035	1251	1799	215	791	1007	1223	1829	245	821	1037	1253
1195	1411	1627	403	619	1163	1379	1595	371	587	1139	1355	1571	347	563	1179	1395	1611	387	603	1151	1367	1583	359	575	1181	1397	1613	389	605
161	737	953	1529	1745	189	765	981	1557	1773	145	721	937	1513	1729	129	705	921	1497	1713	183	759	975	1551	1767	153	729	945	1521	1737
1313	1889	305	521	1097	1341	1917	333	549	1125	1297	1873	289	505	1081	1281	1857	273	489	1065	1335	1911	327	543	1119	1305	1881	297	513	1089
665	881	1457	1673	449	693	909	1485	1701	477	649	865	1441	1657	433	633	849	1425	1641	417	687	903	1479	1695	471	657	873	1449	1665	441
1817	233	809	1025	1241	1845	261	837	1053	1269	1801	217	793	1009	1225	1785	201	777	993	1209	1839	255	831	1047	1263	1809	225	801	1017	1233
1169	1385	1601	377	593	1197	1413	1629	405	621	1153	1369	1585	361	577	1137	1353	1569	345	561	1191	1407	1623	399	615	1161	1377	1593	369	585
159	735	951	1527	1743	175	751	967	1543	1759	163	739	955	1531	1747	141	717	933	1509	1725	127	703	919	1495	1711	195	771	987	1563	1779
1311	1887	303	519	1095	1327	1903	319	535	1111	1315	1891	307	523	1099	1293	1869	285	501	1077	1279	1855	271	487	1063	1347	1923	339	555	1131
663	879	1455	1671	447	679	895	1471	1687	463	667	883	1459	1675	451	645	861	1437	1653	429	631	847	1423	1639	415	699	915	1491	1707	483
1815	231	807	1023	1239	1831	247	823	1039	1255	1819	235	811	1027	1243	1797	213	789	1005	1221	1783	199	775	991	1207	1851	267	843	1059	1275
1167	1383	1599	375	591	1183	1399	1615	391	607	1171	1387	1603	379	595	1149	1365	1581	357	573	1135	1351	1567	343	559	1203	1419	1635	411	627

Example 30.4. A **block-wise** magic square of order 30 for the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{1149/2, 1151/2, \dots, 2945/2, 2947/2\}$ is given by

574.5	862.5	970.5	1258.5	1366.5	596.5	884.5	992.5	1280.5	1388.5	601.5	889.5	997.5	1285.5	1393.5	607.5	895.5	1003.5	1291.5	1399.5	590.5	878.5	986.5	1274.5	1382.5	581.5	869.5	977.5	1265.5	1373.5
1150.5	1438.5	646.5	754.5	1042.5	1172.5	1460.5	668.5	776.5	1064.5	1177.5	1465.5	673.5	781.5	1069.5	1183.5	1471.5	679.5	787.5	1075.5	1166.5	1454.5	662.5	770.5	1058.5	1157.5	1445.5	653.5	761.5	1049.5
826.5	934.5	1222.5	1330.5	718.5	848.5	956.5	1244.5	1352.5	740.5	853.5	961.5	1249.5	1357.5	745.5	859.5	967.5	1255.5	1363.5	751.5	842.5	950.5	1238.5	1346.5	734.5	833.5	941.5	1229.5	1337.5	725.5
1402.5	610.5	898.5	1006.5	1114.5	1424.5	632.5	920.5	1028.5	1136.5	1429.5	637.5	925.5	1033.5	1141.5	1435.5	643.5	931.5	1039.5	1147.5	1418.5	626.5	914.5	1022.5	1130.5	1409.5	617.5	905.5	1013.5	1121.5
1078.5	1186.5	1294.5	682.5	790.5	1100.5	1208.5	1316.5	704.5	812.5	1105.5	1213.5	1321.5	709.5	817.5	1111.5	1219.5	1327.5	715.5	823.5	1094.5	1202.5	1310.5	698.5	806.5	1085.5	1193.5	1301.5	689.5	797.5
602.5	890.5	998.5	1286.5	1394.5	580.5	868.5	976.5	1264.5	1372.5	608.5	896.5	1004.5	1292.5	1400.5	587.5	875.5	983.5	1271.5	1379.5	594.5	882.5	990.5	1278.5	1386.5	578.5	866.5	974.5	1262.5	1370.5
1178.5	1466.5	674.5	782.5	1070.5	1156.5	1444.5	652.5	760.5	1048.5	1184.5	1472.5	680.5	788.5	1076.5	1163.5	1451.5	659.5	767.5	1055.5	1170.5	1458.5	666.5	774.5	1062.5	1154.5	1442.5	650.5	758.5	1046.5
854.5	962.5	1250.5	1358.5	746.5	832.5	940.5	1228.5	1336.5	724.5	860.5	968.5	1256.5	1364.5	752.5	839.5	947.5	1235.5	1343.5	731.5	846.5	954.5	1242.5	1350.5	738.5	830.5	938.5	1226.5	1334.5	722.5
1430.5	638.5	926.5	1034.5	1142.5	1408.5	616.5	904.5	1012.5	1120.5	1436.5	644.5	932.5	1040.5	1148.5	1415.5	623.5	911.5	1019.5	1127.5	1422.5	630.5	918.5	1026.5	1134.5	1406.5	614.5	902.5	1010.5	1118.5
1106.5	1214.5	1322.5	710.5	818.5	1084.5	1192.5	1300.5	688.5	796.5	1112.5	1220.5	1328.5	716.5	824.5	1091.5	1199.5	1307.5	695.5	803.5	1098.5	1206.5	1314.5	702.5	810.5	1082.5	1190.5	1298.5	686.5	794.5
585.5	873.5	981.5	1269.5	1377.5	579.5	867.5	975.5	1263.5	1371.5	586.5	874.5	982.5	1270.5	1378.5	600.5	888.5	996.5	1284.5	1392.5	604.5	892.5	1000.5	1288.5	1396.5	595.5	883.5	991.5	1279.5	1387.5
1161.5	1449.5	657.5	765.5	1053.5	1155.5	1443.5	651.5	759.5	1047.5	1162.5	1450.5	658.5	766.5	1054.5	1176.5	1464.5	672.5	780.5	1068.5	1180.5	1468.5	676.5	784.5	1072.5	1171.5	1459.5	667.5	775.5	1063.5
837.5	945.5	1233.5	1341.5	729.5	831.5	939.5	1227.5	1335.5	723.5	838.5	946.5	1234.5	1342.5	730.5	852.5	960.5	1248.5	1356.5	744.5	856.5	964.5	1252.5	1360.5	748.5	847.5	955.5	1243.5	1351.5	739.5
1413.5	621.5	909.5	1017.5	1125.5	1407.5	615.5	903.5	1011.5	1119.5	1414.5	622.5	910.5	1018.5	1126.5	1428.5	636.5	924.5	1032.5	1140.5	1432.5	640.5	928.5	1036.5	1144.5	1423.5	631.5	919.5	1027.5	1135.5
1089.5	1197.5	1305.5	693.5	801.5	1083.5	1191.5	1299.5	687.5	795.5	1090.5	1198.5	1306.5	694.5	802.5	1104.5	1212.5	1320.5	708.5	816.5	1108.5	1216.5	1324.5	712.5	820.5	1099.5	1207.5	1315.5	703.5	811.5
605.5	893.5	1001.5	1289.5	1397.5	589.5	877.5	985.5	1273.5	1381.5	577.5	865.5	973.5	1261.5	1369.5	597.5	885.5	993.5	1281.5	1389.5	583.5	871.5	979.5	1267.5	1375.5	598.5	886.5	994.5	1282.5	1390.5
1181.5	1469.5	677.5	785.5	1073.5	1165.5	1453.5	661.5	769.5	1057.5	1153.5	1441.5	649.5	757.5	1045.5	1173.5	1461.5	669.5	777.5	1065.5	1159.5	1447.5	655.5	763.5	1051.5	1174.5	1462.5	670.5	778.5	1066.5
857.5	965.5	1253.5	1361.5	749.5	841.5	949.5	1237.5	1345.5	733.5	829.5	937.5	1225.5	1333.5	721.5	849.5	957.5	1245.5	1353.5	741.5	835.5	943.5	1231.5	1339.5	727.5	850.5	958.5	1246.5	1354.5	742.5
1433.5	641.5	929.5	1037.5	1145.5	1417.5	625.5	913.5	1021.5	1129.5	1405.5	613.5	901.5	1009.5	1117.5	1425.5	633.5	921.5	1029.5	1137.5	1411.5	619.5	907.5	1015.5	1123.5	1426.5	634.5	922.5	1030.5	1138.5
1109.5	1217.5	1325.5	713.5	821.5	1093.5	1201.5	1309.5	697.5	805.5	1081.5	1189.5	1297.5	685.5	793.5	1101.5	1209.5	1317.5	705.5	813.5	1087.5	1195.5	1303.5	691.5	799.5	1102.5	1210.5	1318.5	706.5	814.5
592.5	880.5	988.5	1276.5	1384.5	606.5	894.5	1002.5	1290.5	1398.5	584.5	872.5	980.5	1268.5	1376.5	576.5	864.5	972.5	1260.5	1368.5	603.5	891.5	999.5	1287.5	1395.5	588.5	876.5	984.5	1272.5	1380.5
1168.5	1456.5	664.5	772.5	1060.5	1182.5	1470.5	678.5	786.5	1074.5	1160.5	1448.5	656.5	764.5	1052.5	1152.5	1440.5	648.5	756.5	1044.5	1179.5	1467.5	675.5	783.5	1071.5	1164.5	1452.5	660.5	768.5	1056.5
844.5	952.5	1240.5	1348.5	736.5	858.5	966.5	1254.5	1362.5	750.5	836.5	944.5	1232.5	1340.5	728.5	828.5	936.5	1224.5	1332.5	720.5	855.5	963.5	1251.5	1359.5	747.5	840.5	948.5	1236.5	1344.5	732.5
1420.5	628.5	916.5	1024.5	1132.5	1434.5	642.5	930.5	1038.5	1146.5	1412.5	620.5	908.5	1016.5	1124.5	1404.5	612.5	900.5	1008.5	1116.5	1431.5	639.5	927.5	1035.5	1143.5	1416.5	624.5	912.5	1020.5	1128.5
1096.5	1204.5	1312.5	700.5	808.5	1110.5	1218.5	1326.5	714.5	822.5	1088.5	1196.5	1304.5	692.5	800.5	1080.5	1188.5	1296.5	684.5	792.5	1107.5	1215.5	1323.5	711.5	819.5	1092.5	1200.5	1308.5	696.5	804.5
591.5	879.5	987.5	1275.5	1383.5	599.5	887.5	995.5	1283.5	1391.5	593.5	881.5	989.5	1277.5	1385.5	582.5	870.5	978.5	1266.5	1374.5	575.5	863.5	971.5	1259.5	1367.5	569.5	897.5	1005.5	1293.5	1401.5
1167.5	1455.5	663.5	771.5	1059.5	1175.5	1463.5	671.5	779.5	1067.5	1169.5	1457.5	665.5	773.5	1061.5	1158.5	1446.5	654.5	762.5	1050.5	1151.5	1439.5	647.5	755.5	1043.5	1185.5	1473.5	681.5	789.5	1077.5
843.5	951.5	1239.5	1347.5	735.5	851.5	959.5	1247.5	1355.5	743.5	845.5	953.5	1241.5	1349.5	737.5	834.5	942.5	1230.5	1338.5	726.5	827.5	935.5	1223.5	1331.5	719.5	861.5	969.5	1257.5	1365.5	753.5
1419.5	627.5	915.5	1023.5	1131.5	1427.5	635.5	923.5	1031.5	1139.5	1421.5	629.5	917.5	1025.5	1133.5	1410.5	618.5	906.5	1014.5	1122.5	1403.5	611.5	899.5	1007.5	1115.5	1437.5	645.5	933.5	1041.5	1149.5
1095.5	1203.5	1311.5	699.5	807.5	1103.5	1211.5	1319.5	707.5	815.5	1097.5	1205.5	1313.5	701.5	809.5	1086.5	1194.5	1302.5	690.5	798.5	1079.5	1187.5	1295.5	683.5	791.5	1113.5	1221.5	1329.5	717.5	825.5

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 30 given in Examples 30.3 and 30.4 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. Both the examples are with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 30720; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 30720 = 921600 = 960^2.$$

Both the Examples 30.3 and 30.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (62,960,962)**, i.e., $62^2 + 960^2 = 962^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

30.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 28 given in List (15):

Order 30, $\mathbf{S}_{30 \times 30} := 14520$, $\mathbf{T}_{900} := 435600 = 660^2$, $E := \{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 30 with **fraction numbers** entries.

Example 30.5. A **block-wise** magic square of order 30 for the **consecutive fraction numbers** entries $\{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$ is given by

34.5	884.5	883.5	834.5	83.5	183.5	35.5	885.5	882.5	835.5	82.5	182.5	36.5	886.5	881.5	836.5	81.5	181.5	37.5	887.5	880.5	837.5	80.5	180.5	38.5	888.5	879.5	838.5	79.5	179.5
783.5	233.5	733.5	234.5	284.5	634.5	782.5	232.5	732.5	235.5	285.5	635.5	781.5	231.5	731.5	236.5	286.5	636.5	780.5	230.5	730.5	237.5	287.5	637.5	779.5	229.5	729.5	238.5	288.5	638.5
633.5	584.5	384.5	433.5	533.5	334.5	632.5	585.5	385.5	432.5	532.5	335.5	631.5	586.5	386.5	431.5	531.5	336.5	630.5	587.5	387.5	430.5	530.5	337.5	629.5	588.5	388.5	429.5	529.5	338.5
483.5	383.5	534.5	583.5	434.5	484.5	482.5	382.5	535.5	582.5	435.5	485.5	481.5	381.5	536.5	581.5	436.5	486.5	480.5	380.5	537.5	580.5	437.5	487.5	479.5	379.5	538.5	579.5	438.5	488.5
184.5	683.5	283.5	684.5	734.5	333.5	185.5	682.5	282.5	685.5	735.5	332.5	186.5	681.5	281.5	686.5	736.5	331.5	187.5	680.5	280.5	687.5	737.5	330.5	188.5	679.5	279.5	688.5	738.5	329.5
784.5	134.5	84.5	133.5	833.5	933.5	785.5	135.5	85.5	132.5	832.5	932.5	786.5	136.5	86.5	131.5	831.5	931.5	787.5	137.5	87.5	130.5	830.5	930.5	788.5	138.5	88.5	129.5	829.5	929.5
39.5	889.5	878.5	839.5	78.5	178.5	40.5	890.5	877.5	840.5	77.5	177.5	41.5	891.5	876.5	841.5	76.5	176.5	42.5	892.5	875.5	842.5	75.5	175.5	43.5	893.5	874.5	843.5	74.5	174.5
778.5	228.5	728.5	239.5	289.5	639.5	777.5	227.5	727.5	240.5	290.5	640.5	776.5	226.5	726.5	241.5	291.5	641.5	775.5	225.5	725.5	242.5	292.5	642.5	774.5	224.5	724.5	243.5	293.5	643.5
628.5	589.5	389.5	428.5	528.5	339.5	627.5	590.5	390.5	427.5	527.5	340.5	626.5	591.5	391.5	426.5	526.5	341.5	625.5	592.5	392.5	425.5	525.5	342.5	624.5	593.5	393.5	424.5	524.5	343.5
478.5	378.5	539.5	578.5	439.5	489.5	477.5	377.5	540.5	577.5	440.5	490.5	476.5	376.5	541.5	576.5	441.5	491.5	475.5	375.5	542.5	575.5	442.5	492.5	474.5	374.5	543.5	574.5	443.5	493.5
189.5	678.5	278.5	689.5	739.5	328.5	190.5	677.5	277.5	690.5	740.5	327.5	191.5	676.5	276.5	691.5	741.5	326.5	192.5	675.5	275.5	692.5	742.5	325.5	193.5	674.5	274.5	693.5	743.5	324.5
789.5	139.5	89.5	128.5	828.5	928.5	790.5	140.5	90.5	127.5	827.5	927.5	791.5	141.5	91.5	126.5	826.5	926.5	792.5	142.5	92.5	125.5	825.5	925.5	793.5	143.5	93.5	124.5	824.5	924.5
44.5	894.5	873.5	844.5	73.5	173.5	45.5	895.5	872.5	845.5	72.5	172.5	46.5	896.5	871.5	846.5	71.5	171.5	47.5	897.5	870.5	847.5	70.5	170.5	48.5	898.5	869.5	848.5	69.5	169.5
773.5	223.5	723.5	244.5	294.5	644.5	772.5	222.5	722.5	245.5	295.5	645.5	771.5	221.5	721.5	246.5	296.5	646.5	770.5	220.5	720.5	247.5	297.5	647.5	769.5	219.5	719.5	248.5	298.5	648.5
623.5	594.5	394.5	423.5	523.5	344.5	622.5	595.5	395.5	422.5	522.5	345.5	621.5	596.5	396.5	421.5	521.5	346.5	620.5	597.5	397.5	420.5	520.5	347.5	619.5	598.5	398.5	419.5	519.5	348.5
473.5	373.5	544.5	573.5	444.5	494.5	472.5	372.5	545.5	572.5	445.5	495.5	471.5	371.5	546.5	571.5	446.5	496.5	470.5	370.5	547.5	570.5	447.5	497.5	469.5	369.5	548.5	569.5	448.5	498.5
194.5	673.5	273.5	694.5	744.5	323.5	195.5	672.5	272.5	695.5	745.5	322.5	196.5	671.5	271.5	696.5	746.5	321.5	197.5	670.5	270.5	697.5	747.5	320.5	198.5	669.5	269.5	698.5	748.5	319.5
794.5	144.5	94.5	123.5	823.5	923.5	795.5	145.5	95.5	122.5	822.5	922.5	796.5	146.5	96.5	121.5	821.5	921.5	797.5	147.5	97.5	120.5	820.5	920.5	798.5	148.5	98.5	119.5	819.5	919.5
49.5	899.5	868.5	849.5	68.5	168.5	50.5	900.5	867.5	850.5	67.5	167.5	51.5	901.5	866.5	851.5	66.5	166.5	52.5	902.5	865.5	852.5	65.5	165.5	53.5	903.5	864.5	853.5	64.5	164.5
768.5	218.5	718.5	249.5	299.5	649.5	767.5	217.5	717.5	250.5	300.5	650.5	766.5	216.5	716.5	251.5	301.5	651.5	765.5	215.5	715.5	252.5	302.5	652.5	764.5	214.5	714.5	253.5	303.5	653.5
618.5	599.5	399.5	418.5	518.5	349.5	617.5	600.5	400.5	417.5	517.5	350.5	616.5	601.5	401.5	416.5	516.5	351.5	615.5	602.5	402.5	415.5	515.5	352.5	614.5	603.5	403.5	414.5	514.5	353.5
468.5	368.5	549.5	568.5	449.5	499.5	467.5	367.5	550.5	567.5	450.5	500.5	466.5	366.5	551.5	566.5	451.5	501.5	465.5	365.5	552.5	565.5	452.5	502.5	464.5	364.5	553.5	564.5	453.5	503.5
199.5	668.5	268.5	699.5	749.5	318.5	200.5	667.5	267.5	700.5	750.5	317.5	201.5	666.5	266.5	701.5	751.5	316.5	202.5	665.5	265.5	702.5	752.5	315.5	203.5	664.5	264.5	703.5	753.5	314.5
799.5	149.5	99.5	118.5	818.5	918.5	800.5	150.5	100.5	117.5	817.5	917.5	801.5	151.5	101.5	116.5	816.5	916.5	802.5	152.5	102.5	115.5	815.5	915.5	803.5	153.5	103.5	114.5	814.5	914.5
54.5	904.5	863.5	854.5	63.5	163.5	55.5	905.5	862.5	855.5	62.5	162.5	56.5	906.5	861.5	856.5	61.5	161.5	57.5	907.5	860.5	857.5	60.5	160.5	58.5	908.5	859.5	858.5	59.5	159.5
763.5	213.5	713.5	254.5	304.5	654.5	762.5	212.5	712.5	255.5	305.5	655.5	761.5	211.5	711.5	256.5	306.5	656.5	760.5	210.5	710.5	257.5	307.5	657.5	759.5	209.5	709.5	258.5	308.5	658.5
613.5	604.5	404.5	413.5	513.5	354.5	612.5	605.5	405.5	412.5	512.5	355.5	611.5	606.5	406.5	411.5	511.5	356.5	610.5	607.5	407.5	410.5	510.5	357.5	609.5	608.5	408.5	409.5	509.5	358.5
463.5	363.5	554.5	563.5	454.5	504.5	462.5	362.5	555.5	562.5	455.5	505.5	461.5	361.5	556.5	561.5	456.5	506.5	460.5	360.5	557.5	560.5	457.5	507.5	459.5	359.5	558.5	559.5	458.5	508.5
204.5	663.5	263.5	704.5	754.5	313.5	205.5	662.5	262.5	705.5	755.5	312.5	206.5	661.5	261.5	706.5	756.5	311.5	207.5	660.5	260.5	707.5	757.5	310.5	208.5	659.5	259.5	708.5	758.5	309.5
804.5	154.5	104.5	113.5	813.5	913.5	805.5	155.5	105.5	112.5	812.5	912.5	806.5	156.5	106.5	111.5	811.5	911.5	807.5	157.5	107.5	110.5	810.5	910.5	808.5	158.5	108.5	109.5	809.5	909.5

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 30 given in Examples 30.5 is with **consecutive fraction numbers** entries. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 14520; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 14520 = 435600 = 660^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2904; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2904 = 17424 = 132^2.$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

31 Magic Squares of Order 31

This section brings magic squares of order 31 in five different ways based on the Lists given in (15), (12) and (10).

31.1 Uniformity Property

Let's consider the expression 29 given in List (8):

$$\text{Order } 31, \quad S_{31 \times 31} := 29791, \quad T_{961} := 923521 = 961^2, \quad E := \{1, 3, \dots, 1919, 1921\} \text{ or } E := \{481, 482, \dots, 1439, 1441\}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 31 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 31.1. For the *consecutive odd numbers entries* $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 1919, 1921\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 is given by

63	89	81	65	1885	1893	61	1877	93	117	1913	1909	69	1917	113	1869	105	77	101	109	85	1905	1901	1881	1873	1921	97	1897	1889	73	1863
1871	1743	1723	159	1711	1707	139	1731	1719	1699	143	131	1735	163	1727	155	147	173	171	1739	1715	127	1691	151	167	1695	135	1703	123	1747	51
1875	165	1475	1129	279	1503	1099	281	1483	1133	267	1505	1107	271	1515	1109	259	1517	1119	247	1491	1141	251	1525	1121	237	1495	1149	239	1757	47
1899	137	265	1521	1097	235	1523	1125	269	1509	1105	243	1513	1127	245	1501	1137	255	1489	1139	277	1493	1113	257	1479	1147	285	1481	1117	1785	23
103	1745	1143	233	1507	1145	261	1477	1131	241	1511	1135	263	1485	1123	273	1487	1111	275	1497	1115	249	1519	1101	283	1499	1103	253	1527	177	1819
1903	1741	1529	319	1035	1557	289	1037	1537	323	1023	1559	297	1027	1569	299	1015	1571	309	1003	1545	331	1007	1579	311	993	1549	339	995	181	19
71	125	1021	1575	287	991	1577	315	1025	1563	295	999	1567	317	1001	1555	327	1011	1543	329	1033	1547	303	1013	1533	337	1041	1535	307	1797	1851
111	1733	333	989	1561	335	1017	1531	321	997	1565	325	1019	1539	313	1029	1541	301	1031	1551	305	1005	1573	291	1039	1553	293	1009	1581	189	1811
1879	1693	1151	1237	495	1179	1207	497	1159	1241	483	1181	1215	487	1191	1217	475	1193	1227	463	1167	1249	467	1201	1229	453	1171	1257	455	229	43
67	129	481	1197	1205	451	1199	1233	485	1185	1213	459	1189	1235	461	1177	1245	471	1165	1247	493	1169	1221	473	1155	1255	501	1157	1225	1793	1855
1883	1697	1251	449	1183	1253	477	1153	1239	457	1187	1243	479	1161	1231	489	1163	1219	491	1173	1223	465	1195	1209	499	1175	1211	469	1203	225	39
115	133	1259	535	1089	1287	505	1091	1267	539	1077	1289	513	1081	1299	515	1069	1301	525	1057	1275	547	1061	1309	527	1047	1279	555	1049	1789	1807
119	161	1075	1305	503	1045	1307	531	1079	1293	511	1053	1297	533	1055	1285	543	1065	1273	545	1087	1277	519	1067	1263	553	1095	1265	523	1761	1803
1895	1729	549	1043	1291	551	1071	1261	537	1051	1295	541	1073	1269	529	1083	1271	517	1085	1281	521	1059	1303	507	1093	1283	509	1063	1311	193	27
79	145	935	589	1359	963	559	1361	943	593	1347	965	567	1351	975	569	1339	977	579	1327	951	601	1331	985	581	1317	955	609	1319	1777	1843
95	1737	1345	981	557	1315	983	585	1349	969	565	1323	973	587	1325	961	597	1335	949	599	1357	953	573	1337	939	607	1365	941	577	185	1827
91	1725	603	1313	967	605	1341	937	591	1321	971	595	1343	945	583	1353	947	571	1355	957	575	1329	979	561	1363	959	563	1333	987	197	1831
87	149	611	859	1413	639	829	1415	619	863	1401	641	837	1405	651	839	1393	653	849	1381	627	871	1385	661	851	1371	631	879	1373	1773	1835
1911	169	1399	657	827	1369	659	855	1403	645	835	1377	649	857	1379	637	867	1389	625	869	1411	629	843	1391	615	877	1419	617	847	1753	11
99	153	873	1367	643	875	1395	613	861	1375	647	865	1397	621	853	1407	623	841	1409	633	845	1383	655	831	1417	635	833	1387	663	1769	1823
1865	157	719	1453	711	747	1423	713	727	1457	699	749	1431	703	759	1433	691	761	1443	679	735	1465	683	769	1445	669	739	1473	671	1765	57
1891	1701	697	765	1421	667	767	1449	701	753	1429	675	757	1451	677	745	1461	687	733	1463	709	737	1437	689	723	1471	717	725	1441	221	31
83	1709	1467	665	751	1469	693	721	1455	673	755	1459	695	729	1447	705	731	1435	707	741	1439	681	763	1425	715	743	1427	685	771	213	1839
1915	1721	341	913	1629	369	883	1631	349	917	1617	371	891	1621	381	893	1609	383	903	1597	357	925	1601	391	905	1587	361	933	1589	201	7
1867	1717	1615	387	881	1585	389	909	1619	375	889	1593	379	911	1595	367	921	1605	355	923	1627	359	897	1607	345	931	1635	347	901	205	55
1887	1713	927	1583	373	929	1611	343	915	1591	377	919	1613	351	907	1623	353	895	1625	363	899	1599	385	885	1633	365	887	1603	393	209	35
107	1705	395	1669	819	423	1639	821	403	1673	807	425	1647	811	435	1649	799	437	1659	787	411	1681	791	445	1661	777	415	1689	779	217	1815
75	141	805	441	1637	775	443	1665	809	429	1645	783	433	1667	785	421	1677	795	409	1679	817	413	1653	797	399	1687	825	401	1657	1781	1847
1907	121	1683	773	427	1685	801	397	1671	781	431	1675	803	405	1663	813	407	1651	815	417	1655	789	439	1641	823	419	1643	793	447	1801	15
1919	175	199	1763	211	215	1783	191	203	223	1779	1791	187	1759	195	1767	1775	1749	1751	183	207	1795	231	1771	1755	227	1787	219	1799	179	3
59	1833	1841	1857	37	29	1861	45	1829	1805	9	13	1853	5	1809	53	1817	1845	1821	1813	1837	17	21	41	49	1	1825	25	33	1849	1859

Example 31.2. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{481, 482, 483, \dots, 1440, 1441\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 is given by

512	525	521	513	1423	1427	511	1419	527	539	1437	1435	515	1439	537	1415	533	519	531	535	523	1433	1431	1421	1417	1441	529	1429	1425	517	1412
1416	1352	1342	560	1336	1334	550	1346	1340	1330	552	546	1348	562	1344	558	554	567	566	1350	1338	544	1326	556	564	1328	548	1332	542	1354	506
1418	563	1218	1045	620	1232	1030	621	1222	1047	614	1233	1034	616	1238	1035	610	1239	1040	604	1226	1051	606	1243	1041	599	1228	1055	600	1359	504
1430	549	613	1241	1029	598	1242	1043	615	1235	1033	602	1237	1044	603	1231	1049	608	1225	1050	619	1227	1037	609	1220	1054	623	1221	1039	1373	492
532	1353	1052	597	1234	1053	611	1219	1046	601	1236	1048	612	1223	1042	617	1224	1036	618	1229	1038	605	1240	1031	622	1230	1032	607	1244	569	1390
1432	1351	1245	640	998	1259	625	999	1249	642	992	1260	629	994	1265	630	988	1266	635	982	1253	646	984	1270	636	977	1255	650	978	571	490
516	543	991	1268	624	976	1269	638	993	1262	628	980	1264	639	981	1258	644	986	1252	645	997	1254	632	987	1247	649	1001	1248	634	1379	1406
536	1347	647	975	1261	648	989	1246	641	979	1263	643	990	1250	637	995	1251	631	996	1256	633	983	1267	626	1000	1257	627	985	1271	575	1386
1420	1327	1056	1099	728	1070	1084	729	1060	1101	722	1071	1088	724	1076	1089	718	1077	1094	712	1064	1105	714	1081	1095	707	1066	1109	708	595	502
514	545	721	1079	1083	706	1080	1097	723	1073	1087	710	1075	1098	711	1069	1103	716	1063	1104	727	1065	1091	717	1058	1108	731	1059	1093	1377	1408
1422	1329	1106	705	1072	1107	719	1057	1100	709	1074	1102	720	1061	1096	725	1062	1090	726	1067	1092	713	1078	1085	730	1068	1086	715	1082	593	500
538	547	1110	748	1025	1124	733	1026	1114	750	1019	1125	737	1021	1130	738	1015	1131	743	1009	1118	754	1011	1135	744	1004	1120	758	1005	1375	1384
540	561	1018	1133	732	1003	1134	746	1020	1127	736	1007	1129	747	1008	1123	752	1013	1117	753	1024	1119	740	1014	1112	757	1028	1113	742	1361	1382
1428	1345	755	1002	1126	756	1016	1111	749	1006	1128	751	1017	1115	745	1022	1116	739	1023	1121	741	1010	1132	734	1027	1122	735	1012	1136	577	494
520	553	948	775	1160	962	760	1161	952	777	1154	963	764	1156	968	765	1150	969	770	1144	956	781	1146	973	771	1139	958	785	1140	1369	1402
528	1349	1153	971	759	1138	972	773	1155	965	763	1142	967	774	1143	961	779	1148	955	780	1159	957	767	1149	950	784	1163	951	769	573	1394
526	1343	782	1137	964	783	1151	949	776	1141	966	778	1152	953	772	1157	954	766	1158	959	768	1145	970	761	1162	960	762	1147	974	579	1396
524	555	786	910	1187	800	895	1188	790	912	1181	801	899	1183	806	900	1177	807	905	1171	794	916	1173	811	906	1166	796	920	1167	1367	1398
1436	565	1180	809	894	1165	810	908	1182	803	898	1169	805	909	1170	799	914	1175	793	915	1186	795	902	1176	788	919	1190	789	904	1357	486
530	557	917	1164	802	918	1178	787	911	1168	804	913	1179	791	907	1184	792	901	1185	797	903	1172	808	896	1189	798	897	1174	812	1365	1392
1413	559	840	1207	836	854	1192	837	844	1209	830	855	1196	832	860	1197	826	861	1202	820	848	1213	822	865	1203	815	850	1217	816	1363	509
1426	1331	829	863	1191	814	864	1205	831	857	1195	818	859	1206	819	853	1211	824	847	1212	835	849	1199	825	842	1216	839	843	1201	591	496
522	1335	1214	813	856	1215	827	841	1208	817	858	1210	828	845	1204	833	846	1198	834	851	1200	821	862	1193	838	852	1194	823	866	587	1400
1438	1341	651	937	1295	665	922	1296	655	939	1289	666	926	1291	671	927	1285	672	932	1279	659	943	1281	676	933	1274	661	947	1275	581	484
1414	1339	1288	674	921	1273	675	935	1290	668	925	1277	670	936	1278	664	941	1283	658	942	1294	660	929	1284	653	946	1298	654	931	583	508
1424	1337	944	1272	667	945	1286	652	938	1276	669	940	1287	656	934	1292	657	928	1293	662	930	1280	673	923	1297	663	924	1282	677	585	498
534	1333	678	1315	890	692	1300	891	682	1317	884	693	1304	886	698	1305	880	699	1310	874	686	1321	876	703	1311	869	688	1325	870	589	1388
518	551	883	701	1299	868	702	1313	885	695	1303	872	697	1314	873	691	1319	878	685	1320	889	687	1307	879	680	1324	893	681	1309	1371	1404
1434	541	1322	867	694	1323	881	679	1316	871	696	1318	882	683	1312	887	684	1306	888	689	1308	875	700	1301	892	690	1302	877	704	1381	488
1440	568	580	1362	586	588	1372	576	582	592	1370	1376	574	1360	578	1364	1368	1355	1356	572	584	1378	596	1366	1358	594	1374	590	1380	570	482
510	1397	1401	1409	499	495	1411	503	1395	1383	485	487	1407	483	1385	507	1389	1403	1391	1387	1399	489	491	501	505	481	1393	493	497	1405	1410

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 31 given in Examples 31.1 and 31.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 27 is with blocks of orders 3. These blocks are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below details.

$$\begin{aligned} S_{31 \times 31} &:= 29791; & T_{961} &:= 31 \times 29791 = 923521 = 961^2; \\ S_{29 \times 29} &:= 27869; & T_{625} &:= 29 \times 27869 = 808201 = 899^2; \\ S_{27 \times 27} &:= 25947; & T_{625} &:= 27 \times 25947 = 700569 = 837^2; \\ Sm_{3 \times 3} &:= 2883; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 2883 = 8649 = 93^2 \end{aligned}$$

The Examples 31.1 and 31.2 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 31, 31^2, 31^3, 31^4 \rangle$.

31.2 Pythagorean Triple

Let's consider the expression 29 given in List (10):

$$\begin{aligned} (64, 1023, 1025) &\Rightarrow 1025^2 - 64^2 = 1023^2, \quad 1025 - 64 = 31^2, \quad \text{Order } 31, \quad S_{31 \times 31} := 33759, \quad T_{961} := 1023^2, \\ E &= \{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\} \text{ or } E = \{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\} \end{aligned}$$

The above expression lead us to two magic squares of order 31 with different entries. Below are these magic squares.

Example 31.3. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{129, 131, \dots, 2047, 2049\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 is given by

191	217	209	193	2013	2021	189	2005	221	245	2041	2037	197	2045	241	1997	233	205	229	237	213	2033	2029	2009	2001	2049	225	2025	2017	201	1991
1999	1871	1851	287	1839	1835	267	1859	1847	1827	271	259	1863	291	1855	283	275	301	299	1867	1843	255	1819	279	295	1823	263	1831	251	1875	179
2003	293	1603	1257	407	1631	1227	409	1611	1261	395	1633	1235	399	1643	1237	387	1645	1247	375	1619	1269	379	1653	1249	365	1623	1277	367	1885	175
2027	265	393	1649	1225	363	1651	1253	397	1637	1233	371	1641	1255	373	1629	1265	383	1617	1267	405	1621	1241	385	1607	1275	413	1609	1245	1913	151
231	1873	1271	361	1635	1273	389	1605	1259	369	1639	1263	391	1613	1251	401	1615	1239	403	1625	1243	377	1647	1229	411	1627	1231	381	1655	305	1947
2031	1869	1657	447	1163	1685	417	1165	1665	451	1151	1687	425	1155	1697	427	1143	1699	437	1131	1673	459	1135	1707	439	1121	1677	467	1123	309	147
199	253	1149	1703	415	1119	1705	443	1153	1691	423	1127	1695	445	1129	1683	455	1139	1671	457	1161	1675	431	1141	1661	465	1169	1663	435	1925	1979
239	1861	461	1117	1689	463	1145	1659	449	1125	1693	453	1147	1667	441	1157	1669	429	1159	1679	433	1133	1701	419	1167	1681	421	1137	1709	317	1939
2007	1821	1279	1365	623	1307	1335	625	1287	1369	611	1309	1343	615	1319	1345	603	1321	1355	591	1295	1377	595	1329	1357	581	1299	1385	583	357	171
195	257	609	1325	1333	579	1327	1361	613	1313	1341	587	1317	1363	589	1305	1373	599	1293	1375	621	1297	1349	601	1283	1383	629	1285	1353	1921	1983
2011	1825	1379	577	1311	1381	605	1281	1367	585	1315	1371	607	1289	1359	617	1291	1347	619	1301	1351	593	1323	1337	627	1303	1339	597	1331	353	167
243	261	1387	663	1217	1415	633	1219	1395	667	1205	1417	641	1209	1427	643	1197	1429	653	1185	1403	675	1189	1437	655	1175	1407	683	1177	1917	1935
247	289	1203	1433	631	1173	1435	659	1207	1421	639	1181	1425	661	1183	1413	671	1193	1401	673	1215	1405	647	1195	1391	681	1223	1393	651	1889	1931
2023	1857	677	1171	1419	679	1199	1389	665	1179	1423	669	1201	1397	657	1211	1399	645	1213	1409	649	1187	1431	635	1221	1411	637	1191	1439	321	155
207	273	1063	717	1487	1091	687	1489	1071	721	1475	1093	695	1479	1103	697	1467	1105	707	1455	1079	729	1459	1113	709	1445	1083	737	1447	1905	1971
223	1865	1473	1109	685	1443	1111	713	1477	1097	693	1451	1101	715	1453	1089	725	1463	1077	727	1485	1081	701	1465	1067	735	1493	1069	705	313	1955
219	1853	731	1441	1095	733	1469	1065	719	1449	1099	723	1471	1073	711	1481	1075	699	1483	1085	703	1457	1107	689	1491	1087	691	1461	1115	325	1959
215	277	739	987	1541	767	957	1543	747	991	1529	769	965	1533	779	967	1521	781	977	1509	755	999	1513	789	979	1499	759	1007	1501	1901	1963
2039	297	1527	785	955	1497	787	983	1531	773	963	1505	777	985	1507	765	995	1517	753	997	1539	757	971	1519	743	1005	1547	745	975	1881	139
227	281	1001	1495	771	1003	1523	741	989	1503	775	993	1525	749	981	1535	751	969	1537	761	973	1511	783	959	1545	763	961	1515	791	1897	1951
1993	285	847	1581	839	875	1551	841	855	1585	827	877	1559	831	887	1561	819	889	1571	807	863	1593	811	897	1573	797	867	1601	799	1893	185
2019	1829	825	893	1549	795	895	1577	829	881	1557	803	885	1579	805	873	1589	815	861	1591	837	865	1565	817	851	1599	845	853	1569	349	159
211	1837	1595	793	879	1597	821	849	1583	801	883	1587	823	857	1575	833	859	1563	835	869	1567	809	891	1553	843	871	1555	813	899	341	1967
2043	1849	469	1041	1757	497	1011	1759	477	1045	1745	499	1019	1749	509	1021	1737	511	1031	1725	485	1053	1729	519	1033	1715	489	1061	1717	329	135
1995	1845	1743	515	1009	1713	517	1037	1747	503	1017	1721	507	1039	1723	495	1049	1733	483	1051	1755	487	1025	1735	473	1059	1763	475	1029	333	183
2015	1841	1055	1711	501	1057	1739	471	1043	1719	505	1047	1741	479	1035	1751	481	1023	1753	491	1027	1727	513	1013	1761	493	1015	1731	521	337	163
235	1833	523	1797	947	551	1767	949	531	1801	935	553	1775	939	563	1777	927	565	1787	915	539	1809	919	573	1789	905	543	1817	907	345	1943
203	269	933	569	1765	903	571	1793	937	557	1773	911	561	1795	913	549	1805	923	537	1807	945	541	1781	925	527	1815	953	529	1785	1909	1975
2035	249	1811	901	555	1813	929	525	1799	909	559	1803	931	533	1791	941	535	1779	943	545	1783	917	567	1769	951	547	1771	921	575	1929	143
2047	303	327	1891	339	343	1911	319	331	351	1907	1919	315	1887	323	1895	1903	1877	1879	311	335	1923	359	1899	1883	355	1915	347	1927	307	131
187	1961	1969	1985	165	157	1989	173	1957	1933	137	141	1981	133	1937	181	1945	1973	1949	1941	1965	145	149	169	177	129	1953	153	161	1977	1987

Example 31.4. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{609, 610, \dots, 1568, 1569\}$ a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 is given by

640	653	649	641	1551	1555	639	1547	655	667	1565	1563	643	1567	665	1543	661	647	659	663	651	1561	1559	1549	1545	1569	657	1557	1553	645	1540
1544	1480	1470	688	1464	1462	678	1474	1468	1458	680	674	1476	690	1472	686	682	695	694	1478	1466	672	1454	684	692	1456	676	1460	670	1482	634
1546	691	1346	1173	748	1360	1158	749	1350	1175	742	1361	1162	744	1366	1163	738	1367	1168	732	1354	1179	734	1371	1169	727	1356	1183	728	1487	632
1558	677	741	1369	1157	726	1370	1171	743	1363	1161	730	1365	1172	731	1359	1177	736	1353	1178	747	1355	1165	737	1348	1182	751	1349	1167	1501	620
660	1481	1180	725	1362	1181	739	1347	1174	729	1364	1176	740	1351	1170	745	1352	1164	746	1357	1166	733	1368	1159	750	1358	1160	735	1372	697	1518
1560	1479	1373	768	1126	1387	753	1127	1377	770	1120	1388	757	1122	1393	758	1116	1394	763	1110	1381	774	1112	1398	764	1105	1383	778	1106	699	618
644	671	1119	1396	752	1104	1397	766	1121	1390	756	1108	1392	767	1109	1386	772	1114	1380	773	1125	1382	760	1115	1375	777	1129	1376	762	1507	1534
664	1475	775	1103	1389	776	1117	1374	769	1107	1391	771	1118	1378	765	1123	1379	759	1124	1384	761	1111	1395	754	1128	1385	755	1113	1399	703	1514
1548	1455	1184	1227	856	1198	1212	857	1188	1229	850	1199	1216	852	1204	1217	846	1205	1222	840	1192	1233	842	1209	1223	835	1194	1237	836	723	630
642	673	849	1207	1211	834	1208	1225	851	1201	1215	838	1203	1226	839	1197	1231	844	1191	1232	855	1193	1219	845	1186	1236	859	1187	1221	1505	1536
1550	1457	1234	833	1200	1235	847	1185	1228	837	1202	1230	848	1189	1224	853	1190	1218	854	1195	1220	841	1206	1213	858	1196	1214	843	1210	721	628
666	675	1238	876	1153	1252	861	1154	1242	878	1147	1253	865	1149	1258	866	1143	1259	871	1137	1246	882	1139	1263	872	1132	1248	886	1133	1503	1512
668	689	1146	1261	860	1131	1262	874	1148	1255	864	1135	1257	875	1136	1251	880	1141	1245	881	1152	1247	868	1142	1240	885	1156	1241	870	1489	1510
1556	1473	883	1130	1254	884	1144	1239	877	1134	1256	879	1145	1243	873	1150	1244	867	1151	1249	869	1138	1260	862	1155	1250	863	1140	1264	705	622
648	681	1076	903	1288	1090	888	1289	1080	905	1282	1091	892	1284	1096	893	1278	1097	898	1272	1084	909	1274	1101	899	1267	1086	913	1268	1497	1530
656	1477	1281	1099	887	1266	1100	901	1283	1093	891	1270	1095	902	1271	1089	907	1276	1083	908	1287	1085	895	1277	1078	912	1291	1079	897	701	1522
654	1471	910	1265	1092	911	1279	1077	904	1269	1094	906	1280	1081	900	1285	1082	894	1286	1087	896	1273	1098	889	1290	1088	890	1275	1102	707	1524
652	683	914	1038	1315	928	1023	1316	918	1040	1309	929	1027	1311	934	1028	1305	935	1033	1299	922	1044	1301	939	1034	1294	924	1048	1295	1495	1526
1564	693	1308	937	1022	1293	938	1036	1310	931	1026	1297	933	1037	1298	927	1042	1303	921	1043	1314	923	1030	1304	916	1047	1318	917	1032	1485	614
658	685	1045	1292	930	1046	1306	915	1039	1296	932	1041	1307	919	1035	1312	920	1029	1313	925	1031	1300	936	1024	1317	926	1025	1302	940	1493	1520
1541	687	968	1335	964	982	1320	965	972	1337	958	983	1324	960	988	1325	954	989	1330	948	976	1341	950	993	1331	943	978	1345	944	1491	637
1554	1459	957	991	1319	942	992	1333	959	985	1323	946	987	1334	947	981	1339	952	975	1340	963	977	1327	953	970	1344	967	971	1329	719	624
650	1463	1342	941	984	1343	955	969	1336	945	986	1338	956	973	1332	961	974	1326	962	979	1328	949	990	1321	966	980	1322	951	994	715	1528
1566	1469	779	1065	1423	793	1050	1424	783	1067	1417	794	1054	1419	799	1055	1413	800	1060	1407	787	1071	1409	804	1061	1402	789	1075	1403	709	612
1542	1467	1416	802	1049	1401	803	1063	1418	796	1053	1405	798	1064	1406	792	1069	1411	786	1070	1422	788	1057	1412	781	1074	1426	782	1059	711	636
1552	1465	1072	1400	795	1073	1414	780	1066	1404	797	1068	1415	784	1062	1420	785	1056	1421	790	1058	1408	801	1051	1425	791	1052	1410	805	713	626
662	1461	806	1443	1018	820	1428	1019	810	1445	1012	821	1432	1014	826	1433	1008	827	1438	1002	814	1449	1004	831	1439	997	816	1453	998	717	1516
646	679	1011	829	1427	996	830	1441	1013	823	1431	1000	825	1442	1001	819	1447	1006	813	1448	1017	815	1435	1007	808	1452	1021	809	1437	1499	1532
1562	669	1450	995	822	1451	1009	807	1444	999	824	1446	1010	811	1440	1015	812	1434	1016	817	1436	1003	828	1429	1020	818	1430	1005	832	1509	616
1568	696	708	1490	714	716	1500	704	710	720	1498	1504	702	1488	706	1492	1496	1483	1484	700	712	1506	724	1494	1486	722	1502	718	1508	698	610
638	1525	1529	1537	627	623	1539	631	1523	1511	613	615	1535	611	1513	635	1517	1531	1519	1515	1527	617	619	629	633	609	1521	621	625	1533	1538

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 31 given in Examples 31.1 and 31.2 are respectively with **consecutive odd numbers** and **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 27 is with blocks of orders 3. These blocks are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below details.

$$\begin{aligned}S_{31 \times 31} &:= 33759; & T_{961} &:= 31 \times 29791 = 1046529 = 1023^2; \\S_{29 \times 29} &:= 31581; & T_{841} &:= 29 \times 31581 = 915849 = 957^2; \\S_{27 \times 27} &:= 29403; & T_{729} &:= 27 \times 29403 = 793881 = 891^2; \\S_{m_{3 \times 3}} &:= 3267; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 3267 = 9801 = 99^2\end{aligned}$$

Both the Examples 31.3 and 31.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (64, 1023, 1025)**, i.e., $64^2 + 1023^2 = 1025^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in **perfect square**.

31.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let's consider the expression 29 given in List (15):

$$\text{Order 31, } S_{31 \times 31} := 15004, T_{961} := 465124 = 682^2, E := \{4, 5, \dots, 963, 964\}$$

The above expression lead us to a magic square of order 31.

Example 31.5. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{4, 5, 6, \dots, 963, 964\}$, a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 is given by

35	48	44	36	946	950	34	942	50	62	960	958	38	962	60	938	56	42	54	58	46	956	954	944	940	964	52	952	948	40	935
939	875	865	83	859	857	73	869	863	853	75	69	871	85	867	81	77	90	89	873	861	67	849	79	87	851	71	855	65	877	29
941	86	741	568	143	755	553	144	745	570	137	756	557	139	761	558	133	762	563	127	749	574	129	766	564	122	751	578	123	882	27
953	72	136	764	552	121	765	566	138	758	556	125	760	567	126	754	572	131	748	573	142	750	560	132	743	577	146	744	562	896	15
55	876	575	120	757	576	134	742	569	124	759	571	135	746	565	140	747	559	141	752	561	128	763	554	145	753	555	130	767	92	913
955	874	768	163	521	782	148	522	772	165	515	783	152	517	788	153	511	789	158	505	776	169	507	793	159	500	778	173	501	94	13
39	66	514	791	147	499	792	161	516	785	151	503	787	162	504	781	167	509	775	168	520	777	155	510	770	172	524	771	157	902	929
59	870	170	498	784	171	512	769	164	502	786	166	513	773	160	518	774	154	519	779	156	506	790	149	523	780	150	508	794	98	909
943	850	579	622	251	593	607	252	583	624	245	594	611	247	599	612	241	600	617	235	587	628	237	604	618	230	589	632	231	118	25
37	68	244	602	606	229	603	620	246	596	610	233	598	621	234	592	626	239	586	627	250	588	614	240	581	631	254	582	616	900	931
945	852	629	228	595	630	242	580	623	232	597	625	243	584	619	248	585	613	249	590	615	236	601	608	253	591	609	238	605	116	23
61	70	633	271	548	647	256	549	637	273	542	648	260	544	653	261	538	654	266	532	641	277	534	658	267	527	643	281	528	898	907
63	84	541	656	255	526	657	269	543	650	259	530	652	270	531	646	275	536	640	276	547	642	263	537	635	280	551	636	265	884	905
951	868	278	525	649	279	539	634	272	529	651	274	540	638	268	545	639	262	546	644	264	533	655	257	550	645	258	535	659	100	17
43	76	471	298	683	485	283	684	475	300	677	486	287	679	491	288	673	492	293	667	479	304	669	496	294	662	481	308	663	892	925
51	872	676	494	282	661	495	296	678	488	286	665	490	297	666	484	302	671	478	303	682	480	290	672	473	307	686	474	292	96	917
49	866	305	660	487	306	674	472	299	664	489	301	675	476	295	680	477	289	681	482	291	668	493	284	685	483	285	670	497	102	919
47	78	309	433	710	323	418	711	313	435	704	324	422	706	329	423	700	330	428	694	317	439	696	334	429	689	319	443	690	890	921
959	88	703	332	417	688	333	431	705	326	421	692	328	432	693	322	437	698	316	438	709	318	425	699	311	442	713	312	427	880	9
53	80	440	687	325	441	701	310	434	691	327	436	702	314	430	707	315	424	708	320	426	695	331	419	712	321	420	697	335	888	915
936	82	363	730	359	377	715	360	367	732	353	378	719	355	383	720	349	384	725	343	371	736	345	388	726	338	373	740	339	886	32
949	854	352	386	714	337	387	728	354	380	718	341	382	729	342	376	734	347	370	735	358	372	722	348	365	739	362	366	724	114	19
45	858	737	336	379	738	350	364	731	340	381	733	351	368	727	356	369	721	357	374	723	344	385	716	361	375	717	346	389	110	923
961	864	174	460	818	188	445	819	178	462	812	189	449	814	194	450	808	195	455	802	182	466	804	199	456	797	184	470	798	104	7
937	862	811	197	444	796	198	458	813	191	448	800	193	459	801	187	464	806	181	465	817	183	452	807	176	469	821	177	454	106	31
947	860	467	795	190	468	809	175	461	799	192	463	810	179	457	815	180	451	816	185	453	803	196	446	820	186	447	805	200	108	21
57	856	201	838	413	215	823	414	205	840	407	216	827	409	221	828	403	222	833	397	209	844	399	226	834	392	211	848	393	112	911
41	74	406	224	822	391	225	836	408	218	826	395	220	837	396	214	842	401	208	843	412	210	830	402	203	847	416	204	832	894	927
957	64	845	390	217	846	404	202	839	394	219	841	405	206	835	410	207	829	411	212	831	398	223	824	415	213	825	400	227	904	11
963	91	103	885	109	111	895	99	105	115	893	899	97	883	101	887	891	878	879	95	107	901	119	889	881	117	897	113	903	93	5
33	920	924	932	22	18	934	26	918	906	8	10	930	6	908	30	912	926	914	910	922	12	14	24	28	4	916	16	20	928	933

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 31 given in Example 31.5 is with **consecutive natural numbers** entries. The inner magic square of order 27 is **block-wise pandiagonal**. The blocks of orders 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below details.

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 15004; \quad T_{961} := 31 \times 15004 = 465124 = 682^2;$$

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 14026; \quad T_{841} := 29 \times 14026 = 407044 = 638^2;$$

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 13068; \quad T_{729} := 27 \times 13068 = 352836 = 594^2;$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 1452; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 1452 = 4356 = 66^2$$

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**.

References

- [1] H. Heinz, Magic Squares, Magic Stars and Other Patterns, <http://www.magicsquares.net>.
- [2] N. J. A. Sloane, NSW numbers: $a(n) = 6 \times a(n - 1) - a(n - 2)$; also $a(n)^2 - 2 \times b(n)^2 = -1$ with $b(n) = A001653(n)$, <https://oeis.org/A002315>, textit<https://oeis.org/A001653>, Numbers k such that $2 \times k^2 - 1$ is a square
- [3] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares with Perfect Square Number Sums, Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Article 11, pp.1-24, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a11.pdf>.
- [4] Inder J. Taneja, Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 128, pp. 1-22, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a128.pdf>.
- [5] Inder J. Taneja, Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 136, pp. 1-62, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a136.pdf>.
- [6] Inder J. Taneja, Generating Pythagorean Triples with Applications to Magic Squares and Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 85, pp. 1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a85.pdf>.
- [7] Inder J. Taneja, Patterns in Pythagorean Triples Using Single and Double Variable Procedures, **Zenodo**, Jan. 19, 2019, pp. 1-134, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2544519>.
- [8] Inder J. Taneja, Multiple-Type Patterns and Pythagorean Triples, **Zenodo**, Jan. 19, 2019, pp. 1-53, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2544527>.
- [9] Inder J. Taneja, Palindromic-Type Pandigital Patterns in Pythagorean Triples, **Zenodo**, Jan. 19, 2019, pp. 1-160, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2544551>.

- [10] Inder J. Taneja, Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, Zenodo, April 29, 2019, pp. 1-65, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2653927>.
- [11] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, Zenodo, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [12] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, Zenodo, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [13] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, Zenodo, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [14] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, Zenodo, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [15] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, Zenodo, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>
- [16] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares With Magic Sums 21, 21^2 and 2021, pp. 1-118, Zenodo, December 16, 2020, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4380343>.
- [17] Inder J. Taneja, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. Zenodo, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [18] Inder J. Taneja, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples. Zenodo. February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>.
- [19] Inder J. Taneja, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, Zenodo, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>.
- [20] Inder J. Taneja, Sequential Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, Zenodo, June 21, 2021, pp. 1-595, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009204>.
- [21] Inder J. Taneja, Creative Magic Squares: Area Representations, Zenodo, June 22, 2021, pp. 1-45, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009224>.
- [22] Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 32 to 47 - under preparation.
-